

‘Architexts: building structure, building texture’

‘The thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Professional Doctorate in Education of the University of Portsmouth.’

Abstract of thesis entitled:

**‘Architexts: building structure,
building texture’**

Submitted by
Jennifer Sizer

For the degree of Doctor of Education
At The University of Portsmouth
In April 2026

This Professional Doctorate in Education research project investigates the academic writing practices of undergraduate architecture students in the UK, addressing a significant gap in English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) provision for creative disciplines. Drawing on Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), academic literacies theory, and ethnographic methodologies, the study employs a textographic approach to analyse architecture student’s undergraduate dissertations in terms of structure and texture while also incorporating an ethnographic interview and texts collected from ethnographic site study. This research explores architecture students’ language choices (linguistic and multimodal), including macrostructure, Thematic progression and image-language relations. Findings reveal diverse dissertation structures: genre-based such as traditional simple and traditional complex; topic-based, and a combination structure, i.e. ‘TopGen’ alongside creative macroTheme naming conventions. Findings also suggest prevalent patterns in terms of texture such as unmarked topical Thematic choices, zigzag (Rheme > Theme) Thematic progression as well as use of images. This study emphasises the importance of contextualised, constructively aligned, and collaborative English for Academic Purposes pedagogy, proposing English for Pracademic Purposes (EPP) as a potential framework. Implications for EAP practice include recommendations for ESAP curriculum design, genre-based instruction, and interdisciplinary collaboration between EAP practitioners and subject specialists.

Declaration

‘Whilst registered as a candidate for the above degree, I have not been registered for any other research award. The results and conclusions embodied in this thesis are the work of the named candidate and have not been submitted for any other academic award.’

Word count: 54494

Acknowledgements

I would like to begin by expressing my gratitude to my supervisors for their encouragement and patience during my doctoral journey. I am also sincerely grateful to my examiners for taking the time to engage so carefully with this work and for their insightful comments, questions, and support. I would also like to extend my thanks and appreciation to friends and colleagues who supported the final stages of this project, particularly those who took part in my mock viva, viva preparation, and EdD presentation. Your encouragement, helpful questions, and willingness to engage with the work helped me approach the viva with far greater confidence.

Thank you to the architecture community who welcomed me into their studios, corridors, and conversations. To the architecture educator (interviewee) who participated in this project: your insight, honesty, and passion for teaching architecture enriched this study immeasurably. I am also eternally grateful to the architecture students whose work formed the heart of this research. Your dissertations, creativity, and generosity in allowing your work to be studied offered important insight into the complex processes of writing within creative and pracademic disciplines.

My sincere thanks also go to my colleagues, whose support and kindness have meant a great deal. I feel especially fortunate that many of you have also become friends along the way.

I am also hugely thankful to the wider English for Academic Purposes (EAP) community, whose collegiality, questions, and genuine interest in this work reassured me, that it was worth continuing and completing. In particular, I would like to thank the BALEAP Creative Disciplines Special Interest Group community. The conversations, collaborations, and shared explorations within this community have enriched both my practice and this research project. I am also incredibly grateful to the attendees of the STEPS sessions (Dr EAP support group), whose generosity in sharing experiences and collective wisdom provided a valuable sense of solidarity and support.

I am also deeply grateful for the time spent at the ChapelGarth Academic Writing Retreats. The dedicated space for reflection and writing, together with the kind support of facilitators and fellow retreaters, created a special environment that was transformative. The encouragement, chats, and sense of shared purpose I experienced at ChapelGarth played a significant role in bringing this thesis to completion.

Finally, my sincere thanks go to my friends and family for their support, encouragement, and patience. Your understanding of the time and energy this project demanded, and cheering me on along the way, made all the difference.

i stand
on the sacrifices
of a million women before me
thinking
*what can i do
to make this mountain taller
so the women after me
can see farther*

- *legacy*

(Kaur, 2017)

Abbreviations list

AcLits – Academic Literacies

BALEAP – British Association of Lecturers in English for Academic Purposes

BAWE – British Academic Written English [corpus]

BAS – BALEAP Accreditation Scheme

CARS – Create A Research Space

CELTA – Certificate in Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages

CEFR – Common European Framework of Reference

CLT – Communicative Language Teaching

CoP – Community of Practice

DfE – Department for Education

DLHE – Destination of Leavers from Higher Education

EAP – English for Academic Purposes

EAS – English for Academic Study

EGAP – English for General Academic Purposes

ELT – English Language Teaching

EOP – English for Occupational Purposes

EPP – English for Pracademic Purposes

ERPP – English for Research and Publication Purposes

ESAP – English for Specific Academic Purposes

ESP – English for Specific Purposes

FLAX – Flexible Language Acquisition

HEI – Higher Education Institution

HESA – Higher Education Statistics Agency

IELTS – International English Language Testing System

IMRD – Introduction, Method, Results, Discussion

JIC – Just in Case

MA – Master of Arts

MiCASE – Michigan Corpus of Academic Spoken English

MOOC – Massive Open Online Course
PDC – Place Discourse Community
PEAP/s – Practitioner/s of English for Academic Purposes
pracademic – *practitioner & academic*
RIBA – Royal Institute of British Architects
SELMOUS – Special English Language Materials for Overseas University Students
SELT – Secure English Language Test
SFL – Systemic Functional Linguistics
SIG – Special Interest Group
SKELL – Sketch Engine for Language Learners
STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
TESOL – Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages
TENOR – Teaching English for No Obvious Reason
textography – *textual analysis & ethnography*
TopGen – *Topic-based & Genre-based*
UEfAP – Using English for Academic Purposes
UKVI – UK Visas and Immigration
VLE – Virtual Learning Environment
WAC – Writing Across the Curriculum

Dissemination. A concise list of the PGRS' relevant publications

- Sizer, J. (2017). *Practitioner-perceived challenges of English for ARTISTIC purposes*. & Ruhr University Bochum. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16414048>
- Sizer, J. (2018). English for Academic Purposes for Architecture. *EAP in the North: Exploring Genre(s) in the Creative Arts*, University of Edinburgh
- Sizer, J. (2019). EAP teachers working in, with and through the Creative Arts: An exploration. *BALEAP Conference 2019: Innovation, Exploration and Transformation*, University of Leeds
- Sizer, J. (2019). Unobtrusive textography of a university building as an innovative research method. *BALEAP Conference 2019: Innovation, Exploration and Transformation, University of Leeds* <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12795602>
- Sizer, J. (2019). *Is teaching EAP a profession? A reflection on EAP's professional status, values, community and knowledge*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12790044>
- Sizer, J. (2019). Textography as a needs analysis and research tool for English for Academic Purposes and learning development practitioners. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.v0i15.554>
- Sizer, J. (2021). Chapter 3. Textography. In *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics* (pp. 40–60). John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/rmal.1.03siz>
- Sizer, J., Carr, C., Maxwell, C., & Rolinska, A. (2021). Cross-institutional collaborative autoethnography as an inclusive and flexible way of researching EAP pedagogies and practice. *BALEAP Conference 2021: Exploring Pedagogical Approaches in English for Academic Purposes (EAP)*, University of Glasgow.
- Sizer, J., Carr, C., Maxwell, C., & Rolinska, A. (2021). EAP teachers working in, with and through the creative arts: An exploration. In *Pedagogies in English for Academic Purposes*.
- Sizer, J. (2022). *In the beginning we are all novices: Textography as initial needs analysis for ESAP*. OsloMet – Oslo Metropolitan University. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16413925>
- Sizer, J., Carr, C., Maxwell, C., & Rolinska, A. (2022). EAP teachers working in, with, and through the creative arts: Reflections on a conference workshop aimed at exploring current practices. *BALEAP Conference 2019: Innovation, Exploration and Transformation - University of Leeds*.
- Sizer, J. (2023). Analysing multimodal written texts submitted by undergraduate architecture students. *BALEAP PIM: Multimodality in EAP Contexts*. Heriot-Watt University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12788127>

Sizer, J., Carr, C., Maxwell, C., Vickers, J., & Gazeley-Eke, Z. (2023). Deconstructing spoken communication in the creative disciplines (in memory of Gary Riley-Jones). *BALEAP 2023 - Caution! EAP under Deconstruction, University of Warwick*.

Sizer, J., Carr, C., Maxwell, C., & Rolinska, A. (2024). Cross-institutional collaborative autoethnography (CAE) as an inclusive and flexible way of researching EAP pedagogies and practice. In *Exploring pedagogical approaches in EAP teaching – Proceedings of the 2021 BALEAP Conference*.

Sizer, J. (2024). Routes into EAP podcast episode. In *BALEAP*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J8Ce0LbBIWU>

Sizer, J. (2025). Textography: Situated academic writing. In *Conference on College Composition & Communication 2025, Baltimore, Maryland, USA*.

Sizer, J. (2025). *Challenges and Benefits of Combining Textual Analysis and Ethnographic Methods to Explore Educational Contexts, Texts, and Practices*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781036221812>

Contents

Acknowledgements	iii
Abbreviations list.....	v
Dissemination. A concise list of the PGRS' relevant publications	vii
Contents	ix
List of tables	xii
List of figures	xiv
1. Introduction	1
1.1 Importance of English for Academic Purposes (EAP).....	1
1.2. EAP: practitioner's perspective	2
1.2.1. Contextualisation.....	3
1.2.2 Constructively aligned	7
1.2.3. Collaborative	12
1.3. EAP knowledge reservoir.....	15
1.3.1. ESAP gap.....	18
1.3.2. ESAP gap: architecture	19
1.4. Pracademic gap.....	20
1.5 ESAP/EOP research with architecture.....	22
1.5.1. Research objectives.....	22
1.5.2. Methodology.....	22
1.5.3. Principal findings:	23
1.5.4. Implications	24
1.5.5. Thesis structure.....	24
2. Selective review of literature which informs this study	26
2.1 Philosophical framework.....	26
2.2 Theoretical framework	26
2.2.1 Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) LINGUISTICS	26
2.2.2. Selective brief overview of SFL Linguistics theory.....	27
2.3 SYSTEMIC	28
2.4 FUNCTIONAL.....	31
2.4.1. Metafunction: textual – Texture: textural choices and Texture: structural choices.....	33

2.4.2. Texture in multimodal texts	37
2.4.3. Structure	43
2.5 Ethnographic: interpretivist	50
2.6 Conceptual framework: texts, contexts and practices	53
2.6.1. Context	53
2.6.2. Texts: <i>definition and architecture as text</i>	55
2.6.3. Texts: <i>Architexts [architecture texts]</i>	57
2.7 Textual practices (<i>literacy practices</i>)	68
2.8 Summary	72
3. Methodology	73
3.1 Research Objectives	73
3.2 Research discipline and positioning	73
3.3 Research approach: textography	74
3.4 Research context	75
3.5 Research methods: participant selection (practices)	76
3.6 Ethical considerations: macro/micro	76
3.6.1. Macroethics	76
3.6.2. Microethics	77
3.7 Research methods: text selection (texts)	77
3.7.1. Contextual texts	77
3.7.2. Textual histories	77
3.7.3. Dissertations	78
3.8 Interview (practices)	85
4 Structure	87
Four macrostructures: introduction of TopGen	87
4.1 Traditional simple/genre-based: rare	88
4.2 Traditional complex/multi study	94
4.2.1. Traditional complex/multi study elements	95
4.3 Topic-based	102
4.3.1. Topic-based: introductions & conclusions	103
4.3.2. Topic-based: naming conventions	106
4.4 TopGen, i.e. Topic-based & Genre-based	109
5 Texture	114

5.1 Thematic choice: unmarked dominant but marked prevalent	114
5.2 Thematic choice: topical > textual > interpersonal	117
5.3 Thematic progression: zigzag > iteration > peripheral > derived	119
5.4 Thematic progression: image and language relations	131
5.5 Logico-semantics image-language relations	140
6. Conclusion	153
6.1 Research Summary	153
6.2 Research contributions	154
6.2.1 Research findings	155
6.2.2. Contribution to community	156
6.2.3. Contribution to scholarship	157
6.3 Limitations	158
6.4 Implications.....	160
6.5 And finally	161
References	162
Appendices	186
Appendix A: Favourable Ethical Opinion (2019).....	
Appendix B: Favourable Ethical Opinion (2020)	
Appendix C: Application for Ethics Review (2019)	
Appendix D: Application for Ethics Review (2020)	
Appendix E: Research Ethics Checklist (UPR16)	
Appendix F: Participant Information Sheet (Version 5, November 2024)	
Appendix G: Red 1/1 dissertation.....	
Appendix H: Yellow 1/1 dissertation	
Appendix I: Yellow 2/3 dissertation.....	
Appendix J: Yellow 3/3 dissertation	
Appendix K: Blue 1/2 dissertation	
Appendix L: Blue 2/2 dissertation.....	
Appendix M: interview with architecture educator transcript	

List of tables

Table 1: HESA (2025) 'Where do students come from?'	2
Table 2: BALEAR conference abstracts.....	19
Table 3 HESA HE student enrolments by CAH level 1 subject and sex [sex removed, just totals] Academic years 2018/19 to 2022/23 Architecture highlighted	20
Table 4 North's (2004) marked Theme with subject analysis example	36
Table 5: Paltridge & Starfield (2024) postgraduate thesis types	48
Table 6: Nesi & Gardner (2012) essays and research reports: purpose, stages, networks and examples.....	49
Table 7 Gardner (2012) a simplified view of AcLits vs SFL investigations of academic writing.....	52
Table 8 CABA (2006) & Dobson (2014) value of built environment.....	54
Table 9: Alias (2004) Functions and systems in architecture (reproduced from O'Toole, 1994: 86).....	56
Table 10 Motta-Roth & Herberle (1995) review genre moves and functions	63
Table 11 Caballero (2003) Moves and steps building review.....	65
Table 12 Lillis (2001) comparison between AcLits and SFL based on metafunctions	68
Table 13 Nesi & Gardner (2012) six essay genres and stages, introduction in bold.	70
Table 14 T-unit, page and image number comparison between 3 analysed dissertations	81
Table 15 Theme categories, examples and illustrative instances	81
Table 16 Thematic progression patterns with descriptions and examples.....	82
Table 17 Expansion and projection system types and descriptions.....	84
Table 18 Detailed transcription process.....	86
Table 19 Yellow 2/3 Traditional Simple/genre-based macrostructure (from contents page).....	89
Table 20 Yellow 2/3 feedback comments, bold added for emphasis	90
Table 21 Swales (2002) CARS model for introductions.....	92
Table 22 Dissertation research methods	93
Table 23 Red 1/1 traditional complex/multi study macrostructure	95
Table 24 Red 1/1 traditional complex/multi study compared to Paltridge & Starfield's (2024) traditional complex in architecture example	96
Table 25 Pink exemplar dissertation, traditional complex/multi study macrostructure	98
Table 26 Expanded subtitles for Paltridge & Starfield's 2024 traditional complex/multi study example showing IMRD internal structure	99
Table 27 exemplar dissertations with traditional complex/multi study macrostructure with 'literature reviews'	101
Table 28 Exemplar dissertation with traditional complex/multi study macrostructure: left-hand side literature review with topic-based subtitles, right-hand side no explicit literature review	102

Table 29 Blue 1/2 topic-based macrostructure compared to 2 Paltridge & Starfield (2024) examples, first 2 columns 100% topic-based, right-hand column similar interdisciplinary topic but includes conclusion	103
Table 30 Exemplar dissertation with topic-based macrostructure + conclusion.....	103
Table 31 3 Nesi & Gardner examples of topic-based macrostructure, all with introduction, 2 with conclusion	104
Table 32 Yellow 3/3 topic-based macrostructure with introduction and conclusion, interesting naming convention 'intro'	105
Table 33 Exemplars with topic-based macrostructure + introduction + conclusion, interesting naming conventions gerund verb to begin subtitle.....	106
Table 34 Exemplar dissertations with topic-based macrostructure and alternatives for introduction and conclusion: preface and finale	106
Table 35 Blue 2/2 TopGen macrostructure, topic-based + introduction, literature review, methodology, conclusion	110
Table 36 Yellow 2/3 with TopGen structure: topic-based + introduction, discussion & conclusion	110
Table 37 Two exemplar dissertations with TopGen macrostructure with non-typical order compared with Paltridge & Starfield (2024).....	111
Table 38 Dissertations with TopGen elements but multi study.....	113
Table 39 Theme choice in 3 analysed dissertations based on percentages	114
Table 40 Table comparing Themes in Gunawan & Aziza and yellow 2/3 5 chapter dissertations	119
Table 41 Demonstrating zigzag Thematic progression pattern in yellow 2/3, also some Theme iteration.....	121
Table 42 Yellow 1/3 Theme iteration in introduction section	123
Table 43 Yellow 2/3 Theme iteration in 'methodology' section.....	124
Table 44 Yellow 1/3 Theme iteration in 'discussion & results' section.....	124
Table 45: Theme iteration 'I' (yellow 2/3)	125
Table 46 Blue 1/2 Theme iteration with images - figure 9 and 8 repeated as Theme	126
Table 47 yellow 1/3 derived Themes, i.e. mental limits from introduction section...	128
Table 48 Yellow 1/3 derived Themes, i.e. seasons in introduction section	129
Table 49 Peripheral Theme types with examples	130
Table 50 Yellow 1/3 peripheral Themes with indication of type/s in 'final remarks' section.....	131
Table 51 Burkhard's 2004 visualisation types and suggested knowledge types for architects.....	132
Table 52 Visualisation types and suggested knowledge types for architecture students (adapted from Burkhard, 2004).....	133
Table 53 image type count for 6 collected dissertations	134
Table 54 Count of images in comparison to word 'figure/s' as part of written component [not caption or figures list].....	145

List of figures

Figure 1: The Migration Observatory (2025) 'Student migration to the UK'	2
Figure 2: Blue (1998, p. 96) ELT family tree	4
Figure 3: Jordan (1997, p. 39) Methods of collecting data for needs analysis diagram	6
Figure 4: Gillet (2025) UEfaP 'Levels of Communication: discourse-semantics'	10
Figure 5 ESP family tree with the addition of EPP	21
Figure 6 Conceptual framework diagram	23
Figure 7: SFL stratification onion: architectural view of language.....	28
Figure 8 text, context of situation and context of culture relationship based on Butt et al. 2000	31
Figure 9: Theme choice system	35
Figure 10: Theme choices, examples of unmarked Theme.....	36
Figure 11 metafunctions for analysis of images.....	38
Figure 12 Kress and van Leeuwen's reading images framework	38
Figure 13 Martinec & Salway (2005) p358 network of combined status and logico-semantics	39
Figure 14 Swales (2004, p. 136) factors shaping form and purpose of dissertation .	44
Figure 15: Adapted from Martin & Rose (2007) & Monbec (2020) macro>hyper>theme	45
Figure 16: Bunton (1998, p.112) Three-stream model for PhD thesis macrostructures.	47
Figure 17: Newman (2024) 'the design squiggle'	58
Figure 18 RIBA (2020) Plan of work stages	59
Figure 19 NESTA (2003) Model of creative industries.....	60
Figure 20 Lillis (2001) 3 dimensions of student meaning in writing	68
Figure 21 screenshot of identifying elements and sequence in dissertations.....	80
Figure 22 Screenshot of macroTheme analysis and colour-coding.....	82
Figure 23 Screenshot of Thematic analysis and colour-coded Themes	82
Figure 24 Martinec & Salway's (2005) original 'image-text relations' (in this thesis: 'image-language' relations)	83
Figure 25 Factors in assigning status.....	85
Figure 26 four macrostructure typology triangle	88
Figure 27 Undergraduate Architecture dissertation criteria 2019/20	89
Figure 28 Changes in dissertation criteria assessment in 2021, 3 to 4 criteria.....	94
Figure 29 screenshot of assessment criteria and descriptors in 60-69 range, 'interdisciplinary' in 3 out of 4 criteria.....	107
Figure 30 Graph showing level of genre vs topic-based chapter subtitles as percentages, red = topic-based, blue = genre-based, most fall somewhere between.	109
Figure 31 screenshot of assessment criteria which mentions 'clarity'.....	117
Figure 32 Blue 1/2 'figure 8' and 'Figure 9'	127

Figure 33 Martinec & Salway (2005) Status system for image-text (image-language) relations.....	136
Figure 34 Yellow 1/3 'figure 2' with equal status image-language, equal: complementary.....	138
Figure 35 Stoller & Robinson (2013) setting the stage in chemistry result sections articles.....	139
Figure 36 Blue 1/2 Figure 9 (seen previously) but with accompanying equal status language	140
Figure 37 Logico-semantics system with expansion and projection systems (Martinec & Salway, 2025)	142
Figure 38 Salway & Martinec (2005) online art gallery page, image in Theme position, image position and salience: image subordinate to language.....	143
Figure 39 Yellow 3/3 pages 9 & 10 comparison to Salway & Martinec (2005) online art gallery, image subordinate to language.....	144
Figure 40 Blue 1/2 lexical references, 'figure' start, middle and end of written component	145
Figure 41 Yellow 3/3 Figure 3 + caption and accompanying language demonstrating expansion.....	147
Figure 42 (Figure 13 as described in yellow 1/3 list of figures).....	149
Figure 43 Yellow 1/3 'figure 13' demonstrating enhancement: spatial	149
Figure 44 Illustrations of locution 'speech bubble' and idea 'thought cloud'.....	149
Figure 45 Yellow 3/3 'figure 6' with extended description demonstrating projection: idea	151

1. Introduction

1.1 Importance of English for Academic Purposes (EAP)

Higher education in the UK is an important sector and has a significant economic impact, approximately £265 billion, with much of this total attributed to the two fundamental areas for universities: research (£63 billion) and teaching (£95 billion) (*The Economic Impact of Higher Education, Teaching, Research and Innovation*, 2025). Despite this economic impact, in recent years, more UK universities have been reporting financial difficulties, with many universities increasingly reliant on international students (Elapatha, 2025) and plans to increase revenue through the recruitment of more higher-fee-paying international students. International student numbers have steadily been increasing in recent years (*Where Do HE Students Come from?* | HESA, 2025). However, the prospect of future increases in international students, while simultaneously cutting university staff numbers, highlights concerns about the support available for international students.

Similar concerns regarding supporting international students with academic language and literacy needs were first expressed in the 1960s by academics at the University of Birmingham following the recent introduction of differential (higher) fees for international students as well as increasing international student enrolments (Gillet, 2025; Jordan, 2002). Colleagues from the University of Birmingham, and a group from other universities, came together to discuss provision and support for international students (Jordan, 2002). In 1972, four founding universities (Birmingham, Manchester, Newcastle and Leeds) formed the SELMOUS group (Special English Language Materials for Overseas University Students). Shortly after, in 1974, the University of Reading also joined SELMOUS (Bell, 2024; Jordan, 2002). SELMOUS began by discussing the support available for international students with English language skills in their various contexts. SELMOUS held its first conference in 1975 to share current practice, such as specialist courses for international students before beginning university study (subsequently named and still referred to as 'pre-sessional courses') and ongoing support and provision for international students during university study, often referred to as 'in-sessional'. Papers from this conference were the first to use the phrase 'English for Academic Purposes' or 'EAP'. In 1989, SELMOUS became the British Association of Lecturers in EAP (BALEAP), then later shortened to 'BALEAP' (Jordan, 2002; Gillet, 2022; BALEAP, 2024). In more recent years, there has been a huge increase in the number of international students studying in the UK, from less than 200,000 in the 1990s to nearly 800,000 based on recent estimates (Table 1 and Figure 1: 'Student Migration to the UK', 2025).

Table 1: HESA (2025) 'Where do students come from?'

	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23
UK					
England	1,617,000	1,627,305	1,775,015	1,807,295	1,812,200
Wales	101,865	103,590	110,380	110,360	108,165
Scotland	173,855	177,190	191,265	194,170	184,760
Northern Ireland	63,710	62,640	65,545	66,095	64,045
Other UK	4,440	4,445	4,495	4,640	6,360
Total UK	1,960,865	1,975,170	2,146,700	2,182,565	2,175,530
Non-UK					
European Union	146,725	147,920	152,910	120,145	95,505
Non-European Union	349,590	406,310	447,225	555,060	663,355
Total Non-UK	496,315	554,230	600,135	675,200	758,855
Not known	70	80	255	90	2,770
Total	2,457,250	2,529,485	2,747,090	2,857,855	2,937,155

[↑ Reset filters](#) | [Download table \(csv\)](#) | [Download source data \(csv\)](#) | [About SB269 Figure 9](#)

Number and share of international students in UK higher education

Non-UK domiciled students, 1994/95 to 2021/22 academic years

Figure 1: The Migration Observatory (2025) 'Student migration to the UK'

1.2. EAP: practitioner's perspective

In my role as an EAP (English for Academic Purposes) lecturer, or my preferred title practitioner, I support university students with their academic communication (e.g. essays, dissertations and presentations) and academic literacy needs (e.g. critical reading, listening to lectures). Much of a Practitioner in EAP, i.e. PEAP's role, is working with international students through EAP provision. BALEAP's website currently lists 30+ BALEAP-accredited institutions offering EAP provision globally (BALEAP, 2026). EAP provision can include preparatory courses, i.e. previously mentioned pre-session courses, and/or in-session provision (Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026). Pre-session courses can vary in terms of delivery (online/in-person/hybrid) and length (4-week to year-long courses) but are usually scheduled for completion in the weeks preceding the start of the academic year. Thus, international students pay to attend pre-session courses to develop academic language and literacy skills before beginning their university course. For many international students, pre-session courses are a prerequisite, as they have not yet met the language entry requirements for their chosen course. International students (unless exempted, i.e. significant previous education in English) must demonstrate the required language level via a SELT (Secure English Language Test, e.g. IELTS) and/or a pre-session course to be accepted and enrolled on their chosen course. The UK government requires at least CEFR B2, or equivalent, to study at a HEI in

the UK, but some courses, e.g. some postgraduate courses, may have higher language level entry requirements (*Student Visa*, 2026).

EAP courses (e.g. pre-sessional and/or in-sessional courses) accredited by BALEARP must demonstrate three pedagogic principles:

1. “**Contextualised**: providing EAP courses (e.g. preparatory courses; in-course provision for students; research publication work with staff) that are appropriate to the institutional and disciplinary context, and which constantly seek to develop in response to changing needs.
2. **Constructively aligned**: delivering teaching, learning activities and assessment that are aligned to learning outcomes which are informed by the context that students are in or hoping to progress to and underpinned by clearly articulated principles and/or theory.
3. **Collaborative**: raising awareness of academic literacy needs and practices among students, fellow academics and colleagues in the wider context, to promote better understanding of the interconnectedness of academic knowledge and the discourse that conveys it.”

(*BAS Accreditation Handbook V10a*, 2024, p. 3)

This research project embodies these three principles as it aims to investigate a specific disciplinary context to better understand literacy needs and textual practices and raise awareness of the needs associated with this context, texts and practices. The disciplinary context under investigation is a university architecture department. As an EdD project, the overall aim is to develop EAP provision informed by the context.

1.2.1. Contextualisation

During pre-sessional courses, students need to demonstrate the required language level to progress onto their chosen course. This places much emphasis on the language level of students but also recognises the importance of target language needs, i.e. preparing students for future study and context. In contrast, in other English Language Teaching, e.g. general English, needs analysis retains importance in terms of language level but places limited importance on the target language needs, so is less contextualised than EAP and has sometimes been referred to as TENOR (Teaching English for No Obvious Reason) (Abbott, 1980) and may cover very general language such as literature and/or grammar (Hutchinson & Waters, 2008). In contrast, needs analysis to inform syllabus design and approach is a central tenet of English for Specific Purposes, which subdivides into English for Occupational Purposes (EOP) and English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and then further subdivides into English for General Academic Purposes (EGAP) and English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Blue (1998, p. 96) ELT family tree

(Blue, 1988)

In terms of contextualisation, academic communication and literacy needs can vary depending on the context:

- macro context e.g. higher education in the UK, i.e. tertiary sector
- mezzo context, e.g. specific higher education institution, i.e. institutional
- micro context, e.g. specific subject area and/or course i.e. disciplinary

In addition, academic communication and literacy needs may differ at an individual level, i.e. students themselves (level, knowledge, experience). With such scope for variation of needs, English for Academic Purposes (EAP), as a branch of English for Specific Purposes, relies on both aspects of needs analysis:

- target situation language analysis, i.e. frequent text types or genres, students will encounter and produce during studies, as well as frequent words and phrases they will come into contact with and use during studies. Can also include Hutchinson & Waters' (2008) *necessities, lacks* and *wants*
- present situation language analysis, (learning needs), i.e. student knowledge, experience and expertise in their chosen subject as well as preparedness for university study and/or studying in English. This can also include strategy use, motivation and self-assessment.

(Brown, 2016; Bruce, 2015; Jordan, 1997)

In addition, EAP needs analysis can be conceptualised as needs viewpoints. Brown's (2016) first two needs viewpoints have some overlap with target and current

situation analysis, but also broadens to include the democratic view and analytic view:

- diagnostic view, i.e. missing [prerequisite] ESP elements which could cause harm if absent (most similar to target situation analysis)
- discrepancy view, i.e. discrepancy/difference between what students can do and should be able to do (difference between what they should be able to do in target situation and what they can currently do)
- democratic view, i.e. ESP elements stakeholders (e.g. subject experts) want
- analytic view, i.e. ESP elements students should learn next based on SLA

The democratic view is very relevant for PEAPs (practitioners in EAP), particularly those actively working with stakeholders such as receiving departments or 'course commissioners' (Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026). The analytic view is perhaps more relevant to general EFL/ESL/ESOL provision in which curricula can be developed based on particular linguistic elements and/or items in a specific order, particularly at lower language levels, e.g. CEFR A1/A2. And perhaps then less relevant to EAP provision, which often begins at B2 (sometimes B1) and often follows a more communicative approach, e.g. Just-in-Time (JIT) or Just-in-Case (JIC) syllabus (see below) rather than a more traditional approach, e.g. SLA-informed 'i+1' syllabus (Brown, 2016; Johns, 2015; Nunan, 2000). Brown (2016) problematises a solely analytic view as it assumes more knowledge than perhaps, we have about language hierarchy, and order and does not account for individual needs and/or contextual needs. Thus, EAP practitioners can draw on a range of needs viewpoints as well as incorporate a range of needs analysis methods.

PEAPs can use a multitude of needs analysis methods (Figure 3) to identify language and learning needs. These methods can also be used in tandem to collect students' necessities, lacks and wants which may differ depending on viewpoint, e.g. student 'insiders' vs subject expert 'insiders' vs PEAP 'outsiders' (Flowerdew, 2025; Hutchinson & Waters, 2008). Based on an extensive survey of published needs analysis, Serafini et al., (2015) recommend using two or more needs analysis methods (e.g. interviews and surveys) alongside triangulation via available literature in order to establish a more complete picture of learner needs as well as lacks and wants. Once established, these needs can aid selection and adaptation of available EAP materials, e.g. textbooks, or the creation of new materials and tasks. This breadth of collection methods is only limited by the time and access PEAPs have at their disposal before, during and after teaching. In many cases, PEAPs may have limited access to the students and/or future contexts before student arrival. Therefore, PEAPs may opt for more learning-centred approaches (Jordan, 1997). A learning-centred curriculum could be collaborative and involve students in decision-making about the provision (Nunan, 2000) and may involve needs analysis, such as student self-assessment. However, there are some drawbacks to such approaches. Students may struggle to identify and articulate their language needs. This can be particularly challenging for novice students, i.e. newcomers who are new to studying

in the UK and/or specific subjects and may have unrealistic expectations and/or lack background knowledge (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026).

Figure 6 Methods of collecting data for needs analyses

Figure 3: Jordan (1997, p. 39) Methods of collecting data for needs analysis diagram

After conducting a thorough needs analysis, PEAPs (EAP Practitioners) can find themselves creating bespoke contextualised materials and tasks which account for contextual needs and language in terms of macro context, i.e. tertiary sector, mezzo context, i.e. institution and micro context, i.e. discipline/subject or perhaps even individualised provision (Blue, 1988). Indeed, Hyland (2002; 2017) suggests PEAPs ‘go as far as we can’ in terms of specificity, i.e. English for **Specific** Academic Purposes (ESAP). However, as Jordan (1997) explains, decisions around specificity can be subject to local institutional considerations, e.g. available time for needs analysis and associated preparation, as well as access to specific context, texts and practices within other departments. The number of international students studying a specific course, or within a specific school and/or faculty, can be one of the most influential factors in ESAP planning. The extent to which English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) provision can be offered to specific cohorts is also subject to funding, e.g. ESAP provision may be funded by specific departments. In the absence of departmental funding, EAP may be funded centrally, e.g. ‘top-sliced’, i.e. a proportion of all international student fee income (Hill et al., 2010). In addition to funding, the identified needs and/or number of students, as well as PEAP availability will impact provision organisation, e.g. course/school/faculty specific groupings, as well as chosen tasks, syllabus and assessment.

1.2.1.1 Contextualised Approach: EGAP>ESAP

EAP student groups may be mixed in terms of subject and follow a more English for General Academic Purposes (EGAP) approach. EGAP provision often results in the adoption of a more ‘just-in-case’ (JIC) model (Johns, 2015) in which PEAPs focus on likely genres and activities students may encounter, which are considered common

across university subjects. An example of the JIC model in practice is the Writing Across the Curriculum (WAC), which features across higher education institutions in the USA. WAC provision usually takes the form of a mandatory first-year rhetoric and composition course, which teaches 'general writing' and writing is usually separated from the subject (Bazerman et al., 2005).

Pre-sessional courses often follow a similar EGAP (English for General Academic Purposes) as pre-sessional students may be from any subject and/or stage of study. In pre-sessional provision, a JIC approach could include more frequent genres of the 13 genre families, such as essays (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). Essays may be frequent across university study but may be less common in some subject areas, e.g. STEM. The BAWE corpus features just 65 essays from the Physical Sciences compared to 601 from Arts & Humanities (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). However, pre-sessional provision is not always solely EGAP and may also follow Widdowson's wide-angle approach (Ding & Bruce, 2017) and feature some ESAP elements, including, but not limited to, subject-specific texts, subject groupings, or more subject-specific assessments, e.g. student-led or department-led essay questions, choice of referencing system. Similarly, in-sessional EGAP provision may adopt a more 'JIC approach with sessions/courses focused on a particular skill, e.g. grammar, or genre: exposition essays, which students from across the institution can choose to attend based on perceived needs. A just-in-case approach has a wealth of resources to draw on, such as Garnet's 'English for Academic Study' (EAS) series, published between 2004 and 2007, with books focussing on specific skills such as 'reading' and 'listening' skills. And other publishers, such as the University of Michigan Press producing similar skills-based EAP books during this period (Gillet, n.d.-a). In recent years, publishers such as Macmillan Education have published editions of their 'Skillful' range with each book focused on 2 or more skills, e.g. listening and speaking skills. Other EGAP books may feature a more integrated skills approach covering all four main language skills such as EAP Foundations & EAP Frameworks (2010 & 2014) and more recently the Oxford [University Press] EAP series. This is by no means an exhaustive list, but with departmental budget constraints, textbooks may be difficult to fund. Instead, PEAPs may need to rely on already available in-house materials as well as other available materials such as UEfAP, EAP Foundation as well as MOOCs (FutureLearn, 2025). However, these 'off the peg' generic materials may not always be suitable for ESAP provision and PEAPs may need to adapt and/or create bespoke materials to address the specific needs of specific groups. Flowerdew and Peacock (2001) suggest that custom-made materials are one of the identifying characteristics of EAP provision.

1.2.2 Constructively aligned

1.2.2.1 Principles

Stevens (1988) introduced a matrix to describe ESP (and resulting EAP) in terms of characteristics, claims and perspectives. The four absolute characteristics and related claims can be summarised as:

- distinct from general English teaching and TENOR approaches (not only in terms of specificity but also location, e.g. universities)
- designed to meet the needs of the learner (through target and current situation needs analysis)
- related and relevant in content to the context
- featuring language appropriate to activities as well as the context

Constructively aligned EAP provision must be informed by the context students are in or hoping to join and underpinned by principles and theories from language teaching and applied linguistics. Context is key for EAP. As previously mentioned, EAP provision should be contextualised to address differing language needs associated with specific contexts. Contexts, and the people within these contexts, shape the language as well as pedagogic practices. The importance of [target] context for language learning is widely acknowledged among the linguistics community (Butt et al., 2000; Halliday, 1999). The purpose of language is to communicate a message. The message (or text) itself, as well as the way in which the message is shared, is influenced by the contexts and participants. Halliday (1994, p. 24) claimed 'text represents choice...from the total set of options' available within the context.

The importance of context is rooted not only in linguistics research but also in anthropological and ethnographic research. Ethnographic research involves 'sustained engagement' within the context (Lillis, 2008). This sustained engagement not only allows for thick description of the context and contextual practices but also for collection of linguistic/textual data, i.e. contextual and situated language (Swales, 1998b). Ethnographic research developed from traditional anthropological studies about community practices in which research is conducted within the research context. Malinowski and other anthropologists would collect data from the participants within the context (2003). In the 1920s, Malinowski was the first to call for an extension to the notion of context and propose the term 'context of situation'. For Malinowski (2003) and many linguists after him, e.g. Firth and Halliday, language and context are inextricably linked, and the conditions in which the language is used (social context) should be considered alongside language use (content) in order to understand the text. (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Martin, 1984, 1992). Halliday (1994) went further and via his language as a social process theory 'Systemic Functional Linguistics', he drew parallels between Malinowski's 'context of culture' and *genre* and Malinowski's 'context of situation' and *register* (Eggins, 2004; Halliday, 1999; Martin, 1992). When different text types/genres share the same context of situation, they are said to share the same register.

A group that shares the same social context, i.e. context of culture and context of situation, may share similar content in terms of language and texts and may even self-identify as a community. From a linguistic perspective, Swales provided a conceptual framework he called a discourse community with:

1. Shared goals: broadly agreed set of common public [and often historical] goals [e.g. *shared intellectual endeavour of pursuit and dissemination of subject knowledge*]
2. Shared correspondence: mechanisms of intercommunications among members often with predictable timing, i.e. rhythms [e.g. *meetings, bulletins, newsletters, noticeboards*]
3. Shared information: participatory mechanisms for information and feedback [e.g. *departmental research forums and/or conferences sharing current research progress*]
4. Shared texts: possess one or more genres (text types) to reach goals [e.g. *shared conventions in discipline-specific texts such as journal articles*]
5. Shared language: specialised lexis (terminology) [e.g. *community-specific / departmental terms*]
6. Shared membership: threshold level of members with relevant expertise [e.g. *students enter as novices/apprentices, and some students remain and others join the community/department and become experts when able to demonstrate understanding and contribution to 5 other characteristics*]
7. Shared silential relations: shared and accepted expectations and situated norms of often implicit 'unsayable' shared knowledge [e.g. *abbreviations which do not require explanation for community members*]
8. Shared rhythms: a shared community history and past, and a predictable rhythm of events [e.g. *graduation and 'grad show'*]

(Sizer, 2025; Swales, 2002; Swales, 2016)

Swales' linguistic perspective of a discourse community may include a community of members not always in the same physical context, but who communicate via written rather than spoken communication, e.g. community of architects communicating via journal or trade magazine articles. Whereas, from a more sociological perspective, in Lave & Wenger's (1991) community of practice (CoP), the situated (physical) context is emphasised and may also include face-to-face spoken communication (Bruce, 2015). Swales' (1998) textography used a discourse community framework but included communities who shared the same physical context, so adopted both textual analysis and more ethnographic techniques. In a pracademic (portmanteau of practitioner and academic) context, academic and practitioner discourse communities, and associated shared texts, may influence the pedagogic community of practice and associated communication and vice versa. Therefore, research exploring pracademic contexts, e.g. creative disciplines may opt for a more text-based linguistic analysis of a discourse community or a more speech-based ethnographic analysis of a community of practice. But both frameworks and approaches value analysing the context and practices and texts.

Figure 4: Gillet (2025) UEfaP 'Levels of Communication: discourse-semantics'

For systemic functional linguists, the social context and language are important in understanding texts. As previously explained, the social context includes the 'context of culture' and 'context of situation'. Halliday conceptualises three dimensions encompassing the context of situation (or register) plane. These three dimensions of context of situation (field/tenor/mode) correspond to three metafunctions at a linguistic level, i.e. discourse-semantics.

- *field: What is taking place and being communicated? How are ideas being managed?* i.e. the social action expressed in texts through ideational meanings at a discourse level and transitivity systems at a lexicogrammar level.
- *tenor: Who is participating? How are relationships managed?* i.e. relationships and roles of community participants expressed in texts through interpersonal meanings at a discourse level and mood/modality systems at a lexicogrammar level.
- *mode: What role is language playing in the text being made? How is the text managed?* i.e. function of texts expressed through textual meanings at a discourse level and Theme/Rheme systems at a lexicogrammar level.

(Butt et al., 2000; Eggins, 2004; Martin, 1992; Swales, 2002)

Halliday's extensive functional grammar can be used to analyse texts in several ways, including texture and structure. *Texture* includes the text's coherence with its extratextual social and cultural context and the text's cohesion, i.e. how meanings fit

together in a text and how clauses are connected (Eggins, 2004). In Systemic Functional Linguistics, Theme refers to “the order of constituents in a clause” (Martin, 1984, p. 23). The first being ‘Theme’ which helps link and orientate clause to wider context, such as text development, e.g. paragraph, and at the end, new information (Rheme) (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014; Martin, 1984). While *structure* refers to the obligatory structural elements that provide the shape of the text and how sections are ordered and connected (e.g. macrostructure of a text) (Butt et al., 2000; Hasan, 1998).

EAP is based not only on theoretical principles but also pedagogic principles. For example, Flowerdew and Peacock (2001) suggested the following EAP pedagogic principles in addition to Strevens’ (1988) ESP matrix. These pedagogic principles are summarised below with added hedging as describing EAP as a set of particular idealised principles does not allow for the importance of context, and therefore contextual constraints.

- EAP is distinctive from ELT in terms of not only purposefulness but also in terms of students, e.g. adults preparing for university.
- Designing EAP provision to meet specified needs may result in creation of custom-made and tailored materials.
- EAP provision may include authentic texts.
- EAP usually adopts a communicative task-based approach.

One of the most dominant principles in EAP is Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). This pedagogic approach fosters students’ communicative competence in the classroom rather than passive learning. Ma (2009, p. 40) claims “communicative Language Teaching has a rich, if somewhat eclectic, theory base” and is derived from a multidisciplinary perspective (Savignon, 1991). CLT draws on linguistic theory via the systemic functional linguistic description of language as a social semiotic, as both content (language) and context, and combines with communicative competence alongside other competency frameworks such as intercultural competence (Savignon, 1991). CLT also draws on educational and sociolinguistic theories such as Dewey’s learning by doing, i.e. communicate to learn language and Kolb’s experiential learning, as well as others, such as Vygotsky’s zone of proximal development, i.e. feedback on communication (Savignon, 1991).

Despite CLT being dominant, it should not be assumed to be the only approach and/or applied consistently across EAP. In fact, some have advocated for more ‘principled eclecticism’ (Mellow, 2002) drawing from broader pedagogic principles, as well as diverse knowledge reservoirs as a result of practitioner experience as well as training, e.g. CELTA and/or study, e.g. MA TESOL.

1. Learning is development.
2. Learning is a thinking process.
3. Learning in an active process.*
4. Learning involves making decisions.

5. Learning a language is not just a matter of linguistic knowledge.
6. Second language learners are already communicatively competent.*
7. Learning is an emotional experience.
8. Learning is not systematic.
9. Learning needs should be considered at every stage of the learning process.
(Jordan, 2002 p.100)

**some crossover with CLT approach*

The principles used to inform EAP practice are not restricted to English Language Teaching (ELT) and/or education-based practice but also draw on theories and studies from applied linguistics, such as Swales' genre theory. For Swales (2002), the starting point of a genre is that it needs to be a communicative event. If a collection of communicative events has a shared set of communicative purposes, it may be considered a genre. Genre exemplars may differ but should be prototypical, i.e. have similar patterns in terms of form, structure and audience. Note here that Nesi and Gardner (2012) expanded genre to genre families which have similar social purposes, stages and network but could be realised by different example texts. Also, for Swales (2002), a genre's purposes and conventions are shared and recognised by members of the discourse community and may only be partially identified by novices or non-members. Finally, discourse community members have the 'greatest genre-specific expertise' and as such are a valuable source of information and understanding as the authors and/or audiences of the genre (Swales, 2022). Many pre-sessional and in-sessional courses can follow a genre-based approach, which aims to introduce students to genres commonly found in academic contexts and familiarise students with the moves and steps which feature in specific genres. However, this approach can assume genre stability, which contrasts with new rhetoric/rhetorical genre approaches from the USA. New rhetoric/rhetorical genre approaches take a more critical approach to genre and focus more on exploiting rather than teaching genres (Bruce, 2015).

In addition to knowledge of genre, Ferguson (1997) suggested two additional areas (three in total) of specialised [professional] knowledge for PEAPs.

- *knowledge of genre and discourse*
- knowledge of disciplinary cultures and values (essentially sociological or anthropological)
- knowledge of the epistemological basis of different disciplines (philosophical)

1.2.3. Collaborative

In order to understand a specific community and associated contextual practices, PEAPs require authentic texts for linguistic analysis. These authentic texts are often collected in collaboration with the target community through three main research methods: ethnographic, genre and corpus research (Bruce, 2015). Firstly, the aim of ethnographic research is to develop understanding through a rich and thick description of the context, often through methods such as observations of the

community and/or interviews with community members. Ethnographic studies of specific contexts have been particularly influential for ESAP provision (Paltridge et al., 2016). Secondly, genre research collects shared texts from the community and analyses the text types and shared language. Genre analysis may follow a Swalesian approach, identifying the moves and steps and associated language within these moves and steps. An influential, and ubiquitous in EAP provision, example of this is Swales' CARS (Create a Research Space), detailing the moves and steps for introduction (Swales, 2002). A Systemic Functional Linguistics approach to genre analysis analyses the structure and texture of authentic texts (Martin, 1984; Monbec, 2020). For example, some EAP provision may explicitly teach Theme and Rheme to support student cohesion. Thirdly, corpus studies collect a range of authentic texts such as the BAWE corpus and can generate word lists based on frequency of certain lexical items. Groundbreaking research by Coxhead produced the Academic Word List (Coxhead, 2011), which has spawned many wordlists ranging in specificity, such as Business Word List (Hsu, 2011). These three methods are not always used in isolation and can be used in combination. For example, Nesi and Gardner's influential thirteen genre families work is closely associated with corpus linguistics but also adopts some genre analysis and includes interviews (a method most commonly associated with ethnography).

These authentic texts not only support PEAPs in understanding of texts and practices within a specific context or discipline but can also support student understanding through the use of authentic texts as exemplars. Exemplars can represent the language features of a specific genre, particularly when this genre is being assessed (Smyth, 2019). These exemplars can be collected in collaboration and/or corpus data. PEAPs may use corpus tools such as SketchEngine to identify academic texts from a corpus such as BAWE (British Academic Writing in English) or MiCASE (Michigan Academic Speaking in English) to identify samples from specific subject areas or genre or text type (e.g. Flax Greenstone for PhD abstracts (Fitzgerald et al., 2017) and/or include a particular language feature, e.g. stance (Nesi & Gardner, 2017). Students can also use corpus tools such as SKELL (Sketch Engine for Language Learners) or CorpusMate but may need support in navigating these tools.

As previously discussed, exemplars can be used as a template but can also be used to demonstrate the choices available to students (Smyth & Carless, 2021). These exemplars may be written by students or published exemplars from the discourse community, or may even be teacher-constructed (Smyth & Carless, 2021) or even AI-generated. EAP materials may be considered authentic if realistic, e.g. viewed as correct by subject specialists, but may also be considered communicatively authentic, i.e. covering appropriate language, or operationally authentic, i.e. simulations or roleplay (Strevens, 1988). Some authentic exemplars and/or textbook exemplars may be too linguistically challenging for students based on language needs, so PEAPs may need to supplement, adapt or even generate new materials

(Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026). These adaptation processes can include, but are not limited to:

- adapting challenging vocabulary
- converting mode (listening/speaking) or re-genreing
- expanding via examples and/or definitions
- shortening/reordering
- simplifying through modifying content, e.g. textual density
- supplementing with additional accessible texts
(Stoller, 2016)

However, ideally, this adaptation should not be conducted in isolation. Dudley-Evans and St John (2003) called for PEAPs to move beyond cooperation, and Raimes' waiter metaphor, and later Hyland's handmaiden metaphor, or Pecorari and Coxhead's 'Cinderella status' and towards more collaboration with subject specialists (Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026; Hyland, 2006; Raimes, 1991). Collaboration and cooperation are central tenets of BALEAP Accreditation Scheme and opportunities for engaging with the disciplines can vary across institutions and departments. In EGAP provision, cooperation may take the form of texts, genres or tasks suggested by subject specialists. In ESAP provision, PEAPs may be assigned roles encouraging cooperation, such as ESAP module convener or Academic Literacy and Language or work within institutions with a subject focus, e.g. arts-based or STEM-focussed institutions (Tibbetts & Chapman, 2023). Cooperation with disciplines within an assigned role may involve opportunities such as access to virtual learning environment (VLE), invitations to meetings, e.g. boards, or even observation of subject specialist provision, such as attending lectures or observing, e.g. studio teaching (Bernstein, 2021). These observations can inform planning of ESAP provision from prioritising genres featured across a number of modules or focussing on particular skills and/or assessments.

This cooperation may result in opportunities for collaboration with subject specialists via collaborative discussion and work on materials development and/or changes to assessment. The distinction here between cooperation and collaboration depends on flow of information and learning. PEAPs may find themselves receiving requests and information from the disciplines and may feel they are working 'for' the subject specialists. Ideally, there should be bidirectional learning with both parties learning from the collaboration. Thus, PEAPs may feel they are working 'with' the subject specialists. Dudley-Evans and St John (1998) suggest methods for collaboration, including parallel provision in which the ESAP class 'follows' a subject specialist class, often providing simplified texts and discussions around sources, lectures and/or assessments to consolidate knowledge. Pecorari and Coxhead (2026) advocate for collaboration between PEAPs and subject specialists in identification of students' needs, as well as joint development of materials, assessment, research e.g. subject specialists and PEAPs presenting together at BALEAP and/or team-

teaching. Dudley-Evans and St John (1998) suggest that the ultimate collaboration via team-teaching can result in collaborative materials and/or assessment alongside team-taught sessions in which both parties are present and work collaboratively with students. This type of collaboration requires a close working relationship between subject specialist and PEAP and considerable investment of time and resources (Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026). These collaborations can be challenging without an assigned role and/or secondment.

In summary, EAP is a type of English Language Teaching designed for a specific purpose, i.e. university study/academia. EAP is defined by its contextualisation, constructive alignment and collaboration. EAP teaching is contextualised, drawing on needs analysis of not only the students' current language needs but also target language analysis of future language use, e.g. academic context. EAP can adopt a more specific or generic approach (ESAP or EGAP) depending on contextual factors, including the students and their associated language needs. EAP teaching is also constructively aligned and adopts several principles from English for Specific Purposes to inform teaching such as distinctions from general English Language Teaching, informed by needs analysis and contextually relevant. EAP is collaborative and uses authentic and/or adapted texts where possible. In addition to being contextualised, constructively aligned and collaborative, EAP also draws on theory and research from educational/pedagogical perspectives: ESP, ELT, academic literacies and broader education field, as well as linguistics perspectives: SFL corpus, genre and sociocultural perspectives: ethnography, anthropology, sociology.

1.3. EAP knowledge reservoir

The EAP knowledge reservoir is based on many of the principles and theories discussed previously, e.g. education (including language teaching) principles and theories, linguistics principles and theories (such as Systemic Functional Linguistics) and sociocultural principles and theories (such as intercultural communicative competence). These theoretical frameworks and pedagogic principles, alongside several influential empirical studies, continue to inform EAP practice. Influential studies from ELT include Dörnyei's (1990) study on motivation of language learners at a language school, which helped develop our understanding of learner motivation as dynamic and changeable over time and influenced by the context but also by the learners themselves, i.e. how they think about themselves, identities and previous learning experiences. This resulted in teachers reflecting on their own practice, particularly around supporting students' motivation, e.g. teacher supportive motivational discourse (Salimi et al., 2022). Further examples of influential studies on practice include studies on specific pedagogic practices such as flipped learning (Hung, 2017) or particular pedagogic approaches, e.g. drama for speaking skills (Galante & Thomson, 2017) or specific language subskills, e.g. pronunciation (Smotrova, 2017). Note that all 3 previous studies were in the top 5 'most downloaded' articles from TESOL Quarterly, with downloads perhaps having more influence on practice than citations, which may have more influence on research.

The other two most downloaded articles were also related to motivation and pronunciation. Influential studies for EAP have included pedagogic practices such as authentic lecture recordings for listening skills (Flowerdew & Miller, 1997), practices such as task-based learning for reading (Carrell & Carson, 1997) and practices such as process approach to thesis writing, e.g. proposals (Paltridge, 1997) or assessment practices (Feak & Salehzadeh, 2001).

In general, education-based research tends to focus, although not exclusively, and there is considerable crossover, on practices. However, some education or practitioner-based research includes practices but focuses more on the context, either the current context (EAP learning) or future context, e.g. academic department. These contextual explorations can take the form of ethnographic studies and in situ studies of communities. Ethnographic studies often involve data collection methods such as observation of practices and/or interviews about context and practice. However, ethnography is not only a research method but also underpinned by methodological assumptions about naturalism (i.e. authentic texts and practices), understanding (i.e. emic/insider understanding via deep engagement and thick description) and discovery (i.e. hypothesis building) (Hammersley, 1994; Sizer, 2021). Similarly, Collins and Holliday (2022) describe ethnographically-informed EAP research as:

- Ethnography is more than just ethnographic methods and should go further and explore not only the context (e.g. department) but also the broader context (e.g. higher education) and associated areas, e.g. power and identities.
- Allow meanings about context and contextual writing practices to emerge from discovery, i.e. hypothesis building rather than hypothesis testing.
- Noticing how community members respond and interact within the context through deep engagement.
- Using thick descriptions to connect and reflect on instances and develop understanding of meaning.

In recent years, there have been several influential ethnographic accounts of higher education and/or academic writing, such as Lillis' (2008) work with student writers, particularly 'non-traditional' and/or female students, around their writing practices and identities. Lillis and her coauthors have also used ethnographic studies to explore academic writing from the perspective of academics. Other ethnographic studies have also focussed on student writing and implications for teachers and/or academic writing by academics (Guillen-Galve & Bocanegra-Valle, 2021; Paltridge et al., 2016). Paltridge et al. (2016) provide examples of ethnographic approaches such as autoethnography in which the researcher takes a participant/researcher role and reflects on own academic writing. These autoethnographic approaches can include PEAPs exploring their own writing practices as well as pedagogic practices and identities as a solo endeavour or also as a duoethnography (Winiarska-Pringle & Rolińska, 2024) or collaborative autoethnography (Carr et al., 2022). Paltridge et al.

(2016) also include textography, a type of linguistic ethnography first developed by Swales and the methodology used in this thesis.

Linguistic ethnography, such as textography, combines data collection and analysis methods to develop understandings of context, texts and practices (Sizer, 2021). In contrast, most linguistics-based research tends to focus less on practices and contexts and more on texts. Influential studies include genre approaches to textual analysis, but can also include some elements of practice, e.g. Hyon's reflections (2001) on genre-based instruction for developing reading skills. In addition, Ding & Bruce (2017) as well as Flowerdew & Peacock (2021) suggest Hyland's (1994) study on hedging in scientific discourse compared to textbooks (teaching practices) as a landmark publication. Flowerdew & Peacock (2021) also suggest Tarone et al's (1998) study of the passive and active voice in astrophysics articles as particularly helpful for PEAPs. Other suggestions for influential studies from Flowerdew and Peacock (2021) include texts students receive rather than produce, e.g. introductory textbooks (Love, 1991) and lectures (Thompson, 1994). Others include texts students may have roles beyond the audience, e.g. presenting in seminars (Weissberg, 1993). However, studies have primarily focused on research articles (Flowerdew & Peacock, 2021), which students may be expected to read but are often not the intended audience, i.e. wider discourse community. Much of what we 'know' and teach about writing dissertations and theses is based on research articles, e.g. IMRD (Introduction, Method, Result, Discussion) macrostructure and moves and steps within particular sections, e.g. CARS (Create A Research Space) for introductions (Swales, 2002). Research articles share new knowledge and are written by experts for an expert audience, whereas PhD students play more of an 'apprentice expert' sharing new knowledge whilst also demonstrating knowledge of the field (Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026). In 1999, Dudley-Evans pleaded with the PEAP community to also study under-researched genres students write themselves, e.g. dissertations, in which students are considered more novices than experts.

Since Dudley-Evans' (1999) call, numerous studies have investigated dissertation writing using both linguistic and ethnographic approaches. Paltridge et al. (2016) list several examples of ethnographic research on dissertations, such as roles and expectations of postgraduate student writers. There is also an increasing body of literature on doctoral dissertations, which includes the structure and types of dissertations, i.e. traditional simple; traditional complex; topic-based & PhD by publication (Paltridge et al., 2016; Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). Others include the difficulties relating to writing doctoral dissertations, particularly a qualitative dissertation, which Belcher and Hirvela (2005) refer to as a 'fuzzy' genre based on (Medway, 2002), i.e. 'many modes of realisation'. A further complexity for dissertation writing is disciplinary variation, e.g. in history it may be called a 'long essay', in engineering a 'project' and in other subjects a 'dissertation', while all are part of the 'research report' genre family (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). These disciplinary differences may also be reflected in the research report's macrostructure, e.g. a genre-based

IMRD structure or less common topic-based macrostructure (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). Academic writing research may also explore linguistic features within dissertations, e.g. transitivity as part of field and ideational metafunction, exploring the use of verbs and associated process types and actors and goals (Manar et al., 2020) or exploring tenor and interpersonal metafunction through appraisal system and author's voice and stance (Loghmani et al., 2020). Note, many studies draw on research articles and/or doctoral dissertations as data and/or a source of comparison with undergraduate/postgraduate dissertations. Academic writing research can also explore the mode and textual metafunction via the texture, i.e. the cohesion and coherence of text through thematic structure (Butt et al., 2000). For example, Suharsono et al., (2024) compared the type of Themes, i.e. marked/unmarked, in undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral dissertations. As in the case for structure, texture may also be subject to disciplinary variation. For example, Hewings and North (2009) found disciplinary differences in Theme in undergraduate essays, with history of science essays featuring significantly more marked Themes than in geography essays.

1.3.1. ESAP gap

As discussed, PEAPs can draw upon research from the EAP knowledge reservoir. This research may involve various methods to investigate a range of texts, practices and contexts. However, some subjects and contexts continue to dominate. Business and Management, the most popular university subject (*Governance News Alert: HESA Enrolment Data 2023/24 | Advance HE*, n.d.), with over half a million enrolments in 2022, tends to attract the largest numbers of international students. Over a quarter of a million non-UK students enrolled on business and management courses in 2022/2023, and over 150,000 non-UK students enrolled on STEM courses (engineering, technology, computing & subjects allied to medicine) (Table 3). It is no wonder then that some subjects such as business or science or engineering have several ESAP options for PEAPs to select and/or adapt, e.g. Garnet ESAP coursebook range includes 17 subjects (mainly business or STEM but also law, languages & linguistics) or Disigma ESAP coursebook range includes 8 mainly science coursebooks, or the Market Leader range of coursebooks for business subjects from Pearson, or standalone books such as Bailey's Academic Writing for International Students of *Business* and *Economics* now in its 3rd edition. This glut of resources is market-driven as more international students study these subjects. This may also explain the dominance of ESAP research in these subjects, as these students are also more likely to feature in research. For example, the BAWE corpus features just 9 students' written assessments from architecture representing just 0.3% of the corpus and is the least represented of all the named disciplines (apart from 'other'). This compares to 146 from business and over 200 (238) from engineering (Heuboeck et al., 2019).

However, the predominance of research with business/STEM subjects is not only a predictable consequence of larger student populations but also reflects historically

established research traditions in these areas. In the 1960s and 1970s, there was a dramatic increase in research analysing scientific and technical English, so much so, that at the time, ESP (English for Specific Purposes) was almost synonymous with English for Science and Technology (EST) (Hutchinson & Waters, 2008). Again, this research appears to be, in part, market-driven with enormous interest in learning not only EST (English for Science and Technology) but also Business English to support technology and commerce after the Second World War (Hutchinson & Waters, 2008).

This predominance for research on business/STEM subjects continues to be a significant trend for EAP (Table 2):

Table 2: BALEAP conference abstracts

BALEAP 2017	Fewer than 30 ESAP presentations (90%+ business or STEM subjects)
BALEAP 2019	Fewer than 30 ESAP presentations (90%+ business or STEM subjects)
BALEAP 2021	Fewer than 10 ESAP presentations (80%+ business or STEM subjects)
BALEAP 2023	Fewer than 10 ESAP presentations (90%+ business or STEM subjects)

Table 2 provides a general overview of ESAP research at BALEAP conferences. However, some ESAP research may have been overlooked, e.g. 'ESAP' not stated in the abstract. It is also worth noting that some of these BALEAP conference abstracts include other subjects, in addition to business and STEM. The dominance of business and/or STEM is also replicated in conference proceedings. In 2025, BALEAP's conference proceedings were published as open access and featured 14 full articles. Three articles explicitly mentioned ESAP, and two articles mentioned EAP with specific cohorts. All 5 articles had a business or STEM focus.

1.3.2. ESAP gap: architecture

When assigned a group of architecture students, locating suitable ESAP resources and research was challenging. Like most PEAPs, the majority of my experience and expertise was developed with business and/or STEM students. It was also difficult to draw upon experience and expertise of colleagues, as in many contexts, just one PEAP role covered architecture, or often all of the creative disciplines. In the hope of bringing together PEAPs with experience, or even resources and research, I helped found the BALEAP Creative Disciplines Special Interest Group, which I continue to convene. As a SIG, we continue to share helpful readings and often bespoke resources to support ESAP for creative disciplines. We have also shared and conducted research into ESAP for Creative Disciplines. This EdD research project

aims to provide PEAPs with an accessible methodology to explore creative disciplines within their own contexts as well as adding to the limited range of available ESAP research for creative disciplines, particularly architecture. Given the real-world problem of limited practitioner resources and research, this project seeks to develop a better understanding of how architecture students write, given the underrepresentation in research and resources, despite increasing number of international students. As can be seen from Table 3, enrolments for architecture have been steadily increasing. Additionally, over 25% of architecture students are ‘Non-UK’, international students, representing a large proportion of architecture cohorts and one of the top 10 (8) subjects with the largest total of ‘Non-UK’ students.

Table 3 HESA HE student enrolments by CAH level 1 subject and sex [sex removed, just totals] Academic years 2018/19 to 2022/23 Architecture highlighted

		2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23
	Subject Area	Total	Total	Total	Total	Total
	Total	2,457,250	2,529,485	2,747,090	2,857,855	2,937,155
	Total non-science CAH level 1	1,346,105	1,395,380	1,505,205	1,563,945	1,613,320
	Total science CAH level 1	1,111,145	1,134,105	1,241,890	1,293,910	1,323,835
1	17 Business and management	384,900	412,650	475,145	530,580	587,165
2	02 Subjects allied to medicine	296,530	292,230	334,085	361,340	369,455
3	15 Social sciences	227,610	260,325	282,595	286,225	285,540
4	25 Design, and creative and performing arts	184,705	186,990	190,180	189,930	188,535
5	10 Engineering and technology	167,805	175,245	183,165	185,725	185,830
6	11 Computing	116,000	132,130	153,830	164,260	180,640
7	16 Law	112,865	122,795	138,145	142,315	146,590
8	04 Psychology	111,125	119,090	135,085	140,425	141,065
9	22 Education and teaching	142,935	129,880	136,030	135,980	130,000
10	03 Biological and sport sciences	126,535	112,950	117,320	117,510	117,830
11	19 Language and area studies	102,505	96,705	92,635	87,800	84,890
12	01 Medicine and dentistry	68,000	70,555	77,050	81,665	84,230
13	20 Historical, philosophical and religious studies	88,600	86,080	85,990	83,085	79,040
14	13 Architecture, building and planning	57,540	59,570	62,235	63,630	67,035
15	07 Physical sciences	63,110	66,465	68,195	67,205	66,305

<https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/08-08-2024/sb269-higher-education-student-statistics/subjects>

1.4. Pracademic gap

In Blue’s (1988) ELT family tree, we can see that the focus of EAP is academic rather than occupational purposes. Most of the texts authored by students at university are intended solely for an academic audience. This is particularly prevalent at doctoral level where the intention is to share new knowledge with an academic audience and perhaps later participate as a member of that discourse community (Swales, 2002). For a number of university subjects, e.g. applied linguistics, archaeology and English literature, students are being prepared for future academic life and research within the university context and academy (Flowerdew & Peacock, 2001). Many EAP researchers may also consider themselves a former and/or current member of one of these discourse communities (particularly applied linguistics) or, by extension, part of the wider university/academic community. However, in contrast,

more ‘pracademic’ (practitioner/academic) subjects, such as architecture and nursing, prepare students for occupational life outside university. And as a result, texts may have a wider audience beyond university and may reflect the texts and genres of a more occupational, rather than a purely academic context, meaning distinction between EAP and EOP is not ‘wholly clear-cut’ (Flowerdew, 2025, p. 130). Perhaps, EAP should, as Flowerdew and Peacock (2001) suggest, be subdivided into ‘academic’, i.e. focussed on the subject of study, or ‘occupational’, i.e. focussed on the intended occupation or ‘English for *general* academic contexts’ and ‘English for disciplinary contexts’ (including university AND workplace settings) (Flowerdew, 2025). An alternative approach would be my suggestion for the introduction of EPP (English for **Pracademic** Purposes) teaching, materials and research to sit alongside and complement English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and English for Occupational Purposes (EOP).

Figure 5 ESP family tree with the addition of EPP

An EPP (English for Pracademic Purposes) approach would need to include research and exploration beyond linguistic analysis of texts authored and consumed by students, and also seek knowledge of texts, practices and context of the wider discourse community. The texts featured in EPP research could be similar in terms of genre to those often featured in EAP research, e.g. essays, which are ubiquitous across academic contexts. Essays across the disciplines may share a social purpose, i.e. demonstrate an ability to construct an argument and employ critical thinking skills (Nesi & Gardner, 2012), but may differ in terms of network. For example, essays at university often have one reader in mind, i.e. academic audience (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). In contrast, pracademic essays, such as architecture essays, may be written for an academic audience but share features of genres

written for a practitioner audience, i.e. architecture magazine and as a result, may be multimodal in format, such as illustrated essays (Parnell, 2023).

In contrast to more traditional academic genres, many courses also include genres with a more explicit pracademic focus and shared social purpose, i.e. 'preparing for professional practice', such as case study, design specification, problem question and proposal (Nesi & Gardner, 2012) and may feature in EAP and/or EOP research and teaching. For the creative disciplines (including architecture), many texts may combine academic, professional as well as creative influences and result in hybrid genres (Carr et al., 2022) with sections and/or stages from several genre families. These hybrid genres can also be described as 'fuzzy' genres because there are many possible textual responses to the assessment brief. For example, Medway (2002) defined architectural sketchbooks as a fuzzy genre. Dissertations have also been described as a similarly fuzzy genre (Belcher & Hirvela, 2005). This thesis seeks to explore the fuzzy nature of undergraduate dissertations within architecture, as well as variation in purposes and practices of dissertations for community members (Damron & Spector, 2010).

1.5 ESAP/EOP research with architecture

1.5.1. Research objectives

- Identify language choices architecture students make in terms of structure and texture in academic written texts, i.e. dissertations.
- Explore reasons why architecture students make these language choices in academic written texts.

1.5.2. Methodology

The methodological approach used in this project is 'textography'. A type of linguistic ethnography, first introduced by Swales (1998), which combines linguistic analysis of texts with contextual understandings of practices via ethnographic interviews. This research goes further than adopting ethnographic methods and operates within interpretivist/constructivist research paradigm and is underpinned by academic literacies (Lillis, 2008; Tuck, 2022). The theoretical framework also draws on Systemic Functional Linguistics, a language-as-social-process theory which explores how language is structured for use and how people use language in different contexts (Eggins, 2004). Systemic Functional Linguistics also forms part of the analytical framework as texts will be analysed in terms of structure (macrostructure: section headings, type of dissertation) and texture (Theme and Rheme structure). The analytical approach of systemic functional linguistics of texts is combined with Braun and Clarke's (2022) thematic analysis and interpretation of interview data to develop understanding of emic perspectives of authors and intended audience as well as etic/outsider perspective based on linguistic analysis.

The conceptual framework is based on the textographic triangle: texts, context and practices (Sizer, 2021). The texts are undergraduate architecture dissertations, the context is an architecture school at a university in the UK, and the practices are the writing practices and language choices made by students and pedagogic and other practices which informed these choices.

Figure 6 Conceptual framework diagram

1.5.3. Principal findings:

a) dissertation choices

Dissertation writing practices for undergraduate architecture students differ from academic writing practices by experts and other academic writing at postgraduate level. Undergraduate architecture dissertations do not represent the final submission, so may have less prominence than the end-of-year show for architecture students. Undergraduate architecture students may be given a list of possible dissertation topics to choose from, indicating support needed from experts and not yet a fully-fledged member of community. Undergraduate architecture students are not explicitly taught research methods, so primary data collection methods are uncommon.

b) dissertation structure (+ influences)

Undergraduate architecture dissertations can range from a more traditional genre-based macrostructure, or a more topic-based macrostructure or can include a more complex multiple study structure. Architecture textbooks and instructional materials advise a structure more in keeping with a long essay than a traditional dissertation. This reflects the secondary nature of much of the data included in undergraduate architecture dissertations and often results in a more topic-based structure. Students may be influenced in terms of structure by other research reports, such as research articles, but may also be influenced by exemplar architecture dissertations available via the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE).

c) dissertation texture (+ influences)

Due to the fuzziness, as well as hybridity of undergraduate architecture dissertations (part academic dissertation/part professional portfolio), architecture students have more choices in terms of texture. The layout can be landscape, instead of portrait, and include multiple columns and layout can change from page to page. Undergraduate architecture dissertations are also multimodal and include a number of images. The images are not often directly referred to in the text but often maintain an equal status with the language and image working together to deliver the meaning. Placement of images and interplay between language and text can be a personal stylistic choice and can be influenced by professional genres such as architecture magazines and other genres from creative disciplines, e.g. blog posts. Students are expected to demonstrate research skills and knowledge but also present this in a creative and aesthetically pleasing dissertation. Theme and Rheme choices are often implicit but may be influenced by the type of dissertation structure and approach, e.g. topic-based secondary data dissertations may have more textual themes due to more narrativization but may also be influenced by personal stylistic choices.

1.5.4. Implications

The main implications of this research project are for PEAP community and approaches to needs analysis and pedagogy for students studying pracademic subjects. English for Pracademic Purposes pedagogy could foster needs analysis of not only the current but also future context of language use, e.g. architecture studio.

For architecture educators, this research project may make some of the language choices available to undergraduate dissertation writers more explicit. For architecture students, I hope a future book with possible language choices can serve as a more explicit guide and support them in writing their dissertations.

1.5.5. Thesis structure

- Introduction –
- Literature review

- conceptual framework (architecture texts: pracademic & multimodal); practices: pedagogy; context: architecture)
- theoretical framework (AcLits + SFL)
- Methodology
 - Research paradigm & author positioning
 - Methodological approach – textography (justification)
 - Text collection and selection
 - Context and participants
 - Ethics (micro & macro considerations)
 - Analytical frameworks (text analysis [SFL+multimodal] & interview analysis)
 - Research objectives
- Findings & discussion chapters
 - Structure – macrostructure, dissertation types, observed choices, influences over choices (interviews + literature)
 - Texture – theme/rheme analysis, multimodal analysis (layout & image use), observed choices, influences over choices (interviews + literature)
- Conclusion
 - Research contributions and findings
 - Contribution to community
 - Contribution to scholarship
 - Limitations, implications & recommendations for future research

2. Selective review of literature which informs this study

2.1 Philosophical framework

Linguistics, my main area of practice, i.e. teaching, previous study and current research, is multi-paradigmatic. Linguistics research is also pluralistic as it can range from positivist to constructivist, to more pragmatic in positioning (Cook, 2015). My own position is constructivist/interpretivist. I draw on constructivist ontological understandings that reality is co-constructed in groups and epistemological understandings that knowledge and meanings are also co-constructed. I explore these meanings through Halliday's social semiotic theory of Systemic Functional Linguistics which states, what seems to me obvious, 'different groups of people tend to mean different things' (Halliday, 1979, p. 86).

Systemic functional linguistics also draws on interpretivist epistemological understandings that meanings are made and interpreted by participants within the context. In addition to SFL, interpretivist epistemological understandings of knowledge and meanings being interpreted within the context can also be explored through methodologies such as ethnography. Ethnography emphasises interpreting understandings of participants within the context and can draw on theories such as academic literacies.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This research project is operating within an interpretivist/constructivist paradigm and informed by not only Halliday's theory of language, i.e. SFL, but also informed by academic literacies as a theoretical lens.

2.2.1 Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) LINGUISTICS

Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) appears an appropriate theory for analysing architecture texts as it is often described as having 'extravagant architecture' (Bartlett, 2017). SFL is also described by many as an extravagant theory (Bateman, 2017). Halliday spent a lifetime articulating this rich and complex theory of language with many Systemic Functional Linguists, continuing this tradition. SFL can appear to many PEAPs as intimidating and often even impenetrable (Monbec, 2022) 'with a bewildering array of technical terms, many of which seem, at first sight, to refer to the same concept' (Bartlett, 2017). This extravagance and complexity presents a challenge not only for PEAPs, who Monbec (2022) offers a reading path to guide self-exploration of SFL, but also for those attempting to use SFL in EAP research. Summarising and synthesizing such a grand and complicated theory is not possible within the confines of an EdD literature review chapter. However, this chapter will attempt to provide a brief overview of SFL and how SFL has been used to inform EAP research, will highlight the importance of context for SFL and the synergy this

has for ESAP teaching and research. Then explain how SFL can be used to analyse texts, text type, and structure, and texture and analyse language based on textual metafunction of Theme and Rheme and provide a rationale for this particular research path. Finally, this chapter will discuss how SFL complements other theories in this study's theoretical framework such as genre theory from linguistics and ethnography as a theoretical lens.

2.2.2. Selective brief overview of SFL Linguistics theory

As I write this in Halliday's home county of Yorkshire, I'm reminded of his incredible legacy through Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). Halliday's (1961) groundbreaking paper 'Categories of the theory of grammar' introduced his initial theory of language, i.e. 'pre-SFL', in the 1960s which later became Halliday's (1979) theory of language as a social semiotic or 'SFL proper' (Bateman, 2017). Halliday's theory was largely inspired by previous work from Firth, Halliday's former PhD supervisor. Sadly, Firth died before Halliday's groundbreaking 1961 paper was published but Firth is acknowledged repeatedly as hugely influential in the development of Systemic Functional Linguistics. Firth's influential notion of the 'context of the situation', first coined by Malinowski (1923), an anthropologist involved in ethnographic research, became an integral part of Halliday's SFL theory. Both Firth and Malinowski used the term 'context of situation' to mean 'things going on in the world outside the text that make the text what it is' (Butt et al., 2000), i.e. extralinguistic or extratextual. However, both arrive at the 'context of situation' from slightly different perspectives. Malinowski's context of culture based on an ethnographic approach aims of developing understanding of culture through language use within a specific context. Whereas, Firth extended the notion of context of culture from a linguistic perspective via linguistic predictability (Eggins, 2004). Firth (1968) suggests that a description of the context (including but not limited to social structure, interpersonal relationships, and text types) can help identify and even predict language used in a specific context. In addition, Eggins (2004) explains that this predictability can also be explored via examples which can also allow for predictions about the context.

SFL is based on four main theoretical claims about language:

1. Language is a semiotic system: a process of making meanings by choosing.
2. Language use is functional.
3. Its function is to make meanings.
4. These meanings are influenced by the context in which they are exchanged.

(Eggins, 2004, p. 3)

These four claims are the foundation of SFL: Language is a series of systems (SYSTEMIC), language is functional (FUNCTIONAL), language is contextual (LINGUISTICS)

2.3 SYSTEMIC

The systemic, not to be confused with systematic, approach to language is rooted in Firth's (1968) polysystemic conception of language, with different modes of meanings such as phonetic, syntactical, and collocational, which can be deployed and analysed depending on analytical focus. Similarly, SFL views language as 'a collection of systems' (Bateman, 2017, p. 16) including the meaning potential system, as well as the multi-layered complexity of the language system. The meaning potential, or social semiotic system, is fundamentally about language choices and providing descriptions of the available choices rather than providing rules for language use, i.e. descriptive rather than prescriptive. My own research objectives are formed based on this notion from Firth and SFL: '*Identify language choices architecture students make in terms of structure and texture in academic written texts*'. Another system at work is the multilayered language system. This system is made up of different layers or strata, including social context, i.e. context of culture and context of situation as well as language and is referred to as stratification by Halliday (1979) and described by others as an 'architectural view of language' (Purser et al., 2020). In addition to social context, language is split into two layers 'content' and 'expression'. Within the content strata there is discourse-semantics or meanings and the LexicoGrammar or wordings, i.e. structures and words (Gillet, 2025). The final stratum is 'expression' with the smallest components of language: phonology, i.e. sounds, and graphology, i.e. spelling. The other networks impacting the language system are extralinguistic and relate to the social context.

Figure 7: SFL stratification onion: architectural view of language

As briefly discussed in the introduction, both SFL and EAP emphasise the importance of context for language. In SFL, context is crucial. Without an understanding of language within its social context, 'successful applications of

linguistics would be impossible' (Hasan, 2009, p. 166) as 'texts carry their contexts with them' (Eggins, 2004, p. 87). The importance of context is also emphasised in language teaching more broadly. In (ESP) English for Specific Purposes provision, a specific context, e.g. department or course, is supported and provision is often supplemented with context-specific texts and associated textual practices. This acknowledgement of the importance of context has led to several influential studies incorporating SFL research and/or approaches to explore texts in specific pedagogic contexts, often within specific disciplines, e.g. science (De Oliveira & Lan, 2014) or even specific subjects, e.g. biology (Accurso, 2020; Hao & Humphrey, 2019). This SFL research can include, but is not limited to, textual analysis of contextual texts and may also include, pedagogic techniques incorporating SFL analysis with students and/or teachers.

SFL research has also been hugely influential on academic contexts, particularly on EAP practice. After Halliday's death in 2018, a special JEAP issue on Halliday and SFL recognised how the PEAP community 'have all benefitted so much from his thinking, even if we didn't always know it.' (Gardner & Donohue, 2020, p. 1). SFL has been widely used with staff and/or students to explore academic texts within a university context. In EGAP provision, students have been taught to deconstruct contextually-relevant model texts from specific disciplines using SFL textual analysis and reconstruct and transfer to own discipline texts (Monbec, 2020). In ESAP provision, SFL has been used to analyse texts in a more specific academic context, for example business school assessment briefs and their impact on register i.e. professional or academic register in, often pre-academic, business reports (Henry, 2019). Also in a university context, ERPP (English for Research and Publication Purposes) provision, i.e. working with early career researchers, has also incorporated SFL. For example, SFL studies on texture and structure of context-specific research texts such as grant proposals in specific subjects, e.g. medicine (Stenglin & Cléirigh, 2020).

Contextualisation is a fundamental principle for EAP pedagogy. Despite this, some EAP and academic writing research has been described as having a myopic focus on texts (Lillis, 2008; Sizer, 2019a, 2021). For example, focus on texts, particularly written texts, can be prevalent in corpus linguistics research, for example, in which texts are 'torn out' (Malinowski 1923, p. 306) removed from their context or 'disembodied' (Swales, 1998a) to form a new body of texts or 'corpus'. However, some recent corpus studies have attempted to recontextualise texts, through either ethnographic interviews and/or observations, and/or may include texts from just one context or discipline or a sub-corpus from a specific context. Nesi and Gardner (2012) recontextualised BAWE corpus texts by incorporating authors and audience perspectives through ethnographic interviews with staff and students and collecting contextual texts in an attempt to provide a 'thick' description of the context. Another corpus-based approach is to collect texts from one specific context, e.g. academic department. For example, Gledhill's, (2000) Pharmaceutical Sciences corpus was

constructed following initial ethnographic research with 15 researchers at Aston University's Pharmaceutical Sciences department. However, despite a place discourse community (PDC) community who regularly work together (Swales, 1998). Gledhill (2000) describes the researchers as a 'very loose' discourse community represented by several disciplines and 22 separate journals leading to a broader context of study. Single discipline corpora or sub-corpora are often built with research articles from specific discourse communities. These discipline-specific corpora or sub-corpora are often compared to highlight disciplinary and contextual differences. Hyland's corpus featured 8 disciplines and he also interviewed specialist informants, emphasising disciplinary variation and the importance of context (2004). Hyland (2004a) also recommends questionnaires, interviews, diary entries, and observations with informants from the context alongside textual/corpus analysis to develop understanding of practices and context.

In SFL, context is conceptualised as context of situation and context of culture, and all texts occur and are shaped by both (Butt et al, 2000). The context of culture refers to the big picture and all the meanings possible in that specific culture. To use an analogy from textile [rather than text] design, the context of culture could be compared to the fashion tradition or even fashion house. The context of situation is more of a snapshot of 'the motivating features [shaping] the text's construction' (Butt et al, 2000, p. 186). If we return to our textile analogy, the context of situation is probably most like an outfit or ensemble which is shaped by not only the wider context of culture but also the specific situation, e.g. event.

The context of situation has 3 parameters:

- **Field:** what is being discussed in the text and short/long term goals of text
- **Tenor:** relationship between text's author and audience
- **Mode:** the type of text

(Butt et al, 2000, p. 5)

These three parameters (field, tenor & mode) form the context of the situation and are also sometimes referred to as 'register' (Butt et al., 2000; Eggins, 2004; Gillet, 2025; Hasan, 2009).

Figure 8 text, context of situation and context of culture relationship based on Butt et al. 2000

2.4 FUNCTIONAL

The three extratextual parameters of the context of the situation (field, tenor, and mode) relate to the three main functions of language:

- Discuss what is happening, what will/has happened
- To interact and/or express viewpoint
- Turn into a coherent whole the output of the previous two functions

(Butt et al, 2000, p. 5)

Halliday (1973) later developed and refined these functions of language into three metafunctions, or semantic choices (Purser et al., 2020), which also correspond with the 3 parameters of the context of situation:

- Ideational metafunction: language use to represent experience through experiential and logical meanings. Relates directly to the Field parameter.
- Interpersonal metafunction: language use to represent interaction and relationships. Relates directly to the Tenor parameter.
- Textual metafunction: language use to organise meanings into a coherent and structured whole. Relates to the Mode parameter.

(Butt et al., 2000)

Due to the extravagant nature of Systemic Functional Linguistics, it is not always possible, or even advisable, to analyse a text using all three metafunctions. In this particular study, my focus is on the textual metafunction, i.e. textual analysis of the

structure and texture and the mode parameter of multimodal texts. This focus on the textual metafunction stems from my own position as outsider, i.e. not architect. From this outsider position, I can only make limited contributions on *what* is being communicated, i.e. ideational meanings, so instead focus on *how* it is being communicated, i.e. textual meanings (Stenglin & Cléirigh, 2020). As a linguist, and not a trained architect, I am more interested in the text's structure and texture. Thus, the textual metafunction, and associated texture and structure, was prioritised over ideational metafunction. This textual metafunction-focussed approach has been adopted in several academic writing research projects for similar positioning reasons (North, 2005; McCabe, 1999; Stenglin & Cléirigh, 2020).

Despite this focus on textual metafunction in academic writing research, other SFL research has focused analysis on ideational metafunction. This approach is often associated with comparative ESAP studies (i.e. disciplinary differences) via transitivity, such as processes chosen by the author, e.g. reporting verbs featured in academic articles, which has provided some useful insights for EGAP and ESAP provision. For example, Halliday and Martin's (2003) book 'writing science' suggests that science writing tends to use more material and relational processes, e.g. 'reacts'. However, transitivity studies often rely on expert writers in specific subjects. These disciplinary differences in verb use in sciences vs arts and humanities may be more subtle in undergraduate writing and perhaps less relevant for interdisciplinary subjects such as architecture.

Additionally, this research project is primarily interested in the text's structure and texture but places less emphasis on the personal relationships between author and audience, power and attitudes as signified in the text. The relationship between author and audience can often be signified via the appraisal system (Martin & White, 2007). As an outsider to this discourse community, I am not the intended audience for these texts. Thus, the author and audience relationship is of less importance to me in comparison to the text's texture and structure. The interpersonal metafunction has been explored in SFL research using modals and personal pronouns in academic writing. For example, Hyland, (2002a) and others have explored writer stance using the personal pronoun 'I' with some interesting disciplinary variation, particularly among expert writers, e.g. 'I' in humanities, vs 'we' in sciences. Again, as previously mentioned, these findings are often based on expert writers and are often specific rather than interdisciplinary subject areas.

These two approaches, i.e. analysing texts with a focus on ideational and/or interpersonal metafunctions, may yet prove illuminating in future research, e.g. identifying other language choices made and available to undergraduate architecture students. The choice of the most appropriate verbs, modals and pronouns may subtly indicate the writer's status as a member of the discourse community and give the reader more confidence in the writer's message (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Swales, 1998a). However, without the full package of clear ideational, interpersonal and textual meanings, the text remains at 'novice approximations of particular disciplinary

ways of making knowledge' rather than 'expert, insider prose' (MacDonald, 1994, p. 187). If the text's message is unclear and/or incoherent due to issues with structure and texture, the message may be lost. If students find themselves like Eric Morecambe, 'playing all the right notes. But not necessarily in the right order' (Morecambe, 1971). This can prove challenging for architecture educators to mark and ultimately pass the text as it may not follow the brief. As Martin (1984, p. 28) explains "...you can't write if you don't first know language. But it is equally true to say that you can't write if you don't control the appropriate register and genres."

Therefore, as an EAP practitioner researcher, this research project focuses primarily on the textual metafunction and how meanings are structured and textured as a coherent and unified text (Halliday & Hasan, 1976). In addition, as will be discussed, the textual metafunction via Thematic progression allows for identification of topical/ideational and interpersonal Themes and how these are brought together in the text's structure and texture providing, perhaps, more comprehensive analysis of text through exploration of ideational, interpersonal and textual meanings and how these are structured in the text. It is also worth noting at this point, that textual analysis can be complemented by ethnographic interview presenting an opportunity to explore ideational meanings and practices via relationships and perhaps, interpersonal meanings, in addition to linguistic analysis via textual metafunction.

2.4.1. Metafunction: textual – Texture: textural choices and Texture: structural choices

The textual metafunction and mode parameter are concerned with textual meanings, how a text is organised to become a cohesive whole as well as coherent with not only itself but also its context (Butt et al., 2000). The textual metafunction is expressed through cohesion. Cohesion can be achieved via structural cohesion across a text, as well as textural cohesion between clauses/clause complexes, i.e. cohesion within a text. Text, texture, and textile have a similar etymological root in that their threads (actual or metaphorical), i.e. meanings in texts, are woven together (Butt et al., 2000) to give texture. Texture is described as a complex interplay of many systems and is inherent to not only texts but also buildings (O'Toole, 2011). Texture as a design feature is familiar to architects who often use textile metaphors in architecture reviews to describe buildings and highlight structural elements in architecture (Caballero, 2013; 2003). This gives rise to the subtitle of this project, i.e. **architexture**. A text's texture is achieved 'not only through linguistic patterns of cohesion [texture] but also from the text's coherence with its social and cultural context [structure]' (Eggins, 2004, p. 23). The context of culture is more than just a two-dimensional 'backcloth' or backdrop for meanings, but how the text is woven into the fabric of life through texture (Firth 1968; O'Toole, 2011). This is a familiar concept for architects who consider not just their building design but also the fabric buildings in the wider context. 'Fabric buildings form a physically cohesive texture that is indicative of an underlying social fabric' (Frederick, 2017, p. 89). Architects often use textural metaphors in architecture writing. For example, "the bridge is, says

Couvelas, 'a *thread darning the hole* caused by the excavation', and, *in the darning, the pattern of the old weave* of the city has been brought to the surface to take part in *the modern tapestry*' (Caballero, 2013, p. 155).

A text's cohesion can be lexical, e.g. repetition of keywords, or grammatical [textural], e.g. Theme/Rheme, or structural, e.g. Thematic progression (Butt et al., 2000: 147). It should be noted that in this study, Thematic progression, i.e. linguistic analysis of texts, and thematic analysis, i.e. analysis of interviews, are two separate and distinct approaches (see methodology). To aid in differentiation, I will be following Eggins' (2004) use of capital T for linguistic analysis of Theme and Thematic progression. In the Theme/Rheme system, clauses are separated into Theme 'the starting-point for the message: what the clause is going to be about' (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014, p. 64). In English, the Theme is almost always the start of a clause, other languages may vary. Once the Theme has been identified, the rest of the sentence is therefore the Rheme (Eggins, 2004). The Theme can be identified in terms of type of Theme, e.g. simple Theme which relates to one of the three metafunctions: topical Theme [ideational], interpersonal Theme [interpersonal] and textual Theme [textual] or multiple Theme in which more than one of the Themes is present in the Theme position (Butt, et al., 2000) (Figure 9). Butt et al. (2000) suggest that if a Theme is simple and topical then it can just be labelled as 'Theme' as this is almost the default position for most sentences in English. Topical Theme can be identified through the first element of a clause, such as a noun or noun phrase/nominal group (including premodification and postmodification). In contrast, clauses with textual Themes usually begin with a group or phrase to connect the message to previous text (Butt et al., 2000) as part of cohesion and texture. The final Theme type is interpersonal which has modal adjuncts in the first constituent position, e.g. mood, vocative, polarity, and comment. Authors have choices about single (topical) or multiple Themes. Multiple Themes can either be attitudinal, conjunctive or both (Eggins, 2004).

Figure 9: Theme choice system

In addition, authors also have other texture choices in terms of Theme system including using a marked or unmarked Theme. Unmarked Themes are expected and are the most typical Themes (Eggins, 2004; Butt et al., 2000). In academic texts, unmarked Themes are usually the most prevalent. Suharsono et al., (2024) found unmarked to be the most typical and prevalent across all academic texts studied, especially in undergraduate theses (55%). Bakaa (2015) also found unmarked Themes to be most typical in TESOL postgraduate essays but found them more prevalent for specific participants and hypothesised this was due to differences in linguistic background. Eggins (2004, p. 320) suggests that ‘skilful writers...choose marked Themes to add coherence and emphasis in their texts’. In academic texts, unmarked Themes are likely prevalent and typical, but with more textual Themes, in comparison to other texts, to support coherence and cohesion across a longer text.

Unmarked Themes can be identified when occupying one of four roles in particular clause types (Figure 10). In contrast, marked Themes are more atypical or unusual and can often, particularly in academic writing, include information before the topical Theme, if a marked sentence. There are several ways to analyse marked Themes, e.g. the presence and frequency of marked Themes and/or degree of markedness. North (2005) suggests extending the definition of Theme, going beyond marked/unmarked dichotomy to also record the ‘subject’, in addition to the marked Theme (Table 4). The recording of subject, as well as marked Theme, may be helpful in exploring field and ideational meanings. North (2005 p. 437) states “the role of subject choices in indicating the writer’s orientation towards their subject matter may be particularly sensitive to disciplinary difference”, based on her own findings as well as Macdonald (1994). The identification of ‘subject’ in marked clauses deviates

slightly from Halliday’s original SFL but this extension of Theme, is an approach also adopted by Martin and Rose (2003). This EdD study has followed suggestions by North and records not only marked Themes but also the subject choices made in these instances. This is for two main reasons. Firstly, this approach allows for comparison with similar research about writing in other disciplines using a similar analytical framework. Secondly, recording the subject choice also allows for more analysis of the texture and structure rather than purely statistical analysis of marked or unmarked Theme.

Table 4 North’s (2004) marked Theme with subject analysis example

(4) Penny A 6/f/31–33

Marked theme	Subject	Rheme
In Sweden,	leading researchers	tended, like Linnaeus, to organise their observation into systems.
[and] in the nineteenth century,	Constedt and Wallerius Berzilius	did this in mineralogy, followed in chemistry.

Figure 10: Theme choices, examples of unmarked Theme

In addition to marked or unmarked Theme, authors have choices about how they structure clauses and sentences. Firth (1968, p. 103) and many subsequent linguists consider the sentence or whole clause as ‘the essential object of study’. However, there is some ambiguity around what does and does not constitute a clause. This ambiguity around clause identification can require careful interpretation by the linguist as there are not always explicit indicators from the author where a clause starts/ends, particularly in longer texts. In contrast, sentences have explicit punctuation indicators from the author, i.e. full stops. Thus, sentences are the object of study for this research project.

Thematic progression analysis for whole sentences and texture between sentences, or clause complex (Eggins, 2004) or T-unit (Nesi & Gardner, 2012) can cross sentence boundaries and ‘it is the intersentence cohesion that is significant’ in distinguishing between and analysing texts (Halliday & Hasan, 1976, p. 9). Sentence-level rather than clausal-level analysis may result in fewer textual Themes, which are often present between clauses, but allows for more comparison with similar research on writing in other disciplines using a similar analytical framework. In addition to significance, analysis of at a sentence/clause complex/T-unit level for Theme allows for identification of textural and structural patterns and Thematic progression. Identification of Theme and Rheme allows for more analysis of texture via Thematic progression (Martin & Rose, 2007). Thematic progression is frequent in longer and written texts, such as texts written by university students (Eggins, 2004). Thematic progression within the text itself, can include e.g. Theme iteration (repeated Theme) or zigzag pattern (Rheme becomes Theme of next sentence) or multiple Rheme (topic sentences with subtopics/Rheme) (Eggins, 2004). Thematic progression can but also be extended to other parts of text, e.g. hyperTheme, e.g. topic sentences in paragraphs, and corresponding hyperNew, e.g. concluding sentences, or macroTheme, which can include the title and/or subtitles or thesis statement, and corresponding macroNew, which can include the conclusion (Monbec, 2020; Martin & Rose, 2003).

2.4.2. Texture in multimodal texts

In addition to language, architecture texts often include images which play a part in the text’s texture. As previously mentioned, Halliday’s social semiotic theory views language as one of number of systems used to communicate. This conceptualisation allows for other modes of communication, e.g. images, to be considered and analysed as semiotic resources. In Kress and van Leeuwen’s (2006) ‘reading images: the grammar of visual design’ Halliday’s metafunctions are adapted for analysis of images:

Ideational	Representations of experience through participants and processes (transitivity)	Visual representations of experience through participants (who) and processes (actions)
Interpersonal	Relationships and interactions with audience (use of I, modality)	Relationships and interactions with audience (gaze, self-insertion)
Textual	Text structure and texture (cohesion, Theme/Rheme)	Text structure and texture (layout, given/new)

Figure 11 metafunctions for analysis of images

The Theme/Rheme system is complemented and in parallel with the Given/New system. In many unmarked clauses, the Theme can fall within the Given and the New fall within the Rheme. (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). However, these two systems are different in that Theme/Rheme refers to organisation and position within the clause whereas Given/New refers to status of information (known/unknown) (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). The given/new system was further expanded by Kress and van Leeuwen (2006) to analyse images and multimodal texts (Figure 12). Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006) framework can be particularly helpful in 'reading' images and image-only texts but in multimodal and multipage texts, such as dissertations, Theme/Rheme analysis provides a more comprehensive linguistic overview. Thus, this study will discuss images and/or language in the Theme/Rheme position rather than given/new.

Figure 12 Kress and van Leeuwen's reading images framework

Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006) work features analysis of visual rather than linguistic communication resources including famous artworks, sculptures, and even

video games. Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006) work also includes several multimodal texts which include not only visual but also linguistic communication sources, e.g. magazine pages. Kress and van Leeuwen (2006) borrowed from Halliday's textual metafunctions and brought this together with Barthes' (1977) image-text relations based on Halliday's logico-semantic relations of elaboration, extension, enhancement. However, Barthes (1977) prioritised text over image as the more important mode in his analysis, something that Kress and van Leeuwen and later Martinec and Salway were keen to rectify. Martinec and Salway developed their own image-text relations system based on Kress and van Leeuwen, but also borrowed heavily from not only Barthes but also Martin's (1994) macro-genres.

Figure 17 Network of combined status and logico-semantics.

Figure 13 Martinec & Salway (2005) p358 network of combined status and logico-semantics

Martinec and Salway's framework uses elements of Kress and van Leeuwen and also Barthes to identify the status of image-text (image-language) relations in multimodal texts based on not only the position of the image e.g. given/new, ideal/real and salience but also logico-semantic relations. As previously mentioned, the given/new system is similar to the Theme/Rheme system in that the first element or clause, i.e. Theme contains the topical Theme whereas in the given/new system the first element or clause contains information that is shared between the audience and the author (Eggins, 2004). As previously mentioned, this project will focus on Theme/Rheme system due to the multimodal as well as multipage nature of analysed texts, i.e. dissertations. However, the given/new system can be helpful to analyse multimodal texts as the layout of the language or page can indicate the relationship between language and image and the resulting status. For example, if an image is on the left in the given position the language following the image (to the right) can provide new information based on the image. This analysis of texture and how meanings are woven together in both visual and linguistic formats in multimodal texts can help identify the status of image and language alongside real/ideal and salience systems. An image in the top left corner position of the page could indicate 3 levels of prominence i.e. in the Theme position, in the new position and in the ideal position. If, in addition to prominence based on Theme/Rheme, given/new and ideal/real, this image also occupies more space, i.e. salience, than the corresponding written component, then the image-language status could be considered unequal status and language subordinate to the image (Martinec & Salway, 2005). For modernist architects in the 1920s, language was always subordinate to image (Forty, 2004). However, more recently, architecture has been more accepting of the intertwined relationship of image and language. For example, famous architect Bernard Tschumi (1981) suggests 'architecture does not exist without drawing, in the same way that architecture does not exist without texts.' (Forty, 2004 p. 29).

This could then suggest that image and language can achieve complementary status as they are working together to communicate the message (Martinec & Salway, 2005). Status can be determined by analysing the relationship between the language and image. If equal status, then the visual and written component can stand on their own (Martin, 1994). In unequal status, an image may only correspond to part of the written component, this could mean the image is subordinate to the language (Martinec & Salway, 2005). Other factors can also indicate unequal status. For example, Martinec and Salway (2005) suggest the written component could be considered subordinate to the visual component, if there are several references (implicit or explicit) to the image, (e.g. 'this image/figure/work'). In addition to position, or references, the size of the image can also indicate the status between image and language. For example, a very large image may occupy multiple quadrants (or quintants) or may occupy one enlarged quintant, e.g. central, based on Kress and van Leeuwen's visual representation of a text. This may be the case in multimodal texts featuring columns, such as architecture dissertations. It is worth

noting that the definition of text can vary somewhat from Martin's (1994) whole text, Kress & van Leeuwen's (2006) whole page as text, which can even more visual artefacts like paintings, and Martinec & Salway's (2004) paragraph or section as text. For Halliday and Hasan (1976, p. 1) a text can be 'any passage, spoken or written, of whatever length, that does form a unified whole'. Thus, SFL allows for some flexibility in the definition of text. For this EdD project, text predominantly refers to the whole text, i.e. the whole dissertation. However, due to the length of text, i.e. 5000 words plus, image-text (image-language) relations are analysed based on the specific page/s.

In short simple texts, with limited instances of writing alongside visual images, e.g. one page poster with one image and corresponding writing, identifying the status can be relatively straightforward based on the page layout i.e. size and position of image. However, in longer texts with multiple images and sections of writing, such as architecture dissertations, further analysis is needed to identify the image-text (image-language) status as well as determine the text's texture through SFL's expansion and projection systems. In a clause complex, the relationship between clauses can be defined as either expansion or projection (Eggins, 2004). Martinec and Salway, inspired by Martin (1994), and Kress and van Leeuwen before them, borrow the systems of expansion and projection from SFL and further expanded their use to multimodal texts.

In expansion, clauses (or images) provide elaboration (i.e. restatement), extension (i.e. addition) or enhancement (i.e. multiplied by time/space/manner/cause/condition) (Eggins, 2004). Elaboration, extension and enhancement are often signified by (=), (+) and (x) respectively (Martin 1994; Eggins, 2004). Eggins (2004), based on earlier work by Halliday, suggests elaboration can be achieved between clauses through exposition (e.g. paraphrasing i.e. same idea in other words), exemplification (providing an example) or clarification (to be precise). Martinec and Salway (2005) developed a system to be abstract enough to apply to analysis of images but simplified the expansion system to include just exposition and exemplification. It should be noted here that Barthes (1977) used an analogous system in which he described elaboration as being achieved through illustration, where language appears first followed by an image, (similar to the Rheme or possibly Real position) or through anchorage in which the image appears first (similar to the Theme and/or Ideal position) followed by language (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2005). It would appear Barthes' illustration and anchorage are most similar to Halliday's elaboration, specifically exemplification, but the distinction is about which element is prioritised, i.e. appears first. In Martinec and Salway's (2005) system, this prioritisation is addressed via analysis of status (via positioning e.g. Theme) more so than logico-semantic relations and instead they distinguish exemplification in terms of generality, i.e. if language more general. If the written component (language) and visual component (image) are deemed to have the same level of generality then, this would be exposition (i.e. same idea expressed in different form rather than different words)

(Martinec & Salway, 2005). This similarity in generality as well as idea can often indicate an equal status between visual component (image) and written component (language). In fact, for Martin (1994) all expansion, not just exposition, denoted equal status. This can often be the case, but this project takes a more global view in determining status incorporating both elements of Kress and Leeuwen's quintant system as well as Martinec and Salway's status and logico-semantic relations system to analyse image-text [image-language] relations and status.

As can be seen from Figure 13, in addition to elaboration, another method of expansion is extension. Halliday defined two types of extension: addition and variation. Addition is where two clauses are joined together, without causal or temporal relationship, using common conjunctions such as *and* but can also include 'negative additions' such as *nor* or 'adversatives' such as *but* (Eggs, 2004). The second type of extension is variation in which one clause could be a total/partial replacement using common conjunctions such as *instead of, or* (Eggs, 2004). Martinec and Salway's (2005) system does not define different types of extension and focusses mostly on addition, e.g. the visual or written component providing/adding new information. Barthes again had an analogous system and referred to these additions not as extension but instead as relay (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2005). Barthes believed elaboration was more dominant and 'relay' (or extension) was 'more rare' (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2005).

The final type of expansion is enhancement which Eggs (2004 p. 278) describes as 'everything else', i.e. neither enhancement nor extension. For Eggs (2004) and others, enhancement is where a clause qualifies another clause via making reference to either time, space, cause (as in Figure 13) or manner or condition. Martinec and Salway's (2005) system focusses on how language or image qualifies the other 'circumstantially', i.e. temporal, spatial, and causal. The examples Martinec and Salway use to illustrate enhancement usually include a direct reference in language to the corresponding image. This direct reference such as 'figure x' with description of extra temporal, spatial or causal information can feel more like a footnote in some texts (see examples from Martinec and Salway). In fact, Martin (1994) indicates that enhancement clauses [or images] have an unequal status with the written component (language) dominating and visual component (image) embellishing with circumstantial information.

In keeping with the metaphor of texture, Martin (1994) helpfully describes enhancements as embellishing. If we consider text as a textile and enhancements as embellishments, then we could expand this metaphor to include elaboration as topstitching, i.e. retracing and repeating, and extension as a zip, i.e. bringing two pieces of fabric together. O'Toole (2011) uses the alternative term 'connector' to describe the bringing together of elements in texts, such as buildings. Projection, another logico-semantic relations system alongside expansion, could be the textile's lining. Projection logico-semantic relations can involve either locution (the wording: what someone said and often a verbal process, e.g. *say, report or write*) or idea (the

meaning: what someone thought and often a mental process, *know, believe or think*) (Eggins, 2004; Martinec & Salway, 2005). Projection involves re-expressing meanings. In multimodal texts, projection could be viewed as re-representing in another mode (Martinec & Salway, 2005). Projection is common in multimodal texts such as comics or graphic novels in which the visual component (image) and written component (language) mirror one another. In other genres featuring multimodality such as textbooks, scientific and academic publications, projection can be used to re-represent diagrams or maps or similar illustrations (Martinec & Salway, 2005). For Martinec and Salway (2005), projection via locution (or wording) can result in the same or similar words (synonyms) being repeated in both the image and accompanying language. This locution is usually as a result of the image having a caption and/or title and/or labels which repeats words from elsewhere in the text. It is worth noting at this point that Kress & van Leeuwen (2006) consider language items such as captions, titles, or labels to be part of the image. Martinec and Salway, will consider captions, titles, and labels as part of the image when the image is not readable without the labelling language, e.g. Venn diagrams. However, Martinec and Salway diverge from Kress and van Leeuwen and consider some captions, titles, or labels as written/linguistic elements in their own right, if labels serve to provide clarification or elaboration of the image. In these cases, the labels are then considered to be expansion rather than projection. This approach of treating some labels/captions/titles as written/linguistic components allows for linguistic comparisons between the language in the wider text and the language associated with the image.

An image (visual component) is considered projection if re-representing language (written component) based on wording then words will be repeated. However, an image (visual component) could instead be re-representing the ideas, rather than the words, from the written component (language). This may be the case in images with no labels or titles in which the image represents and mirrors the ideas of the written component. However, in many cases, images used to represent ideas are usually part of the expansion system, e.g. a visual example of one or more ideas (Martinec & Salway, 2005). One indication to differentiate between expansion and projection systems when images are used in similar ways is to return to the status of the image. Martin (1994) suggests that in projection (as mentioned previously for enhancement) images (visual component) have a more dependent (unequal) status and that the written component is often more dominant.

2.4.3. Structure

A text should be coherent with the context, i.e. context of culture (or genre) and context of situation (or register) but also cohesive within the text through texture to create a 'unified whole' (Eggins, 2004, p. 24). In addition to texture there is another design feature to consider when authoring texts, i.e. structure. Butt et al. (2000, p. 15) refer to structure as 'a kind of architecture with a unifying, structural shape – through which the text achieves its purpose'. If we continue the metaphor of text as

texture and texture including, as previously discussed, expansion, i.e. elaboration as topstitching, extension as a zip and enhancement as embellishment and projection as the garment's lining, then structure could be considered a sewing pattern. Butt et al. (2000, p. 3) describe a text's structure as 'certain obligatory structural elements appropriate to [the text's] purpose and context.' Like a sewing pattern, a text's structure can be 'tailored' to 'fit' the designer and/or end user's specifications but needs to include particular elements. In addition to the author, the discourse community and shared set of communicative purposes also shape and structure the text (Swales, 1990). There can be several influences on a text's shape, structure and purpose, e.g. Swales' (2004) factors shaping form and function for PhD theses (Figure 14).

Figure 4.7. Factors shaping the form and purpose of a dissertation

Figure 14 Swales (2004, p. 136) factors shaping form and purpose of dissertation

Texture and structure work together to create a harmonious and cohesive text (Butt et al., 2000). As previously discussed, texture can be analysed through Theme analysis at a clausal or clause complex level, i.e. Theme and Rheme as part of the discourse-semantics strata. The Theme and Rheme structure represents information flowing through the text via little waves or ripples (Martin & Rose, 2007). A text's structure can be further analysed to explore Thematic progression across paragraphs via Theme iteration (repeated Theme), the zigzag pattern (Rheme of one clause/sentence becomes Theme of subsequent sentence or multiple Rheme (Rheme split and become Theme of subsequent clauses/sentences) (Martin & Rose, 2007; Eggins, 2004). The final type of Thematic progression, i.e. multiple Rheme is common in longer expository texts (Eggins, 2004), but it should be noted that both multiple Rheme and zigzag pattern are common across written texts (Eggins, 2004). Theme iteration in written texts can also be frequent via nominalisation, a common feature among academic texts (Eggins, 2004). It should also be noted here that some texts may make use of multiple methods of Thematic progression even in the same paragraph. Martin and Rose (2007) also added a further type of Thematic

progression named derived Themes in which the HyperTheme or topic sentences contained multiple subtopics which become the Theme for sentences across the paragraph.

Martin and Rose's (2007) HyperTheme represents information flowing through the text via bigger waves. A further extension of Thematic progression is MacroTheme which Martin and Rose describe as a tidal wave and at a higher level of Theme (Monbec, 2020). MacroThemes can include titles of chapters or subtitles at one level or at a higher MacroTheme level could include the title of the whole text (Martin & Rose, 2007), or other text-wide MacroTheme such as research objectives or thesis statements. The subtitles or macroThemes used in a text make up the macrostructure (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024), sometimes referred to as rhetorical structure (Thompson, 2018).

Figure 15: Adapted from Martin & Rose (2007) & Monbec (2020) macro>hyper>theme

Macrostructure choices reflect both the genre and context. There are several specific genres in academic writing, such as reports, which mimic the staging and Macrostructure of similar genres written by scientists or other practitioners (Martin & Rose, 2006), e.g. subtitles or macrostructure often set and/or agreed in advance. Research articles, such as journal articles, also have fairly fixed subtitles, often assigned by a journal, or replicate common structures such as Swales' IMRD. Swales' (2002) analysis of research genres found many research articles replicated the IMRD structure, i.e. Introduction, Methodology, Results & Discussion. However, Swales would suggest this is not the only possible structure and writers have some, albeit limited, freedom in choice of subtitles. For example, Swales (2002) suggests research articles, in some areas such as astrophysics, argumentative research articles are common and therefore require a different macrostructure. Another small, but significant, difference in macrostructure for research articles is the use of the

subtitle 'results' for subjects allied to STEM and possibly more quantitative numbers-based results, compared to more qualitative 'findings' subtitle for subjects allied to arts, humanities and social sciences (Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

Many dissertation writing courses and guides often teach this IMRD structure as a guideline for writing 'traditional' dissertations (Swales, 2002). This approach has been criticised for assuming a 'standard' thesis has a standard macrostructure (Bunton, 1998; Paltridge, 2002). However, studies have found there is much variation and little standardisation in terms of structure, i.e. macrostructure, in theses and dissertations (Bunton, 1998; Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). Bunton's (1998) PhD study suggests the only 'standard' section/subtitle, i.e. present in all theses and dissertations, was 'introduction'. In addition, he also found that the subtitle conclusion was present in almost all analysed theses. These findings led to Bunton (1998) identifying a three-stream model for PhD and MPhil theses:

Table 5.7: Three-Stream Model for a Ph.D Thesis

I N T R O D U C T I O N		
(Literature Review)		
(Pilot Study / Development of / Theoretical Instrument or Model Framework)		
<i>Topic:</i> Intro-(Lit)-Meth-Res-Disc	METHOD	Method
<i>Topic:</i> Intro-(Lit)-Meth-Res-Disc	RESULTS	<i>Topic:</i> Analysis-Discussion
<i>Topic:</i> Intro-(Lit)-Meth-Res-Disc	DISCUSSION	<i>Topic:</i> Analysis-Discussion
<i>Topic:</i> Intro-(Lit)-Meth-Res-Disc		<i>Topic:</i> Analysis-Discussion
C O N C L U S I O N S		

Figure 16: Bunton (1998, p.112) Three-stream model for PhD thesis macrostructures.

This three-stream model has many similarities with Paltridge’s postgraduate thesis types (Table 5) with traditional complex a frequent structure in science and topic-based structures often more prevalent in arts, humanities and social sciences (Paltridge & Starfield; Pecorari & Coxhead, 2026).

Table 5: Paltridge & Starfield (2024) postgraduate thesis types

Traditional complex	Traditional simple	Topic-based	Compilation of research articles
Bunton left column (mainly science & technology)	Bunton central column, 'genre-based' (Nesi & Gardner, 2012)	Bunton right column (mainly arts & humanities)	Not featured in Bunton [irrelevant to undergraduate dissertations]
<i>Introduction</i> <i>Background to study + review of literature</i> <i>Study 1: IMR+C</i> <i>Study 2: IMRD+C</i> <i>Study 3 etc.: IMRD+C</i> <i>Discussion</i> <i>Conclusions</i>	<i>Introduction</i> <i>Literature Review</i> <i>Materials & Methods</i> <i>Results</i> <i>Discussion</i> <i>Conclusions</i>	<i>Introduction</i> <i>Topic 1</i> <i>Topic 2</i> <i>Topic 3 etc.</i> <i>Conclusions</i>	<i>Introduction</i> <i>Background to study</i> <i>Research article 1: ILMRDC</i> <i>Research article 2: ILMRDC</i> <i>Research article 3 etc.: ILMRDC</i> <i>Discussion</i> <i>Conclusions</i>

As previously mentioned, Swales (2002) suggests that instead a PhD thesis should be treated as separate genre not only due to length but also due to different purposes and genre chains e.g. thesis defence. For example, Yamada (2015) found novice undergraduate Japanese students experienced guided participation in related genres before the top genre, i.e. a dissertation via a genre chain. In addition to different genre chains an undergraduate and postgraduate/PhD thesis have different purposes. The purpose of a doctoral thesis is a unique contribution to research and implications for future research. Whereas Swales (2002) claims that many dissertations at master's level conclude and/or feature with real-world implications. Perhaps then an undergraduate dissertation should also be considered a separate genre in that they are less likely to feature research and/or real-world implications but more likely to include personal implications. However, with relatively few studies on undergraduate dissertations macrostructure to draw on, for the purposes of this literature review, extend this definition out to Nesi and Gardner's (2012) genre family, i.e. 'research report' in order to report on a wider range of macrostructure studies. Also, when describing 'research reports' with a topic-based macrostructure, Nesi and Gardner (2012) describe these as 'long essays' with a five-part structure. It is worth mentioning here some crossover of research reports with other genre families, particularly in terms of networks (Table 6).

Table 6: Nesi & Gardner (2012) essays and research reports: purpose, stages, networks and examples

	Essays	Research reports
Social purpose	<i>Demonstrate/develop ability to construct coherent argument and employ critical thinking</i>	<i>Demonstrate/develop ability to undertake a complete piece of research including research design, and an appreciation of its significance in the field</i>
Stages	<i>Introduction, series of arguments, conclusion</i>	<i>Student's research aims, investigation & relevance to other research in field</i>
Networks	May correspond to a published academic/specialist paper	May correspond to published experimental research article or topic-based research paper
Examples	<i>Challenge, commentary, consequential, discussion, exposition, factorial</i>	<i>Research article, student research project, topic-based dissertation</i>

The structure of texts can also be analysed through genre analysis. Genre analysis with research reports can often focus on the more 'standard' dissertation sections, e.g. introduction, conclusion, which are usually present for almost all dissertation types but also other identifying elements such as abstract or acknowledgements. Genre analysis involves identifying the moves and steps in a text, often within these sections. For example, Swales' (2004) CARS (Create a Research Space) model for research article introductions identifies three moves:

1. Establishing a territory [contextual background]
2. Establishing a niche [gap in practitioner and/or academic knowledge]
3. Occupying the niche (or 'Presenting the work' in revised versions usually if IMRD structure)

The CARS model seems less appropriate for undergraduate dissertation writers for whom the purpose is not to identify nor occupy a niche in either practitioner or academic knowledge, as is often the case for postgraduate dissertations and research articles. In addition, Swales' (2002) genre research with research articles identified disciplinary differences in particular sections, e.g. more clipped (shorter) methods section in science-based research articles, and more elaborated (longer) methods section in the humanities and social sciences. Given the already shorter nature of undergraduate dissertations, due to word counts, all sections would appear 'clipped', perhaps limiting comparisons between disciplines and other genres, e.g. postgraduate dissertations.

Despite calls for more research on undergraduate dissertations, there are a small number of studies based on undergraduate dissertations (Dudley-Evans, 1999). One explanation for this is limited access to undergraduate dissertations compared to very available research articles, routinely available PhD theses and postgraduate dissertations which may also be available online via library websites as exemplars. However, undergraduate dissertations may too be available online via library websites, making dissertations, less occluded and more available than other

undergraduate genres (Swales, 2002). There are also more undergraduate than postgraduate research reports available via BAWE. Over three quarters of the 61 research reports from undergraduate students in year 1, 2 or 3, with research reports making up just over 4% of BAWE corpus. In addition, novice undergraduate writers with little explicit knowledge via training or perhaps little implicit knowledge via reading of other dissertations, may vary in terms of consistency and success in typical moves and steps from such sections. Therefore, Thematic progression and analysis of macroTheme and macrostructure may provide more illuminating findings for structural and textural features of undergraduate dissertation texts.

2.5 Ethnographic: interpretivist

This EdD research project and associated theoretical framework and philosophical positioning are heavily influenced by SFL but this by no means represents the full picture. As previously mentioned, SFL could be considered not only constructivist, due to the notion that reality and knowledge are co-constructed in groups, but also interpretivist in valuing interpretation and perspectives from participants within the context. However, within the confines of linguistics research, interpretivist understandings of participant perspectives can be challenging with textual analysis alone. As previously discussed, my position is a constructivist/interpretivist, and my theoretical framework draws on both aspects of this position: SFL with more constructivist understandings and interpretivist influences as well as incorporating more interpretivist understandings via ethnography as a theoretical lens and academic literacies as a theory.

For over 100 years, there have been calls for linguistic research to include not only textual analysis but also community perspectives on textual practices and contextual texts. Malinowski (1923) was one of the first to suggest that we should ‘burst the bonds of mere linguistics’ and to truly understand a word, or expression, you must also develop understanding of the word’s function and context (context of situation) and associated practices. As mentioned previously, Malinowski was informed by his experiences as an anthropologist. Later, in papers between 1934-1951, further developed the idea of the ‘context of situation’ from a linguistic perspective (Firth, 1957). Also, from a linguistic perspective, ethnolinguistics, Hymes (1964) called for ‘emphasis and primary of speech [text] over code; function [practices] over structure; context over message’. Hymes’ (1964) ethnography of communication had two key characteristics:

1. Data should not be collected from separate perspectives with separate methods, i.e. linguistics and anthropology, then artificially fused but instead should collect data to understand language patterns and practices within the context of situation.
2. The main frame of reference should be the community and not the text.

Swales’ (1998) textography has many similarities to Hymes’ (1964) approach as it explores situated academic writing i.e. bringing together text, context, and practices.

However, in contrast to Hymes, Swales was uncomfortable with the label ethnography and continued in linguistic tradition of prioritising text as the main frame of reference while also exploring context and practices. During the same time period, Lillis (2008) from an ethnographic background, called for less 'textual bias' and saw writing as not only a text but also as an act and practice as a result of the context. Lillis' work was inspired by the academic literacies which shared SFL's focus on context but emphasised writing practices over text analysis. The academic literacies model had 6 main characteristics:

1. Meaning of literacy depends upon the social institutions [context] in which it is embedded.
2. Literacy cannot be treated as it were an autonomous thing without political and/or ideological significance.
3. The particular practices of reading and writing that are taught in any context depend upon such aspects of social structure.
4. The processes whereby reading and writing [practices] are learnt are what construct the meaning of it for particular practitioners.
5. Refers to 'literacies' rather than to any single 'literacy'.
6. Writers who tend towards this model...recognise as problematic the relationship between the analysis of any autonomous qualities of literacy and the analysis of ideological and political nature of literacy practice.

(Street, 2009, 2012)

Lea and Street (2006, p. 368) continued to develop the academic literacies model, which views 'reading and writing as social practices that vary with context'. Academic literacies differs from the skills approach which assumes academic texts and language are transparent and the context and authors are somehow neutral and PEAPs (and other practitioners) should teach 'appropriate' literacy skills (Lillis, 2001; Street, 2009). In contrast, the academic literacies model sees text and language as situated and context-dependent which has parallels with both SFL and textography. The academic literacies model as a theory informs much academic writing research, including this EdD project, but research projects can prioritise texts, context and practices differently. Gardner (2012) suggests that traditionally, academic literacies research has tended to focus on writers in context, whereas SFL has tended to focus on texts in context. Ethnographers researching academic writing have been most interested in writer-focussed research and contextualised writing practices and less so with texts (Sizer, 2021). This can also result in a more critical stance in academic writing research problematising the highly contested nature of 'appropriate' academic texts and academic writing. Whereas linguists researching academic writing have traditionally been most interested in texts and text-focussed research within a particular context. That is not to say that ethnographic research is devoid of texts or linguistic research is devoid of writers' perspective. In fact, Lillis' (2008) 'talk around texts', i.e. 'academic literacy histories interviews' with writers about situated writing processes and practices bears a striking resemblance to Swales' (1998) 'textual life

histories', i.e. 'text-based interviews' despite Swales' discomfort with ethnography. Both approaches emphasise context and contextualising data such as contextual texts, interviews, observations, and field notes to create a thick description of the context (Lillis, 2001; Sizer, 2021; Swales, 1998). Interestingly, despite the potential for differences in focus, i.e. practices (AcLits) and texts (SFL), there is much complementarity, thanks to a shared heritage (via Malinowski) and shared recognition of the importance of context (Gardner, 2012). Gardner (2012) endorses and recommends SFL and AcLits as not only compatible but also complementary approaches for EAP research.

Table 7 Gardner (2012) a simplified view of AcLits vs SFL investigations of academic writing

Table 1
A simplified view of AcLits vs SFL investigations of academic writing.

AcLits		SFL
Ideology	<i>Discourse</i>	Ideology
Literacy practices	<i>Context of culture</i>	Genres
Literacy events	<i>Context of situation</i>	Registers (Field, Tenor, Mode)
Ethnography	<i>Main method</i>	Linguistic analysis (Experiential, Interpersonal, Textual systems)
Writers and writing in context: what socially situated writers do	<i>Main focus</i>	Written texts: how linguistic resources construe meanings in context
Transformative	<i>Main aims</i>	Applicable

Context remains a key component for academic writing studies. There have been a number of calls to also foster practices as well as texts, and/or texts as well as practices (Gardner, 2012; Lillis, 2008; Rampton et al., 2015). Previously mentioned linguistic studies have aimed to recontextualise texts and incorporate more writer-based research and focus on practices (e.g. Nesi & Gardner, 2012). Also, ethnographic studies have incorporated textual analysis (e.g. Lillis, 2008). Linguistic ethnographic (or ethnolinguistic) studies, including textographic studies, aim for a more balanced equilateral triangle with all 3 concepts: context, text and practice receiving attention and emphasis.

2.6 Conceptual framework: texts, contexts, and practices

Academic literacies theorist Lillis, and before her Lea and Street were some of the first advocates for the trio of key concepts in this EdD research project i.e. **texts**, **contexts**, and **practices**. As can be seen by the conceptual framework diagram below.

Figure 6 'conceptual framework diagram' [repeated]

2.6.1. Context

The importance of context for language has been emphasised by SFL theory as well as EAP/ESAP practice. Similarly, context is also important to architectural theory and practice, i.e. design practice and pedagogical practice. Context is key as “architecture doesn’t exist in vacuum” (Dobson, 2014) and neither does language. The UK Commission for the built environment (CABE) described the value of the built environment as the following values which extends beyond value of individual learners and incorporates a wider context with many values equally applicable for built environment as well as language.

Table 8 CBE (2006) & Dobson (2014) value of built environment

Exchange value	commercial value
Use value	Contribution
Image value	Identity
Social value	social interaction and inclusion
Environmental value	Sustainability
Cultural value	relates to rich tapestry of context and history

When designing buildings, architects must consider their influences from and on the wider context. This context includes but is not limited to the local context, e.g. fabric buildings around designed building, and extends beyond to a broader context, e.g. social fabric and social and cultural value (CBE, 2006; Dobson, 2014; Frederick, 2007). Similarly, linguists consider the influences from and on the context of situation as well as the context of culture. In addition, to similarities in the importance of context on practice on both architecture and linguistics both occupy a similar theoretical context in the nexus between science and art. Both architecture and linguistics draw upon art and science (Crystal, 1968; Martin, 1984; Pearce & Toy, 1995; Schön, 1988) and linguistics may occupy similar theoretical spaces but architectural practice occupies a very different physical context, i.e. studio.

2.6.1.1. Architecture studio: pedagogy

Studio pedagogy is a vital and ubiquitous aspect of architecture education. RIBA validated courses require at least 50% of Part 1 (undergraduate) programmes to be undertaken as design studio projects. Studio pedagogy, i.e. learning ‘to architect’, described in the verb form by many architecture educators, must involve architecture practice and has a long history (Broadbent, 1995; Unwin, 2023). Schön (1988) was one of the first to write about architecture studio pedagogy and its perceived virtues in providing opportunities for reflection and application of architecture and preparation for professional practice which informed his ‘reflective practitioner’ and associated theory. Studio pedagogy is also typified by its mirroring of architecture studio practice through location, i.e. physical studio, as well as collaborative, project-based work. However, the immersive nature of studio pedagogy has been criticised for difficulties associated with students learning by architecting and the pressure this places on students to perform before fully understanding. Crits are often heavily criticised for this reason, and knowledge, and ultimately power, imbalance between students (apprentices) and architecture educators (masters) and recommendations widely available for more inclusive studio pedagogy (Day et al., 2024; Flynn et al., 2023; Parnell & Sara, 2007; The Bartlett School of Architecture Environmental Investigation, 2022; Webster, 2008).

2.6.2. Texts: *definition and architecture as text*

The practice and study of architecture produces not only designs but also texts. As previously mentioned, image-text (image-language) relations status can be determined through comparison between the image and 'text'. However, the definition of what constitutes a text can vary. Firstly, Halliday's SFL definition of text considers text not just as a 'material artefact' but instead as an instance of meanings (Purser et al., 2020). This broadens the definition of text. For linguists, texts are not only written communication, such as books but also spoken communication as well as multimodal communication, e.g. image and speech or image and written word. "A text is understood here as communication motivated and shaped by the needs of a particular social context" (Purser et al., 2020). For linguists, text length is less important. In fact, a one-sentence poem, or monostich can be considered a text:

"If you shed tears when you miss the sun, you also miss the stars."

(Rabindranath Tagore, 1916, *The Stray Birds*)

The defining feature of a text for Halliday (1985) is the language "any instance of language, in any medium, that makes sense in context." However, Kress and van Leeuwen (2010) suggested that even without language some examples, such as paintings, could be considered semiotic artefacts which communicate a message and can be read and interpreted in context as texts. As previously mentioned, Kress and van Leeuwen (2010) expanded Halliday and SFL's definition of text and developed a visual grammar system to interpret semiotic artefacts/texts based on given/new and real/ideal systems. Martinec and Salway (2005) adopted and adapted this to develop their own system for analysing image-text (image-language) relations in multimodal (visual and written) texts. 3D spaces, such as buildings, are also considered, by some, to be texts. Ravelli (2011, p. 30) argues 'buildings are still texts, they make and enable meanings, they are socio-cultural constructs, as such, need to be understood, appreciated, critiqued, applauded and criticized, just as any other text can and should be.'

Several researchers share the view that buildings are texts and present various frameworks using SFL, or more accurately Systemic Functional theory, to 'read' buildings as texts (Kress & Leeuwen, 2010; McMurtrie, 2011; Pang, 2004; Ravelli, 2011; Stenglin, 2004). One approach for reading buildings is using Kress and Van Leeuwen's (2004) visual grammar, but not all architectural elements can be read in the same way. For example, 'the façade of a building, its vertical dimension, is the building we 'read'; the horizontal dimension, the floor plan, is the building we 'use' (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2004, p. 256). Another approach is O'Toole's (2004) systemic-functional semiotic model of architecture, which analyses a building in terms of experiential/ideational meanings (uses), interpersonal (public image and engagement with world and visitors) and textual/textural meanings (sculptural coherence and relation to context) (O'Toole, 2011) (Table 9). O'Toole's (2004) model also includes floors, rooms, and other elements as well as buildings. Like a text,

these elements are brought together as a coherent whole through cohesion with context, and other elements, via reference (projection), or conjunction (expansion) systems (O’Toole, 2004). Alias’ (2004) framework, adapted from O’Toole, adopts the same experiential, interpersonal and textual meanings as well as elements, i.e. buildings, floors, room, and other elements, although these elements are slightly adapted, and then extended to other contextual [external] elements, i.e. area, roads, and open space. This focus on the external part of the building is also a feature of Ravelli’s (2011) analysis of a university building drawing on Kress and van Leeuwen as well as SFL-inspired metafunctions:

- ‘space as arrangement: organisational [textual] metafunction’,
- ‘space as persona: interactional [interpersonal] metafunction’
- ‘space as content: representational [ideational] metafunction’

An earlier study, on the same building, focussed on SFL’s interpersonal metafunctions, particularly the appraisal system, and also drew upon Stenglin’s (2004) binding and bonding systems based on SFL’s interpersonal metafunction to analyse the building’s interior (Ravelli & Stenglin, 2008).

Table 9: Alias (2004) Functions and systems in architecture (reproduced from O’Toole, 1994: 86)

Table 1.1 Functions and systems in architecture (reproduced from O’Toole 1994: 86)

Units/ Functions	Experiential	Interpersonal		Texture
Building	Practical function: Public/Private; Industrial/Commercial/Agricultural/ Governmental/Educational/Medical/ Cultural/Religious/Residential; Domestic/ Utility	Size Verticality Chthonicity Façade Cladding Colour Modernity Exoticism	Orientation to neighbours Orientation to road Orientation to entrant Intertextuality reference mimicry contrast	Relation to city Relation to road Relation to adjacent buildings Proportions Rhythms: contrasting shapes, angles Textures: rough/smooth Roof/wall relation Reflectivity Opacity
	Orientation to light Orientation to wind Orientation to earth Orientation to service (water/sewage/ power)			

Other studies have also analysed the interior of buildings as a text using systemic-functional theory. McMurtrie (2011) presented an approach in which ‘spatial texts’, i.e. buildings, can be viewed as a dynamic communicative event using a parallel system analysing pathways instead of clauses that thread through the text. Pang (2004) also focussed on the interior of the building and similarly included circulation paths and flow within the text, in this case a museum. Pang (2004) also includes textual analysis of exhibition artefacts and contextual texts photographed within the museum which feels reminiscent of Swales’ textography (1998), albeit with less linguistic/textual analysis.

These SFL-inspired approaches may prove to be a helpful analogous system for architecture students and/or educators to support understanding and use of SFL for textual analysis. I can envisage PEAPs teaching how to analyse not only texts but also buildings using SFL’s interpersonal, ideational, and textual/textural meanings.

However, these approaches, so far, have been used to analyse real and complete buildings. In architecture education, students are not asked to build, but design buildings. These designs are hypothetical and conceptual, but not fully contextualised. Therefore, it may be challenging to fully analyse meanings of interiors and exteriors of conceptual buildings, in much the same way decontextualised texts can prove challenging for analysis (see previous comments about corpus linguistics). Additionally, as a linguist and PEAP, my interest centres on textual/linguistic texts rather than buildings as texts. Many of these analytical approaches draw on and cite 'systemic-functional theory' rather than 'systemic-functional linguistics', pushing these methods outside the scope of this study. Finally, from the etic-position of outsider, understanding and analysing architectural artefacts, e.g. buildings/building designs as texts would require considerable ethnographic fieldwork and/or interviews to support understanding of all potential meanings as well as access to building models (physical or software-generated) and designs. However, analysing buildings/building designs as texts and/or analysing a university building as a text could present an interesting future research project, perhaps a project with more emphasis on communication, particularly multimodal communication, rather than written academic communication and texts.

2.6.3. Texts: *Architexts [architecture texts]*

Architecture is a multimodal practice involving both visual and verbal modes, which is reflected in the variety of multimodal texts and semiotic artefacts/texts consumed and/or produced in the practice and study of architecture (Spector & Damron, 2017). The study of architecture and civil engineering often involves the consumption and subsequent transformation of texts such as lectures and reports into artefacts such as models and/or plans (Hellwig et al., 2022). This can lead to authentic (pracademic) assessments which replicate real-world practice realised through multiple artefacts and/or texts using multiple modes e.g. spoken, written as well as models and plans (Hellwig et al., 2002; Spector & Damon, 2017). However, this research project is most interested in written texts.

Caballero (2013) describes three main genres/text types for written architecture texts:

- Technical [more practitioner-focused, micro-context] genres, including architectural projects such as competition briefs, tender or bid documents, building specifications
- Theoretical genres [more academic-focused, meso-context]: Texts dealing with architectural history, design, methodology (e.g., manifestoes)
- Critical genres [more pracademic, macro-context]: Texts covering buildings of particular importance (e.g., books about the work of an outstanding architect, architectural reviews) (Caballero, 2013).

Many architecture texts, particularly more technical texts, could be considered occluded genres (Swales, 1996) as others, outside the discourse community, or

even micro-context, e.g. specific architecture studios, have limited access to these texts. These occluded texts can be an important part of the design process but may be conducted behind the scenes and not shared due to confidentiality as well as competition concerns. Swales (2002) suggests that many research genres have several stages before and after dissemination which he terms genre chains. This is also the case for architecture. Medway and Clark's (2003) observations in an ethnographic study of an architecture studio, found architects have a complex flow/chain of texts (including visual, verbal, written and multimodal) creation, collaboration and discussion throughout the design process, much of which is not shared beyond the architecture studio, but can culminate in an external text such as a presentation or report.

2.6.3.1. Technical Architexts: Architecture practitioner design presentations

Architecture presentations are often towards the end of the design process after much internal discussion and process. This can be a complex process and can include but is not limited to preliminary enquiries; briefing; preliminary design; structural design; building materials; buildings services; design presentation (Heidenreich, 2016). The design process may not always follow this order as design can be a complex process. This complexity is reflected in Figure 17 (Design Squiggle) demonstrating the process of uncertainty (Newman, 2024).

Noise / Uncertainty / Patterns / Insights

Clarity / Focus

Research & Synthesis

Concept / Prototype

Design

Figure 17: Newman (2024) 'the design squiggle'

Much uncertainty and complexity is within the research and synthesis stage which is complex due to the collaborative nature of design studios and design projects, as well as involvement of a client. The RIBA [Royal Institute of British Architects] (2020) workflow lists 8 stages (Figure 18). The first 3 stages correspond to the design process and mirror Figure 17. In the first stage, architects need to confirm the clients' requirements and may also need to produce a business case (RIBA, 2020). In the

second stage, architects need to produce and have a project brief approved by clients. At this stage architects may also produce a number of reports, such as feasibility studies, site information such as surveys and field reports, project budget/programme, procurement strategy and responsibility matrix and/or organogram (Chappell, 2016; *RIBA Plan of Work*, 2020; Spector & Damron, 2017). Then at stage three, architects need to produce the architectural concept design, often delivered via a presentation, and have this approved by clients (RIBA, 2020). The architectural concept design presentation may be private, i.e. for client only, may be semi-private, with clients as well as other stakeholders and/or other practitioners, i.e. contractors, sub-contractors and suppliers (Brookhouse, 2013).

Figure 18 RIBA (2020) Plan of work stages

Architectural concept design presentations can also include other architecture practitioners as a competitors and/or judges via a charette. Originally, a charette (or cart) was used by architecture students to wheel their designs to a jury or exhibition hall and the term design charette became synonymous with design competitions (Day et al., 2024). However, ‘charette’ can also refer to practitioner design competitions (as well as students competitions) with organisations like RIBA regularly advertising design charettes for students and/or practitioners or hosting live pitch sessions for a panel of clients (Dobson, 2014). Modern-day design charettes/presentations can involve clients, stakeholders and architects, but also other practitioners involved in the design and implementation, collaborating as a multidisciplinary group (Willis, 2011). Architects, alongside clients, may also offer stakeholders and/or community groups, such as amenity groups, a public presentation, often followed by a letter offering to keep them informed of relevant updates beyond design stage (Chappell, 2020).

This involvement of clients and stakeholders at several stages including design (first three stages) demonstrates the ‘service’ architecture provides clients. NESTA (2006) developed a refined model of the creative industries in the UK which depicts architecture as a creative service provider/enterprise. Unlike other areas within the creative industries, architects design with a client rather than for a customer and as such require a good working relationship over an extended period through multiple stages (Dobson, 2014). Good architecture is understanding the client (Yarrow, 2019). Medway and Clark (2003) suggest architectural presentations for clients require drawing on clients’ expertise and recontextualising design features for the specific audience. Successful architectural design and presentations are as a result of collaboration with the client as well as colleagues within the architecture studio.

Figure 19 NESTA (2003) Model of creative industries

2.6.3.2. Technical Architexts: architecture education presentations: crits/critiques/reviews

Architecture education at university attempts to reflect this focus on presentations for clients through the use of ‘crits’ or ‘reviews’ as assessments. Crits (also called critiques, design review or design jury) are an identifying feature of architectural education and often described as a tradition, ritual or rite of passage (Dannels, 2016; Flynn et al., 2023; Yarrow, 2019). During crits, students present their design to an audience (sometimes also examiner) often in a scenario-based fashion with audience members acting as clients. There has been much discussion about the

place of the crit in design (including architectural design) education and perceived positive aspects, i.e. reflective of design practice and instant feedback, and more negative aspects of the crit, such as difficulties with preparation as well as performance, e.g. holding the floor during a barrage of critique (Flynn et al., 2023; Swales et al., 2001). Swales et al. (2001) suggested postgraduate architecture crits were between 20-90 mins long and had two main parts: the presentation followed by the critique.

Part 1: Individual presentation of the student's work:

- *Level A Description of the site*
- *Level B Architecturally contextualized description/rationale of the site*
- *Level C Depiction of the design details*
- *Part 2: Proffering of advice/questions about the project and suggestions/unpredictable discussion of the project*

(Swales et al., 2001)

Research and discussion of crits has most often included postgraduate architecture crits and has provided some useful insights, such as organisation with Swales et al.'s (2021) ABC structure, or Frederick's (2017) general to specific structure (with 6 steps: [design] problem, principles, process, parti [design concept], present [drawings/models], perform self-critique). However, the unpredictable nature of crits, particularly length, as well as critique element [part 2] can make preparation particularly challenging for both students and PEAPs (Swales et al., 2001). PEAPs may also find offering support with crits challenging due to access, as many crits may not be recorded. Additionally, more ethnographic study of events preceding crits, such as more informal desk crits, which can occur frequently but sporadically in the design studio (Swales et al., 2001) as well as crit alternatives, e.g. more dialogic and collegial round-table reviews (Sara, 2023) or charettes or live pitches may also be helpful, depending on the context.

Crits are a ubiquitous feature of architecture education and design studio pedagogy aiming to replicate architecture practice in an academic setting (Flynn et al., 2023). Research indicates some potential similarities and transferable skills between crits during architectural education and presentations from architects for clients such as recontextualising designs for the audience (Swales et al., 2001; Medway & Clark, 2003). However, Dobson (2014) suggests that crits, while useful in developing communication and persuasion skills, can become echo chambers and encourage architecture students to be fluent in the language of architects but less able to communicate with clients. Architects must communicate effectively with both. "If you can't explain your ideas to your grandmother...you don't know your subject well enough" (Frederick, 2007). Spector and Damron (2017) describe architects as having two indispensable discourse communities, internal discourse community, i.e.

fellow architects, and an external community, i.e. clients and, general public. Student crits and architect presentations also differ in terms in intertextuality. Crits at university tend to draw mainly on an assessment from a design studio module with possible references to other modules, e.g. history and theory of architecture and environmental technology (Swales, et al., 2001). In contrast, in architecture presentations, architects draw on a number of texts which they have co-authored and/or read as part of the design process, e.g. brief, site investigations, among others.

After design presentations, architects move on to subsequent stages which can involve co-authoring and/or reading texts, e.g. reports as part of the building process. These more technical texts are often referred to as business documents/documentation and can include but are not limited to planning permission, tender documentation, contracts, reports, manuals, specification lists, site meetings, project diaries, inspections and snag lists (Spector & Damron, 2017; Heidenreich, 2016; RIBA, 2020; Spector & Damron, 2017). These texts are often written with an internal audience, e.g. colleagues and/or client in mind, and not often shared with a wider audience, so could be considered occluded genres (Swales 2002). Spector and Damron (2017) describe one type of occluded genre, i.e. field report as a summary of observations coherently structured in a narrative description from general to specific. They provide an example of a poorly written field report description of a university library building's façade, provided by Oklahoma State University, and provide suggestions for improvements, e.g. clarity in terms of shorter sentences and specificity in language use. Spector and Damron (2017) share snippets of the facade description but not a full version in the appendix nor a link in the references. Instead, they advise readers attempt writing their own descriptions and then ask a colleague to draw the façade based on description (Spector & Damron, 2017).

Qualified architects, as well as students, can consult several guides on writing more technical practitioner-based texts (e.g. Heidenreich, 2016; Chappell, 2020; Spector & Damron, 2017) or ethnographic accounts of architecture practice (e.g. Medway & Clark) or even purchase exemplar or boiler plate texts (e.g. RIBA). However, this guidance must be treated with caution as texts can be very contextually dependent, e.g. in-house (architecture studio) style, and subject to changes in national legislation, local regulations, technology, codes of practice and other external influences. Limited access and relevance of technical texts written by architecture practitioners can mean these text types do not often feature in architecture undergraduate courses but may be more common on construction management and engineering postgraduate courses with more industry focus.

2.6.3.3. Critical texts: architecture practitioner texts: reviews

In contrast, to the limited access of technical practitioner texts, such as design presentations and reports, some practitioner texts, such as architectural magazines are more accessible to architecture students and PEAPs alike. Architectural

magazines, such as *Architectural Review*, are multimodal texts written by architects for architects. These professional magazines are often considered more influential on practitioners than other more academic texts, e.g. research journals (Parnell, 2023). Architecture magazines have a rich and varied history and often include both online and print versions, usually via a subscription. The magazine itself should be considered more of a genre colony housing several possible text types/genres. Like a beehive, independent units work towards a common goal but can be jumbled up in different orders. “If the parts are jumbled, the utility may be affected but the meaning remains the same” (Hoey 1986, p. 4). Dissertations may feature a number of genres (Zhang & Pramoolsook, 2019), such as a report alongside an argument, e.g. exposition, but due to interdependency of sections should be considered more of a hybrid genre than genre colony with hybridisation being a common feature of texts in creative disciplines (Carr et al., 2022). Or could be considered a macrogenre (Zhang & Pramoolsook, 2019) in which multiple genres coalesce. Whereas genre colonies such as architecture magazines will feature several independent text types/genres.

One of the most popular (frequent) text types in architecture magazines is the review article. In fact, one of the most influential, and oldest (since 1896) architecture magazines is named the ‘*Architectural Review*’. Reviews can feature in print form or in online magazines or blogs such as *Dezeen* and *Bldgblog* (Spector & Damron, 2017). According to Massey (2025), online publications such as *Dezeen* rarely have formal selection criteria and instead prefer ‘fresh, innovative and newsworthy’ content. An architectural review can review buildings, architects, architectural styles, books and exhibitions. The review structure may have some similarities with a book review. Motta-Roth & Heberle (2015) analysed book reviews from a linguistic perspective via genre analysis suggesting 4 moves and several optional sub-functions.

Table 10 Motta-Roth & Herberle (1995) review genre moves and functions

Move 1 INTRODUCING THE BOOK

Sub-function 1 Defining the general topic of the book and/or

Sub-function 2 Informing about potential readership and/or

Sub-function 3 Informing about the author and/or

Sub-function 4 Making topic generalizations and/or

Sub-function 5 Inserting book in the field

Move 2 OUTLINING THE BOOK

Sub-function 6 Providing general view of the organization of the book and/or

Sub-function 7 Stating the topic of each chapter and/or

Sub-function 8 Citing extra-text material

Move 3 HIGHLIGHTING PARTS OF THE BOOK

Sub-function 9 Providing focused evaluation

Move 4 PROVIDING CLOSING EVALUATION OF THE BOOK

Sub-function 10A Definitely recommending/ disqualifying the book or

Sub-function 10B Recommending the book despite indicated Shortcomings

Architectural reviews of buildings have a similar rhetorical structure to book reviews and critiques with two main stages: describe/summarise and review/evaluate/critique with a number of optional steps and sub-steps (Caballero, 2003, 2013; Nesi & Gardner, 2012). However, as building reviews tend to be longer in word count, they may have a more elaborated rhetoric structure with additional moves, steps and optional sub-steps as identified by Caballero (Table 11). The options chosen depend on the length, what is being reviewed, and level of critique. For example, Massey (2025) suggests the first two sentences of an exhibition review should summarise the exhibition (step 1) and claim importance/significance (step 2). This appears to lead to a more clipped introduction (Swales, 2004), but perhaps more elaborated description and evaluation. Caballero's (2013) analysis suggests architectural reviews provided detailed descriptions of buildings, and different elements of the building, often using metaphors comparing buildings to texts, textiles and music or more organic metaphors comparing buildings to animals or building parts to parts of the body. A clipped introduction may allow for a more elaborated building description and may also allow for more critique in a critical genre. Massey (2025) recommends a 'kiss, kick, kiss' approach where architectural review articles start with a positive tone and end with congratulatory tone with critique in the central section. It is worth mentioning at this point that some architects and/or architecture schools use the term 'review' for oral presentations, such as crits, as well as written critiques. While Nesi & Gardner (2013) use the umbrella term critiques for a number of written genres. There are some similarities in the oral vs written reviews in that both provide opportunities to critique design, methods and other elements. And in both cases, this critique is provided by experienced architecture practitioners and experts. Architecture students may be encouraged to read architectural reviews in architectural magazines, especially as many reviews are timed to coincide and reflect recent events (Massey, 2025). Some architecture students may also be asked to submit a text which incorporates elements of an architectural review, but as novices rather than experts in their discourse community, are unlikely to write an architectural review as part of their studies until postgraduate level, e.g. MArch and very unlikely to submit an architectural review to a magazine and/or blog until after qualification and more experience as an architecture practitioner.

Table 11 Caballero (2003) Moves and steps building review

VISUAL DATA	TITLE + LEAD (Topic introduction and evaluation summary)	
	INTRODUCTION	
	Move 1: Creating Context	Step 1: Building a situation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generalisations and/or • Background information and/or • Description and/or • Other (narrative, anecdote) Step 2: Evaluating the situation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem spotting and/or • Claiming importance
	Move 2: Introducing building	Step 1: Positioning the building in the previous context Step 2: Highlighting a specific trait of the building Step 3: Introducing the building
	Move 3: Providing first evaluation of building	
	DESCRIPTION	
	Move 1: Providing technical details of building	Step 1: Sitting details Step 2: Information on budget and/or construction
	Move 2: Outlining the general organisation/appearance of building (overall plan)	
	Move 3: Describing the parts/components of building	
	Move 4: highlighting parts of the building	
CLOSING EVALUATION		
Move 1: Providing closing evaluation of building		
TECHNICAL CARD		

2.6.3.4. Theoretical architexts: architecture essays and manifestos

Architecture magazine articles are not only limited to critical texts, such as reviews, but can also include more theoretical texts such as manifestoes and essays. Architectural manifestoes can be published in more general publications, such as art magazines, as well as architecture magazines. For example, Le Corbusier's fundamental architecture manifesto was published in various forms including an art magazine 'L'Esprit Nouveau as a series of essays, as well as featuring in architecture magazines and books (Oechslin & Wang, 1987). Manifestoes as theoretical texts can also be shared with a broader audience, for example, Marinetti's earlier Manifesto of Futurist Architect (1909) was published in the French newspaper Le Figaro) (Turan, 2013). Architectural manifestos, much like political manifestos, are introductory and ideological texts and can range from call-to-action essays in architecture magazines to entire architecture manifesto books espousing a new architectural approach (Massey, 2025; Turan, 2013). Central to the manifesto is the architect's design philosophy and this can also influence the writing style. For example, if an architect promotes economy in design, their writing style could be economical, i.e. brief, or if an architect promotes inclusivity in design their manifesto writing may seek more clarity/accessibility (Spector & Damron, 2017). Often poetic, polemic and persuasive, architectural manifestos can be highly influential on theory and practice of architecture and are usually reserved not just for architectural experts but for architectural titans (Spector & Damron, 2017; Turan, 2013). Manifestoes can often herald a new architectural era and previously have been most associated with

modern architecture of early 20th century, as well as post-modernism (e.g. Venturi's 1966 *Nonstraightforward Architecture: A Gentle Manifesto*) (Spector & Damron, 2017; Turan, 2013). While, manifestos continue to be influential, many have questioned the future of architecture manifestos in the current era of intelligence-driven architecture rather than modernism's previous manifesto-driven architecture (Dimovski, 2011; Obrist, 2010; Turan, 2013).

Manifestos in modern day architectural magazines may be increasingly rare, whereas essays continue to be a staple genre in architectural magazines such as *Architectural Review*. The architectural essay is described as creative non-fiction and can be personal and persuasive (Spector & Damron, 2017). Architectural essays can vary in purpose from calls to action (possibly following a challenge essay structure: *challenge; evidence; thesis*) or editorial (possibly following a discussion essay structure: *issue; alternative arguments; final position*) or thought-provoking (possibly following a commentary essay structure: *texts [could be images]; introduction; comments; summary*) (Nesi & Gardner, 2012; Spector & Damron, 2017). Essays written by architects can also vary greatly in terms of topic as well as publication with commentary-type essays with historic approaches featuring in broader publications such as *Country Life* and *Vogue Living* (Massey, 2025). However, Spector and Damron (2017) suggest architectural essays are far from formulaic and often resist linear narrative structures, in favour of connecting with the audience, as well as focus on creativity and unpredictability.

These architectural essays can be influential on not only practising architects but also students who may be asked to read, select, and/or write a text in the style of an architecture magazine as part of their studies. Some architecture practitioners, e.g. Parnell (2003), lament that in recent years architecture magazines may have less impact on students, who may prefer other media and influences. Architecture students who do engage with architecture essays may struggle to replicate the 'lively, stylish, engaging, concise and clear' style of an architecture essay (Massey, 2025). However, the essay's continuing influential impact on practice and study of architecture is reflected in the annual Berkley Prize which has been accepting 500-word essay proposals and 2500-word essays from undergraduate architect students for over 25 years (Spector & Damron, 2017).

The essay continues to be an influential genre on both the practice and study of architecture. In addition to reading essays, architecture students may also need to write their own essays as part of history and theory of architecture elements and modules elements and modules (Swales et. al, 2001). In undergraduate architecture courses, essays are often submitted in the second year (as part of history and theory of architecture modules) and in the third and final year, students may also submit a dissertation, sometimes referred to as a long essay (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014; Mey, 2013). Dissertations are common across architecture undergraduate courses but perhaps not as ubiquitous as in other subjects. Mey (2013) suggests that essays, long essays, and dissertations are considered by many art and design educators to

be academic dinosaurs. This view is not unique to architecture nor art and design, with educators recently questioning if dissertations are dead and suggesting alternatives including group-based and capstone projects (Khusainova et al., 2025). A group-based project as an alternative to a dissertation is a feature of many undergraduate programmes as demonstrated by the RIBA dissertation medal which accepts both individual and group-based submissions. This reflects the pracademic nature of architecture, which in practice is usually collaborative rather than individual endeavour (Dobson, 2014). In addition, architecture courses may also offer individual projects often referred to as capstone projects. Capstone, or keystone, is a term borrowed from architecture referring to a final stone in an arch. These final year projects can include conceptual and design projects in which students submit a shorter written piece alongside designs, illustrations, models and/or simulations (Healey et al., 2013). This reflects the pracademic nature of architecture combining design and text together. This may also indicate, to some extent, the weighting given to writing vs practice or text vs design by architecture educators. Mey (2013) suggests a weak dissertation or written project can, in some cases, be compensated for by excellent design practice but very rarely is the reverse true. This combination of text and design in projects also mirrors options available in further study such as practice-based doctorates in architecture and art and design (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024) as well as the two types of research defined by RIBA (2013) design research and research project. However, despite these options, it appears that the majority of final year submissions are dissertations rather than individual capstone projects or collaborative group projects. This is not surprising given that most of the guidance available for architecture final year projects is focussed wholly on dissertations (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014; Naoum, 2013; Spector & Damron, 2017).

Architecture undergraduate dissertations may also differ in terms of timing. The submission deadline may vary but for many architecture programmes the dissertation is not the final submitted artefact. Grad/Graduate shows and exhibitions often represent the final submitted artefact, as well as a ritual for students to be welcomed by the architecture community and share their knowledge and experience (Sizer, 2019c). As such, architecture students may be offered support with choosing a dissertation topic such as a list of potential dissertation topics, e.g. implications of new technology for building type, or new technique for building analysis, or design guidelines for a specific context, or architectural solutions to social problems (Spector & Damron, 2017), or may even be offered a list of potential architecture dissertation titles to choose from, as well as standard guidance on dissertation topics i.e. topic from previous assessment and/or module the student found interesting (Naoum, 2013). In addition to choice of type of dissertation (e.g. collaborative or capstone project) and choice of topic, architecture students also have other choices relating such as texture and structure which will be described in more detail below.

2.7 Textual practices (*literacy practices*)

Textual practices refers here to literacy practices from academic literacies which considers writing to be a social practice. As previously discussed, SFL and academic literacies share an understanding of writing as a social and contextualised activity. Lillis (2001) brought SFL and academic literacies together in a heuristic for understanding student writing practices:

Figure 20 Lillis (2001) 3 dimensions of student meaning in writing

Table 12 Lillis (2001) comparison between AcLits and SFL based on metafunctions

AcLits	SFL
Authorship: What can you say? What do you want to say?	Ideational metafunction
Authority: Who can you be? Who do you want to be?	Interpersonal metafunction
Authorial presence: How can you say it? How do you want to say it?	Textual metafunction

In terms of authorial presence and textual metafunction, student writers have a choice about some aspects of dissertation writing such as obligatory and optional elements. The obligatory elements of a text reflect the context and purpose of the text (Butt et al, 2000). The contextual configuration (context of situation and culture) can help predict the obligatory and optional elements of the text as well as order of these elements in what Hasan describes as 'generic structure potential' (1998). Hasan (1998) explains that a genre can be defined through its obligatory structural elements. In dissertations there are several obligatory structural elements:

- bibliography/reference list
- abstract
- title/cover page

However, these obligatory elements (bibliography/reference list, abstract and title/cover page) are ubiquitous across academic writing and could describe several academic genres, such as a research articles or a report.

One of the optional elements which could be considered obligatory and perhaps an identifying feature of a dissertation is the acknowledgements section.

Acknowledgements sections can feature in books and occasionally journal articles but are much more common in dissertations (Hyland, 2003, 2004b) and very infrequently among other academic genres such as essays. Hyland (2003; 2004b) found widespread 'almost universal' usage of acknowledgments sections in over 90% of postgraduate dissertations studied which could be considered obligatory based on Huettner's (2010) guidelines [100% - 90% obligatory; 89%-50% core; 49% - 30% ambiguous; 29% - 1% optional]. Afful (2016) also found acknowledgements sections to be prevalent in undergraduate dissertations and follow a structure similar to Hyland's three-move structure: reflecting, thanking, and announcing. Hyland (2004) suggests acknowledgment sections can provide authors with a number of interpersonal choices about the author's place [or authority] in the world from a personal, practitioner and academic perspective.

- **acknowledgements**
- *list of figures*
- contents list/contents page
- appendix/appendices

Another optional element which could be considered an identifying element of architecture (and creative disciplines) dissertations is the list of figures. Often a list of figures can refer to graphs and charts used in a report or dissertation. However, for architecture dissertations a list of figures often refers to images and sketches as well as graphs and charts. Due to the multimodal nature of architecture dissertations and prevalent use of images, a list of figures could also be considered an obligatory element.

An additional element which could be considered obligatory is the contents page/list due to almost universal appearance in dissertations. Research on contents lists is fairly limited but almost all macrostructure and rhetorical structure research on dissertations and theses includes analysis of and reference to the contents list (Bunton, 1998; Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). Similarly, appendices are also frequent across dissertations and other genres such as books and reports and are not usually associated with other academic writing such as essays. However, appendices tend to be less obligatory in dissertations, particularly undergraduate dissertations not collecting raw and/or primary data. Bunton (1998) suggests that introduction and

conclusion sections should also be considered obligatory elements in dissertations. The obligatory inclusion of both introductions and conclusions is also reflected in Borden and Ruedi Ray's (2014) and Naoum's (2013) guidance for architecture and construction dissertations. However, it is worth noting that while some sections may contain features, moves and steps to be recognisable as an introduction/conclusion section, this may not always be reflected in the author's nomenclature of subtitles. For example, in topic-based theses the introduction and/or conclusion may be indicated by a topic-based rather than genre-based subtitle (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024), so may not explicitly state 'introduction' or 'conclusion'.

As previously mentioned, several studies have explored the rhetorical structure of dissertation introductions (often postgraduate) based on CARS model of introductions of research articles (Swales 2002). An interesting study compared introduction structures from postgraduate dissertations, doctoral theses and research articles and found few postgraduate students followed the CARS 3 moves pattern as consistently as research articles and found differences in approach for move 2 [establishing a niche] (Choe & Hyun Hwang, 2014). Bunton's (1998) study found fewer doctoral thesis following the CARS 3 move model (T: territory; N: Niche; O: Occupy niche). Instead, Bunton (1998) found the majority of theses used a T-N structure, followed by T-O and the minority were TNO leading to Bunton's suggestion of a modified CARS model for PhD theses with fewer steps. Other studies have indicated that postgraduate and undergraduate dissertations are less likely to follow a CARS model with a number missing move 2 leading to a T-O introduction structure (Devira et al., 2021; Indrian & Ardi, 2019). Other studies have indicated a TNO structure with some steps missing. For example, a recent study of Vietnamese undergraduate theses showed less than half [40% so therefore ambiguous rather than core or obligatory status according to Huettner (2010)] included Move 2 (N) step 2, i.e. indicating a gap and only a small minority [17% so therefore optional based on Huettner's (2010) guidance] included Move 3 (O) step, i.e. principal outcome (Pham & Vu, 2024).

Thus, undergraduate dissertation introductions are likely to be clipped, i.e. fewer obligatory steps and/or fewer obligatory moves, than, for example, research articles. An alternative structure to consider for undergraduate dissertation introductions is an 'essay' introduction. However, with six separate genres, essay introductions can vary significantly. Table 13 shows six essay genres and stages [introduction stage highlighted in bold] (Nesi and Gardner, 2012, p. 98).

Table 13 Nesi & Gardner (2012) six essay genres and stages, introduction in bold

<i>exposition</i>	<i>discussion</i>	<i>challenge</i>	<i>factorial</i>	<i>consequential</i>	<i>Commentary</i>
<i>thesis</i> ,	<i>issue</i> ,	<i>challenge</i> ,	<i>state</i> ,	<i>state</i> ,	<i>text(s)</i> ,
<i>evidence</i> ,	<i>alternative</i>	<i>evidence</i> ,	<i>contributory</i>	<i>ensuing</i>	<i>introduction</i> ,
<u><i>restate</i></u>	<i>arguments</i> ,	<u><i>thesis</i></u>	<i>factors</i> ,	<i>factors</i> ,	<i>comments</i> ,
<u><i>thesis</i></u>	<u><i>final</i></u>		<u><i>summary</i></u>	<u><i>summary</i></u>	<u><i>summary</i></u>
	<u><i>position</i></u>		<u><i>thesis</i></u>	<u><i>thesis</i></u>	

The other section, considered by Bunton, to be obligatory in dissertations are conclusions. Conclusions could also be analysed using Table 13 and final stage of essays [underlined] (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). Again, there is much variation depending on essay genre. However, these structures are not the only choices available to dissertation writers. Bunton (1998) suggests that much advice on the structure of conclusions in postgraduate dissertations and theses is again based on research articles and often conflates conclusion section with discussion section. In many PhD theses, the conclusion as a separate section may be more obligatory (12/13 in Bunton's 1998 study and 41/45 in Bunton's 2005 study) and less likely to be obligatory and instead more core in masters' dissertations (13/15 in Lewkowicz's 2009 study) with an option to include the conclusion with the discussion section (Bunton, 1998, 2005; Lewkowicz, 2009). This merging of conclusion and discussion may also be prevalent in shorter undergraduate theses. However, architecture dissertation guidance lists the conclusion as a separate chapter (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014; Naoum, 2013).

An alternative conclusion structure is proposed by Bunton (1998) who suggests the following 4 move structure for PhD theses with optional steps for science/technology theses or humanities/social sciences theses (Bunton, 2005). Bunton (2005) found most theses followed moves 1 & 2 (with move 1 & 2 featuring most consistently and could be considered obligatory according to Huettner (2010)). However, Bunton (2005) also found several PhD did not follow this pattern with moves 3 and 4 being less consistent so should not be considered obligatory and added an optional fifth move: '*concluding restatement*'.

Move 1: Introductory Restatement

Move 2: Consolidation of Present Research

Move 3: Practical Applications / Implications

Move 4: Recommendations for future research

Other studies on postgraduate dissertations, e.g. masters' dissertations, appear to show very few follow this conclusion 4 or 5 move pattern. In fact, Lewkowicz's (2009) study suggests there is no single pattern for postgraduate dissertations and much variation (Thompson, 2016). Much like the CARS model for introductions, Bunton's pattern for conclusions is less likely to be strictly followed among undergraduate conclusions which are likely to be clipped, i.e. fewer moves and/or steps due to the shorter length as well as differing purposes of undergraduate dissertations. However, Adzimah (2021) identified 8 potential move choices for undergraduate conclusions but found only 6 of the 8 moves featured in Chemistry undergraduate dissertations and found only move 4 (summarising the study) to be obligatory, i.e. featured in over 90% of theses (Huettner, 2010). Adzimah (2021) also found further disciplinary variation with move 5 (giving recommendation/s) obligatory for chemistry dissertations (over 90%) but more ambiguous status for history dissertations (30-

49%). Other moves such as move 2 (restating objectives) were more frequent in history dissertations and described as core (50-89%) but less frequent and described as ambiguous (30-49%) for chemistry dissertations. Move 3 was also described as ambiguous (30-49%) for history dissertations but optional (1-29%) in chemistry dissertations. All other moves (1, 6, 7 & 8) were described as optional with descriptions based on Huettner's (2010) guidelines for individual move status [100% - 90% obligatory; 89%-50% core; 49% - 30% ambiguous; 29% - 1% optional] With so few obligatory moves and much ambiguity and optionality, this would suggest significant variation in undergraduate dissertation conclusions with, as previously mentioned, some dissertations not featuring a conclusion chapter at all.

Move 1: Stating the aim(s) of the chapter

Move 2: Restating the objective(s) of the study

Move 3: Describing the methods used

Move 4: Summarising the study

Move 5: Giving recommendation(s)

Move 6: Stating challenges

Move 7: Extending well wishes

Move 8: Stating the importance of the study

2.8 Summary

As you may have already surmised from the description of the context, text and textual practices in architecture, architecture dissertations are likely to draw both practitioner and academic genres. We move on then to the process of collecting and analysing dissertations alongside contextual texts and interview with an architecture practitioner and educator.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Objectives

- Identify language choices architecture students make in terms of structure and texture in academic written texts, i.e. dissertations.
- Explore reasons why architecture students make these language choices in academic written texts.

3.2 Research discipline and positioning

Applied linguistics is interdisciplinary. Linguistics is often described as the ‘science’ of language and is ‘in many respects a science’ (Crystal, 1968, p. 56). While, Sealey and Carter (2004, p. 184) observed that “since using language is a social practice, accounts of language in use must be informed by sociological insights, including ...social scientific research methods”. However, in reality, linguistics departments, and by extension, applied linguists, may be housed within the arts and humanities at some universities, but in the social sciences at other universities. Linguistics, like architecture, finds itself at the nexus of art and science. This interdisciplinarity is further demonstrated by the epistemological and methodological diversity in linguistics research (Norris & Ortega, 2007; Ortega, 2005). Some areas of linguistics may also be more closely associated with a more positivist paradigm, e.g. neurolinguistics (drawing on psychology) and clinical linguistics (i.e. speech and language therapy drawing on biology) and/or collect more quantitative data, e.g. language testing and corpus research. In contrast, linguistics research operating within a more interpretivist/constructivist paradigm may use more qualitative data such as interviews with text’s authors and audiences as well as ethnographic observations of context. Interpretivists may refute the positivist ontological assumption that reality is a single reality or truth (Waring, 2012), but it is worth noting that these are not the only ontological positions. Beyond this dichotomy, applied linguistics may operate within a more pragmatic paradigm and utilise mixed methods approaches, e.g. both quantitative and qualitative, or perhaps action research.

I value the diversity of approaches in linguistics research. My own research operates within an interpretivist/constructivist paradigm. This paradigm adopts a less realist position of one single reality and instead assumes reality is co-constructed in groups and needs to be interpreted to be understood (Sun, 2019). This understanding is interpreted not only by the researcher, and their reflexive position, but also by participants and community members. For linguists operating within an interpretivist/constructivist paradigm, text-based research goes beyond a myopic focus on textual analysis (Lillis, 2008; Sizer, 2021), and statistical representations of texts and practices, and instead seeks to also interpret contextual and textual practices from the perspective of the authors and/or audiences. A textographic approach adopts both textual analysis and ethnographic methods but does so from

an interpretivist/constructivist perspective. Textographic methods are combined in a conscious effort to offset linguistic/textual focus with methods which can explore context and practices, i.e. ethnography. This positioning should not be misconstrued as pragmatic mixed methods which may adopt any combination of methods to solve a research problem driven by pragmatism rather than theoretical underpinnings.

3.3 Research approach: textography

Textography as a research approach was first used and coined by John Swales in 1998 in his groundbreaking work 'Other floors, other voices: a textography of a small university building.' Swales' (1998) textography, explored three departments in the same university building by collecting and analysing contextual texts, community members' textual histories and text-based interviews with participants about their situated writing and textual practices. Swales (1998, p.1) used 'textography' as he felt this work was "something more than a disembodied...textual analysis, but something less than a full ethnographic account". Like Swales, I believe textography is neither one nor the other (textual analysis or ethnography) but both, simultaneously adding value and perspective through their integration. Defining research as textographic requires two identifying features:

1. explicit use of the term textography and fostering a textographic approach combining textual analysis and ethnographic methods.
2. awareness of benefits of using methods as one unified textographic approach. From a linguistic perspective: less myopic focus on texts and commitment to also incorporating textual practices and context through inclusion of authors' and/or audiences' perspectives and from an ethnographic perspective: less discussion and observation of practice but more analysis of textual practices and situated writing.

Without these identifying features, researchers may undertake research which may appear to be textography but in fact is one of two alternative approaches, i.e. linguistic ethnography, or mixed methods. Textography is a specialised linguistic ethnography that focusses on text collection and may include contextual texts from the linguistic landscape, a term originating in linguistic ethnography (Ben-Rafael, 2009). However, linguistic ethnographies cannot be considered textographies if a) not explicitly stated and/or b) linguistic analysis is focussed on spoken rather than written texts. The SFL notion of text includes spoken discourse and I too believe 'text' can include both spoken, written and multimodal texts. However, linguistic ethnography researching exclusively spoken communication would likely focus on investigating communities of practice rather than Swales' discourse community with shared texts and genres (Bruce, 2015). I do not mean to be a gatekeeper here. However, linguistic analysis solely of spoken communication would represent a departure from Swales' original textography and may be more comfortably defined by the umbrella term linguistic ethnography. The second approach which can appear textographic is mixed methods. Some linguistic studies may also adopt interviews

with authors or audiences as a form of triangulation and confirmation of findings. However, this is often more pragmatic than ethnographic approach with focus on text and limited engagement with context and situated writing. Additionally, research can bear the hallmarks of textography, e.g. explicit awareness of the benefits of adopting textual analysis and ethnographic approaches, but it is for the researcher to define as a textography. Although, researchers may define their de facto textography after completion due to unfamiliarity with textography, given the relatively narrow range of textographic research. For more detailed analysis and examples of textography see (Sizer, 2021, 2025).

3.4 Research context

The context for this study is an architecture school at a post-92 university in the UK. The architecture department is housed within a university building shared with other schools within the Creative Disciplines faculty. The School of Architecture has its own area within the building and special-use/designated spaces such as architecture studios (Scollon & Scollon Wong, 2003; Sizer, 2019c). Swales' (1998) textography provided a brief history of the university building based on archival research. Similarly, my unobtrusive textography began with accessible archival research, which uncovered an interesting history of a building originally constructed in the 1950s to house the College of Art and an architecture community history which predates the building with architecture extension courses first offered in 1897. For a more detailed description of the building's history see (Sizer, 2019c). Additionally, Swales' (1998) textography explored and photographed the context to provide a pictorial sense of a university building. In my earlier unobtrusive textography of a university building, i.e. photographing accessible texts within the context, I explored the context and the distinctive linguistic landscape during the grad [end of year] show. The unobtrusive textography illustrated a community with a shared past, hope to share a future through acquiring new members, i.e. via grad show, and distinctive from other communities, i.e. in terms of special-use spaces and linguistic landscape (Traweek, 1988). The initial findings of the unobtrusive textography seemed to indicate the school of architecture as a 'place discourse community' (Swales, 1998), i.e. a group who regularly work together with a range of texts (both spoken and written), some specific language, e.g. abbreviations, sense of history and communication of history and traditions, i.e. grad show. It is worth noting here that Swales' (1998, p. 204) place discourse community was 'not always at the same time or the same [physical] place'.

The School of Architecture recently merged with the School of Art and Design, but at the time of this EdD study, the school was dedicated solely to teaching architecture with undergraduate and postgraduate courses in architecture and interior architecture. The school is RIBA validated and has 3 accredited areas: RIBA part 1 (BA undergraduate), RIBA part 2 (MA postgraduate/March) and Part 3 (postgraduate: final examination in professional practice) alongside apprenticeship courses (RIBA, 2021). The focus of this research was on the undergraduate students, and had an

intake of between 80-150, on average around 100 new students annually. As mentioned in the introduction, a significant proportion of these students were European or international, i.e. non-UK students, 34%-38%, from 50 different countries based on internal data available during research period. The teaching staff also consider themselves to be international, with many having studied and/or worked outside of the UK.

3.5 Research methods: participant selection (practices)

Students who had recently completed and passed their architecture undergraduate course were sent an email inviting them to participate. The initial recruitment campaign in 2020, did not recruit as many participants as hoped and was repeated in 2021 and 2022. In addition, in 2021 (post-covid), recruitment posters were also displayed around the building. Emails and posters included links to participant information sheet, participant information clip and consent form (Sizer, 2020). Following 3 rounds of recruitment, 12 students completed the consent form, (2 were deemed ineligible as they were interior architecture and/or postgraduate students, 4 students were also excluded from the study as they had not provided current contact information). This remaining group of 6 participants was a self-selecting sample, and as this was a qualitative study with a small population size, the sampling strategy was not intended to be representative. Textual histories of submitted work were collected via the virtual learning environment from the 6 participants. Efforts were made to collect complete textual histories, i.e. all submitted work as part of their architecture undergraduate course. However, three participants had incomplete textual histories, e.g. non-submission and/or missing assessments. The three students with complete textual histories were, at the time of writing, still working within the architecture field and were invited to interview. However, due to work and other commitments, all student participants opted out of the interview stage. In addition to architecture student participants, one architecture educator also completed the consent form (Sizer, 2024) and agreed to a recorded interview.

3.6 Ethical considerations: macro/micro

Ethical considerations are important factors in research with participants particularly ethnographic research. In this study attention was paid to macroethics, i.e. institutional and departmental consent as well as microethics, i.e. participants' consent (Copland & Creese, 2015; Sizer, 2021).

3.6.1. Macroethics

Before embarking on ethical approval from the institution, I met with the Head of School of Architecture to discuss any concerns and/or restrictions to my initial collection of contextual data and texts. Favourable ethical opinion was awarded for this research stage in 2019, and I was provided with full access to all undergraduate modules on the school's virtual learning environment as well as internal documentation and data.

3.6.2. Microethics

A second application for ethical approval was made and approved in 2020 which included participant recruitment and consent, i.e. microethics. Students invited to participate were sent a copy of the consent form, participant information sheet and participant information clip (Sizer, 2020). The [participant information clip](#) was produced as an accompaniment to the participant information sheet which was long and not always accessible text and may be challenging for some students with additional needs and/or English as a second or other language, after reading about the benefits of clips in recruiting hard to reach and sensitive groups (Hammond & Cooper, 2011). The clip was also produced in lieu of attending in-person teaching events, e.g. lectures and studio during covid.

3.7 Research methods: text selection (texts)

3.7.1. Contextual texts

The first stage of data collection was collecting contextual texts from the School of Architecture including undergraduate architecture modules on the virtual learning environment. It should be noted that some optional modules were excluded from collection as they were not owned by the School of Architecture, e.g. faculty-wide or institution-wide modules. In addition to the participants' previously submitted assessments and feedback, learning materials from the VLE were collected and included, but were not limited to:

- Lecturer slides and handouts
- Assessment briefs and rubrics
- Module descriptors and reading lists
- Student exemplars – previously submitted & anonymised submitted work
- Other assessment guidance – including dissertation topic lists

Other documentation and/or data provided by the school included but was not limited to:

- course handbooks, course/module specifications, course delivery mapping diagram and other documentation
- class lists with cohort characteristics, e.g. nationality
- assessment workloads and deadlines
- internal data from Graduate Outcomes Survey and Destination of Leavers from Higher Education (DLHE) survey and other sources

3.7.2. Textual histories

As part of the study, texts submitted by 6 consenting student participants to virtual learning environment over 3-year course were collected. In addition, marks, comments, and feedback on submitted work were also collected, where available. Due to the nature of tutorials as well as studio pedagogy, feedback and particularly

feedforward may be delivered verbally, so may not always be accessible via the virtual learning environment.

After textual histories and contextual texts were collected it became clear that several assessments would be unsuitable and therefore excluded from textual analysis.

- Collaborative work as not all authors consented to use.
- Presentations as not written texts but also as usually performed live and recordings not available.
- Submitted work without sufficient language (not 'texty' enough) to analyse at a lexicogrammar level, e.g. limited thematic progression between clauses and/or sentences, i.e. image-based texts with labels and/or titles.
- Submitted work with more than one associated artefact, e.g. an accompanying model or other artefact, e.g. presentation, which must be accessible and understood by audience.
- Any submitted work which failed.

The pracademic nature of architecture assessments can result in submission of interrelated multimodal artefacts and texts (Hellwig et al., 2022), which can prove challenging for linguistic analysis. For example, the six design modules (50% of the course) were deemed unsuitable due to image-based assessment texts, i.e. insufficient language for text analysis. The six 'professional' modules, i.e. communication and technology were also deemed to be unsuitable as they too either had assessments with insufficient language, and/or modules which involved other artefacts, e.g. presentations/models/drawings and/or other unconsenting students. This left the three 'history & theory' modules. Year 1 and 2 history and theory modules again either involved unsuitable assessments and/or the assessments which changed during the course of collection (3 cohorts) i.e. visual essay to annotated bibliography, limiting opportunities for analysis and comparisons. Finally, the one remaining module deemed suitable for textual analysis was the history and theory module in year 3, i.e. the dissertation.

3.7.3. Dissertations

Dissertations as the final submitted written assessment were chosen as the focus of this study as they were most suitable for textual analysis and also represented the students' textual histories over 3 years of the undergraduate architecture course. As the most text-based assessment (5000 words), dissertations also presented the best opportunities for sustained textual analysis over a longer text. Dissertations are also common text types across undergraduate programmes presenting opportunities to compare key features, e.g. contents pages. Finally, as dissertations are part of a wider research genre family (Nesi & Gardner, 2012), this also allowed for comparisons to postgraduate dissertations, theses, and research articles.

3.7.3.1. *Dissertations: structure*

After collecting 6 undergraduate architecture dissertations and 21 exemplar dissertations (Smyth, 2019). The first stage was to analyse all dissertations based on genre conventions to confirm the genre and genre family. Nesi & Gardner (2012) suggest that the research genre family (including dissertations) would contain elements such as an abstract and list of figures. The next stage was to analyse the dissertations in terms of macrostructure. Firstly, Paltridge and Starfield's (2024) dissertation typology was used to identify dissertation type:

- Traditional simple (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024) or genre-based (Nesi & Gardner 2012) [i.e., IMRD introduction, literature review, materials and methods, results, discussion, conclusion]
- Traditional complex (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024) [reports on more than a single study, e.g. case study approach]
- Topic-based [i.e., introduction, topic 1, topic 2, topic 3, etc., conclusions]

Paltridge and Starfield (2024) had an additional typology, i.e. 'PhD by publication', but this is irrelevant to this study. Paltridge and Starfield (2024) also included one 'mixed' example in their study but did not list 'mixed' in their 4-way typology. 27 dissertations, including 21 exemplars, were analysed in terms of structure, i.e. macrostructure: traditional simple; traditional complex or topic-based (Paltridge, 2002; Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). It is important to clarify that these exemplar dissertations were already anonymised, so authors could not be contacted for consent to be included in this study and as such they will not feature in the appendix. However, they had consented for use as learning materials, and I had been granted consent to gather learning materials. As learning materials, the exemplars' macrostructure, i.e. subtitles, were analysed and compared, but other identifying features were excluded from analysis. The six participant dissertations were also analysed in terms of macrostructure and compared to the 21 exemplar dissertations. I would like to highlight here that macrostructure analysis involved using verbatim dissertation author's subtitles to avoid biased etic interpretations of what qualifies as an 'introduction'/or 'conclusion'.

After analysing and documenting dissertation elements and macrostructure, a further stage involved the Generalised Structure Potential (GSP) (Hasan, 2014, p. 10):

- The status of functional elements is visibly indicated: an element is either obligatory, i.e., it defines the nature of that register family, or it is optional, the appearance of the elements is subject to specifiable variation in the underlying CC (contextual configuration).
- The order in sequence of the functional elements that can relate to each other is visibly indicated, some being fixed vis-à-vis others, and some free within specifiable limits.
- The possibility of recursion/reiteration for some element is visibly indicated.

Hasan's GSP (2014) was used to illuminate language choices available based on the choices made in collected texts and not to create some sort of register classification, but to explore the potential for undergraduate architecture dissertations. In this project, an expanded understanding of obligatory to optional cline is used based on Huettner's (2010) guidelines [100% - 90% obligatory; 89%-50% core; 49% - 30% ambiguous; 29% - 1% optional]. Once the macrostructure typology had been established and language choices in terms of structure (RO1) identified, the dissertations could be compared with each other as well as macrostructure examples in research, e.g. (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024) and guidance, e.g. (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2006) in order to explore potential reasons for these language choices.

See below for a screenshot demonstrating the identification of elements and sequence based on the author's [6 participants] contents page. For due diligence, the analysis went beyond the contents page, as some elements featured in the dissertation were not always listed in contents.

	Yellow 1/3	Yellow 2/3	Yellow 3/3	Blue 1/2	Blue 2/2
acknowledgements	Figures list	acknowledgement	REFACE / ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	Abstract	abstract
Introduction	Acknowledgements	abstract	INTRODUCTION	List of figures	table of images
Methodology	Abstract	introduction	P. 03] _____ 1) 1. Why should we care?	INTRODUCTION	INTRODUCTION
MOROCCOGENERALINFC	Introduction	Literature Review	P. 03] _____ 2) 2. Acts of a caring city	LITERATURE RIEW	LITERATURE RIEW
WHATISMOROCCANARCH	Chapter 1 Climate/	Methodology	P. 03 - P. 04] _____ 3) 3. How caring is Commu	METHODOLOGY	METHODOLOGY
FINALDEFINITION	Chapter 2 Community	Discussion and Re	ODY _____ 4) 4. A caring urban outdoo	1) STEPS OF NARRATIVE - SNOWPIERCER	1) STEPS OF NARRATIVE - SNOWPIERCER
CASABLANCA	Chapter 3 Settlement	Conclusion	P. 05] _____ 5) 5. References	3) INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY -	3) INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY -
COSMOPOLITANISM	Case Studies	Bibliography	P. 05 - P. 07] _____ 6) FORM VS FUNCTION IN PL	9) INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY -	9) INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY -
CA BESTUDY1	Discussion - Conclu	appendix	P. 07 - P. 11] _____ 7) FORM EXAMPLE 1 : JAMES	15) CONCLUSION	15) CONCLUSION
CA BESTUDY2	Final Remarks		P. 11 - P. 13] _____ 8) FORM EXAMPLE 2 : HEAR	16) REFERENCES	16) REFERENCES
CONCLUSION	Bibliography		P. 14 - P. 16] _____ 9) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 1 : PA	17) DE LA VILLETTE	17) DE LA VILLETTE
TARIDOUALALOU	Appendix		P. 17 - P. 18] _____ 10) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 2 : RA	18) CHEL WHITEREAD	18) CHEL WHITEREAD
ILLUSTRATIONLIST			P. 18] _____ 11) CONCLUSION	CONCLUSION	CONCLUSION
BIBLIOGRAPHY			BIBLIOGRAPHY	BIBLIOGRAPHY	BIBLIOGRAPHY
			P. 20 - P. 21] _____	BIBLIOGRAPHY	BIBLIOGRAPHY
genre-based chapter	3	3	5	2	4
total chapters	11	7	5	10	4
	27%	48%	100%	20%	6%
Traditional complex + TopG	TopGen	Traditional simple	Topic	Toplo	TopGen

Figure 21 screenshot of identifying elements and sequence in dissertations

3.7.3.2. Dissertations: texture

As previously discussed, the 21 exemplar dissertations were excluded from texture analysis. In addition, three of the six participant dissertations were also excluded from texture analysis, due to incomplete textual histories which may have impacted later interviews and/or analysis. Before making this exclusion, I confirmed the 3 remaining dissertations were as representative as possible in terms of macrostructure as well as marks. One dissertation (blue 1/2) featured the highest mark, i.e. 82, one dissertation was midrange, i.e. 68 (yellow 1/3) and one at the lower end of range, i.e. 62 (yellow 2/3). These marks are also representative of the overall marks awarded to wider architecture cohort 1st (23-27%) and 2:1 (46-49%), based on internal data available during research study. One of the excluded dissertations also fell outside of the 2:1 or 60 or higher criteria, i.e. a 'good' degree, with an overall score of 52, again excluding this dissertation. The other excluded

dissertations received similar marks to the analysed dissertations (65 & 82). Additionally, the 3 analysed dissertations represented a range of macrostructures from topic-based to genre-based. The three analysed dissertations are indicated in the screenshot above.

3.7.3.3. Dissertations: texture: Theme/Rheme

Before Theme/Rheme analysis, each dissertation was added to a spreadsheet following these steps:

- isolate and number t-units,
- record corresponding chapter/section (macrostructure subtitle),
- record new page, new paragraph, new column, new line [page break],
- copy and add images (visual components) in the most appropriate position, i.e. between written components,
- copy caption/label [+ corresponding information from list of figures]

Table 14 T-unit, page and image number comparison between 3 analysed dissertations

	T-units	Pages	images
Yellow 1/3	249 (+24 appendix)	21 (+5 blank/references)	26
Yellow 2/3	156	24 (+7 blank /references /appendix, i.e. interview transcript)	17
Blue 1/2	286	16 (+1 references)	23

Then each t-unit was analysed in terms of Theme and Rheme using the following categories (Table 15). The table provides a brief explanation of categories. For a more detailed explanation, please return to the literature review. It should be noted that pages without t-units, e.g. blank/contents/list of figures/reference list, were excluded from Theme/Rheme analysis. Labels and captions were included if deemed part of the text, i.e. a t-unit and not part of the image, i.e. label.

Table 15 Theme categories, examples and illustrative instances

marked	subject	interpersonal	Textual	topical	Rheme
adverbial/ circumstantial adjunct, prepositional phrase, dependent clause [before subject]	see topical, but after marked element	modal adjuncts: mood, vocative, polarity, comment	continuity adjuncts, conjunctive adjuncts	first element: noun, noun phrase or nominal group	[last] element in which Theme is developed
<i>In Wales,...</i>	<i>writers</i> ...	<i>Fortunately,...</i>	<i>However,...</i>	<i>Architecture</i> ...	<i>...is vital.</i>

As previously discussed, this study includes subject, as well as marked status (North, 2005), to support Thematic progression analysis and identification of hyperThemes and/or macroThemes which may feature in marked Themes as well as topical Theme and/or Rheme. This Thematic analysis was also colour coordinated to compare mac, (Figure 22) from yellow 2/3 'notes' with the macroThemes (title and research question) listed with colour-coordinated Themes and key. Figure 23 highlights Themes from the subtitle as well as other Themes with corresponding colours.

Figure 22 Screenshot of macroTheme analysis and colour-coding

Figure 23 Screenshot of Thematic analysis and colour-coded Themes

3.7.3.4. Dissertations: texture: Thematic progression

Once Theme/Rheme language choices had been identified, I could move on to identifying the texture choices between t-units. Table 16 provides a brief explanation of Thematic progression categories for a more detailed explanation please see literature review and/or texture chapter. It is worth noting here that some SFL research can adopt either derived Theme or multi-Rheme, while others have counted these as separate categories. This study combines the two together as almost all derived Themes are included either in the Rheme, thus multi-Rheme, sometimes called split Rheme. Or instances in which derived Themes occur in previous Theme are covered by Theme iteration/repeat. An additional category 'peripheral Themes', was added for Themes which did not fit the three original Thematic progression criteria. It should be noted that writers can use one or more types of Thematic progression in the same paragraph and/or section/chapter.

Table 16 Thematic progression patterns with descriptions and examples

iteration / repeat (R)	zig zag/ Rheme > Theme (Z)	derived Theme / multi Rheme (D)	peripheral Theme (P)
Theme (element in first position) is repeated in next and possibly	Rheme (element in final position) becomes the Theme of	Rheme is split into subtopics, and subsequent t-units derive their Theme from one or more of these subtopics [often first or second	Pragmatic: macroThemes/key Themes: keywords; new Themes: authors with reporting verbs Extralinguistic feelings: I feel..., we believe..., [some crossover with interpersonal] Grammatical: '-ing' gerund or question word in Theme position Metatextual: 'this text', 'figure x...'

across t-units.	the next t-unit	sentence in paragraph have split Rheme]	[some crossover between McCabe's (1999) categories, so umbrella category peripheral]
-----------------	-----------------	---	--

3.7.3.5. Dissertations: texture: image-language [image-text] relations

Figure 17 Network of combined status and logico-semantics.

Figure 24 Martinec & Salway's (2005) original 'image-text relations' (in this thesis: 'image-language' relations)

In the final stage of texture analysis, having established Theme/Rheme and Thematic progression choices, we can move on to image-language [image-text] relations. Martinec and Salway (2005) theorised image-text [image-language] choices are based on the status and logico-semantic systems illustrated above (Figure 23). It is worth noting here that I refer to 'image-language' rather than 'image-text' as the term 'text' refers to the textual artefact, e.g. document, and for Martinec and Salway (2005), and Barthes (1977) before them, 'text' can also refer to

the written linguistic component, i.e. ‘the text of the text’. Len Unwin often uses ‘image-*text*’ relations to refer to particular frameworks, e.g. Martinec and Salway, but his use of ‘image-language’ is more prevalent, particularly in more recent works, and I have adopted a similar approach preferring ‘image-language’, where appropriate (Daly & Unsworth, 2011; Unsworth, 2006, 2007).

Firstly, despite Martinec and Salway’s (2005) framework (Figure 24) beginning with status, it is helpful to first identify the logico-semantic relations, i.e. expansion and projection systems. This is because, having identified how the image-language are related, we are in a better position to establish the status of these visual and written components. The visual and written components can either be linked through expanding or projecting meanings. The expansion and projection systems are briefly explained in Table 17, adapted from Eggins (2004), but for a more detailed explanation, please refer to literature review and texture chapters. The identification of the text’s Themes, via Theme/Rheme and Thematic progression, can support the identification of the relationship between visual and written components, either expansion or projection. For example, Theme iteration patterns may be accompanied by images which also restate the repeated Theme, i.e. elaboration.

Table 17 Expansion and projection system types and descriptions

Expansion	Elaboration	<i>restating signified by (=)</i>
	Extension	<i>adding [or varying] signified by (+)</i>
	Enhancement	<i>qualifying by time/space/reason/purpose signified by (x)</i>
Projection	locution (wording)	<i>projecting could be signified by (>)</i>
	idea (meaning)	

Next, we can move on to status and decide which element image-language (image-text) is subordinate, or if there is a more equal independent/interdependent relationship. Status relations are complex and sometimes ambiguous, so are informed by three, sometimes overlapping factors: positioning, salience and relations as represented in the diagram below. Much of Martinec and Salway’s (2005) status relations is influenced by work of key theorists, including but not limited to (Barthes, 1977; Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2002).

Figure 25 Factors in assigning status

3.8 Interview (practices)

The identified structural choices relating to macrostructure, textural choices relating to Theme/Rheme and Thematic progression and image-language relations were then discussed at interview. This interview aimed to explore some of the reasons for these structural and textural language choices. Unfortunately, as previously mentioned, all former student participants declined an interview. The academic interview participant was an architecture dissertation supervisor as well as a practising architect, currently involved in architecture practice and discourse community as well as responsibility for global engagement in the department, thus providing an enhanced understanding of international students' needs. This participant had also completed their own architecture undergraduate dissertation, as well as two postgraduate dissertations and at the time of the interview was working on their own doctoral thesis.

Prior to the interview, the participant was invited to an unrecorded online meeting to confirm understanding of participant information sheet, completion of consent form as well as discuss any questions and provide more detail, e.g. potential questions, if requested. At this stage, the participant confirmed they were happy to use the analysed dissertations as artefact prompts for interview (Kara, 2015). The participant also offered to look over their own 3 previous dissertations, ready for interview. The use of texts to guide the interview was in keeping with Swales' (1998) text-based interviews and also has some similarities to Lillis' (2001) talk around text interviews. However, the interview was not completely unstructured, and a list of potential discussion topics was included in the participant information sheet:

“texts such as dissertations (language used and choices made within the texts), textual history and textual journey, textual practices and processes, how others texts have influenced work, how context/s have influenced work and discussion about experiences as an architecture student and/or architecture lecturer.”

This list, as well as probing/prompting questions during the interview, were informed not only by Swales’ (1998) original interviews, but also Paltridge and Starfield’s interview questions for supervisors (2024, p. 249), Hakim’s, (2023, p. 6) genre-related episodes and Montgomery’s (2021, p. 156) questions for fine art specialists. The online interview was recorded using Teams. The interview recording was 1 hour and 40 minutes, including a short comfort break, so 90 minutes total. The interview was transcribed using Teams. Patkin (2025) calls for more disclosure of transcription processes and in line with his suggested best practice, see Table 18 for more details.

Table 18 Detailed transcription process

Ethical considerations	Contextual information e.g. references to specific people or places replaced with [REDACTED] to protect participant identity. The audio file of the interview not shared to protect identity. The researcher was the only person with access to the recording, which was saved on Teams using a password-protected account.
Transcription type	Verbatim (word-for-word) transcription, including repetition of words. No transcription symbols
Transcription check	Transcription checked by listening to entire recording at slow speed and correcting any errors, e.g. tutor often incorrectly transcribed. Issues with transcribing pauses and associated punctuation, i.e. after a pause assumed to be a new sentence, not corrected as meaning still clear
Transcription equipment	Camera and microphone from a plug-in webcam. Headphones not needed as recording in a private, quiet unoccupied office

After the interview, the transcript was analysed and coded following a more deductive orientation, i.e. researcher-driven (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The existing research (textual analysis) providing a lens to interpret interview data and theme development (not to be confused with SFL’s ‘Themes’) and coding (Braun & Clarke, 2022). In line with SFL and this study’s focus on choices, as well as reasons behind choices, there were two overarching interview themes: dissertation choices and dissertation influences. Dissertation choices had three interview themes: design, structure and texture and associated codes. Dissertation influences had three interview themes: personal, pedagogic and professional and associated codes.

4 Structure

This chapter will focus on the structure of dissertations written by undergraduate architecture students. Structure is a metaphor, used by architecture, while also a concept from Halliday's SFL. Halliday refers to multiple structures in SFL including mood, transitivity, and Theme. The mood structure is part of the interpersonal metafunction and can involve the mood system (e.g. declarative, interrogative, imperative). Whereas the transitivity structure is part of the experiential metafunction and can involve the process type system (e.g. material, mental, relational, verbal, behavioural or existential). The structure that is of most interest for this particular EdD research project is Theme. As previously discussed, Theme/Rheme analysis is concerned with cohesion between clauses/T-units. How these threads are woven together provides the texture. This can be extended to larger elements through Thematic progression and how these are woven together such as hyperTheme, e.g. topic sentences or macroTheme, e.g. subtitles. The text's macroThemes relate to macrostructure, so in this project to differentiate between the structural layers of language, Thematic progression, Theme/Rheme and image-language relations are referred to as texture while, macroThemes and macrostructure referred to as structure. Analysis of the structure, i.e. macrostructure can not only help identify language choices architecture students made but also aid in description of dissertations as genre, i.e. what elements can/must occur, where can/must they occur and how often they can occur (Hasan, 1998).

Four macrostructures: introduction of TopGen

We begin with the structural choices architecture students made in their submitted dissertations, i.e. macrostructure. The 6 participant dissertations included three main dissertation typologies identified by Paltridge & Starfield (2024) with an addition of a fourth typology I've named 'TopGen'.

- Traditional simple (genre-based, usually IMRD structure) [1]
- Traditional complex (often genre-based, multi study, e.g. case studies) [1]
- Topic-based [2]
- **TopGen** (mixed, i.e. topic and genre-based subtitles) [2]

Figure 26 four macrostructure typology triangle

4.1 Traditional simple/genre-based: rare

- **Traditional simple [1 participant, total: 1]**
- Traditional complex [1 participant, 8 exemplars total: 9]
- Topic-based [2 participants, 10 exemplars total: 12]
- TopGen [2 participants, 3 exemplars total: 5]

The 21 exemplar dissertations collected from the virtual learning environment as learning materials included all the typologies in the above matrix, except one. The typology missing from the exemplars was traditional simple. This finding may come as a surprise to PEAPs given the seemingly ubiquitous genre-based structure often reflecting something more akin to IMRD, see advice from EAP community (Gillet, n.d.; Smith, 2020) as well as advice beyond EAP. For example, Paltridge (2002) found seven of the eight textbooks studied discussed traditional simple structure in detail while one did not mention this structure and just three included other potential structures in any detail. In my own practice, I have almost always introduced the traditional simple structure for teaching dissertation writing. However, this finding would be less of a surprise for the architecture community who often advise architecture undergraduates to structure dissertations as a long essay with 3 parts: introduction, main argument, and conclusion. This advice is repeated in Borden & Ruedi Ray's (2014) book 'the Dissertation: A Guide for Architecture Students' which is not only on the dissertation module's reading list but also directly referred to in lecture slides collected from the virtual learning environment. And during the interview, the participant explained that their own undergraduate 'dissertation' was referred to as an 'essay' and recalled that it was not until around 2004 that the site of

study began using the term ‘dissertation’ over essay. This essay over IMRD/IMRAD structure is not exclusive to architecture. In the BAWE corpus study, Nesi and Gardner (2012) refer to topic-based dissertations as ‘long essays’ and provide an exemplar topic-based macrostructure with 5 chapters and a similar structure to Warschauer’s (2002) five-part essay: introduction, three body paragraphs and a conclusion. The interview participant also repeats the advice they have given students, i.e. chapter 1: introduction, chapter 2: 1 building/architect, chapter 3: 1 building/architect, chapter 4: 1 building/architect and chapter 5: conclusion. The 21 exemplar dissertations were texts selected by lecturers (between 2014-2018) exemplifying dissertations with not only high marks but also examples of ‘good’ dissertations, i.e. 2:1 or above. These ‘good’ dissertations represent good choices in not only content but also appropriate choices in how this content is structured (Figure 27). Additionally, traditional simple/genre-based structures are also missing as exemplars in other guidance, e.g. Borden and Ruedi Ray’s (2014) book.

		Distinct (1st) 70%+	High Pass (2.1) 60-69%
Does the work...			
1	demonstrate a research focus with a scope and structure appropriate to the topic?	Scope and structure are clearly articulated, strengthening the significance of the overall project	Scope and structure are clear and appropriate
2	demonstrate critical, analytical and interpretive skills through the use of scholarly sources and/or primary research?	Research approach, including use of sources, is approaching publishable standards	Research approach, including use of sources, consistently demonstrates critical and analytical skills
3	present a judicious and polished execution of language and formatting decisions?	The use of language and formatting of the final document are approaching publishable standards	Presentation of the final document displays a level of elegance in terms of language and formatting

Figure 27 Undergraduate Architecture dissertation criteria 2019/20

This absence of traditional simple as a model or exemplar or in undergraduate architecture student guidance might suggest this structure is not an appropriate choice. However, this is not the case. In fact, one of the six participants (yellow 2/3) submitted an undergraduate architecture dissertation with a traditional simple structure:

Table 19 Yellow 2/3 Traditional Simple/genre-based macrostructure (from contents page)

<p>Acknowledgements</p> <p>Abstract</p> <p>Introduction</p>
--

Literature Review
Methodology
Discussion and Results
Conclusion
Bibliography
Appendix

And for the same criterion as above, i.e. (1/3): ‘Does this work demonstrate a research focus with a scope and structure appropriate to the topic?’, this dissertation scored a high pass (60-69%). The descriptor chosen by the marker and verifier/second marker for this first (1/3) criterion was ‘Scope and structure show a critical and appropriate level of focus of the chosen topic.’ Therefore, the structure (traditional simple) chosen is also deemed appropriate. Yellow (2/3) did receive some suggestions for improving structure in their feedback (Table 20) such as relocating interview methods to methodology rather than discussion and avoiding repetition of research question. It is perhaps to be expected that architecture students, following a traditional simple structure, may encounter similar difficulties in terms of element location and repetition (Hasan, 1998), as they are neither explicitly taught this structure, nor appear to have an exemplar to draw from. The interview participant reflected on his concerns about an IMRD genre-based structure and challenges this can present for undergraduate architecture students (see snippet below)

Table 20 Yellow 2/3 feedback comments, bold added for emphasis

<p><i>Strengths of the work [yellow 2/3]:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Appreciable engagement and commitment during all the research phases. - Clear articulation of the uniqueness of Zaha Hadid’s work. - Very well-presented layout, including very good primary sources (diagrams, collages, and interview).
<p><i>Ways in which the work could be improved:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contents of single chapters could be organised and structured in a clearer way according to the title and the research question of the dissertation: i.e. interview as a methodology (rather than part of the discussion). - Few minor inconsistencies in the use of APA style standards (i.e.: authors included in Bibliography are not mentioned as in-text citation). - Avoid repetitions of parts of the text, e.g., research question, interview.

20:23: ..”Considering the 5000 word and 10,000 word limits for the undergraduate and the postgraduate they were trying to shoehorn in the chapters, OK, what is your introduction? What is your research methodology for this 5000 word essay? You know what is your analysis of the data? What are your findings? What are your conclusions?
 Me screaming internally that how does a poor undergraduate student who may have issues with learning and writing...deal with this, which is a science.”

4.1.1. Results and Discussion sections

This particular dissertation (yellow 2/3) is very typical of a traditional simple or conventional dissertation structure (Nesi & Gardner, 2012; Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). It also follows the IMRD structure (Swales, 2002) albeit not as strictly, as the discussion unusually comes before results in this subtitle, but as a combined (R & D) section. However, given this combined section appears to have a more 'integrated' (R & D) section, i.e. no obvious delineation between results and discussion, the order is less important here compared to more blocked [Results 1, Results 2 > Discussion 1, Discussion 2] or iterative [Results 1 > Discussion 1] structure (Stoller & Robinson, 2013). This traditional simple structure has also been observed in one analysed postgraduate architecture dissertation (Paltridge, 2002). It is worth noting that while 'traditional' or 'conventional' may seem appropriate for describing genre-based dissertations with IMRD structures, the reverse is true for architecture. In fact, the interview participant repeatedly refers to this genre-based dissertation as 'new', i.e. new for architecture, particularly at undergraduate level. Thus, it is worth reflecting on the terminology/metalinguage we use with students and/or subject specialists as their emic/insider understandings may not always fit our etic/outsider understanding (Sizer, 2021).

Before we move on to the other macrostructure types, I'd like to briefly discuss the sections associated with 'traditional simple' genre-based IMRD structure. We have briefly covered R & D (Research & Discussion) sections, i.e. blocked, iterative and our example which featured a more integrated R & D section, so let's discuss introductions and methods/methodology.

4.1.2. Introduction sections

It is difficult to draw conclusions based on just one example of traditional simple and a relatively short introduction (under 500 words, i.e. under 10%). The brevity of undergraduate dissertations, as well as differing purpose, i.e. undergraduate research less likely to establish a research gap and very unlikely to fill a research gap makes analysis with conventional frameworks, e.g. CARS model (Table 21) for research articles, challenging (Swales, 2002). Other models, such as Borden and Ruedi Ray's (2014) 5 components of an introduction may be closer in purpose, e.g. postgraduate dissertations, but are at least double the length, thus undergraduates are unlikely to cover all components. The yellow 2/3 introduction appears to cover the first two components, i.e. (1) *Zaha Hadid*, (2) *computation design, parametricism* and partially covers the third component, (3) *identifies history and previous reports on ideas*, but does not include the final two components.

1. Objects of study: summarise subject and identify main architects, buildings etc. dissertation investigates
2. Interpretive ideas: introduce main theoretical/intellectual ideas
3. Academic context: identify other work completed by historians and theorists, what work has already been done on this subject; what new ground

4. *Methodology: summarise procedure, history, theory or personal writing, e.g. politicised history or social science investigation?*
5. *Structure: preview dissertation structure*

This suggests that while the introduction can be considered an obligatory section (Bunton, 1998), and some moves/steps/components optional, more research is needed to analyse introductions in terms of moves, steps and components and optionality/choice. However, the extent to which the introduction section is obligatory across dissertation structures and types of dissertations, e.g. theses is also unclear. For example, in the BAWE corpus, a CQL query for <head> i.e. headings and subheadings, suggested at least 989 texts in the research report genre did not include 'introduction' as a heading/subheading. Paltridge and Starfield (2024) found a number of PhDs without a named introduction section, e.g. one of the seven analysed practice-based visual arts doctorates did not include an explicit introduction section, but all examples of traditional simple/genre-based included an introduction. This EdD research project reports similar findings i.e. an introduction section may be considered obligatory for traditional simple and complex but less so for topic and TopGen structure.

Table 21 Swales (2002) CARS model for introductions

Move 1: Establishing a territory	Step 1: claiming centrality and/or Step 2: making topic generalizations and/or Step 3: reviewing items of previous research
Move 2: Establishing a niche	Step a: counter-claiming or Step b: indicating a gap or Step c: question-raising or Step d: continuing a tradition
Move 3: Occupying a niche	Step 1a: outlining purposes or Step 1b: announcing present research Step 2: announcing principal findings Step 3: indicating structure

4.1.3. *Methods sections*

Yellow 2/3 is one of the very few collected dissertations which included a discrete section on methods or methodology. In addition to the featured dissertation, an additional exemplar dissertation included a section entitled 'method of interrogation'.

An absence of a discrete methods or methodology section is not unusual in the creative disciplines, even at doctoral level. Paltridge and Ravelli (2025) found that PhDs incorporating creative practice often did not feature a discrete methods/methodology section. And if methods were referred to this often occurred in the introduction section. In fact, the interview participant, questioned if undergraduate needed to discuss their methods at all in their dissertations. This aligns with criterion 2 of the undergraduate architecture dissertation copied below with added emphasis on the or, meaning students do not need to incorporate, and therefore, discuss primary research.

demonstrate critical, analytical and interpretive skills through the use of scholarly sources and/or primary research?

As previously mentioned, (yellow 2/3) adopts a less common (in architecture undergraduate) research approach as it employs primary data collection, i.e. interview with an architect. Only a small minority of analysed dissertations explicitly mentioned primary data methods such as interviews, observations, and phenomenology.

Table 22 Dissertation research methods

interview	1	
observation	1	
Phenomenology	2	1 explicitly mentioned in macrostructure, 1 in text

While the majority (20/27) explicitly mentioned ‘case study’ in contents and/or text. However, this method is rarely discussed further than presenting a building/architect/time period/style as a case study. This mirrors the interview participant’s use of case study in terms of a *design* case study, which blurs the lines somewhat between the design process and what those outside of architecture may consider the research process.

4.1.4. Summary

It is difficult to draw conclusions based on one example, but it appears traditional simple/genre-based dissertations are relatively uncommon in undergraduate architecture dissertations. However, the interview participant’s conceptualisation of genre-based as ‘new’ and discussion about trickle down impact of pressure to publish on architecture educators resulting in primary data methods being ‘shoehorned’ or ‘crowbarred’ into undergraduate architecture dissertation suggests instability (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). For example, there may be an increase in future traditional simple/genre-based architecture dissertations. This increased focus on research methods is reflected in changes to the dissertation assessment criteria (Figure 28) which increased from 3 to 4 criteria with a separate ‘methodology, methods and process’ criterion in 2021 and explicit reference to a genre-based IMRD

section, i.e. methodology. Thus, traditional simple/genre-based structures are a worthy inclusion in ESAP and EGAP provision, alongside other structures, i.e. Traditional complex/multi-study, topic-based and TopGen.

Does the work...		
1	demonstrate a research focus with a scope and structure appropriate to the topic?	Proposal and Focus Establish focussed research proposal from the practical and theoretical contexts within which they sit. [LO1, LO2]
2	demonstrate critical, analytical and interpretive skills through the use of scholarly sources and/or primary research?	Methodology, Methods and Process Evidence of systematic and/or iterative interrogation of the subject and focus. [LO1, LO3] Evaluation Evidence of exploration and evaluation of the history / theory / practice of the subject and focus. [LO2, LO3]
3	present a judicious and polished execution of language and formatting decisions?	Communication and Expression Clarity and structure of writing and/or design and uses of sources and/or precedent [accurate use of a referencing system is assessed here]. [LO3]

Figure 28 Changes in dissertation criteria assessment in 2021, 3 to 4 criteria

However, stability cannot be assumed and while the architecture department may be encouraging more traditional genre-based dissertations with primary research methods, the faculty has been investigating alternative formats for dissertations. Based on internal documentation, it appears one proposal is for a research by design alternative for undergraduate architecture students, i.e. a design-based exploration with 2000-word research report. At this stage, this is only a proposal and yet to be implemented but such proposals could be future forces for change (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024).

4.2 Traditional complex/multi study

As previously mentioned in the literature review, and earlier in this chapter, the traditional complex structure has many similarities with traditional simple in that it has genre-based macroThemes/subtitles. Traditional complex is often associated with science and technology dissertations (Bunton, 1998) as this structure allows for inclusion of multiple studies, e.g. experiments, each with their own IMRD structure. The interdisciplinary nature of architecture means that it can draw on science and technology (especially engineering) influences and adopt a traditional complex structure. For architects, this traditional complex structure presents an opportunity to include multiple case studies rather than scientific experiments. As previously mentioned, most of the 27 dissertations explicitly mentioned a case study. While 8 of the 27 collected dissertation featured a traditional complex structure and one of the participants' dissertations used a traditional complex structure.

In red 1/1 the traditional complex/multi study structure is as follows:

Table 23 Red 1/1 traditional complex/multi study macrostructure

acknowledgements	
Introduction	
Methodology	
MOROCCO GENERAL INFORMATION*	*Literature review?
WHAT IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE?*	
FINAL DEFINITION*	
CASABLANCA*	
COSMOPOLITANISM**	**Theoretical framework?
CASE STUDY 1	
CASE STUDY 2	
CONCLUSION	
TARIQ OUALALOU	
ILLUSTRATION LIST	
BIBLIOGRAPHY	

The submitted red (1/1) dissertation achieved a 65 overall demonstrating a high pass 60-69% in all 3 criteria. For the first undergraduate architecture dissertation marking criterion (1/3): '*Does this work demonstrate a research focus with a scope and structure appropriate to the topic?*' this dissertation scored a high-pass (60-69%). The descriptor chosen by the marker for this first (1/3) criterion was '*Structure and scope are clear and appropriate*'. The marker's choice indicates the structure (traditional complex/multi study) chosen is deemed appropriate. In the feedback, the dissertation was described as 'well structured' and advice provided on improving the conclusion section.

Strengths of the work (red 1/1)

A very credible piece of work, well structured with a convincing narrative

You provide the reader with a comprehensive outline across history

Excellent use of appropriate images

Ways in which the work could be improved

The layout was rather 'impacted'

The conclusion could have been further developed.

4.2.1. Traditional complex/multi study elements

Red 1/1 features the obligatory interdiction section for traditional complex/multi study (Bunton, 1998). Introductions also feature and are named as a macroTheme/subtitle for all 8 traditional complex exemplar dissertations. In addition to the obligatory introduction, Bunton (1998) includes an optional move of *literature review* followed by an additional option of either *pilot study*, *development of instrument or model* or *theoretical framework*. Two of the exemplar traditional complex/multi study dissertations featured a section named 'literature review' prior to case studies. These

optional moves, such as literature review and theoretical framework, may be realised by generic subtitles, i.e. literature review and/or more topic-based subtitles, i.e. 'history of...'. Three of the traditional simple/multi study exemplars featured a subtitle with 'history' which appears to be a short literature review. Also, red 1/1 dissertation does not explicitly mention *literature review* nor *theoretical framework* as macroThemes/subtitles. However, the four named sections (*) MOROCCO GENERAL INFORMATION* WHAT IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE?* FINAL DEFINITION* CASABLANCA* appear to be a literature review with topic-based subtitles (pages 3-11). Additionally, the next named section (**) COSMOPOLITANISM** (pages 10-11) seems to be functioning as a theoretical framework with the featured theory: cosmopolitanism. In a similar example, from a thesis in an allied field i.e. 'planning, landscape architecture, the author explicitly refers to a *theoretical framework* in chapter 3 and chapter 2 appears to represent a topic-based literature review section (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). Although a note of caution here, as without an interview with the author and more emic rather than etic understandings it can be difficult to recategorize sections as a 'literature review'. For example, the final traditional complex/multi study exemplar dissertation with an optional section between introduction and case studies has 2 chapters (1. *Utopia and Distopia: The evolution of open plan*; 2. *Factors affecting office well-being*; 2.1. *Access to green space and views*; 2.2. *Lighting*; 2.3 *Control over Environment/ Territory*; 2.4. *Sound*) which appear to be acting as a literature review, but this is not always clear.

Table 24 Red 1/1 traditional complex/multi study compared to Paltridge & Starfield's (2024) traditional complex in architecture example

<p>Red (1/1) architecture undergraduate dissertation</p> <p><i>acknowledgements</i></p> <p><i>Introduction</i></p> <p>Methodology [chapter 4]</p> <p>MOROCCO GENERAL INFORMATION</p> <p>WHAT IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE?</p> <p>FINAL DEFINITION</p> <p>CASABLANCA</p> <p>COSMOPOLITANISM</p> <p>X</p> <p>CASE STUDY 1</p> <p>CASE STUDY 2</p>	<p>Planning, landscape architecture and surveying thesis</p> <p>Chapter 1: Introduction</p> <p>Chapter 2: Byron Bay: from sacred sites to tourist attraction</p> <p>Chapter 3: Place character: a theoretical framework</p> <p>Chapter 4: Methodological considerations</p> <p>Chapter 5: A threat to town character</p> <p>Chapter 6: Community description of town character</p>
---	--

<p>CONCLUSION TARIQ OUALALOU ILLUSTRATION LIST BIBLIOGRAPHY</p>	<p><i>Chapter 7: Identifying town character features</i> <i>Chapter 8: Relating landscape features to town character</i> <i>Chapter 9: General discussion</i></p>
---	---

In addition to these optional elements of literature review and theoretical framework, red (1/1) dissertation also includes a methodology section prior to the case studies. This deviates from the traditional complex structure suggested by Bunton (1998) with IMRD mini sections for each case study. However, Paltridge and Starfield's (2024, p. 45) traditional complex structure features an optional 'general methods' section prior to case study. As can be seen from Table 24, red 1/1 inclusion of methodology section before case studies bears a striking similarity to the traditional complex dissertation from planning, landscape architecture and surveying featured in Paltridge & Starfield's (2024) research. Another exemplar dissertation (Table 25) also mirrors this traditional complex structure, with separate methodology/methods. The inclusion of methodology outside of the mini IMRD structures suggests the methodology is consistent across all case studies so each case study may skip the methodology section and focus on an IRD structure. However, this is not always be the case, especially for longer texts, e.g. PhD thesis which as suggested by Bunton (1998) each case study follows an IMRD structure without a prior separate methodology section. The exemplar PhD thesis (Table 26) in Paltridge and Starfield's (2024) research follows this IMRD for case study chapters (5,6, 7 & 8). The undergraduate architecture dissertations with a methodology section (Table 23 (red 1/1) & Table 25 pink) summarise the shared methodology for both case studies as a separate section. This may be due to lower word count, so brevity rather than repetition needed. For example, red 1/1 the 'methodology' section is only 150 words and pink exemplar's phenomenology 258 words. A shorter shared methodology also reflects architecture teaching practices as architecture undergraduate students are often not taught nor expected to use primary research methods.

In line with the interview participant's questioning of inclusion of research methods, most of the traditional complex/multi study dissertations do not refer to a methodology or methods at all. It is also worth noting here that both red 1/1 (Table 23) and pink (Table 25) methodology/methods section appear before what we could consider to be a literature review. This, alongside yellow 2/3's previous issue with order, i.e. discussion > results, suggests these students may have difficulties in deciding when elements appear in dissertations (Hasan, 1998). These basic difficulties with order reiterate the need for these students to receive explicit support and guidance, as well as exemplars, to develop understanding of what elements go

where in a dissertation as well as their options for inclusion depending on chosen structure.

Table 25 Pink exemplar dissertation, traditional complex/multi study macrostructure

<i>List of Figures</i>	
<i>Introduction</i>	
<i>Background</i>	
<i>Phenomenology***</i>	<i>***Methodology</i>
<i>Senses*</i>	<i>*Literature review?</i>
<i>Tourism, Landscape & Genius Loci*</i>	
<i>Case Studies Background</i>	
<i>Case Study 1 – Trollstigen Plateau & Visitor Centre</i>	
<i>Design</i>	
<i>Case Study 2 – Giant’s Causeway Visitor Centre</i>	
<i>Experiencing the Place</i>	
<i>Design</i>	
<i>Results & Conclusion</i>	

Table 26 Expanded subtitles for Paltridge & Starfield's 2024 traditional complex/multi study example showing IMRD internal structure

Chapter 5: A threat to town character	Chapter 6: Community description of town character	Chapter 7: Identifying town character features	Chapter 8: Relating landscape features to town character
Club Med development proposal [I]	Survey aims and research questions [I]	Research questions [I]	Research questions [I]
Research questions	Method [M]	Method [M]	Inventory of town character features
Method [M]	Results [R]	Results [R]	Randomly selected landscape scenes
Results [R]	Discussion [D]	Discussion [D]	Part one: respondents and rating scales [M]
Conclusions [D]			Analysis and results [R]
Limitations of the study and future research			Part two: respondents and rating scales [M]
			Analysis and results [R]
			Discussion and further research [D]
			Conclusion

In summary, all nine traditional complex/multi study dissertations included an obligatory introduction. One dissertation (Table 28) did not include any of Bunton's (1998) optional elements and jumped straight from introduction to case studies. All the other dissertations included at least one of Bunton's optional elements, usually a literature review, which can be realised by genre-based and/or topic-based subtitles. Two dissertations included an optional step of 'methods' element which features in Paltridge and Starfield (2024) as an option but not in Bunton (1998).

In conclusion, traditional complex/multi-study structures in undergraduate architecture dissertations are characterised by the use of multiple case studies chapter/s or sections. Dissertations using a case study approach with just one case study cannot be considered a multi study. Most of the traditional complex dissertations featured two case studies but 2 of the 9 dissertations featured 3 case studies. The three case studies approach mirrors advice from the interview participant. The case studies are usually indicated clearly in the macrostructure/contents page but may not explicitly use the term 'case study' in the subtitles but may refer to 'case study' within the text itself. Finally, it is worth making a distinction between the internal structure of these chapters, between PhD IMRD

structure as advocated by Bunton (1998), and undergraduate 'compare, contrast, conclude' structure as advocated by the interviewee. This is partly due to differences in focus either multi study, i.e. experiments; or multi study, i.e. case studies. This focus on case studies goes some way to explain why only two dissertations included a methods/methodology section and discussion of methods and when included, is fairly brief. For example, Red 1/1 briefly attempts to explain the featured research process "analysing in depth", and to some extent, research method: "examining two case studies" but does not go beyond this. Most of the dissertations with a case study approach are drawing on secondary rather than primary data. Although, as the interviewee explains, visiting, and photographing a site/building yourself is considered, by some, to be primary data collection and this process is likely to be rewarded in terms of marks.

1:06:04 "...the way you could get a higher mark was by going and visiting the buildings and using your own photography and that was considered to be primary research investigation."

Photographs can be considered primary data, for example in ethnographic studies (Pink, 2012, 2013) but these are often accompanied by some discussion of the process of collection and analysis of this primary data. Many of the case studies follow the interviewee's 'compare, contrast and conclude' mantra and as such can feel more like an essay. Therefore, PEAPs teaching/supporting a traditional complex/multi study dissertation structure may need to consider the expectations of the receiving subject in terms of method/methodology as well as other optional elements, i.e. literature review, as well as pilot study; development of instrument/model; theoretical framework. This has an impact not only on content but also structure. It is important to note here that due to architecture's case study approach often involving secondary data and more compare, contrast and conclude than IMRD structure, this limits the traditional complex/multi study in terms of genre-based subtitles in the case study chapters. Writers can include genre-based chapters between the introduction and case studies, but these are optional (Bunton, 1998) and can also be realised by topic-based subtitles. Thus, traditional complex/multi study in architecture is not necessarily always a traditional, strictly genre-based structure. This has implications for ESAP/EGAP teaching as an architecture multi study, and perhaps other multi studies, are not always just a series of traditional simple IMRD structures repeated and is in fact, more, well complex.

Table 27 exemplar dissertations with traditional complex/multi study macrostructure with 'literature reviews'

<i>illustrations list</i>		X		<i>list of illustrations Abstract</i>	<i>list of illustrations</i>	<i>Illustrations</i>
<i>Introduction</i>	<i>& Literature Review</i>	<i>Introduction</i>	<i>& Literature Review</i>	<i>Introduction</i> - <i>Outline of Importance of Social Housing Today</i> - <i>History and development of Social Housing</i>	<i>Introduction</i>	<i>Introduction</i>
<i>Historical Context</i>		X		X	<i>Chapter 1- history and context</i>	<i>History of healthcare Modernism and healthcare - The Zonnestraal Sanatorium an Alvar Aalto's Sanatorium New healthcare design - The Circle Hospital Bath</i>
<i>Case Study One - Letchworth Garden City</i> <i>Case Study Two - Welborne Garden Village</i>		<i>Case Study One</i> <i>Case Study Two</i>		<i>Case Study 1 : Park Hill, Sheffield</i> - <i>Overview of Location, Design Factors/Features</i> <i>Case Study 2 : Byker Estate, Newcastle</i> - <i>Overview of Location, Design Factors/Features</i> <i>Case Study 3: Coin Street, London</i> - <i>Overview of Location, Design Factors/Features</i>	<i>Chapter 2- Case Studies</i> 1. <i>Welbeck Street London</i> 2. <i>Tricorn and Northern Quarter Portsmouth</i> 3. <i>Avenue de Chartres Chichester</i>	<i>Maggie Cancer Care Centres</i> <i>Maggie Centre - Inverness by Page and Park</i> <i>Maggie Centre - London Rogers Stirk Harbour and Partners</i>
<i>Conclusion</i> <i>Bibliography</i> <i>Appendices</i>		<i>Conclusion</i> <i>Bibliography</i>		<i>Conclusion</i> <i>Key factors from each Case Study which are successful</i> <i>Key factors which could be improved</i> - <i>The role of the designer within the Social Housing sector</i> <i>Bibliography + videography</i>	<i>Conclusion</i> <i>Bibliography</i>	<i>Conclusion</i> <i>Bibliography</i>

Table 28 Exemplar dissertation with traditional complex/multi study macrostructure: left-hand side literature review with topic-based subtitles, right-hand side no explicit literature review

<i>List of Illustrations</i>	<i>List of Illustrations</i>
<i>Introduction</i>	<i>Introduction</i>
<i>1. Utopia and <u>Distopia</u>: The evolution of open plan</i>	x
<i>2. Factors affecting office well-being</i>	
<i>2.1. Access to green space and views</i>	
<i>2.2. Lighting</i>	
<i>2.3 Control over Environment/ Territory</i>	
<i>2.4. Sound</i>	
<i>3. Case Study 1: <u>Centraal Beheer</u> Headquarters,</i>	<i>Chapter I Findhorn Foundation, Scotland</i>
<i>4. Case Study 2: <u>Interpolis Insurance</u> Headquarters, Tilberg</i>	<i>Chapter II Vauban, Freiburg, Germany</i>
<i>5. Comparative Analysis</i>	<i>Conclusion</i>
<i>5.1. Environmental Control</i>	<i>References</i>
<i>5.2. Building as City</i>	<i>Bibliography</i>
<i>5.3. Equality</i>	
<i>5.4. Restoration</i>	
<i>Conclusion</i>	
<i>Bibliography</i>	

4.3 Topic-based

The majority of the collected undergraduate dissertations included topic-based macroThemes/subtitles. Several previously discussed traditional complex dissertations have included topic-based macroThemes and subtitles, e.g. red 1/1 chapter on Morocco with a series a topic-based titles and subtitles. There is a continuum to consider here from all topic-based macroThemes/subtitles to all genre-based macroThemes/subtitles. In this research project, we have an example of both, i.e. all genre-based (yellow 2/3) and all topic-based (blue 1/2). However, it is worth bearing in mind that both these structures, at the extreme ends of this cline, do not appear in the exemplar dissertations. As previously mentioned, this does not necessarily mean these structures are inappropriate. In fact, the fully topic-based macroThemes/subtitles of blue 1/2 was awarded 82 by the marker with three criteria in the outstanding range and communication and expression in the excellent range. It is difficult to draw comparisons with previous cohort (19/20) as the criteria changed from 3 criteria to 4 descriptors. Copied below with structure elements (bold) and texture elements (underlined) highlighted.

*Communication and Expression: **Clarity and structure of writing and/or design and uses of sources and/or precedent [accurate use of a referencing system is assessed here]. [LO3]***

There is limited feedback on the appropriacy of (blue 1/2) structure. However, the excellent mark alongside the following feedback comment ‘a very engagingly told narrative’ demonstrates that the structure, is appropriate.

A topic-based structure with no genre-based subtitle is appropriate for undergraduate architecture dissertations. In fact, one of the five architecture (postgraduate) dissertations also featured an all topic-based macrostructure (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014). In addition, 100% topic-based it is a structure used by in allied fields such as the creative disciplines, e.g. practice-based visual arts doctorates (Table 29: middle column) (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). Or a majority topic-based structure can be used in other interdisciplinary areas such as education (Table 29: right-hand column) (Paltridge & Starfield, 2024). Notice here the similarity between topics, i.e. care in left- and right-hand columns due to interdisciplinary nature of both education and architecture.

Table 29 Blue 1/2 topic-based macrostructure compared to 2 Paltridge & Starfield (2024) examples, first 2 columns 100% topic-based, right-hand column similar interdisciplinary topic but includes conclusion

<i>Blue (1/2)</i>	<i>What is happening here? [exploits of the nonhuman]</i>	<i>Self-Care and Care-for-Others in Education</i>
<i>Abstract</i> <i>List of figures</i>	<i>List of figures</i>	<i>x</i>
1. <i>Why should we care?</i> 2. <i>Acts of a caring city</i> 3. <i>How caring is Commercial Road?</i> 4. <i>A caring urban outdoor space</i>	<i>The Situation</i> <i>The Look</i> <i>The State(s)</i> <i>The Frame</i> <i>The Furred</i> <i>The Feathered</i> <i>The Consequence</i>	<i>Chapter 1: Hakbeolism</i> <i>Chapter 2: The reciprocity of Cuerrer, a reconstruction if self, and autobiographical theory</i> <i>Chapter 3: An ethic of care</i> <i>Chapter 4: Self-care</i> <i>Chapter 5: Care for others</i> <i>Chapter 6: Self-care and care for others</i>
	<i>x</i>	Conclusion
5. <i>References</i>	<i>Bibliography</i> <i>Appendices</i>	<i>References</i>

4.3.1. Topic-based: introductions & conclusions

The remaining topic-based dissertations (11 – not including blue 1/1) included a genre-based subtitle either an introduction, conclusion, or both. Albeit one of the exemplars includes only a conclusion (Table 30) and features no named introduction which is reflective of the doctorate thesis in Table 29 (right-hand column).

Table 30 Exemplar dissertation with topic-based macrostructure + conclusion

<p>2019 architecture exemplar dissertation on sound contents and list of figures</p> <p>1. The sound and our mind 3</p> <p>Introduction to sound 3</p> <p>Human perception 3</p> <p>Contemporary approach - neuroscience 4</p>
--

<i>Environmental psychology</i>	4
<i>2. Architecture and Sound</i>	5
<i>Aural Architecture</i>	5
<i>Pallasmaa's approach</i>	7
<i>3. Case studies and discussion - sound as a design tool</i>	8
4. Conclusions	
<i>Bibliography</i>	

This inclusion of introduction and/or conclusion reflects Bunton's (1998) three-stream model in which he suggested that introduction and conclusion sections are considered obligatory for all three thesis types. Whereas Paltridge suggests sections are more 'typical' than obligatory. And for topic-based dissertations lists the following typical sections: *introduction > topic 1 > topic 2 > topic 3 etc. > conclusion*. Nesi and Gardner (2012) suggest that topic-based structures are often 'long essays' with a 5-part structure with an introduction and conclusion section. See three examples from Nesi and Gardner (2012) (Table 31) from arts and humanities and all featuring an introduction chapter and a conclusion section, although one dissertation does not explicitly name a concluding section (left-hand column). The 61 research reports in the BAWE corpus (including those featured below) all included an introduction section. However, not all 61 are topic-based, for example 37 of these include a results section and a further 2 include a findings section, indicating around 22 could be considered topic-based but would require further analysis of whole texts.

Table 31 3 Nesi & Gardner examples of topic-based macrostructure, all with introduction, 2 with conclusion

Classics dissertation (Nesi & Gardner, 2012)	Sociology dissertation (Nesi & Gardner, 2012)	Philosophy long essay (Nesi & Gardner, 2012)
X	Abstract	x
Chapter 1: Introduction	Introduction	Introduction
<i>Chapter 2: State Magic</i>	1. <i>The Immanent Critique of Science and Sociology</i>	<i>Chapter 1: War and Rule of Law</i>
<i>Chapter 2: Funerary Magic</i>	2. <i>Morphogenesis</i>	<i>Chapter 2: Self-Defence</i>
<i>Chapter 4: Popular Magic</i>	3. <i>The Mills Vs Parsons Debate Reconsidered</i>	<i>Chapter 3: Humanitarian interventions</i>
	4. <i>The 'Essentially Contested' Status of power</i>	<i>Chapter 4: Alternatives to Violence</i>
	5. <i>The 'Essentially Contested' Status of Sociology</i>	Conclusion
<i>Chapter 5: The Legitimacy of the Proposed Ethical System</i>	Conclusion: Towards a Realist Sociology?	
<i>Bibliography</i>	<i>Bibliography</i>	x

Despite, 100% of BAWE research reports featuring a named introduction and Bunton's (1998) suggestion obligatory status of introductions, two of the undergraduate architecture dissertations, previously mentioned, did not feature an

introduction. Borden and Ruedi Ray's (2014) exemplar architecture dissertations (postgraduate) includes three with no introduction section and two with both introduction and conclusion. Paltridge's (2002) study also identified an architecture thesis with a topic-based structure. Paltridge and Starfield's (2024) research features a number of doctorates with neither named introduction or conclusion sections (see middle column Table 29) from various disciplines across arts and humanities, and science and technology. The use of topic-based in science and technology is somewhat surprising given that Bunton (1998) was unable to identify any science or technology theses in this third stream, i.e. topic-based. This may be partly due to more primary data collection methods and fewer long essay (secondary data) dissertation in sciences, so genre-based structures more likely. However, some areas of science may include an essay format, e.g. theoretical physics in which primary data can be difficult to collect. Long essays may be more common in arts and humanities in which secondary data is prioritised, e.g. history or literature (Nesi & Gardner, 2012), or as previously discussed, in architecture case studies. Both the interviewee and guidance on dissertation writing in architecture suggest approaching the dissertation as a long essay with three parts: introduction, main argument and conclusion (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014). This 3-part (introduction/main body/conclusion) structure is very clear in the yellow 3/3 dissertation structure (Table 32). The introduction section of these topic-based dissertations may then be more reminiscent of introductions for essays than research reports with familiar IMRD structure. In the collected undergraduate architecture dissertation Yellow 3/3 (below), the introduction section's main purpose is to define key terms and contextualise rather than Create A Research Space (CARS) (Swales, 2022).

Table 32 Yellow 3/3 topic-based macrostructure with introduction and conclusion, interesting naming convention 'intro'

Yellow 3/3

PREFACE / ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

INTRODUCTION

[P. 03] _____ 1) INTRO

[P. 03] _____ 2) DEFINITION OF ART

[P. 03 – P. 04] _____ 3) DEFINITION OF PUBLIC AND TERM PUBLIC ART
BODY

[P. 05] _____ 4) BRIEF HISTORY OF PUBLIC ART

[P. 05 – P. 07] _____ 5) FORM VS FUNCTION IN PUBLIC ART

[P. 07 – P. 11] _____ 6) FORM EXAMPLE 1 : JAMES TURRELL

[P. 11 – P. 13] _____ 7) FORM EXAMPLE 2 : HEART-SHAPED INSTALLATION

[P. 14 – P. 16] _____ 8) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 1 : PARC DE LA VILLETTE

[P. 17 – P. 18] _____ 9) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 2 : RACHEL WHITEREAD

CLOSING

[P. 19] _____ 10) CONCLUSION

BIBLIOGRAPHY

4.3.2. Topic-based: naming conventions

From the previously discussed examples there is much variation in topic-based naming conventions with nominalisations ‘architecture and sound, e.g., interrogative, e.g. ‘why should we care?’ There are also some examples of topic-based titles using verb forms:

Table 33 Exemplars with topic-based macrostructure + introduction + conclusion, interesting naming conventions gerund verb to begin subtitle

<p>2016 topic-based exemplar: regeneration</p> <p>Introduction</p> <p>Place-based Crime Prevention</p> <p>The <u>Hexgate Estate</u></p> <p>Gentrification</p> <p>Concealing the Issues</p> <p>Conclusion</p> <p>Bibliography</p>	<p>2018 topic-based exemplar: Wabi-Sabi</p> <p>Introduction</p> <p>Chapter One: The History and Representation of Wabi-Sabi</p> <p>Chapter Two: A Tea Ceremony</p> <p>The Importance of Wabi-Sabi in the Tea Ceremony</p> <p>Experiencing A Tea Ceremony</p> <p>Conclusion</p> <p>Bibliography</p>
---	---

Another variation for topic-based dissertations is in the naming of introduction and conclusion chapters. As previously discussed, some dissertations opted for topic-based alternative to genre-based introduction and/or conclusion. While others took a more interesting approach. For example, two exemplar undergraduate architecture dissertations refer to ‘preface’ [introduction] and ‘finale’ [conclusion] (Table 34).

Table 34 Exemplar dissertations with topic-based macrostructure and alternatives for introduction and conclusion: preface and finale

<p>2018 exemplar dissertation on memorial</p>	<p>2018 exemplar: House of nature & light</p>
<p>list of illustrations</p> <p><u>Foreward</u></p> <p>Preface</p>	
<p>A framework for reflection (<u>Pallasmaa's multi-sensory discourse</u>; Scale and Navigation)</p> <p>Maya Lin's Paradigm Shift</p> <p>Libeskind's experimentation in conjunction to the multi-sensory discourse</p> <p>The World Trade Centre 'Master Plan' combining precedents (Introduction; The museum: a place of reflection, The waterfalls and Tower One: Recognising absence)</p>	<p>METHOD OF INTERROGATION</p> <p>CHRONOLOGY OF INFLUENCE</p> <p>HEIDEGGER'S HUT</p> <p>CHRONOLOGY OF INFLUENCE</p> <p>JØRN UTZON</p> <p>CAN LIS</p> <p>MENORCA CONTEXTUAL FRAME</p> <p>THE FAVÀRITX LIGHTHOUSE</p> <p>INTRODUCTION</p> <p>BRIEF HISTORY OF SPANISH LIGHTHOUSES</p> <p>THE FAVÀRITX LIGHTHOUSE</p> <p>THE FAVÀRITX LIGHTHOUSE</p> <p>INTERPRETATION</p>
<p>Finale</p> <p>Bibliography</p>	<p>FINALE</p> <p>BIBLIOGRAPHY</p>

During interview with the architecture educator, they suggested this modification of subtitles was by design. The interviewee confirmed reading previous theses with *preface/finale* and offered alternative subtitles from their own dissertation such as *‘epilogue’* and *‘scene 1’*. This creative modification of subtitles may be due to interdisciplinary roots and influences on architecture, drawing on design from other disciplines. For example, Paltridge and Starfield (2024) include an interdisciplinary thesis using performance ethnography which also includes ‘prologue’ as well as ‘Act 1’, ‘Act 2’. In fact, architecture undergraduates are awarded for being able to demonstrate interdisciplinarity, see 3 rubric descriptors for 60-69 range (Figure 29) stating interdisciplinary.

60-69	
Very Good	
Proposal and Focus Establish focussed research proposal from the practical and theoretical contexts within which they sit. [LO1, LO2]	Well-informed, Wide-ranging, Accurate, Interdisciplinary
Methodology, Methods and Process Evidence of systematic and/or iterative interrogation of the subject and focus. [LO1, LO3]	Critically reflective, Consistent, Well-organised, Interdisciplinary
Evaluation Evidence of exploration and evaluation of the history / theory / practice of the subject and focus. [LO2, LO3]	Critically reflective, Exploratory, Thought-provoking
Communication and Expression Clarity and structure of writing and/or design and uses of sources and/or precedent [accurate use of a referencing system is assessed here]. [LO3]	Well-crafted, Accurate, Interdisciplinary

Figure 29 screenshot of assessment criteria and descriptors in 60-69 range, ‘interdisciplinary’ in 3 out of 4 criteria

In addition to these interdisciplinary influences, undergraduate architecture students are actively rewarded for creative language use and design. In previous years, the rubric descriptors included the following:

- **Exceptional/outstanding/excellent use of language and formatting that enables a rewarding understanding of the chosen subject.**
- **Presentation displays critical levels of elegance and clarity in the work’s language and formatting.**

And in more recent years, the rubric has been updated to include adjectives such as:

- **Innovative, risk-taking (80-100)**
- **Beautifully-crafted, poetic (70-79)**
- **Well-crafted, interdisciplinary (60-69)**

The use of preface and finale also has some poetic connotations with preface used by famous poets such as Wordsworth and Auden. Both poets and dissertation authors use preface in a similar [poetic] way to contextualise and introduce principles and approaches. The dissertation author may well have been influenced by genre colonies from architecture such as architecture magazines and manifestos. For example see manifestos which feature a short preface, but are not named as such in Jencks and Kropf (1997). In the Architectural Review blog, Gregory (2019) likens a preface to a building's entranceway or threshold or vestibule, a metaphor with immediate resonance for architecture students. In addition to 'finale' an alternative subtitle for conclusions, was 'closing' as shown below in yellow 3/3. 'Closing' implies a closing of the metaphorical door or text and could be accompanied by its antithesis i.e. opening. The same dissertation (yellow 3/3) also features a preface but in the paratextual position rather than as alternative for introduction (Gregory, 2019) and 'intro' as an alternative for introduction. This may well be a shortened form of introduction but does have musical connotations 'intro'. Other innovative alternatives for introduction and conclusion could include poetic *prelude/postlude*, or musical *intro/outro*, or literary *foreword/afterword* (foreword featured in 2 exemplar dissertations but in the paratextual position) or theatrical e.g. monologue, soliloquy, or act-based structure.

In summary, the majority of the undergraduate architecture dissertations had some element of topic-based structure. Twelve of the 27 were identified as topic-based while others had some genre-based subtitles and were either genre-based, i.e. traditional simple/complex or a combination of topic-based and genre-based, i.e. TopGen.

4.4 TopGen, i.e. Topic-based & Genre-based

Topic-based dissertations were the most dominant type in the collected dissertations (12/27). However, there were several dissertations with a mix of topic-based and genre-based macroThemes/subtitles. The graph below demonstrates the full cline from 0% genre-based macroThemes (Blue 1/2) to 100% genre-based macroThemes (yellow 2/3). Blue representing a higher percentage of genre-based chapters and red representing a higher percentage of topic-based chapters. However, percentages and quantitative data do not tell the full story, and further linguistic analysis was needed.

Figure 30 Graph showing level of genre vs topic-based chapter subtitles as percentages, red = topic-based, blue = genre-based, most fall somewhere between.

As previously discussed, 9/27 were considered to be genre-based, i.e. traditional complex and 1 traditional simple, while 12/27 were considered topic-based, leaving at least 5 meddlers in the middle with a combination of topic-based and genre-based subtitles. Paltridge and Starfield (2024) refer to this hybrid structure of both topic and genre-based subtitles as 'mixed'. However, in this work, I refer to this structure as *TopGen*, a portmanteau of topic and genre, rather than 'mixed' which is unclear which structures are mixed, e.g. traditional simple + traditional complex, traditional simple/traditional + topic-based and to complicate things further PhD by publication + traditional simple/traditional and/or topic-based which Anderson et al., (2020) refer to as 'hybrid'.

TopGen is defined as having more than one genre-based macroTheme/subtitle, in addition to introduction and/or conclusion (plus alternatives, i.e. preface/finale, opening/closing, intro/outro). These genre-based subtitles will often mirror IMRD

subtitles (Swales, 2022). This mix of topic and genre-based macroThemes/subtitles is dependent on writer’s choice. Below, blue 2/2 dissertation (Table 35) features an introduction and conclusion as well as a literature review and methodology, but the findings and discussion section have topic-based macroThemes/subtitles. This hybridity could be considered innovative and the marker agreed, awarding an overall score of 82 and 80-100 for criterion 4: *Communication and Expression: Clarity and structure of writing and/or design and uses of sources and/or precedent* with the following descriptor ‘*Original, Innovative, Risk-taking, Extraordinary*’. The marker also provided the following feedback: ‘*Your dissertation is well structured*’ suggesting this structure is not only appropriate but valued in undergraduate architecture dissertations.

Table 35 Blue 2/2 TopGen macrostructure, topic-based + introduction, literature review, methodology, conclusion

Blue 2/2 collected undergraduate dissertation

Abstract

table of images

INTRODUCTION

LITERATURE REVIEW

METHODOLOGY

STEPS OF NARRATIVE – SNOWPIERCER

INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY –

INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY –

CONCLUSION

REFERENCES

Another of the analysed dissertations (yellow 2/3 – table 36) also featured a TopGen structure with the inclusion of genre-based introduction and conclusion as well as discussion. This structure was also deemed appropriate in terms of demonstrating a research focus with a scope and structure appropriate to the topic (criteria 1). ‘*Scope and structure show a critical and appropriate level of focus of the chosen topic*’ (60-69%). However, the marker suggests the following improvement: ‘*I would suggest to dedicate more space to comparison of the case studies in one section. Now they seem split partly in the Settlement and in the Case Studies sections.*’ This appears to suggest a preference for a more traditional complex/multi study approach in which the settlements are viewed and treated as case studies. The interviewee suggests this dissertation is a combination of old (topic-based) and new (genre-based):

1:08:30: “*This isn’t an adoption of what I would call the **new method** [genre-based/primary methods]...Which is actually the traditional method, right?*

This is a quasi-version of what we just looked at...”

Table 36 Yellow 2/3 with TopGen structure: topic-based + introduction, discussion & conclusion

Yellow 2/3 collected undergraduate dissertation

Introduction

Chapter 1 Climate/location
Chapter 2 Community
Chapter 3 Settlements
Case Studies
Discussion - Conclusion
Final Remarks
Bibliography
Appendix

These quasi-versions combining topic-based and genre-based, i.e. TopGen, are appropriate. For example, one of Borden and Ruedi Ray's (2014) exemplar dissertations adopts a five-chapter TopGen structure with three topic-based chapters followed by two genre-based chapters: findings & conclusions. But the topic-based structure, i.e. other five Borden and Ruedi Ray (2014) examples and 12/27 UG dissertations are more prevalent, while TopGen structures are less prevalent. Perhaps, for architects combining topic-based and genre-based represents a combination of the older architectural structure and newer academic structure, i.e. pracademic. But there is tension and risk here choosing between and finding a balance.

Other exemplar dissertations also follow a TopGen structure but may take more risks and/or be more flexible in terms of naming practices and/or order of sections. Notice in Table 37, the less typical order of literature review and discussion sections (*). All three examples below are TopGen with a mix of traditional simple genre-based and topic-based subtitles. Paltridge and Starfield (2024, p. 23) identified a mixed simple traditional and topic-based doctorate from a practice-based theatre practitioner which includes a literature review as well as methodology section, in addition to introduction and combined results and conclusion section (Table 37, right-hand column).

Table 37 Two exemplar dissertations with TopGen macrostructure with non-typical order compared with Paltridge & Starfield (2024)

		Paltridge & Starfield (2024) example
<i>ABSTRACT</i>	<i>Illustrations</i>	
INTRODUCTION	INTRODUCTION	Introduction
x	DISCUSSION*	Literature review
		Methodology
<i>CHAPTER 1 (The Emergence and Evolution of Photography)</i> <i>CHAPTER 2 (Visual Perception of Architecture)</i>	<i>CASE STUDY: MAGGIES WEST LONDON USER RESPONSE</i>	<i>A summary of the studies</i> <i>The stylistic qualities of postdramatic theatre & intermediality</i>

<i>CHAPTER 3 (Architect & Photographer Partnerships)</i>	ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK	<i>The poetics of postdramatic theatre: findings and conclusion</i>
CONCLUSION	CONCLUSION	
<i>Figures in colour Illustrations list Literature review*</i>	<i>BIBLIOGRAPHY Appendix</i>	X
Bibliography		

TopGen elements can also feature in traditional complex through genre-based subtitles and topic-based subtitles. Although, perhaps less frequent as genre-based subtitles in traditional complex are optional elements between the introduction and case studies (Bunton, 1998). As discussed previously, red (1/1) is traditional complex due to multiple case studies but also has TopGen elements as it uses optional genre-based macroTheme/subtitle ‘methodology’ in addition to introduction and conclusion. The pink 2016 exemplar in the right-hand column of Table 38 is similar as it is also traditional complex with multi-study (case study) approach but includes the ubiquitous introduction but also combines ‘conclusion’ section with ‘results’, similar to the practice-based doctorate in right-hand column in Table 37 from Paltridge and Starfield (2024). In addition, this exemplar (pink 2016) also features a methodology section but refers directly to the method used, i.e. ‘phenomenology’. However, it is important to note that while both examples below have TopGen features they have been recorded as Traditional complex. As previously discussed, if we accept that traditional complex/multi study can be realised through genre-based and/or topic-based subtitles, then the examples below are defined first and foremost by their obligatory elements, i.e. multiple case studies structured in separate chapters (Bunton, 1998). Dissertations with just one case study or one chapter with multiple case studies cannot be considered multi study but depending on naming conventions could be genre-based, i.e. traditional simple, topic-based or a mix of the two, i.e. TopGen. Although no examples were identified, it may be the case that dissertations with one chapter and multiple case studies adopt genre-based chapter subtitles which could qualify it as TopGen. I also accept that due to hybridity and encouragement for innovation that there may be some texts and structures not accounted for which could be considered both Traditional complex/multi study and TopGen.

Table 38 Dissertations with TopGen elements but multi study

Red (1/1) architecture undergraduate dissertation <i>Acknowledgements</i> Introduction Methodology MOROCCO GENERAL INFORMATION WHAT IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE? FINAL DEFINITION CASABLANCA COSMOPOLITANISM CASE STUDY 1 CASE STUDY 2	2016 architecture exemplar dissertation on landscape <i>List of Figures</i> Introduction <i>Background</i> <u><i>Phenomenology</i></u> <i>Senses</i> <i>Tourism, Landscape & Genius Loci</i> <i>Case Studies Background</i> Case Study 1 – <u><i>Trollstigen Plateau & Visitor Centre</i></u> <i>Design</i> Case Study 2 – <i>Giant's Causeway Visitor Centre</i> <i>Experiencing the Place</i> <i>Design</i> Results & Conclusion <i>Bibliography</i>
CONCLUSION TARIQ OUALALOU ILLUSTRATION LIST BIBLIOGRAPHY	

In summary, TopGen appears to be an appropriate and perhaps emerging structure typology among architecture undergraduate dissertations. For example, the first exemplar TopGen is in 2016, there were no examples in either 2014 or 2015, then two examples in 2018. Due to the small numbers of texts, this does not represent a trend, as such, but the inclusion of TopGen in exemplars signifies an acceptance and encouragement of the structure. In contrast, the traditional simple/genre-based structure does not appear in the exemplars. TopGen as a 'quasi-version', not quite topic or genre-based, may offer students opportunities for innovation and creativity while providing some underlying safety via structure from traditional simple. As previously mentioned, there is a continuum here from topic-based to genre-based but perhaps in light of the interview, perhaps it should be reframed as practice-based to academic-based structures with TopGen as pracademic alternative. This may allow students to be more "strategic" with structure choices, considering their future goals, i.e. architecture practice and/or architecture educator and/or architecture researcher, while also perhaps mirroring their practice-focussed/pedagogy-focussed/research-focussed supervisor's preferences. For example, supervisors actively engaged in research may prefer a more genre-based structure, whereas practising architects may prefer more topic-based with TopGen presenting an option between the two. This TopGen structure presents an opportunity for risk-taking, and innovation as indicated in the rubric. Architecture values innovation but in an ambiguous studio pedagogy format, risks can be risky. Students need to be better supported in making informed choices which involves making these structure choices explicit as well as recognising students' resources and resourcefulness in

engaging in a personal project which not only reflects their learning journey but also their preparation for practice (Price & Archer, 2021).

5 Texture

In addition to choices about structure, students also have a wealth of texture choices including Theme, Thematic progression, and image-language relations. As previously mentioned, texture choice analysis is limited to three analysed undergraduate architecture dissertations as the other three participants did not have full textual histories and/or contact information. The three analysed dissertations represent a range of structures topic to genre-based and were also discussed with the interviewee.

5.1 Thematic choice: unmarked dominant but marked prevalent

Writers have several choices of Theme when structuring clauses/t-units/sentences, i.e. marked Theme or unmarked Theme (interpersonal, textual, or topical). As discussed previously, the typical and expected choice is ‘unmarked’ whereas atypical choices are described as ‘marked’ (Eggins, 2004). Unmarked Themes are said to be in their expected position and role, e.g. subject in declarative clauses (Eggins, 2004). Academic written texts, such as dissertations, are mostly declarative clauses and sentences, so the expected/typical choice would be unmarked topical Theme. This is the case for the three undergraduate architecture dissertations, unmarked topical Theme was, by far, the most prevalent Theme accounting for the majority of themes i.e. over 50% in topic-based, TopGen and traditional simple structures.

Table 39 Theme choice in 3 analysed dissertations based on percentages

	Topic-based (blue 1/2)	TopGen (Yellow 1/3)	Traditional simple (yellow 2/3)
Unmarked topical Theme	57%	57%	65%
Marked Theme	23%	25%	15%
Textual Theme	14%	11%	13%
Interpersonal Theme	5%	6%	7%

The dominance of unmarked topical Themes is unsurprising given that unmarked topical Themes are usually the most prevalent across academic written genres such as research articles (Alotaibi, 2020; Sajeedin, 2024) as well as student academic writing across multiple genres, e.g. reports and articles (Al-Reshaid & Alhojailan, 2025), essays (Bakaa, 2015; Hewings, 2004; North, 2005) and dissertations (Suharsono et al., 2024). The prevalence of unmarked topical Themes can vary depending on the writer, discipline and/or genre. For example, one study on research articles indicates much greater prevalence of unmarked topical/ideational Theme in sociology (100%) compared to Film and Cinema (71%) with harder sciences like mathematics and chemistry falling somewhere between at around 80% (Ghadessy,

1999). However, given Ghadessy's (2019) study was on research article abstracts this may tell us more about specific journal's abstract preferences than textual practices of particular disciplines. Direct comparisons can be misleading but the trend for fewer unmarked topical Themes in creative disciplines' academic texts, such as film and cinema, may have some bearing on other creative disciplines, such as architecture. A study involving student writing within the creative disciplines, i.e. media, also found unmarked topical Themes to be less dominant with marked Themes accounting for around 20% of student texts and slightly more in expert texts, e.g. newspapers (Hawes & Thomas, 2012). A similar study analysing student essays compared arts and science essays and found unmarked topical Themes to be slightly less dominant in arts-based essays when compared to science essays (North, 2005). Further research is needed with creative disciplines texts to discern the extent to which simple unmarked Themes are less dominant. But given our findings of less dominant unmarked Themes correlate with other studies in creative disciplines, this would suggest marked Themes are a choice for architecture undergraduate dissertation writers and something worth exploring with students in ESAP provision, not only for architecture, but also other creative disciplines and perhaps other disciplines.

Unmarked Theme represents the most expected, and often simplest, choice. This simplicity is interesting in of itself when considering that the 'traditional *simple*' dissertation had the highest proportion of unmarked Themes in this study. It is difficult to generalise based on a small number of cases, but other studies (Al-Reshaid & Alhojailan, 2025) have found marked Themes less prevalent in traditional genres such as dissertations, i.e. research report genre families (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). The choice of unmarked Theme can enhance a text's clarity and directness (Suharsono et al., 2024). Whereas, the choice of marked Theme, rather than unmarked topical Theme, can enhance a text's coherence and provide opportunities for emphasis by skilled and expert writers (Eggins, 2004). The choice of marked Theme, if successful, can lead to well-crafted writing which is an expectation featured in architecture undergraduate dissertation rubric descriptors:

- *Innovative, risk-taking* (80-100)
- ***Beautifully-crafted, poetic*** (70-79)
- ***Well-crafted, interdisciplinary*** (60-69)

Nevertheless, it would be a false assumption to equate more marked Themes with more crafted and/or expert writing as there are several factors involved. Even in poetic writing, e.g. poems and short stories, marked Theme choices can vary between texts written by the same author such as poems by Edgar Allan Poe and short stories by Olga Masters (Hanh, 2021; Khaflan et al., 2021). While unmarked Themes dominate across genres, there is also variation in marked Theme prevalence in academic writing across distinct levels. For example, a study on geography undergraduate essays study showed slightly greater prevalence for

marked Themes when comparing first year and third year essays (Hewings, 2004). Ebrahimi and Ebrahimi's (2012) study had similar findings i.e. slightly greater prevalence for marked Themes when comparing compositions of sophomores, juniors and seniors. The assumption may be that the higher the level, the more skilful and greater prevalence of marked Themes. However, this is not always the case, especially when making comparisons to doctoral theses and research articles. A recent study compared undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral dissertations and found a slight increase in marked Themes prevalence between undergraduate theses (45%) and master's theses (46%) but surprisingly a drop in prevalence for doctoral theses (41%) (Suharsono et al., 2024). A similar study compared undergraduate, postgraduate and research articles and found broadly similar levels of marked Themes with undergraduate compositions having the highest prevalence (10.18%), followed by research articles (10.03%) and postgraduate compositions the lowest (9.24%) (Jalilifar et al., 2017).

I would like to point out here that percentages are included to make comparisons within studies but are not always helpful for making direct, like-for-like comparisons between studies. Theme and Rheme analysis can vary and these studies represent slightly different approaches. For example, Suharsono et al.'s (2024) study adopts clauses as the unit of analysis, whereas Jalilifar et al.'s (2017) study adopts t-units as the unit of analysis leading to differences in percentages. Analysis of the t-unit, rather than clause, allows for greater analysis of Thematic progression. Thus, this study, and most featured studies, use t-units as the unit analysis. Despite some analytical variation, unmarked Theme is dominant, but marked Theme can vary in prevalence with some indications that creative disciplines and/or undergraduate texts may have an increased prevalence in marked Themes in comparison to other texts, e.g. doctorate theses.

There is some rationale for expert writers using fewer marked Themes and this relates to the audience and purpose as well as length. In expert writing genres, such as research articles and doctorates, the purpose and audience are different to those of student writing genres. The distinction here being the former are written by experts and the latter for experts. The apprenticeship model suggests that students begin as apprentices before joining the discourse community of their teachers, i.e. experts (Lave & Wenger, 1991). This transition may begin with normative, conforming texts, meeting the expectations at undergraduate level and emulating texts they have read and perceived levels of complexity, due, in part, to greater prevalence of marked Themes (Al-Reshaid & Alhojailan, 2025; Suharsono et al., 2024). Whereas more expert writers such as doctoral students 'apprentice experts' (Pecorari & Coxhead, 2025) or subject/research experts may also be more experienced in writing across several genres and may subvert or deconstruct rather than conform to genre expectations. For example see BALEAP 2023 conference proceedings with poems and scrapbooks as genres (Cowley-Haselden, et al., 2025). Additionally, experts writing for others may value clarity and directness of unmarked Themes over

obfuscation with marked Themes, particularly when writing for a wider readership (Suharsono et al., 2024). An example of this preference for clarity and directness is perhaps the popularity of genres such as the Conversation which are written to be accessible and clear for non-specialists (*About Us*, n.d.). In architecture, clarity is a sought-after characteristic and reflected in not only the marking rubric, see Figure 31: highlighted 60-69% descriptor below) but also in the overall purpose of a dissertation according to the interviewee, i.e. communication with a wider audience.

50:13: “*What is the point of the dissertation? The point of a dissertation is...That the student knows how to write something in professional language.*”

<p>3 ...present a judicious and polished execution of language and formatting decisions?</p>	<p>Exceptional use of language and formatting that enables a rewarding understanding of the chosen subject, approaching publishable standards.</p>	<p>Outstanding use of language and formatting that enables a rewarding understanding of the chosen subject, approaching publishable standards.</p>	<p>Excellent use of language and formatting that enables a rewarding understanding of the chosen subject.</p>	<p>Presentation displays critical levels of elegance and clarity in the work's language and formatting.</p>	<p>Good use of language and formatting that reinforce the project's strengths.</p>	<p>Language and/or formatting decisions serve to give a general understanding of the topic.</p>
--	--	--	---	---	--	---

Figure 31 screenshot of assessment criteria which mentions 'clarity'

In summary, unmarked Themes are dominant across many written texts including undergraduate architecture dissertations but the prevalence of marked Themes can vary, with writers able to choose between a higher or lower prevalence of marked Theme.

5.2 Thematic choice: topical > textual > interpersonal

Undergraduate dissertation writers using unmarked Themes have a choice between topical, textual, or interpersonal Themes. In general, unmarked topical Themes are the most frequent (57-65%), followed by textual (11-14%), and then interpersonal (5-7%), across analysed dissertations. This trend, i.e. topical > textual > interpersonal also appears in many other written genres such as narratives and expositions (Ghadessy, 1999) as well as academic written genres (Alotaibi, 2020; Sajeedin, 2024; Suharsono et al., 2024). For example, Hůlková et al.'s (2019) study found topical to be most dominant, and textual Themes vastly outnumbering interpersonal Themes in research articles. Although, the balance in some expert [longer] texts, such as research articles, can occasionally be tipped in favour of textual Themes being dominant over topical Themes (Susilowati et al., 2022), although this appears to be rare.

While the trend is for topical to be most frequent, followed by textual and interpersonal, usually having the lowest frequency, these frequencies and prevalences can vary across different sections of dissertations. For example, some studies have examined Thematic choices in particular sections, such as abstracts across subjects with similar Theme distribution: topical around 80%, textual under

20% and textual under 5% (Ghadessy, 1999) with similar findings for the analysed dissertations topical (61%, 80% & 90%) and under 9% for interpersonal. However, the textual Themes were more prevalent in some analysed abstracts (10%, 13% & 60%). Although given the variety of abstract lengths of these dissertations, direct comparisons can be challenging. For example, the three dissertations analysed for Theme/Rheme include vastly different abstracts with blue 1/2 including 23 t-units (487 words), whereas yellow 1/3 and yellow 2/3 had just 10 t-units (182 words & 226 words respectively). It is also interesting to note here that none of these abstracts followed the module guidelines of 250-300 words for an abstract, nor other guidance on abstract length i.e. 'around 200 words' (Naoum, 2013). This inconsistency may be partly due to the abstract falling outside the word count, i.e. in the pre-matter section, so writers may feel more comfortable not following guidelines and taking a judicious risk, in an assessment which values '*Original, Innovative, Risk-taking*' [from assessment descriptors].

Other studies found similar order of prevalence, i.e. topical > textual > interpersonal, though different prevalence in specific introduction moves (Sajeedin, 2024). However, many studies focussed exclusively on research articles and making direct comparisons between sections from undergraduate dissertations and research articles can be misleading, even with the same subtitle, e.g. *abstract* or *introduction*. As these sections are from different genres with different purposes and likely different structures, e.g. CARS structure less appropriate for undergraduate dissertations. In addition direct comparisons can be particularly challenging for topic-based dissertations which may not have a named 'introduction' and/or 'conclusion' and instead prefer more topic-based innovative subtitles for sections. Gunawan and Aziza (2017) attempted to avoid this issue of differing nomenclature by describing the chapters through numbers rather than titles. However, Gunawan and Aziza's (2017) study assumes there are always five chapters in undergraduate dissertations. This 5-part assumption accords with Nesi and Gardner's (2012) 5-part long essay and also with the guidance provided by architecture educators, i.e. *Introduction > Case 1 > Case 2 > Case 3 > Conclusion*

However, only one of the analysed dissertations (yellow 2/3) had five chapters to make direct comparisons with Gunawan and Aziza's (2017) study. Table 14 demonstrates several similarities in Thematic choices. Chapter 3, which is often the methodology in genre-based dissertations, had the highest prevalence for interpersonal Themes compared with the other five chapters. However, interpersonal Themes had low prevalence across all analysed dissertations. This is to be expected with research report genres, as higher prevalence for interpersonal Themes is often associated with more opinion-based or reflective writing genres (Al-Reshaid & Alhojailan, 2025) or in expert genres such as research articles in which writers feel more comfortable expressing voice and stance. For example Hyland (2012) found significantly more examples of stance and voice, including but not limited to interpersonal Theme, in research articles compared to final year undergraduate

essays. The highest prevalence for textual themes in both studies was in chapter 2, often the literature review in genre-based dissertation. Literature reviews are highly informational and involve synthesising multiple texts (Nesi & Gardner, 2012) so may require more textual Themes. Essays too often have a higher prevalence of textual Themes (Al-Reshaid & Alhojailan, 2025). The ‘long essay’ or long literature review (blue 1/2 topic-based) has the highest proportion of textual Themes (14%). However, there is not a huge difference when compared to traditional complex/genre-based at 13%, so more analysis comparing topic-based to genre-based is needed to establish if textual higher for topic-based.

Table 40 Table comparing Themes in Gunawan & Aziza and yellow 2/3 5-chapter dissertations

Highest prevalence of marked Theme	Gunawan & Aziza (2017) Chapters 2 (37%) & 4 (34%)	Yellow 2/3 traditional simple Chapters 5 (22%) & 2 (20%)
Highest prevalence of interpersonal Theme	Chapter 3 (61%)	Chapter 3 (11%)
Highest prevalence of textual Theme	Chapter 2 (44%)	Chapter 2 (25%)

It is again worth bearing in mind that percentages are included for internal comparisons as Gunawan and Azizia’s (2017) report marked/unmarked Themes as clauses and T-units, whereas textual and interpersonal Themes are only reported based on clauses.

5.3 Thematic progression: zigzag > iteration > peripheral > derived

In addition to choices of Theme, writers also have choices around Thematic progression, i.e. how t-units are woven together through either zigzag, iteration, peripheral or derived Thematic progression patterns.

5.3.1. Zigzag pattern

The zigzag pattern (Rheme>Theme) is the most dominant Thematic progression across all three analysed undergraduate dissertations. Zigzag pattern was the most frequent, with some variation of frequency, i.e. nearly 40% in two of the analysed dissertations and around 55% in yellow 2/3, genre-based. This is also reflected in another study which found zigzag patterns to be dominant at around 55% in undergraduate dissertations (Suharsono et al., 2024). The zigzag pattern is particularly frequent in longer sections/chapters (e.g. middle dissertation chapters), which can run over several pages, thus cohesion is important.

The dominance of zigzag Thematic progression reflects other studies, which found dominance across undergraduate and postgraduate dissertations as well as research articles with the highest prevalence among undergraduate dissertations (Suharsono et al., 2024). Another study on research articles found the zigzag progression pattern to be most prevalent (Babaii et al., 2016). Similarly, another study also found even greater prevalence of zigzag patterns in ‘well-established’

disciplines, e.g. mechanical engineering and horticulture (Babaii, et al., 2016). Architecture is also a well-established discipline with a long history, so writing in architecture may have a more dominant zigzag Thematic progression. In contrast, allied subjects such as construction management and engineering, and/or more recent or emerging disciplines within the creative industries, may exhibit a dominant zigzag Thematic progression pattern overall, but with a higher prevalence of Theme iteration.

As well as being associated with particular disciplines, a zigzag pattern can be dominant in specific genres such as essays. For example, a study of argumentative essays found zigzag pattern to be the most dominant (Priangan et al., 2020) and suggests this preference may be due to the zigzag pattern building and progressing an argument based on new information (Rheme > Theme) rather than repeating a Theme (Eggins, 2004). If used well, this culminative building, rather than repeating, provides a cohesive texture and progresses the argument (Eggins, 2004). A zigzag pattern can support building a cumulative argument in essays and perhaps more topic-based dissertations. Surprisingly, in this study, the zigzag pattern was most dominant in the traditional simple dissertation (over 50%) and least dominant in topic-based dissertation (under 40%). However, with little difference between the percentages, the takeaway here is the zigzag pattern was dominant overall and most prevalent in sections with a narrative, process or chronological focus, such as literature reviews and/or findings (Suharsono et al., 2024). For all the analysed dissertations the highest prevalence for zigzag pattern was in the second chapter/section (sometimes the literature review) and penultimate chapter/section (sometimes the discussion and/or findings). In contrast, the first and last chapter/sections (introductions/conclusions) had the lowest prevalence of zigzag pattern and Theme iteration was more prevalent. It is also worth noting that students often combined Thematic patterns, (see Table 41), but zigzag pattern was still most dominant.

Table 41 Demonstrating zigzag Thematic progression pattern in yellow 2/3, also some Theme iteration

<i>The life in <u>this region</u></i>	<i>survives some of the harshest extremes on the planet in terms of light and temperature.</i>
<i>In <u>the arctic</u></i>	<i>a complex ecosystem exists which hosts an abundance of life with a delicate but balanced food chain.</i>
<i>This system</i>	<i>is also key to recycling carbon dioxide in the atmosphere.</i>
<i>As carbon</i>	<i>cycles from the atmosphere to the seawater.</i>
<i>Once in the water</i>	<i>phytoplankton and algae can convert it into an organic carbon of their tissue. (Ashjian, 2020).</i>
<i>In a way they</i>	<i>can extract a heat-trapping gas from going to the atmosphere and keeping it at the bottom of the sea.</i>
<i>A distribution of this ecosystem</i>	<i>can have grave consequences as “They are responsible for half of the photosynthetic activity in earth” (Agar, 2019)</i>
<i>This food chain</i>	<i>is directly accessed by humans who consume the fish which have eaten the phytoplankton</i>
<i>If you</i>	<i>were to kill of the start of the food chain then rest would fall apart.</i>

5.3.2. Theme iteration pattern

Theme iteration (i.e. repeated Theme) is also prevalent but less dominant than zigzag pattern in all analysed architecture undergraduate dissertations (approximately 30-60%). Suharsono et al.’s (2024) study found similar levels (around 40%) of Theme iteration across research articles as well as postgraduate and undergraduate dissertations. Another study on undergraduate writing found that Theme iteration was most prevalent in specific sections of undergraduate dissertations, e.g. introductions, conclusions and methodologies (Gunawan & Aziza, 2017). This correlation is often due to one or both of the following factors: shorter length and descriptive purpose. Introductions, conclusions, and methodologies tend to be the shorter sections of a dissertation and Theme iteration tends to occur for short periods of language (Eggins, 2004). However, this type of repetitive Thematic progression rarely extends beyond one paragraph (Eggins, 2004).

The introduction section, as well as paragraphs in other sections, had a higher frequency of Thematic iteration in comparison to other sections. However, as previously discussed, direct comparisons between undergraduate dissertations can be challenging, particularly if they differ in macrostructure and subtitles. In this study, two of the three analysed dissertations featured introductions (first chapters) with higher frequencies of Theme iteration (over 40% of Thematic progression), in comparison to other sections. The third analysed dissertation did not feature a

named introduction, but their first chapter did feature slightly more Theme iteration (25 t-units) than peripheral Theme (24 t-units).

This preference for Thematic iteration in the introduction section, could be as a result of advice on the dissertation module. For example, all participants were encouraged to read and follow advice from Borden and Ruedi Ray (2006), which also featured in lecture material and describes the introduction as 'say what you are going to say' with a heavy emphasis on the content and argument, i.e. topic or ideational content. Repetition of the same Theme can keep the text and the reader 'focussed' on the topic (Eggins, 2004). This topic focus can be particularly important in the introduction or first chapter, which introduces the topic. Theme iteration can be dominant in not only undergraduate dissertation introductions but also postgraduate dissertations and research article introductory sections (Jalilifar et al., 2017).

Thematic iteration can be used to describe the topic, as in an introduction, or describe events (Nwogu & Bloor, 2011). A constant Theme focussing on one event allows for a fuller description of event (McCabe, 1999). For example, the introduction section paragraph below (table 42, yellow 1/3) demonstrates Theme iteration describing events, sometimes referred to as narrative or recount. Theme iteration is often dominant in descriptive, narrative or recount, although, as in this study, a zigzag pattern was most dominant overall (Nesi & Gardner, 2012; Wan Jusoh et al., 2022). Thus, some sections with a more narrative structure may feature more Thematic iteration progression. It is worth noting here that Theme iteration pattern can feel repetitive, even boring, for some readers (Eggins, 2004). Authors have the option of using synonymous Themes e.g. '*they*' or thematising associated elements e.g. *Nobile's expedition, airship, crew, story*.

Table 42 Yellow 1/3 Theme iteration in introduction section

<p>The well-known case of Umberto Nobile's expedition</p>	<p>can be considered here as a case study that allows us to identify key aspects of the polar regions</p>
<p>Umberto Nobile's airship</p>	<p>floated to the north pole within 24 hours from the Svalbard islands his crew dropped an Italian flag to mark the achievement.</p>
<p>Flying his airship</p>	<p>on return from the North Pole approximately 30km from the finish the arctic weather took a vicious turn as the strength of the wind and snow started to batter the thin exterior of the airship.</p>
<p>Then the over the next two</p>	<p>plummeted down into the frozen ice below.</p>
<p>minutes Umberto Nobile and his crew of 16</p>	<p>has a lot to teach us about architecture as a mediation between man and habitat.</p>
<p>Analysed today this story The story of Nobile</p>	<p>who, for the technologies of the time, can correspond to today's attempt to terraform desserts or a trip to the moon, is a lesson in architecture because what can be done (or <u>can not</u> be done) in extreme conditions it is even more valid in environmental conditions closer to our thermal and psychological comfort.</p>

However, it should not be assumed that Theme iteration is the most dominant in all introductions/introductory chapters. In fact, Yellow 2/3's introduction Theme iteration, while Yellow 1/3's introduction the most dominant progression was iteration as well as peripheral. Theme iteration can provide a detailed description of events, people or concepts but can feel static in comparison to more dynamic zigzag pattern which can allow for exploring connections between phenomena rather than detailed description of phenomena (McCabe, 1999). As mentioned previously, the third analysed dissertation (Blue 1/2) featured a higher prevalence for zigzag pattern than Theme iteration in the introductory/first chapter. Other studies on research article introductions also found the zigzag pattern more prevalent than Theme iteration (Alyousef & Alzahrani, 2020; Leong et al., 2018). Thus, authors have a choice over Thematic progression in the introduction/introductory chapters with Theme iteration being prevalent but not always dominant.

Table 43 Yellow 2/3 Theme iteration in 'methodology' section

<p>TMD Studios</p> <p>↓</p> <p>TMD</p> <p>↓</p> <p>They</p> <p>↓</p> <p>They They</p> <p>↓</p> <p>The <u>first</u> [concern]</p>	<p>is a practice that 'embraces sustainable and technological techniques to the designing framework that adopts the latest advancements in building technology and being focused on Big Data to offer unique and innovative solutions.' (TMD & Ondrej Cudy)</p> <p>offer creatives who want to respond to future challenges using their fields to serve better quality of living for all.</p> <p>go onto theories that there are three concerns when designing buildings with better considerations towards the environment.</p> <p>derive these factors like people, earth, and cost.</p> <p>later go onto state that there are <u>three</u> overriding ecological concerns when designing buildings. is the material used for construction; the <u>second</u> is the building's energy efficiency and the <u>last</u> is the location of the building.</p>
--	--

Theme iteration can also be prevalent in other sections, e.g. methodology (Table 43) and results chapter/section (Table 44) which describe processes and procedures (Nwogu & Bloor, 2011). Note, Table 43 describes the design process rather than research process but is from the dissertation's 'methodology' section. Again, direct comparisons can be challenging as undergraduate and research articles often differ even if they share the same subtitle. For example, the second Theme iteration example (Table 44) is featured in the 'discussion & results' section despite reporting methodological processes.

Table 44 Yellow 1/3 Theme iteration in 'discussion & results' section

<p>I</p> <p>To achieve this I</p> <p>I</p> <p>I</p>	<p>conducted an interview to understand the future image of architecture and to acknowledge how to design using computational methods to create a more future proof design.</p> <p>set out to attain qualitative data to tackle my research question using primary data I gathered in an interview.</p> <p>contacted architect Dr Pierandrea Angius, a lead associate of Zaha Architects in the profession of applying computational design.</p> <p>sent an email with three questions about the computational design benefits and how computational design was utilised within Zaha Architects firm to conduct this interview.</p>
--	--

Thematic iteration can also be frequent in results sections when describing findings. In Gunawan and Aziza's (2017) study, chapter 4 (findings) had the second-highest frequency of thematic iteration. Thematic iteration is also prevalent in research articles, which may report findings as '*we found...*' (Leong et al., 2018; Nwogu & Bloor, 2011). This may suggest Theme iteration, e.g. '*I found*' may be frequent in students' findings section. However, this was difficult to establish as none of the analysed dissertations had a separate results or findings section. Additionally, student writers may be less likely to use such authorial voice and stance markers in comparison to expert writers (Hyland, 2012). Although one t-unit in yellow 2/3's 'discussion and results' uses an authorial marker but does not follow Thematic iteration pattern with subsequent t-units in the paragraph following a zigzag pattern:

Table 45: Theme iteration 'I' (yellow 2/3)

<i>I can infer from this</i>	<i>that not only can these techniques be used to create a sustainable project towards the environment but also future proof the building towards any economic and social context</i>
------------------------------	--

There are other examples of using '*I...*' but these were more frequent in the conclusion/final chapters, and again these were often zigzag pattern. In addition, these examples were usually mental processes, i.e. *feel, believe*, rather than materials processes, i.e. *found* (Egins, 2004). It is also worth noting that some researchers can, in some studies, classify this type of t-unit as a separate type of peripheral Theme, i.e. extralinguistic (Rass & Portman, 2024; McCabe, 1999), if this Theme presents as neither Theme iteration nor zigzag Theme.

In conclusion, Thematic iteration is frequent in undergraduate architecture dissertations but can vary based on author but also the section, with introduction, methodology, results and conclusions reporting higher prevalence for Theme iteration (Alyousef & Alzahrani, 2020; Leong et al., 2018; Nwogu & Bloor, 2011). However, Thematic iteration choices made by the author depend on the purpose of the section and whether a description is being provided. For example, one study found chapter II (often literature review) of undergraduate dissertations to have highest prevalence for Thematic iteration (Gunawan & Aziza, 2017). This result is surprising given that other studies, including this study, found less Thematic iteration in these sections/chapters. Based on the Thematic progression samples provided, it would appear the literature review was organised around topic/Theme and Theme iteration was used to keep the focus on topic (Gunawan & Aziza, 2017). Thus, both zigzag and iteration, or a combination thereof are possible in literature review like sections.

As previously mentioned, Theme iteration can be used to describe events and processes (Nwogu and Bloor, 2011). In addition, Theme iteration can also be used to describe images. Egins (2004) suggests strong topical focus can be achieved through repeating the Theme linguistically in the paragraph. In multimodal texts, this

Theme repetition can be extended to images. In the example paragraph below (table 46: blue1/2), there are two instances of Theme iteration, each describing a separate figure, i.e. *figure 8: 'Global Age-friendly Cities: A Guide - Outdoor spaces and buildings'* by WHO (World Health Organisation) [underlined below] and *figure 9 (b1/2) 'Acts of a caring city'* [in bold below]. Both images are also included below. It is worth noting that while '*figure 8 (b1/2)*' is not an image in the strictest sense, the author has labelled it as a figure. Additionally, as most of the language in '*figure 8 (b1/2)*' do not qualify as t-units, it cannot be analysed in the same way as another language/written component, so it is therefore analysed as an image, i.e. visual component. Thus, also aligning with the authors' intentions. Note that '*figure x*' in italics refer to figures as described in the analysed dissertation.

Table 46 Blue 1/2 Theme iteration with images - figure 9 and 8 repeated as Theme

As mentioned previously,
 outdoor environments
 In a study conducted by
 Kahana et al. (2003, p 435)
 on residential satisfaction of
 older people,
 This
 Based on reviewing existing
 literature, these four acts
 In conjunction with this

subject, WHO

WHO's guide

It

Notably, these **four acts**

The **categories**

The **four key "acts"**
 (blue 1/2 chapter 2)

can be great resources for older people but can
 also prevent them from leaving their homes.
 they suggest that how well an environment relates
 to the individual can impact their levels of chronic
 stress.

can have serious effects on personal well-being.
 have been created in response to the gap
 concerning older people's well-being.
 has developed key characteristics of an age-friendly
 city based on accessibility relating to outdoor
 spaces (see Figure 8).

of physical characteristics indicate how easy it is for
 an older person to utilise an urban space.

can be used to indicate whether these **four acts** are
 present in an outdoor space and have been
 designed to include older people in urban
 life.

have a specific focus on the experience and
 opportunities in urban outdoor spaces which largely
 impact the well-being of older people and reach
 broader than physical navigation of space.
 work in tandem and can overlap in different ways.

are represented in **Figure 9**:

**Global Age-friendly Cities:
A Guide - Outdoor spaces and buildings**

Clean environment with regulations on noise levels and unpleasant/harmful odours	Well-maintained and safe green spaces with shelter, toilet facilities and seating
Pedestrian-friendly walkways without obstructions, with smooth surfaces and access to public toilets	Well-maintained and safe outdoor seating in parks, transport stops, public spaces at regular intervals.
Pavements clear of obstructions and pedestrians have priority of use.	Well-maintained, non-slip pavements wide enough to accommodate wheelchairs with low curbs
Adequate non-slip pedestrian crossings for safe crossing	Well-designed and appropriate road structures (traffic islands, overpasses, underpasses)
Strict traffic rules and regulations with drivers giving way to pedestrians.	Separate cycle paths for cyclists
Public safety is promoted to reduce natural disasters, adequate street lighting, police patrol, law enforcement, community support and personal safety initiatives	Services are clustered in close proximity to where older people live and are easily accessible
	Special customer service for older people
Clean, well-maintained and easily accessible public toilets for people with varying abilities	

Figure 8

Figure 32 Blue 1/2 'figure 8' and 'Figure 9'

In addition to describing images, Thematic iteration in the analysed dissertations is also often accompanied by images. How images are used as well as distinction between describing or accompanying images will be further explored later in the chapter (5.4 & 5.5). But in general terms, images being described are usually large and in the Theme position and ideal position, i.e. before the written component. Whereas Thematic iteration accompanied by an image or images of this Theme or and/or associated Theme/element can help maintain a strong topical and ideational focus for the reader (Eggins, 2004). These images are usually, but not always, in the Rheme position, i.e. after the written component, either in the next column or page and/or in the real position.

5.3.3. *Derived Theme pattern*

The derived Theme pattern is the least prevalent type of Thematic progression across all the analysed dissertations, accounting for less than 10%, and Yellow 2/4 featuring just 1 derived Theme instance. Other studies also found low prevalence (less than 4%) for derived Themes with the lowest prevalence (under 2%) in undergraduate texts (Jalilifar et al., 2017; Suharsono et al., 2024). Also, a recent study on second-year undergraduate writers found no examples of derived Themes (Haji, 2024). One possible reason for such low levels of derived Themes in undergraduate writing could be the perceived complexity of paragraph structure and texture with derived Themes (Suharsono et al., 2024). Whereas, more complex texts with multiple and connected Themes such as creative writing, e.g. short stories, may choose to incorporate more derived Themes (Hanh, 2021). Derived Themes may also be more prevalent in narratives, e.g. impersonal narrative recounts which retell historic events the writer has not experienced in a sequential and narrative way (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). (Table 47, yellow 1/3) This student received feedback from their supervisor praising their '*Very original narrative approach*', i.e. narrative description of the ill-fated expedition. It is also worth noting that this particular student's 'originality' has resulted in both examples of derived Theme being from the same dissertation, as there are so few (less than 5%) in other analysed dissertations.

Table 47 yellow 1/3 derived Themes, i.e. mental limits from introduction section

<i>The harsh environment</i>	<i>and deafening silence pushed the men to their <u>mental limits</u>.</i>
<i>After a few days <u>sensory deprivation</u></i>	<i>started to set in making it harder for them to concentrate and communicate within the group.</i>
<i><u>Visually all the survivors</u></i>	<i>could see was featureless landscapes with only the wind and the silence of the snow to add to the feeling of isolation</i>
<i><u>Their brains</u></i>	<i>were starved of visual stimulation which allowed the brain to start to create hallucinations.</i>
<i>In <u>this case</u> experience</i>	<i>describes another fundamental need of architecture which, taken to the extreme consequences of the Antarctic, becomes paroxysmal. [...paragraph continues]</i>

Derived Theme or sometimes referred to as multiple Rheme or split Rheme, can also be more common, although still less prevalent in comparison to Theme iteration and zigzag pattern, in longer expository texts (Eggins, 2004). The derived Theme pattern allows writers to dissect a Theme into multiple parts, scrutinising each in detail before synthesising (Suharsono et al., 2024). This may partly account for wider use in expert texts such as research articles and limited use in undergraduate texts, e.g. expository/argumentative essays (Haji, 2024). Also, the length of the text, as well as use of section and subsections, may impact use of derived Themes. Undergraduate dissertation writers may prefer to split Themes and explore them in different sections with different subtitles rather than in the same paragraph.

Table 48 Yellow 1/3 derived Themes, i.e. seasons in introduction section

<i>With the arctic</i>	<i>being so far north the earth's tilt and orbit have a large influence over the <u>seasons</u>.</i>
<i>This region</i>	<i>receives less solar energy and heat from the sun as it is set much farther back.</i>
<i>Which</i>	<i>leaves the polar regions with only two seasons, being summer and winter. ("Dive and Discover : Antarctica : Seasons", 2020).</i>
<i>The vertical line of the north pole</i>	<i>is tilted 23.5 degrees away from the sun.</i>
<i>This angle and rotation</i>	<i>are maintained throughout the year.</i>
<i>During the <u>summer</u> solstice the length of the days</i>	<i>will increase dramatically to a point where the sun will not move below the equator and will be visible for 24 hours. (Gedney, 1984).</i>
<i>This</i>	<i>is often known as the midnight sun, as it best describes the sun appearing at midnight. (Tours, 2019).</i>
<i>In contrast the <u>winter</u> solstice, As the sun</i>	<i>starting on December 22nd the days with sunlight will become incredibly short and soon disappear. cannot reach the arctic due to the angle of the tilt. ("Winter Solstice", 2005).</i>
<i>The north pole</i>	<i>90°N will then be plunged into total darkness for 163 days. ("Day Length", 2020).</i>
<i>An important characteristic</i>	<i>of this environment when planning for long term settlement.</i>
<i>The <u>seasons</u></i>	<i>will raise questions on how to adapt building technology to compensate for the lack of light in the winter months.</i>

Another reason for fewer derived Themes is Thematic shift (Eggins, 2004) or Thematic drift (Butt et al., 2000). In derived Thematic progression, Themes are first featured in the HyperTheme, i.e. topic sentence, and then developed in subsequent T-units. Themes which drift/shift and fall outside of the derived, repeated, or zigzag Theme pattern, may be referred to as accidental or peripheral. Accidental Themes are external to the text and therefore do not support Thematic progression nor texture (Eggins, 2004). These are more common in verbal/spoken language and often signalled by a digression marker, e.g. 'by the way' (Traugott, 2020). Peripheral

Themes can deviate from Themes in the hyperTheme, e.g., topic sentence or from Thematic progression patterns, but may correspond to broader macroThemes, e.g., subtitles/research questions and therefore contribute to Thematic progression (McCabe, 1999).

5.3.4. *Peripheral Theme pattern*

As previously explained, in addition to zigzag, Theme iteration and derived, some Themes can fall outside of these patterns. McCabe (1999) introduced peripheral Themes to ease analysis of Thematic progression outside of typical patterns. When T-units aid Thematic progression but relationships between T-units in the paragraph are unclear and/or fall outside of the three Thematic progression patterns these are peripheral Themes (McCabe, 1999). McCabe (1999) also suggested the occurrence of what she called 'problematic Themes' i.e. similar to Eggins' (2004) accidental Themes which do not aid Thematic progression and are considered off topic. I have chosen not to adopt these more subjective labels of problematic/accidental and instead identify all instances under the label of peripheral Themes. McCabe (1999) suggested four, sometimes overlapping, peripheral Themes categories: (see Table 49 for examples, but not an exhaustive list).

Table 49 Peripheral Theme types with examples

Pragmatic	<i>key Themes: key words; new Themes: authors with reporting verbs</i>
Extralinguistic	<i>feelings: I feel..., we believe...,</i>
Grammatical	<i>'-ing' gerund or question word in Theme position</i>
Metatextual	<i>'this text', 'this chapter'; 'figure x...'</i>

A note of caution here, as it is the progression around the examples rather than examples themselves which indicate peripheral Themes. For example, any of these examples may feature previously in the paragraph in previous Rheme (zigzag), previous Theme (iteration) or in hyperTheme (derived). Peripheral Themes need to be outside of these three patterns.

Peripheral Themes were prevalent across the analysed dissertations (at least 25% of Thematic progression) and in two dissertations were third most prevalent behind dominant zigzag pattern, and a similar level to second most prevalent Theme iteration. The third dissertation (blue 1/2) had the highest prevalence of peripheral Themes (over 36%) at a similar level to dominant zigzag pattern, with the other two dissertations featuring similar percentages: Yellow 1/3: 26% and Yellow 2/3.: 28%. Other studies have found similar levels of prevalence for peripheral Themes: 36% of English textbooks (McCabe, 1999); 31-35% of research articles and similar levels in student texts: around 30% (Rass & Portman, 2024) and around 25% (Hawes & Thomas, 1997).

Authors can choose multiple peripheral Themes from differing categories in the same paragraph as part of Thematic progression (Table 50). As alluded to previously, some of McCabe's categories can overlap. For example, the author could be discussing a research limitation and not only referring to other parts of text (metatextual) but also revisiting key Themes (pragmatic). Peripheral Themes were dominant in two of the three dissertations' conclusion/final sections. The other dissertation's conclusion was dominated by zigzag, but peripheral was a close second (yellow 2/3). Borden and Ruedi Ray (2014) suggest architecture dissertation writers 'say that you have said it' in the conclusion section, and there are two main elements, i.e. summary statement, and speculation. Thus, a higher prevalence for peripheral Themes in the final section is to be expected given the likelihood of referring back to key Themes and previous parts of the text in the summary statement, as well as extralinguistic peripheral Themes featuring as part of speculation element.

Table 50 Yellow 1/3 peripheral Themes with indication of type/s in 'final remarks' section

<i>As a conclusion of my research, I</i>	<i>believe there is a bright future in the polar regions especially the arctic.</i>	
<i>If climate, communities, settlements and building technology</i>	<i>were all taken into consideration then the polar regions may be the place of the future.</i>	G
<i>I</i>	<i>believe architecture in the Arctic can be built, providing places to work, live and relax.</i>	E
<i>A large community of non-native and natives With the correct support people</i>	<i>would be successful as long as they could exchange knowledge. could adapt over time to the environment and sociality of the location.</i>	
<i>A limitation with this field of research</i>	<i>to note is the small amount of architecture in the polar regions to compare and contrast to build up a much bigger picture of what exists there.</i>	M/P
<i>I</i>	<i>feel one would have to have a large imagination to envision the large scale sustainable arctic living.</i>	E
<i>As well how long</i>	<i>can it realistically last before the icy deserts consume the architecture.</i>	G
<i>There</i>	<i>is huge potential to learn so much about the world and where architecture can go in the polar regions that is just waiting to be fully unlocked.</i>	G

5.4 Thematic progression: image and language relations

Images are present and prevalent across all 27 collected dissertations and could be considered obligatory elements (Huettner, 2010). The lowest number of images featured in an undergraduate architecture dissertation was 7, and the highest was 61. Similarly, in Borden and Ruedi Ray's (2014) exemplar dissertations, images were prevalent and present for all dissertations but with a slightly lower range, i.e. 3-20. However, this inclusion of fewer images may also reflect publisher preferences for

fewer images in printed books, which may have brought down the average. For example, journals can set a maximum number of images. The British Journal of Radiology recommends a maximum of 17 images (figures & tables) in a 4000-word review article but extends this maximum to 19 figures in a 'pictorial review' (*General Instructions | BJR|Open | Oxford Academic, 2025*). In the 27 collected dissertations, the average number of images was 26-27 per dissertation. This average is similar to the average number of images in longer texts, such as postgraduate dissertations and doctoral theses, within the field of computing (average: 30; median: 26) (van Biljon & Renaud, 2015). I'm reminded here of the old adage that '*a picture is worth a thousand words*', whereas in architecture undergraduate dissertations, images are worth, around 150-200 words across a 4000-5000-word text ('A Picture Is Worth a Thousand Words', 2024). The undergraduate architecture dissertation assessment brief includes a word limit but did not specify an image limit.

5.4.1. Image types: photographs obligatory, maps core, tables and graphs optional

Images is a broad term which can refer to visual components such as photographs or sketches as well as graphs, maps and even tables. In van Biljon and Renaud's (2015) study the focus was on figures (i.e. graphs) in computing. Whereas, another study analysed 780 PhD theses from several disciplines and found figures/graphs were second most prevalent (111) after images and drawings (175) with maps (83), photographs (65) and timelines (23) featuring less frequently (Schöpfel et al., 2016). Schöpfel et al. (2016) also found disciplinary variation with images and/or drawings most prevalent, followed by maps and photographs, and no examples of figures or graphs in History of Art theses, whereas in economical sciences the reverse was true, i.e. no examples of photographs, just 1 example of image/drawing and figures/graphs most prevalent. Similarly to History of Art, images/drawings were present in each Civil Engineering thesis and were significantly more prevalent than graphs and figures (over 7000 images/drawings compared to over 300 figure/graphs) (Schöpfel et al., 2016). This could suggest that specific types of visual components (e.g. images/drawings, photographs, and maps) could be more prevalent in architecture dissertations than perhaps other visual components (e.g. graphs, diagrams). However, it is worth noting that there is relatively little consistency in terminology and analysis of multimodal data particularly in the use of the term 'figure' which often refers to any image in a text, i.e. list of figures, but can also specifically refer to a graph. For clarity, this project refers to visual elements as 'images' but may also use the dissertation author's own terminology e.g. 'figure 1'. Burkhard (2004) suggests architecture draws on five types of images which he refers to as 'visualisations':

Table 51 Burkhard's 2004 visualisation types and suggested knowledge types for architects

Visualisation type (How?)	Knowledge type (What?)
<i>sketch (drawing)</i>	<i>declarative knowledge (Know-what)</i>
<i>diagram (abstract & usually not to scale)</i>	<i>procedural knowledge (Knowhow)</i>

image (rendering, photograph, or painting)
object (model)
interactive visualisation

experimental knowledge (Know-why)
orientational knowledge (Know-where)
individual knowledge (Know-who)

Burkhard's (2004) framework does not include other types of 'visualisations' such as graphs, tables, and maps. Thus, I have extended Burkhard's (2004) framework to include other visualisations (in grey) as well as exchange image for picture in order to retain 'image' as an umbrella noun for all visuals in this project (Table 52).

Table 52 Visualisation types and suggested knowledge types for architecture students (adapted from Burkhard, 2004)

Visualisation type (How?)	Knowledge type (What?)
<i>sketch (drawing)</i>	<i>declarative knowledge (Know-what)</i>
<i>Table</i>	<i>declarative knowledge (Know-what)</i>
<i>diagram (often abstract & not to scale)</i>	<i>procedural knowledge (Knowhow)</i>
<i>Graph</i>	<i>procedural knowledge (Knowhow)</i> <i>and/or experimental knowledge (Know-why)</i>
<i>picture (rendering, photograph or painting)</i>	<i>experimental knowledge (Know-why)</i>
<i>object (model)</i>	<i>orientational knowledge (Know-where)</i>
<i>map</i>	<i>orientational knowledge (Know-where)</i>
<i>interactive visualisation</i>	<i>individual knowledge (Know-who)</i>

When given free-reign over the chosen mode in assessment, architecture and civil engineering students opt for spoken (18/18) over written modes and photographs (16/18) were most frequent, followed by diagrams (15/18), charts (8/18) and drawings (5/18), but other modes such as videos were also prevalent (Hellwig et al., 2022). The analysed undergraduate architecture dissertations were similar to the history of art as well as civil engineering theses in Schöpfel et al. (2016) and Hellwig (2022) et al.'s findings with images, pictures, photographs and renderings by far the most prevalent across all six dissertations and also most frequent type in all but one of the dissertations. Diagrams also featured in all six dissertations but were less prevalent than pictures and photographs. Burkhard's (2004) other suggested visualisations were less frequent. For example, sketches and drawings are often used in architecture during the building design process (Burkhard, 2004; Forty, 2004; Spector & Damron, 2017) but as these students were not designing buildings themselves, sketches were used less frequently and were often from secondary sources which also reflects findings from Hellwig et al.'s, (2002) study. As the dissertation is primarily a written, text-based artefact, objects only appeared in dissertations as photographs of models and were also infrequent. Additionally, the written format of dissertations makes interactive visualisations such as immersive data and augmented reality less possible. However, with the increase in alternative

dissertation formats such as videos and websites (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014) interactive visualisations may become more frequent.

Visualisations often featuring in academic texts but not incorporated into Burkhard's (2004) framework include maps, tables, and graphs. Maps were frequent in the analysed undergraduate dissertation and mirror findings from van Biljon and Renaud's (2015) study of computing theses as well as Schöpfel et al.'s, (2016) study in terms of frequent use of maps in history of art theses. Maps featured in 3 of the 6 analysed theses and could be considered a core element of undergraduate architecture dissertations (Huettner, 2010). Maps can provide orientational knowledge (know-where) in the absence of a 3-D model. Tables, on the other hand, could be considered a more optional element as only one of the analysed 6 dissertations included tables (Huettner, 2010). Tables appear more frequently in other studies (van Biljon & Renaud, 2015; Schöpfel et al., 2016) and in academic texts, e.g. BAWE corpus includes 2761 texts, from several genres, and includes 2180 tables. The 'tables' in undergraduate architecture dissertations differ not only in terms of frequency but also in terms of use. For example, (blue 1/2), the only dissertation with tables, did not contain numerical data and often only included textual information, e.g. list, but presented as a table. Finally, graphs also appear to be optional and only feature in one of the 6 analysed undergraduate architecture dissertations and are often from secondary sources. This would suggest graphs are also an optional element with architecture dissertation writers preferring to incorporate more visual over numerical data (Huettner, 2010).

Table 53 image type count for 6 collected dissertations

	Red 1/1	blue 1/2	y 1/3	y 2/3	y 3/3	blue 2/2	
<i>picture (rendering/photograph/painting)</i>	26	5	21	9	15	34	110
<i>diagram (often abstract & not to scale)</i>	2	3	1	6	1	4	17
<i>map</i>	3	5	2	0	0	0	10
<i>table</i>	0	6	0	0	0	0	6
<i>graph</i>	0	6	0	0	0	0	6
<i>object (model)</i>	0	0	1	1	2	0	4
<i>sketch (drawing)</i>	0	2	0	0	0	1	3
<i>interactive visualisation</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

5.4.2. Image-language: logico-semantic relations

Images, language, and texts are all vitally important to architecture practice. Tschumi (a famous architect) is quoted as saying "architecture does not exist without drawing, in the same way that architecture does not exist without texts" (Forty, 2000 p. 29). This would suggest an almost complementary relationship between image and language in architecture. In the collected undergraduate architecture dissertations there were, on average, at least one image per page which includes all pages e.g.

pre and post matter further demonstrating the complementary relationship of images and language in architecture. This contrasts with another study with a larger dataset of dissertations and theses in which, on average, 1 in 3 pages included an image (10,000+ pages; 3.3 thousand images) (Kahu et al., 2021). Other research has demonstrated a dramatic increase in the number of images used in research articles with 'typical' biology papers in 2019 featuring 13 pictures and 15 graphs across 12 pages, compared to 1989 typical papers featuring 1 picture and 4 graphs across 8 pages (Abdullaeva et al., 2022). This would suggest at least one, possibly two images per page may be becoming increasingly common for some research articles and dissertations. However, it should not be assumed that every page automatically includes an image. For example, only one of the six dissertations had an image on every page while the other five analysed dissertations included page/s (1-6) with no images but also included pages with multiple images. The pages with no images usually appeared towards the end of the dissertation in the final or penultimate chapter/section, often the conclusion. The location of language-only pages towards the end of the dissertation is not surprising given that none of the 12 postgraduate supervisors reported 'expecting' images in the conclusion but one considered it could be 'good practice' to include images in the conclusion and/or introduction (van Biljon & Renaud, 2015).

In the same study, all of the participating supervisors expected images in the findings and 75% also expected images in the literature review. However, it should be noted that this study focussed on figures/graphs only and within computer science and expectations between different disciplines can vary. For example, Schöpfel et al.'s (2016) included PhD theses from over 16 disciplines but focussed on multimodal data sources, such as images, located within the appendices. In contrast, architecture students are advised: 'Figures should be incorporated in the main body of the document, near to where you refer to them in the text' (dissertation assessment brief), and any images in the appendix have not featured elsewhere in the dissertation (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014). The exception to this being the inclusion of full colour images in the appendices with just one of the 27 (dissertations with highest number of images) also including colour images in the appendices. This may be related to old advice about printing dissertations, i.e. print dissertations in grayscale (black and white) and appendices in full colour. For example, the interviewee shared their printed dissertation they submitted in 1997 in which images were all in the back (interview: 1:13:51).

5.4.3. Thematic progression: Image-language: status relations

Images are an important aspect of a multimodal text's texture. Despite this, images are often overlooked in linguistics research in favour of other textural elements such as cohesive ties and cohesive devices (Hasan, 1998). Cohesive ties and cohesive devices as textural elements tend to be lexical items, e.g. words or phrases such as anaphoric (backwards) reference or cataphoric (forwards) reference (Hasan, 1998). Lexical items such as anaphoric/cataphoric references are often analysed using

corpus linguistics to identify *this* and *the* or other lexical items such as *another* (Breban et al., 2011). However, many corpus studies strip out images to analyse just linguistic elements. Jiang and Hyland (2026) call for established research approaches, such as corpora, to be complemented by multimodal research approaches and argue ‘such methodological pluralism strengthens EAP’s empirical reach.’ This study makes a deliberate choice to not only analyse images but also analyse and ‘read’ images alongside language to identify the relationships between image and language within texts rather than artificially separating and ‘viewing’ images (Unsworth, 2008).

The linguistic elements analysed, and previously discussed within this study focus, on Theme, i.e. Thematic choice, and progression. This analysis allows for Themes to be identified at not only t-unit and paragraph level but also section/chapter level through title and subtitles. Identification of Themes in accompanying language as well as the Thematic positioning (Theme/Rheme, ideal/real) of an image, in addition to salience and centrality, can indicate the image’s status in relation to the language/written component (Martinec & Salway, 2005).

In terms of status, almost all 61 images from three analysed undergraduate architecture dissertations were either equal (complementary) or unequal (image subordinate), with most relations (around 75%) unequal (image subordinate), 13 equal (complementary) and 2 equal (independent). It is not surprising that unequal status (image subordinate) is the most prevalent image-language relation type, given the written (wordy) format of a dissertation. As previously discussed, many dissertations have varying levels of multimodality and image use but are primarily written language, with some dissertations containing no images.

Figure 33 Martinec & Salway (2005) Status system for image-text (image-language) relations

5.4.4. Image-language relations: Equal status

Equal status in image-language relations is indicated through the image's position, salience, as well as Theme. Martinec and Salway (2005) describe equal status as the whole image related to the whole text. As previously discussed, the definition of 'whole text' is more challenging with dissertations, i.e. whole dissertation (hyperThemes), whole section/chapter, whole page, or whole paragraph. The unit of analysis for image-language (image-text) relations in this project begins with the paragraph and Thematic progression. However, where appropriate, such as in thematic progression, it may extend beyond one paragraph; for example, an image may have a relationship with multiple paragraphs on the same page and/or in the same section. Another indicator of equal status is position on the page and whether the whole page of language and image/s are of unequal/equal status, e.g. complementary or independent. For Martinec and Salway (2005), image and language are independent if they fulfil different processes, and neither can be considered subordinate. Martinec and Salway (2005) included a number of advertisements with an equal independent image-language (image-text) status. In advertisements, the image may bear little relation to the language. For example, luxury brands associated with jewellery or perfume may produce an advertisement with language (written/verbal) about the product but the image may be evocative or metaphoric of the product, e.g. image of flowers but not feature perfume directly (Bateman, 2014; El-Sayed, 2018). Initially, none of the 61 images from dissertations were coded as equal (independent). However, if we reflect upon which images have comparable properties to advertisements, we could consider cover images and prematter images as adverts for content and thus have the potential for equal (independent) status.

One of the dissertations included a cover image of an 'arctic iceberg from above' [See *Yellow 1/3, figure 25, p. 3*] alongside the accompanying language: 'Arctic Architecture'. Thematically, both the written and visual components (image-language) contain meanings relating to the Arctic, but not 'arctic architecture'. It is also difficult to ascertain which is subordinate (image or language) on this page, so the status could be considered equal (independent). *Yellow 2/3* also includes an image in the prematter section which works as a cover image [*figure 1: Zaha Mohammed Hadid, p. 2*]. Again, it is difficult to decide on subordination as either language or image could be removed and message clear. Another instance of a cover image [See *blue 1/2 figure 17, p. 2 & 3*] is used twice as a background image in the prematter section. Like the 'arctic iceberg', *figure 17* and the list of figures (page 3) do not appear to have explicit references and relations. However, image and language (visual and written components) without an explicit relationship may also have an unequal relationship. For example, the written language is prioritised in (*blue 1/2*) page 3, obscuring most of the image, meaning the image is subordinate to the language and thus unequal. *Blue 1/2's figure 17* is also used as a background image for the contents page, the image exemplifies much of the written language on the same page, e.g. 'caring', 'Commercial Road' and 'urban outdoor space', so could

perhaps be considered equal and complementary. However, given the position and salience of the language, the image is again subordinate to written language, i.e. unequal status. It is worth noting that Blue 1/2's *figure 17* also features later in the text, and it is this instance, which is analysed in the data, whereas earlier instances are only included in analysis if separately listed in the list of figures and not repeated elsewhere in the text.

Ingeniously the survivors in the Arctic had created a tent structure from a white curtain and covered it in aniline giving it a red colour. Better known as the red tent. Which the film by Mikhail Kalatozov, *La Tenda Rossa* was based on. The red colour made it more detectable to any rescue planes flying over the white snow.

Figure 34 Yellow 1/3 'figure 2' with equal status image-language, equal: complementary

As previously mentioned, apart from Yellow 1/3's cover image [figure 26] and yellow 2/3's cover image [figure 1], all other equal status images were considered complementary. Each dissertation had between 4-5 equal (complementary) status images. Again, Martinec and Salway's (2005) whole text/whole image was the starting point for establishing status. Thematic progression analysis supports status relations analysis, i.e. whole text (written component) corresponds with the whole image (visual component). For example, Yellow 1/3's image, i.e. *figure 2: 'La Tenda Rossa film poster'* (Figure 36 above) complements much of the language on the page but has equal status with paragraph 5 (t-units 34-37) with the Theme and/or Rheme of each t-unit captured in and complemented by the image. This equal (complementary) status is often seen alongside language with prevalent Theme iteration, where the image also reiterates the same Theme. The complementary image may appear in the Theme position, i.e. before the associated text, and act as

a stage setter (Shriver, 1997), or perhaps *scene* setter as Yellow 1/3 *figure 2* incorporates a scene from a film. A stage or scene setter can provide not only a visual anchor but also a cohesive link of Themes in both language and image (Barthes, 1977; Shriver, 1997). This concept of setting this stage can also be found beyond architecture, see move structure of chemistry article results section below (Stoller & Robinson, 2013). This setting the stage/scene is also reminiscent of architecture practice which often starts with a sketch, or 'parti' diagram to visualise a concept and/or summarise large amounts of information (Cold, 1995; Unwin, 2023).

[Download: Download full-size image](#)

Fig. 4. Move structure of a typical chemistry journal article Results section.

Figure 35 Stoller & Robinson (2013) setting the stage in chemistry result sections articles

Another example of an image with equal (complementary status) is *Blue 1/2's figure 9: 'Acts of a Caring City'* (Figure 38 below). Again, this image is featured alongside language with prevalent Theme iteration and is directly relevant to Themes in t-units 100-102, as well as Rheme in other t-units which refer to '*the four acts*'. In this example, the image also sets the scene/stage for the whole chapter, i.e. '*acts of a caring city*', and the language reiterates this Theme. A stage setter at the beginning of a chapter can emulate the subtitle/hyperTheme as well as the complementary language and can be a feature in multi-chaptered documents (Shriver, 1997). Images in the pre-matter section could also be considered stage setters if the Theme is complementary rather than independent. Returning to status, the image (*figure 9*)

and language demonstrate an interdependent relationship as they work together and depend on each other to communicate and explain the four acts as well as their importance, as this Theme is also a HyperTheme for the whole text/dissertation. It is worth highlighting that while some of the t-units (e.g. 97-99) are more closely related to another image (*figure 8*, on previous page), they are still related to the four acts in *figure 9* although the relationship is not always explicit.

Figure 36 Blue 1/2 Figure 9 (seen previously) but with accompanying equal status language

5.5 Logico-semantics image-language relations

As previously discussed, image and language can have an equal status (complementary/independent) or an unequal status. This unequal status is similar to dependent clauses in grammar, wherein the clause being modified is regarded as independent and the modifier is regarded as dependent or subordinate (Eggin, 2004). In image-language relations, either the written component or visual component can be modified through expansion or projection systems. It should be emphasised that modification through expansion or projection systems does not necessarily indicate unequal status. In fact, Martinec and Salway (2005) provide several examples of complementary relations for both expansion and projection systems, while independent image-text (image-language) relations for exposition, exemplification (language/image more general), extension, enhancement, and projection (idea). Interestingly, Martinec and Salway (2005) suggest the system does not permit independent projection (locution), although there may be exceptions for hybrid semiotic texts such as word clouds or shape poems (as seen in *blue 1/2*, *figure 1*), i.e. both image and language. However, hybrid image/language would likely have to be in isolation, like Martinec and Salway's (2005) examples, rather

than part of a larger text. In summary, the status system and logico-semantics system in Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework are separate but run in parallel and as previously mentioned, status is also informed by salience, positioning, Theme as well as logico-semantics relations. Other frameworks based on Barthes (1977) may conflate status with logic-semantics systems (Bateman, 2014), but I have chosen to follow Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework which separates the two to allow for more nuance and analysis of multimodal documents with multiple images, pages and instances of language. However, assigning status based on factors, such as salience, can be subjective as well as possibly ambiguous, so drawing on other factors such as positioning, Theme, and logico-semantic relations, while complex, can support more evidence-based status decisions.

5.5.1. Logico-semantics: EXPANSION: elaboration

The most frequent image-language relation type across all three analysed undergraduate dissertations was elaboration. As previously discussed in the literature review, Eggins (2004, p. 279) suggests elaboration could be "signified by (=)" and I introduced the metaphor of topstitching, i.e. retracing and repeating. There are two types of elaboration in Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework:

- exposition (same generality): similar to paraphrasing, i.e. 'in other words' (Eggins, 2004)
- exemplification (language/image more general) 'develops the meaning' (Eggins, 2004), i.e. illustrates

Eggins (2004) also lists clarification as a third type of elaboration. This is omitted from Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework but is included in other similar image-text (image-language) relation frameworks, such as Unsworth (2007), who also adds other typologies. However, much of Unsworth's research focuses on educational textbooks, which often feature multiple images featuring clarification as well as divergence in accompanying language (Bateman, 2014; Unsworth, 2007). Unsworth's (2007) level of complexity and additional typologies were not deemed as helpful as Martinec and Salway's (2005) simplified framework with perhaps, clearer links to SFL.

Figure 37 Logico-semantics system with expansion and projection systems (Martinec & Salway, 2025)

All three types of elaboration image-language (image-text) relations were present in the 3 architecture undergraduate dissertations. Most elaboration image-language relations (around 40%) were elaboration: exemplification (language more general), followed by exemplification (image more general) (around 20%) and finally elaboration: exposition (same generality) was the least prevalent (10%) elaboration type. Elaboration: exemplification (language more general) was by far the most prevalent of image-language relations, across all 3 analysed dissertations. This type of image-language relation is also common across other genres, including advertisements and textbooks (El-Sayed, 2018; Lai, 2018; Zhu & Yang, 2023). In advertisements, El-Sayed (2018) found that the language was more general and in the initial Theme position, followed by an image (visual component), providing an 'instance' of something from the written component, in the Rheme position and often to the right and/or below language, even in Arabic advertisements. This positioning is also common in newspaper articles in which the written component is again often in the Theme position, followed by image in the Rheme position (often to the right of language), depicting a specific aspect of the written component (Salway & Martinec, 2005).

In the analysed dissertations, images (visual component) were most frequently in the Rheme position after and/or to the right of written component and around two-thirds of elaboration: exemplification (language more general), the image was in the Rheme position providing an example of the Theme. However, without the accompanying written component the meaning of a visual component (image) could remain 'cloudy' (Stöckl, 2004), indicating subordination. The elaboration: exemplification (image more general) followed a similar pattern in terms of image positioning, i.e. majority Rheme, but were less prevalent than (language more

general). The 'image more general' instances appeared to work in a comparable way to scene/stage setters by providing a visual accompaniment of the more general Theme, but as mentioned previously, were often included after the written component (language), so more summarisers i.e. stage/scene completers.

Fig. 2 Example of the layout of image and text on an art webpage.

Figure 38 Salway & Martinec (2005) online art gallery page, image in Theme position, image position, and salience: image subordinate to language

In contrast to equal status, in which images (visual component) are often in the Theme position, i.e. to the left and/or above the language (written component), positioning of an image after and/or to the right of language in Rheme position can often indicate an unequal status with image subordinate to language. Salway and Martinec (2005) suggest that in newspaper articles this can often be the case. However, to ascribe status, we also need to consider, among other factors, the real/ideal positioning of the image. For example, an image may appear in the right column but higher than the language or equal to highest point of written component on the page. In Figure 38, Salway and Martinec (2005) provide an example of an online art page with the image in the Theme position but higher than the language in the Real position and with a salient image larger than the corresponding language on the page, indicating an unequal status with language subordinate to image.

Despite the presumed similarity between descriptions of artworks in online galleries and descriptions of artworks/designs in architecture dissertations, there were no examples of unequal status: language subordinate to image. This dominance of language over image is to be expected in lengthy 'texty' texts such as dissertations, with significant word counts. Counterintuitively, it is not only the number of words but also the number of images which suggests dominance of language over image. If multiple images are on a page, there is no 'hero' image and written component/page/paragraph may draw on and dominate multiple images. It is also worth highlighting the complexity in assigning status and logico-semantic relations if multiple instances of images and/or language on the same page. Across the 27 collected dissertations, there were very few instances of image-only pages, including

pages with an image and captions, and these were almost always preceded and/or succeeded by language-only pages. The only exception to this was dissertation (yellow 3/3), which is coincidentally about the topic of artworks, and includes one image-only [with caption] page preceded by a language-only page, followed by 2 pages with a large salient image [with caption] and one short paragraph. However, the image positioning in these cases is after and below the corresponding paragraph, suggesting a more subordinate image with a caption to the left/right of image (see figure 39).

Figure 39 Yellow 3/3 pages 9 & 10 comparison to Salway & Martinec (2005) online art gallery, image subordinate to language

Unequal status (language subordinate to image), alongside positioning and salience is also indicated through logico-semantic relations with the whole text related to whole image, often with repeated lexical references such as ‘figure x shows’. Salway and Martinec (2005) suggest that such lexical references at the start of the text often indicate language subordinate to image (unequal), while lexical references towards the end of the written component may indicate a more equal status. Surprisingly, given the advice that an illustration/image is only considered useful if directly referred to (Borden & Ruedi Ray, 2014), the analysed dissertations have relatively few direct lexical references, i.e. ‘figure x...’. While this is not a corpus study identifying specific lexical items, a subcorpus on SketchEngine of the 6 dissertations revealed 115 examples of the lexical item ‘figure’. However, many of these 115 were either in the list of figures and/or captions (84). However, even with enhanced concordance lines, it was challenging to establish which examples were lexical references within the written component and not part of captions/labels without viewing the language in situ as part of a multimodal text. Thus, I performed a manual count, which shows that 3 dissertations contained no obvious lexical references, two dissertations included lexical references for less than half of the featured images, and one dissertation (blue 1/2) had more lexical references but did not refer to every image (Table 54). Blue 1/2 lexical references were often in the middle of paragraphs and/or referred to

multiple images in the same paragraph. There were some instances of references at the end and/or start of the written component and this, alongside other factors, indicated an equal status. See blue 1/2 figure 40 below which has lexical references at start, end and middle of written component and was ascribed 'equal: complementary status' as both image and language are interdependent.

Table 54 Count of images in comparison to word 'figure/s' as part of written component [not caption or figures list]

	Figures	'figure' in text [not caption]
Yellow 1/3	26	0
Yellow 2/3	16	4
Blue 1/2	22	19
Red 1/1	31	0
Yellow 3/3	16	7
Blue 2/2	38	0

Figure 40 Blue 1/2 lexical references, 'figure' start, middle and end of written component

Another consideration when ascribing status is the logico-semantic relations. For example, when the image is an example of something within the associated language, this often subordinates the image. In contrast, if the image is an exposition

(language/image of the same generality), this may denote a more equal, often complementary status (Martinec & Salway, 2005.) Around half of exposition instances were considered equal: complementary status, with the written component often featuring a nominalised group, e.g. Theme, with a more implicit process, and the image featuring the same nominalised group or Theme at the same level of generality. Identifying the processes in longer academic texts, compared to advertisements and other multimodal texts, can be challenging due to fewer material and behavioural processes and more implicit processes. In academic student writing, material processes (e.g. measure, place) may feature in methodology sections, mental processes (e.g. feel, think) in writer reflections and verbal processes (e.g. say, state) in reporting other sources (Gardner, 2012; Hardy & Friginal, 2016). However, these processes are not often depicted via images in academic texts unless in diagram form, e.g. flowchart in methodology. Instead, processes in dissertation images are often implicit, and a clearer tie is between nominal groups and/or Themes in language and image. Hence the use of Thematic progression in this study.

5.5.2 Extension

Stöckl (2004) claimed image-language relations are usually 'additive', i.e. extension. However, in the analysed dissertations, there was only one instance which appeared to demonstrate an extension image-language relation. In this instance, the written component appears to extend the meaning of the visual component [Zaha Hadid] through the addition of new information (Eggins, 2004). As the language is modifying the image, this may indicate an unequal status with the written component subordinate to the visual component. However, in Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework, language can modify the image but also be independent, i.e. equal status. For example, the language or image [with caption: 'in memory of Zaha Mohammed Hadid'] could be removed and message still clear. This passes Eggins' (2004) deletion test in which one element, e.g. clause/t-unit or image, could be deleted and what is left still makes sense indicating not only an extension relationship but also perhaps independent relationship. The two-sentence/t-unit paragraph adds to the image but in a more equal way, like a zip.

This may suggest the predominance of unequal status with image subordinate to language makes 'equal: extension' image-language relations less likely. Another factor to consider is the analysis and treatment of captions/labels, which can act as extension of an image, but can either be treated as part of the visual component or as part of the written component (Martinec & Salway, 2005). In this case, the caption 'in memory of Zaha Mohammed Hadid' is treated as part of the image, mainly as it does not qualify as a t-unit, so it is the 2-sentence paragraph acting as an extension with equal status to image [and caption]. Other researchers may encounter more examples of extension if captions/labels are considered and analysed as purely written component and not part of the image (visual component), but may want to consider how this language is analysed as part of Thematic progression as well as

the author's intentions, often indicated by layout and placement of caption in proximity to the image and other language.

Figure 1

In Memory of Zaha Mohammad Hadid

One of architecture's most cherished figures, an Iraqi-born architect with extraordinary achievements and honours. Zaha Hadid's groundbreaking career ranked her among the world's most talented and influential.

Figure 41 Yellow 3/3 Figure 3 + caption and accompanying language demonstrating expansion

Elaboration was by far the most prevalent expansion image-language relations type. This prevalence of elaboration is consistent with other image-text (image-language) relations studies on multimodal documents such as textbooks (Lai, 2018; Roehrich, 2013; Zhu & Yang, 2023) with images 'illustrating' meanings, e.g. abstract concepts and often providing visual examples. Interestingly, expansion's dominance is also seen across image types, including photographs and renderings, such as graphs (Roehrich, 2013). The least prevalent elaboration type was extension with just one instance. This is consistent with two studies (Lai, 2018; Roehrich, 2013). A third study reported the reverse pattern, i.e. higher prevalence for extension than enhancement (Zhu & Yang, 2023). This divergence may be due to textbooks for younger learners demonstrating more simple relations, i.e. (=) rather than (x). Zhu and Yang's (2003) study also presents difficulties in like-for-like comparisons due to differences in coding. In contrast, in this EdD study, enhancement was slightly more prevalent than extension, but still infrequent overall. The other two studies (Lai, 2018; Roehrich, 2013) also found enhancement to be more prevalent than extension but still only accounting for a small proportion of images, i.e. under 10%.

5.5.3. Enhancement

In Salway's and Martinec's (2005) framework, the image-text (image-language) can be qualified and enhanced through temporal, spatial, or causal information. Causal enhancements, e.g. reason or purpose, were not identified in any of the analysed dissertations and represented less than 1% in Lai's (2018) study and were not specified in either of the other two studies previously mentioned. One reason for so few instances of 'enhancement: causal' lies in the difficulty, impossibility, of expressing the complexity of causality through images (Lai, 2018; Stöckl, 2004). In addition, a genre's social purpose and social function will impact the likelihood of enhancement: causal in language and/or images. In terms of social function, a dissertation is to build research skills, whereas critiques/essays develop reasoning (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). Thus, critiques and essays may be more likely to include 'enhancement: clausal' than other academic genres.

Temporal enhancements were also not identified in any of the analysed dissertations nor the textbooks in Lai's (2018) study. Lai (2008) suggests this absence may, like causal, be related to difficulty in representing this enhancement, i.e. abstract concept of time in visual form. Despite this difficulty, Roehrich (2013) suggests enhancement: temporal may be achieved in comic-like images expressing time. Another 'enhancement: temporal' option could be timelines, but timelines may also be instances of projection, depending on accompanying language (see 5.5.4.). Martinec and Salway (2005) provided an example of language enhancing image with temporal information through catalogue details of an artwork in an online gallery (see Salway & Martinec, 2005) but as previously discussed, this suggests language subordinate to image, an unlikely pattern in dissertations.

The only instances (2) of enhancement were spatial, i.e. *where*. Initially, based on a modified version of Burkhard's (2004) framework, I assumed 'orientational knowledge', i.e. know-where would be most associated with maps and/or models. However, there was just one instance of 'enhancement: spatial' as a map, while the other was a photograph. Both instances provide orientational knowledge with information about the location and/or setting provided by a photograph or map (Roehrich, 2013). There is some potential crossover here in terms of scene/stage setters, i.e. expansion: elaboration (image more general) which may illustrate a Theme in-situ rather than a setting of a Theme. This is a very subtle distinction which requires further textual analysis. For example, *Yellow 1/3's figure 13* explicitly mentions the setting in the list of figures: "*Clark, P. (2018)...surrounded by icebergs*" (Figure 42). Without a direct reference to the setting, it can be difficult to ascribe 'enhancement: spatial'. Instead, in these instances, I have opted for 'elaboration: exemplification' (image more general) as the image may in part depict a setting/spatial element but is exemplifying a Theme [in-situ]. This is by no means the only example of potential crossover. For example, Eggins (2004) suggests that real texts are multiclausal/multielemental and, as a result, can interweave projection and

expansion relations. This is exemplified by maps which may suggest ‘enhancement: spatial’ relations but the image-language relations indicate projection.

13	Rothera Research Station	6	Clark, P. (2018). The British Antarctic Survey's Rothera base, surrounded by icebergs [Image]. Retrieved 27 January 2021, from https://www.ft.com/antarctica .
----	--------------------------	---	--

Figure 42 (Figure 13 as described in yellow 1/3 list of figures)

Figure 43 Yellow 1/3 'figure 13' demonstrating enhancement: spatial

5.5.4. Projection: locution (wording); idea (meaning)

In SFL, projection between clauses involves one of two processes: ‘verbal processes’, i.e. saying (locution) and ‘mental processes’, i.e. thinking (idea) (Eggins, 2004). Martinec and Salway (2005) adopted locution and idea and suggested that in image-language relations, *locution* may be represented as a speech bubble, whereas *idea* may be represented by a thought cloud (Lai, 2018; Martinec & Salway, 2005). Martinec and Salway (2005) also provided other examples of projection, such as diagrams, which can project the ideas from the written component into a more visual form, i.e. diagrams which can feature in textbooks as well as academic writing, such as dissertations.

Figure 44 Illustrations of locution 'speech bubble' and idea 'thought cloud'

Instances of projection were identified across all 3 dissertations, but not as frequently as expansion. Zhu and Yang (2023) identified a similar pattern, i.e. less projection, and interestingly claimed more instances of expansion and less projection as textbooks increased in age and/or linguistic difficulty. This interesting pattern may, in part, be related to age/language of the audience, as projection provides an opportunity to attribute words and ideas to sources (Eggins, 2004), albeit in a more

simplified way, e.g. speech bubbles and thought clouds. However, during higher, further, possibly secondary education, students are introduced to more formalised attribution, such as referencing systems, perhaps limiting the need for projection.

The 14 instances of projection feature in all 3 analysed dissertations, but only 2 instances were 'projection: locution', while the rest were 'projection: idea'.

'Projection: locution', i.e. rerepresenting words in images can be more challenging without such devices as speech bubbles. As previously discussed, word clouds and shape poems could be classified as 'projection: locution' with a more equal status despite not being deemed possible originally by Martinec and Salway (2005).

'Projection: locution' was common in young learner textbooks with visual vocabulary charts, speech bubbles and pictorial processes (Lai, 2018), but Martinec and Salway's (2005) example of projection, i.e. a Venn diagram, had elements of locution, i.e. matched words between image and language but ultimately the written/visual component rerepresented ideas. The 2 instances of 'projection: locution' are also diagrams with matching words from language and image. However, both diagrams act more as a list of words rather than a diagram exploring the relationships and meanings of words, such as a Venn diagram or flowchart. One instance '4 acts' as we have already seen as part of status relations and the second instance (Figure 45) is copied below. Both instances function as a visual representation of the dissertation's hyperThemes.

Architecture is evolving around us into more complex schemes that aim to tackle worldwide environmental and population growth issues. Thus, throughout the past few years, the invalidity of traditional design approaches such as Modernism and classical architecture has been evident (Valencia, 2020). The main factor that has brought attention to this is COVID-19 the pandemic of 2020, which has made it clear that the world is becoming increasingly dependent on digital technology. When it comes to architecture and design, the rise of Computation design is inevitable. Michael Spence -Nobel Prize Laureate in Economic Sciences-, suggested 'higher risk aversion, increasing investment in digital technologies, and the diversification of supply chains will equate to a rapid expansion of smart cities' in response to being questioned about the major changes in the global economy likely to occur in the aftermath of COVID-19 (Guerrero, 2020). From this, its inferred that three main factors will influence a design shift moving into the future. These primary factors are global transformations, technology, and history. The computational design will shift to become the forefront for architectural design as the dominant style in architecture in this envision of a future world. These factors are strong influencers of this when heading into a future world.

Figure 6: Primary Research

Figure 6 simplifies the causes of design evolution into three main factors: global transformation, advancements in technology and historic influence. Throughout this text these factors will be expanded to assess how much influence they have on design evolution and how they influence shifts in design heading into a future world.

Figure 45 Yellow 3/3 'figure 6' with extended description demonstrating projection: idea

Martinec and Salway (2005) extended the meaning of 'locution' and described this as a type of 'translation'. So perhaps then if 'projection: locution' is word-by-word translating, then 'projection: idea' is more like conceptual interpreting or interpretation. Originally, I hypothesised that projection was like a garment's lining, when in fact it appears 'projection: locution' is more like a garment produced following a pattern but in a different fabric, whereas 'projection: idea' is more like drafting a pattern based on an exemplar garment, then producing the garment. These textile production processes also have some resonance with the potential positioning of these images with both 'projection: locution' instances in the Theme position followed by the accompanying language. Although caution is required here, as positioning of an image on a page with multiple columns and elements, i.e. paragraphs and images is complex. Also, the position may signify a verbal/visual cue which is revealing for some readers but ignored by others (Shriver, 1997), or perhaps even unintentional.

The remaining 12 examples of 'projection: idea' were all diagrams, maps, or graphs. There was one photograph in the set, but this was a photograph of a model, so a 2D version of a 3D model. As well as projecting ideas, the image-language can also project different knowledges: declarative (know-what) / procedural (knowhow) /

experimental (know why) as well as orientational (know-where) depending on the relationship between visual and written components (Burkhard, 2004). In relationships with image subordinate to language, the visual component can take many forms to project the knowledge and idea suggesting Burkhard's (2004) framework is more applicable in relationships where the language is subordinate to the image.

Finally, the projection system does present some challenges for researchers. For example, Bateman (2014) suggests images cannot adequately incorporate verbal processes, i.e. the language cannot 'say' the image, nor the image 'say' the language, so there could be a gap in Martinec and Salway's framework. However, verbal processes can be extended beyond 'say', e.g. the language 'restates' the image, or the image 'restates' the language through translation or interpretation. This extension of meaning or projection does imply a different type of relationship and requires further consideration (Bateman, 2014). For example, many instances of 'projection: idea' could be categorised as 'elaboration: exposition' due to 'restatement' or perhaps categorisation drawing from both systems, e.g. Zhu and Yang's (2023) combination categories: 'locution + elaboration/enhancement/extension' may better reflect the complex image-language relations in long multimodal and multielemental texts but may also further complicate the issue.

6. Conclusion

In summary, my research objectives were as follows:

Identify the language choices architecture students make in their academic written texts (specifically dissertations), focusing on:

- Structure (e.g., macrostructure, section headings, dissertation types)
- Texture (e.g., Thematic progression and image-language relations)

Explore the reasons behind these language choices, considering influences such as:

- pedagogic practices, disciplinary conventions, contextual expectations

This study was originally prompted by a limited range of resources and research to draw from for ESAP provision for undergraduate architecture students. However, my personal motivation for this study was to conduct my own research with my students in my context to develop my personal understanding of their texts, context, and practices in the hope of sharing this knowledge, as well as using this knowledge to develop future ESAP provision.

6.1 Research Summary

With the UK government aiming to increase numbers of international students to 600,000 by 2030 while simultaneously discouraging international students through reduction of graduate route (post-study employment) from 24 months to 18, as well as, removing the right to bring dependant family members and possible future levies on international student income, the pressures on UK universities has never been greater (UKCISA, 2025). Tailored, contextualised, constructively aligned, and collaborative EAP support could play a role in mitigating some of the effects of an increasingly inhospitable environment for international students in UK HE. EAP should be understood not as a cost and expense to minimise but as a strategic asset and high-value investment. Investing in EAP provision can demonstrate a commitment to global engagement and equity and promotion of UK HE as a welcoming and supportive study location.

EAP pedagogy is defined by its contextualisation, constructive alignment, and collaboration. EAP provision exists on a continuum between EGAP (English for General Academic Purposes) and ESAP (English for Specific Academic Purposes), influenced by several factors including but not limited to HEI, EAP Practitioners (PEAPs) and student cohort. ESAP resources and research have been heavily influenced by business and/or STEM subjects, whereas creative disciplines have received relatively little attention. Architecture dissertations are “fuzzy” genres with hybrid academic/professional features and multimodal elements. Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) emphasises linguistic choices and provides tools for analysing structure (macrostructure) and texture (Thematic progression; image-language relations). Academic literacies theory emphasises writing as a

social practice and incorporates ethnographic approaches. Textography integrates SFL and Aclits to study text, context, and practices for richer analysis. Operating within an interpretivist paradigm, this research draws upon a theoretical framework combining SFL and Aclits, utilising textography as a method which combines textual analysis of contextual texts and ethnographic interviews. As a textographic study, this research collected a huge amount of contextual data including but not limited to ethnographic interview with architecture lecturer and dissertation supervisor, full textual histories (i.e. all submitted texts & feedback) of 6 participants (undergraduate architecture students), contextual learning materials, such as slides, handouts, reading lists, student exemplars, assessment briefs, rubrics and guidance and other learning materials.

Research focussed on 3 selected undergraduate dissertations for texture analysis (Thematic progression & image-language relations) and was extended to include 3 collected undergraduate dissertations, as well as 21 exemplar dissertations, for structure analysis, but drew on a wide range of primary sources, i.e. collected texts, as well as secondary sources, i.e. other studies, to explore reasons behind these texture and structure choices.

In terms of structure choices, four dissertation typologies have been identified in undergraduate architecture dissertations ranked here in prevalence order: Topic-Based, TopGen (mixed), Traditional Complex (genre-based) and Traditional Simple (genre-based). The macrostructure of undergraduate architecture dissertations demonstrated creative naming practices, e.g. preface/finale, as opposed to introduction/conclusion, and this creative expression was valued by the discipline. In terms of texture choices, unmarked topical Themes dominate, echoing practices associated with academic writing, such as nominalisation and clarity/brevity. In addition, marked Themes are also frequent, more so in topic-based than genre-based dissertations, reflecting creative expression valued by architecture. The most prevalent Thematic progression was zigzag, i.e. Rheme to Theme, in which the Rheme (end) of one t-unit became the Theme (start) of the next t-unit. Finally, image-language relations indicate the visual component, i.e. images, are integral but often subordinate to the written component. The most prevalent image-language relation pattern was elaboration, where written/visual component elaborates the other, often through exemplification.

6.2 Research contributions

This study sought to fill a gap in resources and research on undergraduate architecture writing. This study has demonstrated the multimodal as well as hybrid nature of undergraduate architecture dissertations, which draws on academic disciplinary norms, as well as reflecting creative nature of architecture practice. This has relevance not only for creative disciplines but also a range of subjects with dissertations, which draw on both academic and practitioner writing practices, e.g. business, law, medicine, education, engineering, policing, social work, aviation,

maritime and hospitality. Architecture as a discipline sits somewhere between arts and science. This may go some way to explain the prevalence of TopGen, i.e. mixed, with Topic-based dissertations traditionally associated with Arts [and Humanities] disciplines and genre-based dissertations, e.g. traditional simple/complex, traditionally associated with sciences. Disciplines which incorporate art and science may also mix topic-based and genre-based macrostructures, i.e. TopGen. These arts/science disciplines can include, but are not limited to, other creative disciplines, as well as geography, archaeology, and education or linguistics. I am very aware my own thesis also follows a TopGen macrostructure.

Undergraduate architecture dissertations are multimodal, and images are prevalent. Images can also be prevalent in other creative disciplines as well as sciences, e.g. graphs and tables. Despite this, the analysis of images, as well as language (both visual and written components), is uncommon in academic writing research, with a tendency for myopic focus on language at the expense of images. This is, in part, is due to methodological/analytical methods available. For example, it is worth noting that even when attempting to use language-only analysis via corpus linguistics, e.g. instances of 'figure', I needed the context, i.e. page and associated image, to better understand the language usage. Recently, Jiang and Hyland's (2026) proposal for a new EAP research agenda has also called for more research in several areas including multimodal academic communication, multimodal texts, and multimodal literacy, which may involve methodological expansion. This proposed expansion may come in many guises, with textography, perhaps, being one option.

6.2.1 Research findings

Identify language choices architecture students make in terms of structure and texture in academic written texts, i.e. dissertations.

Explore reasons why architecture students make these language choices in academic written texts.

This research has identified an expansive range of language choices available to undergraduate architecture students in terms of both structure and texture. These creative, hybrid and multimodal dissertations reflect the creativity, hybridity, and multimodality of architecture. The creative/design process, as illustrated by the design squiggle (Newman, 2024), is reflective of the writing/research process beginning with a seemingly infinite and often bewildering array of choices, before developing into patterns influenced by exemplars, context and community and ending with (hopefully) appropriate personal decisions. Architecture values creativity, respects innovation and often rewards risk-taking. Thus, text design choices (texture and structure) are heavily influenced by [pracademic] context, contextual practices, and contextual texts, but are not normative, and these choices are also reflective of the individual writer/designer. Like architecture, the dissertations represent both academic and practitioner practices, specifically in terms of the spectrum of texture and structure choices. Architecture students are taught by pracademics who bring

not only practitioner experience and architecture practices from their membership of architecture discourse community but also understanding and expectations from their experience as both a former university student and current member of academic discourse community. Architecture's hybrid nature is also illustrated by its position between the arts/humanities divide and continual crossing of visual/verbal divide through multimodality. Architecture texts and artefacts are inherently multimodal as well as intertextual and represent the design process and larger body of work. Dissertations and research reports have been defined by their social function, i.e. 'building research skills', stages, i.e. macrostructure, network, i.e. correspondence with other texts, such as published articles and examples/exemplars (Nesi & Gardner, 2012). However, architecture dissertations extend this definition to include 'preparing for professional practice' as a social function as well as extending the available network beyond purely academic texts to artefacts and multimodal texts such as portfolios, crits, designs, as well as inspiration from a broader range of resources such as books, films, theatre and even music.

6.2.2. Contribution to community

This study's overall aim was first and foremost a practice-based contribution to pedagogy. I hoped by pursuing a professional doctorate in education, rather than PhD, I may develop professionally and pedagogically as well as academically. The diverse and unique structural and textural configurations of these creative, hybrid and multimodal dissertations have renewed and strengthened my commitment to EAP, particularly ESAP provision and EPP provision, which is contextualised, i.e. disciplinary/subject context, constructively aligned, i.e. genre-led and SFL-guided, as well as collaborative, i.e. working/researching with students and academics from the discipline. I identified four differing macrostructures (Topic-based; TopGen; Traditional complex; Traditional simple) and coined the portmanteau 'TopGen' not only for myself, but also for clarity, as previously 'mixed' often sat alongside the previous 3, as well as 'PhD by publication', and it was not always clear what was being mixed. This identification of 4 macrostructures, even at undergraduate level, may encourage PEAPs to conduct their own textual analysis of dissertation structure in specific disciplines and/or consider EAP provision and support beyond traditional simple with students from creative disciplines as well as pracademic and hybrid arts/sciences subjects. In addition, I uncovered some unconventional naming conventions for chapters which mirror the innovativeness, interdisciplinarity and creativity of not only architecture but also architecture students.

The prevalence of Rheme>Theme progression, as well as diversity of Thematic progression patterns, may also encourage PEAPs to conduct their own analyses of texture and perhaps support students in analysing their own Thematic progression, and go beyond traditionally taught paragraph structure (topic sentence and derived Themes) to incorporate various Thematic patterns, e.g. Rheme to Theme, often in combination with other progression patterns. The exploration of image-language relations demonstrates SFL's expansion and projection systems can be extended

and adapted to analyse visual, as well as linguistic elements, and could, perhaps should, be incorporated in future EAP provision. In fact, Daly & Unsworth (2011) suggest literacy teaching should include drawing students' attention to images and language as well as discussions about relationships between image and language. The variety of expansion and projection patterns, as well as all 3 examples of expansion, all beginning with 'e' and close in meaning, led me to adopt textile metaphors, which could be used in EAP provision, to avoid often confusing SFL metalanguage and may be particularly helpful with students from creative disciplines. I also believe the metaphors of structure and texture are helpful, particularly for creative disciplines, although I cannot solely take credit, as Halliday and Hasan (1976) were using 'texture' and 'structure' as SFL metaphors before I was born, albeit texture in a broader sense, e.g. inclusion of cohesive ties, and structure often more microstructure than macrostructure.

This study's academic aim was an empirical contribution to knowledge by exploring an under-researched and under-represented context, i.e. undergraduate architecture. This research has made explicit some of the many language choices available to architecture students in terms of texture and structure. PEAPs and architecture educators, can now make these choices more explicit and support students in developing contextually-appropriate texts and practices, as well as highlighting options for creative subversion, e.g. chapter naming conventions and text design. Swales (2004) cautioned against viewing a PhD thesis as a longer, more complex postgraduate dissertation and instead should be viewed a separate genre. Undergraduate dissertations too, should be viewed as a separate genre. However, much academic writing research has focussed on postgraduate dissertations, theses or even research articles, and these findings have informed EAP practice. This research study has highlighted the diversity of choices available for undergraduate architecture writers and some of the potential differences between undergraduate and postgraduate dissertations. Finally, this research has also emphasised the importance of context, and influence of discipline on texts and practices, which can be challenging to navigate if not part of the discourse community.

6.2.3. Contribution to scholarship

In addition to contributions to practice and knowledge, this research study also offers some methodological contributions. Firstly, via the combination of textual analysis and ethnography through textography, and secondly, via incorporation of SFL to analyse image-language relations. As previously discussed, EAP and linguistics research has been accused of a myopic focus on texts, whereas AcLits (Academic Literacies) has been criticised for lack of texts (Lillis, 2008). A textographic research project brings context, texts, and practices together as the focus of research. Since Swales' original textography in 1998, a small number of textography studies have been published, with most focusing on findings and including scant discussion of textography as method. I hoped to fill this methodological gap with this research, but found a strong appetite for methodological discussion of textography, as

demonstrated by my publications prior to EdD completion (Sizer, 2019c, 2019b, 2021, 2025). A further methodological contribution is the use of SFL expansion and projection systems for image-language relations analysis. Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework was developed using a variety of multimodal texts such as advertisements, newspaper articles, and textbooks, but its use with multimodal academic texts has, up until now, been fairly limited. The framework has been used in marketing, e.g. Alyousef (2016) uses a similar approach to this study, but the analysed images from marketing undergraduates are mainly graphs and tables, and the reporting focusses more on positioning of image, e.g. Theme/Rheme, Real/Ideal. While Wilcox (2014) explores marketing diagrams in academic articles using the expansion system. Archer (2010) has published some interesting work with multimodality in undergraduate architecture texts, but often adopts less linguistic frameworks to explore image-language relations. Archer (2010) draws on Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework in one study, which includes an image from undergraduate architecture essay. In line with my own findings, the image-language relation in this example is 'elaboration' but the analysis focusses on the caption rather than wider language and written component.

6.3 Limitations

Any research study has a time and word limit otherwise, we would go on forever, and also never publish and share our findings. This study began pre-covid, and due to covid restrictions, I did not have the intended access to the physical context of the architecture department and/or students and staff. This impacted recruitment of participants and resulted in 3 separate recruitment rounds, i.e. 3 cohorts (19/20, 20/21 & 21/22), meaning an increasingly elongated time period from student completion of dissertation and architecture course and possible interview. Sadly, despite repeated attempts, the student/graduate participants were not interested in participating in interviews and had moved on with their lives. However, the interviewee was the greatest genre-specific expert, I could have hoped for, due to their experience and expertise in both architecture practice and architecture academia - a true pracademic. As the interviewee mentioned, it can take 7-10 years to become a fully-trained architect, so these students, despite graduating, may still have some way to go before becoming members of the architecture discourse community.

In addition, multiple recruitment rounds and each successive cohort, brought with it changes to assessments and modules, e.g. interesting genres, such as illustrated essays and annotated bibliographies, did not feature consistently across all 3 cohorts. The most consistent module and assessment, particularly in terms of guidance, was the dissertation. This prompts two suggestions for future research:

- Exercise caution when conducting research with specific genres. Module descriptors and assessment can change rapidly, rendering a specific genre obsolete and/or much changed.

- If conducting research with undergraduate students, consider following them through their studies, i.e. recruiting participants in their first year. This longitudinal approach could provide opportunities for richer textual histories, as well as opportunities for engagement, retention and perhaps also interviews. However, population size and recruitment targets, as well as time available, may influence whether this approach is possible. An added consideration is the course/department's retention rates, as participants recruited in year 1 may not always complete the course.

Systemic Functional Linguistics emphasises linguistic choices, but its extravagant and expansive nature also results in choices for the researcher. Choices which limited the scope of this research study include but are not limited to the metafunction (textual), object of analysis (t-unit), boundaries for structure and texture and use of expansion and projection systems for image-language relations. These choices prompt suggestions for future SFL-based research:

- Clause, rather than t-unit, as unit of analysis would better reflect expansion and projection system and thus image-language relations system. However, it can be challenging to differentiate clausal boundaries, especially in long academic texts with long multi-clausal sentences. In lieu of an interview to confirm author's intention, punctuation marks, i.e. full stops indicate the end of a t-unit, and in some cases, other punctuation marks and linguistic cues indicate more than one independent clause in the same sentence. In addition, t-unit analysis provided more opportunities to explore Thematic progression as well as image-language relations through identified Themes and Rhemes.
- Both structure and texture as metaphors are useful, particularly for architecture, and could be broadened and explored beyond the boundaries put in place by this thesis. However, due to time and word count limitations, these boundaries were necessary. Other researchers may choose to explore one of these metaphors alone (either texture or structure) more fully, e.g. structure including microstructure and macrostructure or texture including cohesive ties, e.g. anaphoric/cataphoric references and cohesive devices, e.g. co-reference and co-classification (Hasan, 1998). This research is not devoid of these instances of texture, e.g. there are some mentions of cohesive ties and devices in researcher's notes, but are not in the purview of this study, as they did not add much to the concept of either structure or texture as conceptualised here.
- I have mentioned some of the difficulties in classifying image-language relations and possibility of crossover and ambiguity, as well as decisions surrounding caption or label as written component and/or visual component. Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework was based on several genres, which often included behavioural and material processes. In addition to Martinec and Salway's (2005) framework, there have been other proposed image-language (image-text) relations frameworks often for specific genres. For

example, Unsworth's (2007) classification network for education materials, i.e. textbooks, or Kong's (2006) image-language relations mainly for newspapers (Bateman, 2014). Perhaps then an adapted framework for academic writing genres could be explored in future research, which better addresses processes in academic writing and use of captions/labels and relations to written component.

A final limitation of this study is the number of analysed texts. In comparison to corpus studies, 27 undergraduate dissertations may feel small. However, analysing every page, sentence, and every image in 3 dissertations without corpus or other tools was a worthwhile, albeit slow, endeavour and allowed me to reach saturation. This close linguistic analysis was also accompanied by analysis of participant (6) and exemplar dissertations (21), ethnographic interview with an architecture expert and a wealth of contextual texts, e.g. feedback, assessment brief/rubric and other learning materials, and guidance.

- Future studies may incorporate technology using AI to automate the process of Thematic progression analysis and/or identify the expansion/projection system used in images. However, I found using tools, e.g. corpus analysis for instances of 'figure' challenging and also feel I benefitted from the deliberate human effort, though it was not without error.

6.4 Implications

This research has clear implications for EAP practice and PEAPs, including the proposal of EPP (English for Pracademic Purposes) provision, i.e. considering, analysing, and incorporating language needs and texts not only from inside the academy/university (academic needs) but also from the student's future discourse community (practitioner needs). Future EPP research could take many directions, but may include investigations into the needs as well as relevance of English for future professional practice (Schug, 2022). This study presents an accessible research method which can be modified to analyse disciplinary contexts both inside and outside university, and I warmly encourage fellow PEAPs to conduct and share research in their contexts of interest. While this study focussed on architecture, it has implications for PEAPs working with other creative disciplines with creative, multimodal genres, as well as those working with pracademic subjects, which may include hybrid genres. And I believe other EPP research could have similar implications relevant to a range of contexts and disciplines.

This study also has some pedagogical implications for teaching academic and/or pracademic writing involving multimodal texts. Academic literacy guidance which incorporates not only language (structure) but also raises awareness of role and relationship of images (texture) in multimodal texts and communication, can support not only critical engagement with texts but also highlight choices available to students (Bilotta, 2023; Daly & Unsworth, 2011). With the increase of digital and multimodal texts, EAP needs to provide more support with consuming and producing

texts in which language, image, and other modes come together to create meaning (Jiang & Hyland, 2026). For some excellent examples of recent EAP practice featuring multimodality, and potential benefits of doing so, see Bilotta's (2023) PhD by publication, as well as Christoforou's (2025) EAP study of students' production of multimodal videos and Chan et al.'s (2025) suggestions for multimodal assessments. Also, beyond EAP, Fallin and Bartram's (2026) student guide to multimodal assessments appears promising and will be released later in 2026.

This research also has implications beyond PEAPs, e.g. colleagues working with students to provide academic writing support, e.g. learning development, academic skills, dissertation supervisors, as well as library and engagement colleagues. Dissertations are a representation of the student's learning journey and can be as diverse as the writers themselves. This study demonstrates the diversity of choices available to, and chosen by, undergraduate architecture students and hopefully encourages colleagues to explore, and make explicit, choices available to their students. In a similar way, this research also has implications for architecture educators, particularly dissertation supervisors, and may encourage them to reflect on their own dissertations in terms of texture and structure, as well as provide guidance their students could benefit from. This guidance may also extend to more formal explicit guidance via assessment briefs, including but not limited to naming conventions of chapters, image use in dissertations as well as page design. For undergraduate students, the implications are less obvious as they are unlikely to read a whole EdD thesis, nor would I encourage them to do so. Perhaps a guidebook written specifically for architecture students would make texture and structure choices more explicit, as well as guide them in production of contextually-appropriate texts and engage in contextually-appropriate practices. This book has long been a goal of mine and something I hope to achieve one day.

Finally, there are some implications for research and researchers interested in specific contexts, texts, and practices. If you discover a gap in research and/or resources for an under-researched context and can go some way to filling this gap, please do so and share your findings, as they will have relevance and interest beyond your own context. And if you feel you can't fill the gap, encourage others to do so, perhaps through collaborative research with colleagues as an action research project, or research colleagues at other universities, or with discipline experts and/or students, e.g. collaborative autoethnography.

6.5 And finally

Fundamentally, we are all driven by our creativity and curiosity and throughout our lives 'architect' not only our texts but also our worlds. Applied Linguistics, Architecture and Education are all interdisciplinary at their core, and we can learn a lot from each other.

References

- A picture is worth a thousand words. (2024). In *Wikipedia*.
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=A_picture_is_worth_a_thousand_words&oldid=1262060941
- Abbott, G. (1980). Letter to the editor. In University of Malaya (Ed.), *The University of Malaya English for special purposes project: UMESPP*. British Council.
- Abdullaeva, M., Bromfield, J. J., & Sheldon, I. M. (2022). *Expansion of information in scientific research papers*. Scientific Communication and Education.
<https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.05.06.490896>
- About us*. (n.d.). The Conversation. Retrieved 10 November 2025, from
<https://theconversation.com/uk/who-we-are>
- Accurso, K. (2020). Bringing a social semiotic perspective to secondary teacher education in the United States. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 44, 100801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100801>
- Adzimah, E. C. (2021). *Genre analysis of undergraduate dissertation conclusions* [MPhil, University of the Cape Coast]. <http://hdl.handle.net/123456789/6478>
- Afful, J. B. A. (2016). A Genre Study of Undergraduate Dissertation Acknowledgements in a Ghanaian University. *ESP Today*, 4(2), 202–224.
<https://doi.org/10.18485/esptoday.2016.4.2.4>
- Alias, S. (2004). A semiotic study of Singapore's Orchard Road and Marriott Hotel. In K. L. O'Halloran (Ed.), *Multimodal discourse analysis: Systemic-functional perspectives*. Continuum.
- Alotaibi, H. S. (2020). The thematic structure in research article abstracts: Variations across disciplines. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 7(1), 1756146.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2020.1756146>
- Al-Reshaid, N., & Alhojailan, A. I. (2025). Stylistic Variations in Thematic Structure Across Academic Genres: A Case Study of EFL Graduate Students. *Educational Process International Journal*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.22521/edupij.2025.15.164>
- Alyousef, H. S. (2016). A multimodal discourse analysis of the textual and logical relations in marketing texts written by international undergraduate students. *Functional Linguistics*, 3(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40554-016-0025-1>
- Alyousef, H. S., & Alzahrani, A. A. (2020). A Functional Analysis of the Thematic Organization in Electrical Engineering Research Article Introductions Written in English By Native and Saudi Scholars: A Comparative Study. *Arab World English Journal*, 11(2).

- Anderson, T., Alexander, I., & Saunders, G. (2020). An examination of education-based dissertation macrostructures. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 45, 100845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2020.100845>
- Archer, A. (2010). Visual Dimensions of Academic Discourse in Higher Education. *Communitas*, 15, 57–71.
- Babaii, E., Kharazmi University, Tehran, Atai, M. R., Kharazmi University, Tehran, Shoja, L., & Kharazmi University, Tehran. (2016). A Comparison of Thematic Choices and Thematic Progression Patterns in the Research Articles of Well-established and Emerging Disciplines. *Iranian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 19(2), 33–60. <https://doi.org/10.29252/ijal.19.2.33>
- Bakaa, A. J. A. (2015). Functional Analysis of Marked and Unmarked Theme in Demonstrating a Critical Argument Written by Iraqi and Australian Postgraduate Students. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 5(2), 247. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.0502.03>
- BALEAP. (2026). *Map of Accredited Institutions*. <https://www.baleap.org/bas-accreditation/map-of-accredited-institutions>
- Barthes, R. (1977). *Image, music, text: Essays*. Fontana.
- Bartlett, T. (2017). Context in systemic functional linguistics: Towards scalar supervenience? In T. Bartlett, & G. O'Grady (Eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Systemic Functional Linguistics*. Routledge.
- BAS accreditation handbook v10a*. (2024, March 12). BALEAP. <https://www.baleap.org/downloads/bas/bas-accreditation-hbook-v10a.pdf>
- Bateman, J. (2014). *Text and image: A critical introduction to the visual/verbal divide*. Routledge.
- Bateman, J. (2017). The place of systemic functional linguistics as a linguistic theory in the twenty-first century. In T. Bartlett, & G. O'Grady (Eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Systemic Functional Linguistics*. Routledge.
- Bazerman, C., Little, J., Bethel, L., Chavkin, T., Fouquette, D., & Garufis, J. (2005). History of the WAC movement. *Reference Guide to Writing across the Curriculum*, 14–25.
- Belcher, D., & Hirvela, A. (2005). Writing the qualitative dissertation: What motivates and sustains commitment to a fuzzy genre? *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 4(3), 187–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2004.07.010>
- Bell, D. (2024). *English for Academic Purposes Perspectives on the Past, Present and Future*. Multilingual Matters.

- Ben-Rafael, E. (2009). A Sociological Approach to the study of linguistic landscapes. In E. Shohamy & D. Gorter (Eds), *A linguistic landscape: Expanding the scenery*. Routledge.
- Bernstein, D. (2021, July 15). Teaching language in the art & design studio. *BALEAP Creative Disciplines SIG Blog*.
<https://baleapcreativesig.wordpress.com/2021/07/15/mid-month-musings-4/>
- Bilikozen, N. (2015). *Academic literacy development and identity construction of undergraduates at an American university in the UAE*. University of Exeter.
- Bilotta, J. (2023). *Using multimodality to support culturally responsive learning and writing instruction in the college EAP classroom* [Rutgers University].
<https://doi.org/10.7282/T3-5NG5-TX34>
- Blue, G. (1988). Individualising academic writing tuition. In C. Robinson, Pauline (Ed.), *Academic Writing: Process and Product, ELT documents 129*. British Council.
- Borden, I., & Ruedi Ray, K. (2014). *The Dissertation: A Guide for Architecture Students* (Third). Routledge.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic Analysis*. Sage.
- Breban, T., Davidse, K., & Ghesquière, L. (2011). A typology of anaphoric and cataphoric relations expressed by English complex determiners. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 43(11), 2689–2703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2011.04.013>
- Broadbent, G. (1995). Architectural Education. In M. Pearce & M. Toy (Eds), *Educating architects*. Academy Editions.
- Brookhouse, S. (2013). *Professional Studies in Architecture. A Primer*. RIBA Publishing.
- Brown, J. D. (2016). *Introducing needs analysis and English for specific purposes*. Routledge.
- Bruce, I. (2015). *Theory and Concepts of English for Academic Purposes*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bunton, D. (1998). *Linguistic and Textual Problems in Ph.D and M.Phil Theses: An analysis of genre moves and metatext*. University of Hong Kong.
- Bunton, D. (2005). The structure of PhD conclusion chapters. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 4(3), 207–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2005.03.004>
- Burkhard, R. A. (2004). Learning from architects: the difference between knowledge visualization and information visualization. *Proceedings. Eighth International Conference on Information Visualisation, 2004. IV 2004.*, 519–524.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/IV.2004.1320194>

- Butt, D., Fahey, R., Feez, S., Spinks, S., & Yallop, C. (2000). *Using Functional Grammar An Explorer's Guide*. Macquarie University.
- Caballero, R. (2003). Metaphor and Genre: The Presence and Role of Metaphor in the Building Review. *Applied Linguistics*, 24(2), 145–167. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/24.2.145>
- Caballero, R. (2013). The Role of Metaphor in Architects' Negotiation and (Re)Construction of Knowledge Across Genres. *Metaphor and Symbol*, 28(1), 3–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10926488.2013.742840>
- Caballero Rodriguez, M. d. R. (2003). How to talk shop through metaphor: Bringing metaphor research to the ESP classroom. *English for Specific Purposes*, 22(2), 177–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(02\)00015-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(02)00015-7)
- CABE, U. C. for A. and the B. E. (2006). *The value handbook: Getting the most from your buildings and spaces*. CABE.
- Caldwell, E., & Gregory, J. (2016). Internationalizing the art school: What part does the studio have to play? *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 15(2), 117–133. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.15.2.117_1
- Carr, C., Maxwell, C., Rolinska, A., & Sizer, J. (2022). EAP teachers working in, with and through the creative arts: Reflections on a conference workshop aimed at exploring current practices. In M. Evans, A. Ding, & B. Bond (Eds), *Innovation, exploration and transformation – Proceedings of the 2019 BALEAP Conference*. Garnet.
- Carrell, P. L., & Carson, J. G. (1997). Extensive and intensive reading in an EAP setting. *English for Specific Purposes, English for Academic Purposes*, 16(1), 47–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(96\)00031-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(96)00031-2)
- Chan, S., Khabbazbashi, N., & Clark, T. (2025). Embracing Multimodality to Overhaul Assessment of English for Academic Purposes: Task Design and Validation. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 22(4–5), 460–483. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2025.2605207>
- Chappell, D. A. (2016). *The Architect in Practice*. John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.
- Chappell, D. A. (2020). *Professional Practice for Architects and Project Managers*. John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.
- Charles, M., & Pecorari, D. (2015). *Introducing English for Academic Purposes*. Taylor and Francis.
- Choe, H., & Hyun Hwang, B. (2014). A Genre Analysis of Introductions in Theses, Dissertations and Research Articles Based on Swales' CARS Model. *Korean Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 30(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.17154/kjal.2014.03.30.1.3>

- Christoforou, M. (2025). Gen AI-assisted multimodal meaning *Design*: Exercising a pedagogic metalanguage of transposition. *Pedagogies: An International Journal*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1554480X.2025.2522884>
- Cold, B. (1995). Tree of the sketch. In M. Pearce & M. Toy (Eds), *Educating architects*. Academy Editions.
- Collins, H., & Holliday, A. (2022). Ethnography: Expanding the boundaries in EAP. In A. Ding & M. Evans (Eds), *Social Theory for English for Academic Purposes*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Cook, G. (2015). Birds out of Dinosaurs: The Death and Life of Applied Linguistics. *Applied Linguistics*, 36(4), 425–433. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amv038>
- Copland, F., & Creese, A. (2015). *Balancing the Micro and the Macro*.
- Cowley-Haselden, S., McElveny, G., Pemberton, I., Prentice, N., Rodrigues, S., Sharpling, N., & Tilley, C. (Eds). (2025). Vol. 1 No. 1 (2025): Caution! EAP under DEconstruction: Proceedings from the 2023 biennial conference. In *Caution! EAP under DEconstruction: Proceedings from the 2023 biennial conference*. BALEAP Journal of Research and Practice. <https://journals.warwick.ac.uk/index.php/baleap/issue/view/114>
- Coxhead, A. (2011). The Academic Word List 10 Years On: Research and Teaching Implications. *TESOL Quarterly*, 45(2), 355–362. <https://doi.org/10.5054/tq.2011.254528>
- Creaton, J. (2015). Marking the boundaries: Knowledge and identity in professional doctorates. In T. Lillis, K. Harrington, M. R. ; Lea, & S. Mitchell (Eds), *Working with Academic Literacies*. Parlor Press.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (Sixth edition,). Sage.
- Crystal, D. (1968). *What Is Linguistics?* Edward Arnold.
- Daly, A., & Unsworth, L. (2011). Analysis and comprehension of multimodal text. *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 34(1), 61–80.
- Damron, R., & Spector, T. (2010). Writing by Design, Design by Writing. In B. Goodwin & J. Kinnard (Eds), *Rebuilding*. ACSA.
- Dannels, D. P. (2016). *Communication Education Performing Tribal Rituals: A Genre Analysis of "Crits" in Design Studios*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634520500213165>
- Day, K. M., Deamer, P., Dietz, A., Forde, T., Garcia Fritz, J., Geraki, P., & Lechêne, V. (with Dagnino, R.). (2024). *The organizer's guide to architecture education*. Routledge.

- De Oliveira, L. C., & Lan, S.-W. (2014). Writing science in an upper elementary classroom: A genre-based approach to teaching English language learners. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 25, 23–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2014.05.001>
- Devira, M., Isda, I. D., Purwati, Baihaqi, & Firman. (2021). A Structural Move Analysis in the Introduction Section of Indonesian EFL Undergraduate. *Proceedings of the 11th Annual International Conference (AIC) on Social Science*. 11th Annual International Conference (AIC) on Social Science.
- Dias, P., Freedman, A., Medway, P., & Pare, A. (1999). *Worlds Apart*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410602336>
- Dimovski, V. (2011). An Approach to Avant-Garde Manifestoes. In S. V. Maltseva & E. Stanyukovich-Denisova (Eds), *Actual Problems of Theory and History of Art* (pp. 353–359). Izdatel'stvo Sankt-Peterburgskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta.
- Ding, A., & Bruce, I. (2017). *The English for Academic Purposes Practitioner: Operating on the Edge of Academia*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59737-9>
- Dobson, A. (2014). *21 things you won't learn in architecture school*. RIBA Publishing.
- Doloughan, F. J. (2002). The Language of Reflective Practice in Art and Design. *Design Issues*, 18(2), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.1162/074793602317355783>
- Dörnyei, Z. (1990). Conceptualizing Motivation in Foreign-Language Learning*. *Language Learning*, 40(1), 45–78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-1770.1990.tb00954.x>
- Dudley-Evans, T. (1999). The Dissertation: A Case of Neglect? In P. Thompson (Ed.), *Issues in EAP Writing Research and Instruction*. Antony Rowe Limited.
- Dudley-Evans, T., & St John, M.-J. (2003). *Developments in ESP: A multi-disciplinary approach*. Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Ebrahimi, S. F., & Ebrahimi, S. J. (2012). Markedness in Writing: A Case of EFL Students. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 2(4), 773–777. <https://doi.org/10.4304/tpls.2.4.773-777>
- Egins, S. (2004). *An Introduction to Systemic Functional Linguistics*. Continuum International Publishing.
- Elapatha, N. (2025, March 8). Reading: 'International students keep universities running'. *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c62zvdz6mn4o>
- El-Sayed, Y. M. (2018). Text-Image Relations in Print Advertisement: A Multimodal Discourse Analysis. *Egyptian Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 9(1), 543–605. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejels.2018.134103>

- Fallin, L., & Bartram, J. (2026). *Help, It's Not an Essay! A guide to multimodal assignments using text, visuals and spoken words*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Feak, C. B., & Salehzadeh, J. (2001). Challenges and issues in developing an EAP video listening placement assessment: A view from one program. *English for Specific Purposes*, 20, 477–493. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00021-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00021-7)
- Ferguson, G. (1997). *Teacher education for languages for specific purposes* (R. Howard & Gillian. Brown, Eds). Multilingual Matters.
- Firth, J. R. (1957). *Papers in Linguistics 1934-1951*. Oxford University Press.
- Firth, J. R. (1968). *Selected papers of J.R. Firth 19* (F. R. Palmer, Ed.). Longmans.
- Fitzgerald, A., Mansfield, C., & Wu, S. (2017). *EThOS for EAP: The PhD Abstracts Collections in FLAX with the British Library Electronic Thesis Online Service*. BALEAP Biennial Conference 2017. Addressing the State of the Union: Working Together, Learning Together.
- Flowerdew, J., & Miller, L. (1997). The teaching of academic listening comprehension and the question of authenticity. *English for Specific Purposes, English for Academic Purposes*, 16(1), 27–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(96\)00030-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(96)00030-0)
- Flowerdew, J., & Peacock, M. (2001). In *Research perspectives on English for academic purposes*. Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Flowerdew, L. (2025). Needs Analysis and Curriculum Development in ESP. In S. Starfield & C. A. Hafner (Eds), *The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes* (pp. 129–148). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119985068.ch7>
- Flynn, P., O'Connor, M., Price, M., & Dunn, M. (Eds). (2023). *Rethinking the crit*. Routledge.
- Forty, A. (2004). *Words and buildings: A vocabulary of modern architecture*. Thames & Hudson.
- Frederick, M. (2007). *101 things I learned in architecture school*. MIT Press.
- FutureLearn. (2025). *Writing in English for University—Online Course*. FutureLearn. <https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/english-for-study>
- Galante, A., & Thomson, R. I. (2017). The Effectiveness of Drama as an Instructional Approach for the Development of Second Language Oral Fluency, Comprehensibility, and Accentedness. *TESOL Quarterly*, 51(1), 115–142. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.290>
- Gardner, S. (2012). Genres and registers of student report writing: An SFL perspective on texts and practices. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 11(1), 52–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2011.11.002>

- Gardner, S., & Donohue, J. (2020). Introduction to the special collection: Halliday's influence on EAP practice. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 44, 100831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100831>
- Garnet Education. (2019). *Category: ESAP Series | Garnet Education*. <https://www.garneteducation.com/category/english-for-specific-academic-purposes/esap-series/>
- General Instructions | BJR|Open | Oxford Academic*. (2025). British Journal of Radiology. <https://academic.oup.com/bjro/pages/general-instructions>
- Ghadessy, M. (1999). Thematic organisation in academic article abstracts. *Estudios Ingleses de La Universidad Complutense*, 7, 141–161.
- Gillet, A. (n.d.-a). Materials: Introduction – UEfAP. *UEfAP*. Retrieved 11 November 2025, from <https://www.uefap.org/materials-introduction-2/>
- Gillet, A. (n.d.-b). *Writing Genre Theses – UEfAP*. UEfAP.Net. Retrieved 8 November 2025, from <https://www.uefap.org/writing-genre-theses/>
- Gillet, A. (2025). Grammar in EAP. *UEFAP*. <https://www.uefap.org/grammar-sfl/>
- Gledhill, C. (2000). The discourse function of collocation in research article introductions. *English for Specific Purposes*, 19(2), 115–135. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(98\)00015-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(98)00015-5)
- Governance News Alert: HESA enrolment data 2023/24 | Advance HE*. (n.d.). Retrieved 11 November 2025, from <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/knowledge-hub/governance-news-alert-hesa-enrolment-data-202324>
- Gregory, H. (2019, January 16). Volumes of words: The architecture of the page. *The Architectural Review*. <https://www.architectural-review.com/essays/volumes-of-words-the-architecture-of-the-page>
- Guillen-Galve, I., & Bocanegra-Valle, A. (Eds). (2021). *Ethnographies of Academic Writing Research*. John Benjamins.
- Gunawan, W., & Aziza, F. (2017). THEME AND THEMATIC PROGRESSION OF UNDERGRADUATE THESIS: INVESTIGATING MEANING MAKING IN ACADEMIC WRITING. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 7(2), 175. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v7i2.8350>
- Haji, G. (2024). Exploring Thematic Progression of EFL Students' Argumentative essays. *Ebony - Journal of English Language Teaching, Linguistics, and Literature*, 4(2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.37304/ebony.v4i2.13676>
- Hakim, A. (2023). Genre-related episodes: A tutorial for L2 writing teachers. *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*, 2(3), 100071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmal.2023.100071>

- Halliday, M. A. K. (1961). Categories of the Theory of Grammar. *WORD*, 17(2), 241–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00437956.1961.11659756>
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1979). *Language as social semiotic*. Routledge.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1994). Language as Social Semiotic. In J. Maybin (Ed.), *Language and literacy in social practice: A reader* (p. 271). Multilingual Matters Ltd. in association with the Open University.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1999). The notion of ‘context’ in language education. In M. Ghadessy (Ed.), *Text and Context in Functional Linguistics* (p. 340). J. Benjamins.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Hasan, R. (1976). *Cohesion in English*. Longman Group.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Martin, J. R. (2003). *Writing Science: Literacy And Discursive Power*. Taylor and Francis.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. M. I. M. (2014). *Halliday’s introduction to functional grammar* (4th edition). Routledge.
- Hammersley, M. (1994). Introducing ethnography. In D. Graddol, J. Maybin, & B. Stierer (Eds), *Researching Language and Literacy in Social Context: A Reader*. Multilingual Matters Ltd.
- Hammond, S. P., & Cooper, N. J. (2011). Participant information clips: A role for digital video technologies to recruit, inform and debrief research participants and disseminate research findings. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 14(4), 259–270. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2010.530029>
- Hanh, N. T. (2021). An Investigation on Thematic Patterns and Progression in Two Short Stories. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(6).
- Hao, J., & Humphrey, S. L. (2019). Reading nominalizations in senior science. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 42, 100793. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100793>
- Hardy, J. A., & Friginal, E. (2016). Genre variation in student writing: A multi-dimensional analysis. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 22, 119–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEAP.2016.03.002>
- Hartwick, J., & Barki, H. (1994). Research Report-Hypothesis Testing and Hypothesis Generating Research: An Example from the User Participation Literature. *Information Systems Research*, 5(4), 446. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.5.4.446>
- Hasan, R. (1998). Part B Ruqaiya Hasan. In M. A. K. Halliday (Ed.), *Language, context, and text: Aspects of language in a social-semiotic perspective* (Reprinted with corrections). Deakin University Press.

- Hasan, R. (2009). The place of context in a systemic functional model. In M. A. K. Halliday & J. J. Webster (Eds), *Continuum Companion to Systemic Functional Linguistics*. Continuum International Publishing.
- Hawes, T., & Thomas, S. (1997). Problems of Thematisation in Student Writing. *RELC Journal*, 28(2), 35–55. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003368829702800203>
- Hawes, T., & Thomas, S. (2012). Theme choice in EAP and media language. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 11(3), 175–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2012.04.005>
- Healey, M., Lannin, L., Stibbe, A., & Derounian, J. (2013). *Developing and enhancing undergraduate final-year projects and dissertations*. Higher Education Academy. <https://advance-he.ac.uk/knowledge-hub/developing-and-enhancing-undergraduate-final-year-projects-and-dissertations>
- Heidenreich, S. (2016). *Englisch für Architekten und Bauingenieure—English for Architects and Civil Engineers: Ein kompletter Projektablauf auf Englisch mit Vokabeln, Redewendungen, Übungen und Praxistipps—All project phases in English with vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, exercises and practical advice*. Springer.
- Hellwig, A. F. J., Jones, P. T., Matruglio, E., & Georgiou, H. (2022). Multimodality and English for Special Purposes: Signification and Transduction in Architecture and Civil Engineering Models. *Frontiers in Communication*, 7(901719.). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2022.901719>
- Henry, J. (2019). ‘From doing to being: Process type as indication of purpose in academic business reports’. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 42, 100778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100778>
- Heuboeck, A., Holmes, J., & Nesi, Hilary. (2019). *BAWE Corpus Manual v.III*. Coventry University. <https://www.coventry.ac.uk/globalassets/media/global/05-research-section-assets/research/british-academic-written-english-corpus-bawe/microsoft-word-bawemanual-v3--bawemanual-v3.pdf>
- Hewings, A. (2004). Developing discipline-specific writing: An analysis of undergraduate geography essays. In *Analysing Academic Writing: Contextualized Frameworks*. Bloomsbury Academic. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781474211741>
- Hewings, A., & North, S. (2009). Emergent disciplinarity: A comparative study of Theme in undergraduate essays in geography and history of science. In R. Whittaker, A. McCabe, & M. O’Donnell (Eds), *Language and Literacy: Functional Approaches*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Hill, P., Tinker, A., & Catterall, S. (2010). From Deficiency to Development: The evolution of academic skills provision at one UK university. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, (2). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.v0i2.54>

- Hsu, W. (2011). A Business Word List for Prospective EFL Business Postgraduates. *The Asian ESP Journal*, 7(4), 63–99.
- Huettner, J. (2010). The Potential of Purpose-Built Corpora in the Analysis of Student Academic Writing in English. *Journal of Writing Research*, 2(2), 197–218. <https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2010.02.02.6>
- Hůlková, I., Dontcheva-Navratilova, O., Jančaříková, R., & Schmied, J. (2019). Intercultural variation in academic discourse: Theme zones and the build-up of coherence in research articles. *Topics in Linguistics*, 20(2), 33–53. <https://doi.org/10.2478/topling-2019-0008>
- Hung, H.-T. (2017). Design-Based Research: Redesign of an English Language Course Using a Flipped Classroom Approach. *TESOL Quarterly*, 51(1), 180–192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.328>
- Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. (2008). *English for specific purposes: A learning-centered approach* (23. printing). Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Hyland, K. (1994). Hedging in academic writing and EAF textbooks. *English for Specific Purposes*, 13(3), 239–256. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906\(94\)90004-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906(94)90004-3)
- Hyland, K. (2002a). Authority and invisibility: Authorial identity in academic writing. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 34, 1091–1112.
- Hyland, K. (2002b). Specificity Revisited: How Far Should we Go Now? *English for Specific Purposes*, 21, 385–395. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00028-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00028-X)
- Hyland, K. (2004). *Genre and Second Language Writing*. University of Michigan Press. <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/portsmouth-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3570463>
- Hyland, K. (2006). The ‘ Other ’ English: Thoughts on EAP and Academic Writing. *The European English Messenger*, 2(15), 34–88.
- Hyland, K. (2012). Undergraduate Understandings: Stance and Voice in Final Year Reports. In K. Hyland & C. Sancho Guinda (Eds), *Stance and voice in written academic genres*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hyland, K. (2017). English in the disciplines: Arguments for specificity. *ESP Today*, 5(1), 5–23. <https://doi.org/10.18485/esptoday.2017.5.1.1>
- Hymes, D. (1964). Introduction: Toward Ethnographies of Communication. *American Anthropologist*, 66(6), 1–34.
- Hyon, S. (2001). Long-term effects of genre-based instruction: A follow-up study of an EAP reading course. *English for Specific Purposes*, 20, 417–438. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00019-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00019-9)

- Indrian, R. D., & Ardi, P. (2019). Rhetorical Structures of English-Major Undergraduate Thesis Introduction Chapters. *Indonesian Journal of EFL and Linguistics*, 4(2), 195. <https://doi.org/10.21462/ijefl.v4i2.166>
- Jalilifar, A., Alipour, M., & Rabiee, M. (2017). A Comparative Study of Thematicity in the Argumentative Writing of University EFL Students and the Introduction Section of Research Articles. *Journal of Teaching Language Skills*, 36(1). <https://doi.org/10.22099/jtls.2017.4043>
- Jencks, C., & Kropf, K. (1997). *Theories and manifestoes of contemporary architecture*. Academy ed.
- Jiang, F. K., & Hyland, K. (2026). EAP in a changing world: Towards a new research agenda. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 80, 101647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2026.101647>
- Johns, A. M. (2015). Balancing “Just in Case” with “Just in Time” Learning in the Teaching of Eap Writing, Reflecting, and Critical Thinking. *The Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 3(1), 1–8.
- Jordan, R. R. (1997). *English for Academic Purposes*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jordan, R. R. (2002). The growth of EAP in Britain. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 1, 69–78.
- Kahu, S. Y., Ingram, W. A., Fox, E. A., & Wu, J. (2021). *ScanBank: A Benchmark Dataset for Figure Extraction from Scanned Electronic Theses and Dissertations* (arXiv:2106.15320). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.15320>
- Kara, H. (2015). *Creative research methods in the social sciences*. Policy Press.
- Kaur, R. (2017). *The sun and her flowers*. Simon & Schuster.
- Khaflan, M., Irshad, S., & Khawar, Z. (2021). Theme-Rheme Analysis: Exploring the Thematic Structure of Edgar Allan Poe’s Dream-Themed Poems. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 4(1), 35–48. <https://doi.org/10.37605/pjhssr.v4i1.67>
- Khusainova, R., Sholl, S., & Harte, P. (2025, July 14). Is the dissertation dead? If so, what are the alternatives? | THE Campus Learn, Share, Connect. *Times Higher Education*. <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/dissertation-dead-if-so-what-are-alternatives>
- Kress, G. R., & Leeuwen, T. van. (2010). *Reading images: The grammar of visual design* (2. ed.,). Routledge.
- Kress, G., & Van Leeuwen, T. (2002). Colour as a semiotic mode: Notes for a grammar of colour. *Visual Communication*, 1(3), 343–368. <https://doi.org/10.1177/147035720200100306>

- Kuh, G. D., & Whitt, E. J. (1988). *The Invisible Tapestry. Culture in American Colleges and Universities* (p. 124). Association for the Study of Higher Education.; Canadian Association of Univ. Teachers, Ottawa (Ontario). <https://doi.org/ISBN-0-913317-45-4>
- Lai, H. (2018). Image-text Relations in Junior High School EFL Textbooks in China: A Mixed-methods Study. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 9(6), 1177. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0906.07>
- Lasserre, B. (2012). Speaking the critique in graphic design: The role of metaphor. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 10(1), 51–66. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.10.1.51_1
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lea, M. R., & Street, B. V. (2006). The Academic Literacies Model: Theory and Applications. *Theory into Practice*, 45(4), 368–377.
- Leong, A. P., Toh, A. L. L., & Chin, S. F. (2018). Examining Structure in Scientific Research Articles: A Study of Thematic Progression and Thematic Density. *Written Communication*, 35(3), 286–314. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088318767378>
- Lewkowicz, J. (2009). Concluding Your Master's Level Thesis. *Revista Canaria de Estudios Ingleses*, 59, 63–72.
- Lillis, T. (2001). *Student writing: Access, regulation, desire*. Routledge.
- Lillis, T. (2003). Student Writing as 'Academic Literacies': Drawing on Bakhtin to Move from Critique to Design. *Language and Education*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500780308666848>
- Lillis, T. (2008). Ethnography as method, methodology, and 'deep theorizing' Closing the gap between text and context in academic writing research. *Written Communication*, 25(3), 353–388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088308319229>
- Loghmani, Z., Ghonsooly, B., & Ghazanfari, M. (2020). Engagement in doctoral dissertation discussion sections written by English native speakers. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 45, 100851. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2020.100851>
- Love, A. M. (1991). Process and product in geology: An investigation of some discourse features of two introductory textbooks. *English for Specific Purposes*, 10(2), 89–109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906\(91\)90003-F](https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906(91)90003-F)
- Ma, T. (2009). On Communicative Language Teaching—Theoretical Foundations and Principles. *Asian Social Science*, 5(4), p40. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v5n4p40>
- MacDonald, S. (1994). *Professional academic writing in the humanities and social sciences*. Southern Illinois University Press.

- Malinowski, B. (1923). The problem of meaning in primitive languages. In C. K. Ogden & I. A. Richards, (Eds), *The meaning of meaning*. Harvest Book.
- Malinowski, B. (2003). The problem of meaning in primitive languages. In J. Maybin (Ed.), *Language and Literacy in Social Practice: A Reader*. Multilingual Matters.
- Manar, M., Wachidah, S., & Dewanti, R. (2020). Actor and Goal Representation in the Transitivity System of Undergraduate Theses and Journal Research Articles: An SFL Perspective. *Loquen: English Studies Journal*, 13(2), 88.
<https://doi.org/10.32678/loquen.v13i2.2111>
- Martin, J. R. (1984). Language, register and genre. In F. Christie (Ed.), *Children's Writing: Reader* (pp. 21–29). Deakin University Press.
- Martin, J. R. (1992). Genre and Literacy-Modeling Context in Educational Linguistics. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 13, 141–172.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190500002440>
- Martin, J., R. (1994). Modelling big texts: A systemic functional approach to multi-genericity. *Network*, 21.
- Martin, J. R., & Rose, D. (2007). *Working with discourse: Meaning beyond the clause*. Continuum.
- Martin, J. R., & White, P. R. R. (2007). *The language of evaluation: Appraisal in English*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Martinec, R., & Salway, A. (2005). A system for image-text relations in new (and old) media. *Visual Communication*, 4(3), 337–371.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1470357205055928>
- Massey, A. (2025). *Writing and publishing in architecture and design*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- McCabe, A. M. (1999). *Theme and Thematic Patterns in Spanish and English History Texts* [Aston University]. <http://www.isfla.org/Systemics/Print/Theses/McCabephd.pdf>
- McMurtrie, R. J. (2011). The meaning of [exiting]: Towards a grammaticalization of architecture. *Text & Talk - An Interdisciplinary Journal of Language, Discourse & Communication Studies*, 31(6), 705–731. <https://doi.org/10.1515/text.2011.034>
- Medway, P. (1996). Writing, Speaking, Drawing: The Distribution of Meaning in Architects' Communication. In *The New Writing Environment* (pp. 25–42). Springer London. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-1482-6_3
- Medway, P. (2002). Fuzzy Genres and Community Identities: The case of Architecture Students' Sketchbooks. In R. Coe, L. Lingard, & T. Teselenko (Eds), *The Rhetoric and Ideology of Genre*. Hampton Press.

- Medway, P. (2003). Imagining the building: Architectural design as semiotic construction. *Design Studies*, 24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X\(02\)00055-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X(02)00055-8)
- Medway, P., & Clark, B. (2003). Imagining the building: Architectural design as semiotic construction. *Design Studies, Designing in Context*, 24(3), 255–273. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X\(02\)00055-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X(02)00055-8)
- Mellow, J. D. (2002). Toward Principled Eclecticism in Language Teaching: The Two-Dimensional Model and the Centring Principle. *TESL - EJ*, 5(4).
- Mewburn, I. (2012). Lost in translation: Reconsidering reflective practice and design studio pedagogy. *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education*, 11(4), 363–379. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022210393912>
- Mey, K. (2013). The gesture of writing. In *Thinking Through Art Reflections on Art as Research* (pp. 217–228). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203819869-25>
- Monbec, L. (2020). Systemic Functional Linguistics for the EGAP module: Revisiting the common core. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 43, 100794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100794>
- Monbec, L. (2022, June 29). Systemic Functional Linguistics for the self-taught – Part 1. *BALEAP Research and Publications Blog*. <https://research.baleap.org/2022/06/29/systemic-functional-linguistics-for-the-self-taught-part-1/>
- Montgomery, S. (2021). Dissertations in Fine Art. In M. Whong & J. Godfrey (Eds), *What is good academic writing? Insights into discipline-specific student writing*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Morecambe, E. (1971, December 25). *The Morecambe & Wise Show [Television special]* [TV]. BBC.
- Morton, J. (2012). Communities of practice in higher education: A challenge from the discipline of architecture. *Linguistics and Education*, 23(1), 100–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LINGED.2011.04.002>
- Morton, J. (2016). ‘Adjacent worlds’: An analysis of a genre at the intersection of academic and professional communities. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 22, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEAP.2016.01.003>
- Motta-Roth, D., & Heberle, V. M. (2015). A short cartography of genre studies in Brazil. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 19, 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEAP.2015.05.006>
- Naoum, S. (2013). *Dissertation research & writing for construction students* (Third). Routledge.
- Nesi, H., & Gardner, S. (2012). *Genres across the Disciplines*. Cambridge University Press.

- Nesi, H., & Gardner, S. (2017). Stance in the BAWE Corpus: New Revelations from Multidimensional Analysis. *Proceedings 9th International Corpus Linguistics Conference, Birmingham University July 24-28 2017*. International Corpus Linguistics Conference,.
- NESTA. (2006). *Creating growth How the UK can develop world class creative businesses. Research report*.
https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/creating_growth.pdf
- Newman, D. (2024, April 1). *The Squiggle*. The Squiggle.
<https://thedesignsquiggle.com/>
- Norris, J. M., & Ortega, L. (2007). The Future of Research Synthesis in Applied Linguistics: Beyond Art or Science. *TESOL Quarterly*, 41(4), 805–815.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1545-7249.2007.tb00105.x>
- North, S. (2005). Disciplinary Variation in the Use of Theme in Undergraduate Essays. *Applied Linguistics*, 26(3), 431–452. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/ami023>
- Nunan, D. (2000). *The learner-centred curriculum*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nwogu, K., & Bloor, T. (2011). Thematic progression in professional and popular medical texts. In E. Ventola (Ed.), *Functional and Systemic Linguistics: Approaches and Uses*. Mouton de Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110883527>
- Obrist, H. U. (2010). Manifestos for the Future. *E-Flux*, 12.
- Oechslin, W., & Wang, W. (1987). Les Cinq Points d'une Architecture Nouvelle. *Assemblage*, 4, 82–93. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3171037>
- Ortega, L. (2005). Methodology, Epistemology, and Ethics in Instructed SLA Research: An Introduction. *The Modern Language Journal*, 89(3).
- O'Toole, M. (2004). Opera Ludentes: The Sydney Opera House at work and play. In K. L. O'Halloran (Ed.), *Multimodal discourse analysis: Systemic-functional perspectives*. Continuum.
- O'Toole, M. (2011). *The language of displayed art*. Routledge.
- Paltridge, B. (1997). Thesis and dissertation writing: Preparing ESL students for research. *English for Specific Purposes, English for Academic Purposes*, 16(1), 61–70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(96\)00028-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(96)00028-2)
- Paltridge, B. (2002). Thesis and dissertation writing: An examination of published advice and actual practice. *English for Specific Purposes*, 21(2), 125–143.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(00\)00025-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(00)00025-9)
- Paltridge, B. (2004). The exegesis as a genre: An ethnographic examination. In L. ; Ravelli & R. A. Ellis (Eds), *Analysing Academic Writing*.

- Paltridge, B., & Starfield, S. (2024). *Change and Stability in Thesis and Dissertation Writing*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Paltridge, B., Starfield, S., & Tardy, C. M. (2016). *Ethnographic Perspectives on Academic Writing*. Oxford University Press.
- Pang, K. M. A. (2004). Making history in From Colony to Nation: A multimodal analysis of a museum exhibition in Singapore. In K. L. O'Halloran (Ed.), *Multimodal discourse analysis: Systemic-functional perspectives*. Continuum.
- Parkinson, J., Demecheleer, M., & Mackay, J. (2017). Writing like a builder: Acquiring a professional genre in a pedagogical setting. *English for Specific Purposes*, 46, 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESP.2016.12.003>
- Parnell, R., & Sara, R. (2007). *The Crit: An Architecture Student's Handbook*. Routledge.
- Parnell, S. (2023). Slow Media: Architecture histories of, from, and through architecture magazines. *Charrette*, 9(2), 7–30.
- Patkin, J. (2025). *Transcription in the Research Process* [PhD by publication, University of Portsmouth].
<https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/transcription-in-the-research-process/>
- Pearce, M., & Toy, M. (Eds). (1995). *Educating architects*. Academy Editions.
- Pecorari, D., & Coxhead, A. (2026). *Introducing English for Academic Purposes* (Second edition). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003473138>
- Perks, S., & Whittingham, N. (2017). Timelines in design: Where linguistics meets design history. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 16(1), 23–32. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.16.1.23_1
- Pham, L. T. T., & Vu, T. N. (2024). *Rhetorical structure of introduction chapter in Vietnamese English-majored undergraduate's theses*. 15(4), 144–153. <https://doi.org/10.46223/HCMCOUJS>
- Pink, S. (2012). The visual in ethnography: Photography, videos, cultures and individuals. In J. Hughes (Ed.), *SAGE visual methods*. Sage Publication.
- Pink, S. (2013). *Doing visual ethnography*. Sage Publications.
- Priangan, A., Saleh, M., & Rukmini, D. (2020). Cohesion and Coherence in Undergraduate Students' Argumentative Essays. *English Education Journal*, 10(1).
- Price, C., & Archer, A. (2021). Risk as productive in landscape architecture pedagogy. *Perspectives in Education*, 39(2), 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.18820/2519593X/pie.v39.i2.11>

Purser, E., Dreyfus, S., & Jones, P. (2020). Big ideas & sharp focus: Researching and developing students' academic writing across the disciplines. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 43, 100807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100807>

Raimes, A. (1991). Instruction Balance: From theories to practices in the teaching of writing. In *Georgetown University Round Table on Languages and Linguistics (GURT) 1991*. Georgetown University Press.

Rampton, B., Maybin, J., & Roberts, C. (2015). Theory and Method in Linguistic Ethnography. In S. Shaw, F. Copland, & J. Snell (Eds), *Linguistic Ethnography* (pp. 14–50). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137035035_2

Rass, R. A., & Portman, D. (2024). Towards Coherence: An Analysis of the Theme in the Writing of Arab Efl Students. *Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 12(1), 231. <https://doi.org/10.22190/JTESAP240228019R>

Ravelli, L. J. (2011). Analysing Space: Adapting and Extending Multimodal Frameworks. In C. Coffin, J. Connelly, B. Derewianka, S. Feez, E. Djonov, P. Jones, J. Knox, & K. Love (Eds), *Multimodal semiotics: Functional analysis in contexts of education*. Bloomsbury.

Ravelli, L. J., & Stenglin, M. (2008). Feeling space: Interpersonal communication and spatial semiotics. In G. Antos & E. Ventola (Eds), *Handbook of Interpersonal Communication*. De Gruyter, Inc.

RIBA. (2021). *Report of the RIBA Full Visiting Board to the University of Portsmouth*. RIBA: Royal Institute of British Architects.

https://www.riba.org/media/il1p2nxu/univ_of_portsmouth_riba_report_2021.pdf?rev=16a2622951f6487f9c27621ab2f62036&hash=73594B32357DF8B1863AFF60626280B

RIBA Plan of Work. (2020). <https://www.riba.org/work/insights-and-resources/riba-plan-of-work/>

Riley-Jones, G. (2012). Critical thinking as an embodied criticality: The lived experiences of international art students. *Journal of Writing in Creative Practice*, 5(3), 401–421. https://doi.org/10.1386/jwcp.5.3.401_1

Riley-Jones, G. (2017). *There is a disease, and it's called Goldsmiths*. BALEAP 2017 conference.

Roehrich, L. W. (2013). *A Word is Worth a Thousand Pictures: A Systemic Functional and Multimodal Discourse Analysis of Intersemiotic Evaluation in University Science Textbooks*. Marshall University.

Sajeedin, Md. S. (2024). *SAJEEDIN-THESIS-2024 RAs Theme [MA]*. University of Saskatchewan.

- Salimi, E. A., Mirian, E. S., & Younesi, J. (2022). Anxiety level of mastery and performance avoid goal oriented EAP learners: The effect of teacher supportive motivational discourse. *Learning and Motivation*, 78, 101809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lmot.2022.101809>
- Salway, A., & Martinec, R. (2005). Some ideas for modelling image-text combinations. *Department of Computing, University of Surrey*.
- Sara, R. (2023). Viva co-disegno (Living co-design). In P. Flynn, M. O'Connor, M. Price, & M. Dunn (Eds), *Rethinking the crit*. Routledge.
- Savignon, S. J. (1991). Communicative Language Teaching: State of the Art. *TESOL Quarterly*, 25(2), 261. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3587463>
- Schön, D. A. (1988). Toward a Marriage of Artistry & Applied Science in the Architectural Design Studio. *Journal of Architectural Education*, 41(4), 4–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10464883.1988.10758496>
- Schön, D. A. (1991). *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. Basic Books. <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com>
- Schöpfel, J., Prost, H., Malleret, C., Južnič, P., Češarek, A., & Koler-Povh, T. (2016). Dissertations and Data. *The Grey Journal*, 12(3). <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/78382766.pdf>
- Schriver, K. A. (1997). *Dynamics in document design: Creating texts for readers*. Wiley.
- Schug, D. (2022). English for Other Languages: A Needs Analysis of Future Polyglots at a French University. *Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 9(4), 715–724. <https://doi.org/10.22190/JTESAP2104715S>
- Scollon, R., & Scollon Wong, S. (2003). *Discourses in Place: Language in the Material World*. Routledge.
- Sealey, A., & Carter, B. (2004). *Applied Linguistics as Social Science*. Continuum.
- Serafini, E. J., Lake, J. B., & Long, M. H. (2015). Needs analysis for specialized learner populations: Essential methodological improvements. *English for Specific Purposes*, 40, 11–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2015.05.002>
- Sizer, J. (2019a). Is teaching EAP a profession? A reflection on EAP's professional status, values, community and knowledge. *Professional and Academic English*, June(52), 1–44.
- Sizer, J. (2019b). Textography as a needs analysis and research tool for English for Academic Purposes and learning development practitioners. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, (15). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.v0i15.554>

- Sizer, J. (2019c). *Unobtrusive textography of a university building as an innovative research method*. BALEAP 2019 conference.
- Sizer, J. (Director). (2020, July 9). *Research Participant Information Clip* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eDWvb70umfs>
- Sizer, J. (2021). Textography: Narrowing the gap between text and context in ethnographic explorations of situated academic writing. In I. Guillen-Galve & A. Bocanegra-Valle (Eds), *Ethnographies of Academic Writing Research*. John Benjamins.
- Sizer, J. (2024). *Consent form: Staff interview*. Google Docs. https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdqbvoe6CrUWsB5gHgM3fPfOcQh_Zy3PZ0jHbVU62fF6gNlkg/viewform?usp=drive_web&usp=embed_facebook
- Sizer, J. (2025). *Challenges and Benefits of Combining Textual Analysis and Ethnographic Methods to Explore Educational Contexts, Texts, and Practices*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781036221812>
- Smith, S. (2020). *Thesis/dissertation*. EAPFoundation.Com. <https://www.eapfoundation.com/writing/other/dissertation/>
- Smotrova, T. (2017). Making Pronunciation Visible: Gesture In Teaching Pronunciation. *TESOL Quarterly*, 51(1), 59–89. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.276>
- Smyth, P., & Carless, D. (2021). Theorising how teachers manage the use of exemplars: Towards mediated learning from exemplars. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 46(3), 393–406. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2020.1781785>
- Smyth, P. D. (2019). *How teachers manage exemplar use: A grounded theory of English for academic purposes teachers* (p. 991044166489803414) [Doctor of Education, The University of Hong Kong]. https://doi.org/10.5353/th_991044166489803414
- Spector, T., & Damron, R. L. (2017). *How architects write* (Second edition). Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Stenglin, M., & Cléirigh, C. (2020). Scientific grant application writing: Re/packaging text to enhance its impact. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 44, 100823. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2019.100823>
- Stenglin, M. K. (2004). *Packaging curiosities: Towards a grammar of three-dimensional space* [Doctor of Philosophy]. University of Sydney.
- Stöckl, H. (2004). In between modes: Language and image in printed media. In E. Ventola, C. Charles, & M. Kaltenbacher (Eds), *Perspectives on multimodality*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Stoller, F. L. (2016). EAP materials and tasks. In K. Hyland (Ed.), *The Routledge Handbook of English for Academic Purposes*. Routledge.

- Stoller, F. L., & Robinson, M. S. (2013). Chemistry journal articles: An interdisciplinary approach to move analysis with pedagogical aims. *English for Specific Purposes*, 32(1), 45–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2012.09.001>
- Street, B. (2009). Hidden" Features of Academic Paper Writing. *Working Papers in Educational Linguistics (WPEL)*, 24. <http://repository.upenn.edu/wpel/vol24/iss1/1>
- Street, B. (2012). New Literacy Studies. In M. Grenfell, D. Bloome, C. Hardy, K. Pahl, J. Rowsell, & B. V. Street (Eds), *Language, Ethnography, and Education: Bridging New Literacy Studies and Bourdieu*. Routledge.
- Stevens, P. (1988). ESP after 20 years: A Reappraisal. In M. L. Tickoo (Ed.), *ESP: State of the Art (Anthology Series 21)*. Singapore: SEAMEO Regional Language Centre (RELC).
- Student Migration to the UK. (2025, October 30). *Migration Observatory*. <https://migrationobservatory.ox.ac.uk/resources/briefings/student-migration-to-the-uk/>
- Student visa*. (n.d.). GOV.UK. Retrieved 11 November 2025, from <https://www.gov.uk/student-visa/knowledge-of-english>
- Suharsono, S., Ashadi, A., & Feri, Z. O. (2024). Theme-Rheme Pattern: Its Contribution to Cohesion and Coherence in The Students' Research Background. *Journal of Research and Innovation in Language*, 6(1), 94–110.
- Sun, Q. (2019). *Chinese students' practice of using sources and citations in their one-year taught Master's programmes in a UK university* [PhD]. University of York.
- Susilowati, E., Faridi, A., & Sakhiyya, Z. (2022). Thematic Structure and Thematic Progression in Research Articles Published in Scopus-Indexed International Journals. *English Education Journal*, 12(1), 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.15294/eej.v12i1.53229>
- Swales, J. M. (1990). *Genre analysis: English in academic and research settings*. Cambridge University Press.
- Swales, J. M. (1996). Occluded Genres in the Academy: The Case of the Submission Letter. In E. Ventola & A. Mauranen (Eds), *Academic writing: Intercultural and textual issues*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Swales, J. M. (1998a). *Other floors. A textography of a small university building*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Inc.
- Swales, J. M. (1998b). Textography: Toward a Contextualization of Written Academic Discourse. *Research on Language and Social Interaction*, 31(1), 109–121.
- Swales, J. M. (2004). *Research genres: Explorations and applications*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139524827>

- Swales, J. M. (2016). Reflections on the concept of discourse community. *ASp*, 69, 7–19. <https://doi.org/10.4000/asp.4774>
- Swales, J. M., Barks, D., Ostermann, A. C., & Simpson, R. C. (2001). Between critique and accommodation: Reflections on an EAP course for Masters of Architecture students. *English for Specific Purposes*, 20, 439–458. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00020-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00020-5)
- Tarone, E., Dwyer, S., Gillette, S., & Icke, V. (1998). On the use of the passive and active voice in astrophysics journal papers: With extensions to other languages and other fields. *English for Specific Purposes*, 60th Birthdays of Ann Johns and John Swales, 17(1), 113–132. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(97\)00032-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(97)00032-X)
- The Bartlett School of Architecture Environmental Investigation*. (2022). Howlett Brown. https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/sites/bartlett/files/the_bartlett_school_of_architecture_environmental_investigation_report_june_2022p_6.pdf
- The economic impact of higher education, teaching, research and innovation*. (2025, October 29). Universities UK. <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/what-we-do/policy-and-research/publications/economic-impact-higher-education>
- Thompson, J. (2019). *Narratives of architectural education: From student to architect*. Taylor & Francis. <https://www.waterstones.com/book/narratives-of-architectural-education/james-thompson/9780815358817>
- Thompson, P. (2016). Genre approaches to theses and dissertations. In K. Hyland (Ed.), *The Routledge Handbook of English for Academic Purposes*. Routledge.
- Thompson, S. (1994). Frameworks and contexts: A genre-based approach to analysing lecture introductions. *English for Specific Purposes*, 13(2), 171–186. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906\(94\)90014-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906(94)90014-0)
- Tibbetts, N. A., & Chapman, T. (2023). *A guide to in-session English for academic purposes: Paradigms and practices*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003193715>
- Traugott, E. C. (2020). The development of “digressive” discourse-topic shift markers in English. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 156, 121–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2019.02.002>
- Traweek, S. (1988). *Beamtimes and lifetimes: The world of high energy physicists*. Harvard University Press.
- Tuck, J. (2022). Academic Literacies: Theorising Language as Social Practice. In A. Ding & M. Evans (Eds), *Social Theory for English for Academic Purposes*. Bloomsbury Academic.

- Turan, O. (2013). *The Genre Of Architectural Manifesto In The Society Of The Spectacle*. Middle East Technical University.
- UKCISA. (2025, May 13). *UKCISA responds to Home Office Immigration White Paper May 2025*. <https://www.ukcisa.org.uk/news/ukcisa-responds-to-home-office-immigration-white-paper-may-2025/>
- Unsworth, L. (2006). Towards a metalanguage for multiliteracies education: Describing the meaningmaking resources of language-image interaction. *English Teaching: Practice and Critique*, 5(1), 55–76.
- Unsworth, L. (2007). Image/text relations and intersemiosis: Towards multimodal text description for multiliteracies education. *Proceedings 33rd International Systemic Functional Congress 2006*, 1165–1205.
- Unsworth, L. (2008). Explicating inter-modal meaning-making in media and literary texts: Towards a metalanguage of image/language relations. In A. Burn & C. Durrant (Eds), *Media Teaching: Language, Audience and Production* (pp. 48–78). Wakefield Press.
- Unwin, S. (2023). *Exercises in architecture: Learning to think as an architect* (Second edition, revised and with new exercises). Routledge.
- van Biljon, J., & Renaud, K. (2015). Do visualizations ease dissertation assessment? *Proceedings of the 44th Annual Southern African Computer Lecturers Association 2015*, 177–186.
- Wan Jusoh, W. N. A. S., Abdul Jobar, N., & Md Yusoff, M. Z. N. (2022). What is Thematic Progression in Students' Essay? Revision of Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 11(4), Pages 1142-1163. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v11-i4/16090>
- Waring, M. (2012). Finding your theoretical position. In J. Arthur, M. Waring, R. Coe, & L. Hedges V. ., (Eds), *Research Methods and Methodologies in Education*. Sage.
- Warschauer, M. (2002). Networking into academic discourse. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*.
- Webster, H. (2008). Architectural Education after Schön: Cracks, Blurs, Boundaries and Beyond. *Journal for Education in the Built Environment*, 3(2), 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1120/jebe.2008.03020063>
- Weissberg, B. (1993). The graduate seminar: Another research-process genre. *English for Specific Purposes*, 12(1), 23–35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906\(93\)90025-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0889-4906(93)90025-J)
- Where do HE students come from? | HESA*. (2025, April 3). <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/students/where-from>

- Wilcox, B. (2014). Word and Image in Academic Writing: A Study of Verbal and Visual Meanings in Marketing Articles. *ESP Today*, 2(2), 113–133.
- Willis, D. (2011). Are Charrettes Old School? *Harvard Design Magazine*.
<https://www.harvarddesignmagazine.org/articles/are-charrettes-old-school/>
- Winiarska-Pringle, I., & Rolińska, A. (2024). Finding Space and Voice Duoethnographic Exploration of Teacher Agency in EAP. In A. Ding & L. Monbec (Eds), *Practitioner Agency and Identity in English for Academic Purposes* (p. 136). Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wiseman, C. (2014). *Writing Architecture: A Practical Guide to Clear Communication about the Built Environment*. Trinity University Press.
- Yamada, K. (2015). Cross-Disciplinary Variations: Japanese Novice Writers' Socialization into the Undergraduate Thesis. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 25, 207–217.
- Yarrow, T. (2019). *Architects: Portraits of a practice*. Cornell University press.
- Zhang, Y., & Pramoolsook, I. (2019). Generic Complexity in Bachelor's Theses by Chinese English Majors: An SFL Perspective. *GEMA Online® Journal of Language Studies*, 19(4), 304–326. <https://doi.org/10.17576/gema-2019-1904-16>
- Zhu, Y., & Yang, N. (2023). Visual images and image-text relations in ELT textbooks for young learners. *Language Teaching for Young Learners*, 5(2), 196–216.
<https://doi.org/10.1075/ltyl.00035.zhu>

Appendices

Appendix A: Favourable Ethical Opinion (2019)

Faculty of Humanities and

Professor Matthew Weait,

Professor of Law and Society

Social Sciences

T +44 (0)23 9284 6012

E matthew.weait@port.ac.uk

BA (Hons) MA MPhil DPhil FAcSS

Dean of the

FAVOURABLE ETHICAL OPINION (with conditions)

Name: Jennifer Sizer

Faculty of Humanities and Social
Sciences

Park Building

King Henry I Street

Portsmouth PO1 2DZ

T: +44 (0)23 9284 8484

port.ac.uk/fhss

Study Title: Understanding language use of architecture students. A textographic analysis to inform English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) practice.

Reference Number: FHSS 2019-064

Date: 7/12/2019

Thank you for submitting your application to the FHSS Ethics Committee.

I am pleased to inform you that FHSS Ethics Committee was content to grant a favourable ethical opinion of the above research on the basis described in the submitted documents listed at Annex A, and subject to standard general conditions (*See Annex B*). With this there are a number of ethical conditions to comply with, and some additional advisory notes you may wish to consider, all shown below.

Condition(s)¹

1. Consent: 11.1. "In his role as gatekeeper Oren will decide if sufficient consent from students has been provided in order for access to student authored texts to be granted". The gatekeeper, who is also the HoS, would be expected to provide evidence that consent has either been provided or is not required.
2. Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria: 11.2. These relate to participants and not consent or data. Please amend accordingly.
3. Consent: 11.7. Has or will consent be gained from other organisations involved (if applicable)?
I would expect consent for the research to be carried out to be obtained from the Head of School, who, it is noted, is also a research participant.
4. Date retention: 12.3. Ten years is sufficient. Any plans to make the data available on Pure?

Advisory Note(s)²

- A. Faculty is FHSS and not HUMS.
- B. Start date may need to be revised. This may also apply to the withdrawal deadline.
- C. Initial phase of research. "Initial phase of research involves accessing documentation and texts to find out more about architecture students and their academic written texts. This information will then be used in second phase to guide selection of participants and texts for textual analysis". It might have useful to provide more information about the second phase.

Please note that the favourable opinion of FHSS Ethics Committee does not grant permission or approval to undertake the research/ work. Management permission or

¹ A favourable opinion will be dependent upon the study adhering to the conditions stated, which are based on the application document(s) submitted. It is appreciated that Principal Investigators may wish to challenge conditions or propose amendments to these in the resubmission to this ethical review.

² The comments are given in good faith and it is hoped they are accepted as such. The PI does not need to adhere to these, or respond to them, unless they wish to.

approval must be obtained from any host organisation, including the University of Portsmouth or supervisor, prior to the start of the study.

Wishing you every success in your research

Chair

Mr Richard Hitchcock

Email: ethics-fhss@port.ac.uk

Annexes

A - Documents reviewed

B - After ethical review

ANNEX A - Documents reviewed

The documents ethically reviewed for this application

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Application Form	1	17/11/2019
Invitation Letter	1	Nov 2019
Participant Information Sheet	1	Nov 2019
Consent Form	1	Nov 2019

ANNEX B - After ethical review

1. This Annex sets out important guidance for those with a favourable opinion from a University of Portsmouth Ethics Committee. Please read the guidance carefully. A failure to follow the guidance could lead to the committee reviewing and possibly revoking its opinion on the research.
2. It is assumed that the work will commence within 1 year of the date of the favourable ethical opinion or the start date stated in the application, whichever is the latest.

3. The work must not commence until the researcher has obtained any necessary management permissions or approvals – this is particularly pertinent in cases of research hosted by external organisations. The appropriate head of department should be aware of a member of staff's plans.

4. If it is proposed to extend the duration of the study beyond that stated in the application, the Ethics Committee must be informed.

5. Any proposed substantial amendments must be submitted to the Ethics Committee for review. A substantial amendment is any amendment to the terms of the application for ethical review, or to the protocol or other supporting documentation approved by the Committee that is likely to affect to a significant degree:

- (a) the safety or physical or mental integrity of participants
- (b) the scientific value of the study
- (c) the conduct or management of the study.

5.1 A substantial amendment should not be implemented until a favourable ethical opinion has been given by the Committee.

6. At the end of the work a final report should be submitted to the ethics committee. A template for this can be found on the University Ethics webpage.

7. Researchers are reminded of the University's commitments as stated in the [Concordat to Support Research Integrity](#) viz:

- maintaining the highest standards of rigour and integrity in all aspects of research
- ensuring that research is conducted according to appropriate ethical, legal and professional frameworks, obligations and standards
- supporting a research environment that is underpinned by a culture of integrity and based on good governance, best practice and support for the development of researchers
- using transparent, robust and fair processes to deal with allegations of research misconduct should they arise
- working together to strengthen the integrity of research and to reviewing progress regularly and openly.

8. In ensuring that it meets these commitments the University has adopted the [UKRIO Code of Practice for Research](#). Any breach of this code may be considered as misconduct and may be investigated following the University [Procedure for the Investigation of Allegations of Misconduct in Research](#). Researchers are advised to use the [UKRIO checklist](#) as a simple guide to integrity.

Appendix B: Favourable Ethical Opinion (2020)

Dr Theresa Callan ,

Interim Dean of the Faculty of

Humanities and Social Sciences

T +44 (0)23 9284 6012

E theresa.callan@port.ac.uk Faculty of Humanities and Social
Sciences
Park Building
King Henry I Street
Portsmouth PO1 2DZ

T: +44 (0)23 9284 8484 port.ac.uk/fhss

FAVOURABLE ETHICAL OPINION (with conditions)

Name: Jennifer Sizer

Study Title: Understanding language use of architecture students. A textographic analysis to inform English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) practice.

Reference Number: FHSS 2020-021

Date: 29/04/2020

Thank you for submitting your application to the FHSS Ethics Committee.

I am pleased to inform you that FHSS Ethics Committee was content to grant a favourable ethical opinion of the above research on the basis described in the submitted documents listed at Annex A, and subject to standard general conditions (*See Annex B*).

With this there are a number of ethical conditions to comply with, and some additional advisory notes you may wish to consider, all shown below.

Condition(s)³

1. Anticipated risks: 9.3. "If participants do report poor practice of others and this practice raises concerns for the researcher, this will be discussed with supervisor in order to decide if concerns can/should be passed on anonymously, if possible, and how these concerns may be shared". This needs to be included in the PIS.
2. **a.** Recruitment strategy 11.4. "...and study promoted by colleagues in online teaching sessions and/or tutorials". It is important that students do not feel under any pressure to participate in the research.
2b. Recruitment Strategy 11.4 - Invitations should be sent out by administrative staff to comply with the GDPR, which restricts access to administratively held personally identifiable information including emails until students indicate their willingness to participate. **3.** Retention of data: 12.3 - "The data, may accidentally identify staff/students e.g.

through identifying characteristics: initials, student numbers". Is there any way in which this can be redacted out to anonymise the texts?
4. Confidentiality: PIS section 12 - The researcher needs to be clear whether she intends to comply with the UoP policy for making all data associated with published articles open access, including participants' interview transcripts, study notes, assignments etc. If this is the intention, the consent form should include a specific consent statement, and it may discourage students. The raw data would have to be redacted to ensure anonymity, which may be a

³ A favourable opinion will be dependent upon the study adhering to the conditions stated, which are based on the application document(s) submitted. It is appreciated that Principal Investigators may wish to challenge conditions or propose amendments to these in the resubmission to this ethical review.

burdensome task. The alternative is not to make the redacted raw data open access (which may be a relevant option in this case).

5. PIS Withdrawal - A practical time limit should be set for withdrawal before the researcher commences analysis of the data, e.g. two weeks after data collection.

Allowing for withdrawal after data analysis has begun may have consequences for the analysis of the data (e.g. data saturation).

Advisory Note(s)⁴

- A. Ethics training. It is noted that the applicant has not attended a training session in the graduate school on research ethics. It is a shame that this was not undertaken before F2F teaching was suspended.
- B. Peer review. The guidance states the following: "Please briefly summarise how this project has been peer-reviewed, ideally adding any peer reviews and your response to the review as an appendix or supporting document".
- C. Payments, rewards, reimbursements or compensation to participants. 11.5. The applicant might like to consider offering participants something as compensation or a thank you for their involvement in the project. However, this is not obligatory.
- D. Description of data analysis, 12.1. "Some other statistical analysis including but not limited to averages/frequency e.g. number of learning hours, word counts and grades (depending on access to data)." Is this the students' 'academic grades'? If so, how will they be collected? There is no mention of this in the other parts of application. If students' grades are to be linked to the interview participants, this should be mentioned in the PIS.
- E. Consent form: a tick box is missing for point 8 and should be included.
- F. PIS: What will happen to me if I take part? "Interviews will be conducted online and ..." It may be better to mention what equipment is required to take part in the study e.g. PC/mobile phone with Internet access, what platform etc.

Please note that the favourable opinion of FHSS Ethics Committee does not grant permission or approval to undertake the research/ work. Management permission or approval must be obtained from any host organisation, including the University of Portsmouth or supervisor, prior to the start of the study.

Wishing you every success in your research

Acting Chair

⁴ The comments are given in good faith and it is hoped they are accepted as such. The PI does not need to adhere to these, or respond to them, unless they wish to.

Dr Jonathan Evans

Email: ethics-fhss@port.ac.uk

Annexes

A - Documents reviewed

B - After ethical review

ANNEX A - Documents reviewed

The documents ethically reviewed for this application

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Application Form	1	14/04/2020
Invitation Letter	1	November 2019
Participant Information Sheet	1	November 2019
Consent Form	1	November 2019

ANNEX B - After ethical review

1. This Annex sets out important guidance for those with a favourable opinion from a University of Portsmouth Ethics Committee. Please read the guidance carefully. A failure to follow the guidance could lead to the committee reviewing and possibly revoking its opinion on the research.
2. It is assumed that the work will commence within 1 year of the date of the favourable ethical opinion or the start date stated in the application, whichever is the latest.
3. The work must not commence until the researcher has obtained any necessary management permissions or approvals – this is particularly pertinent in cases of research hosted by external organisations. The appropriate head of department should be aware of a member of staff's plans.
4. If it is proposed to extend the duration of the study beyond that stated in the application, the Ethics Committee must be informed.
5. Any proposed substantial amendments must be submitted to the Ethics Committee for review. A substantial amendment is any amendment to the terms of

the application for ethical review, or to the protocol or other supporting documentation approved by the Committee that is likely to affect to a significant degree:

- (a) the safety or physical or mental integrity of participants
- (b) the scientific value of the study
- (c) the conduct or management of the study.

5.1 A substantial amendment should not be implemented until a favourable ethical opinion has been given by the Committee.

6. At the end of the work a final report should be submitted to the ethics committee. A template for this can be found on the University Ethics webpage.

7. Researchers are reminded of the University's commitments as stated in the [Concordat to Support Research Integrity](#) viz:

- maintaining the highest standards of rigour and integrity in all aspects of research
- ensuring that research is conducted according to appropriate ethical, legal and professional frameworks, obligations and standards
- supporting a research environment that is underpinned by a culture of integrity and based on good governance, best practice and support for the development of researchers
- using transparent, robust and fair processes to deal with allegations of research misconduct should they arise
- working together to strengthen the integrity of research and to reviewing progress regularly and openly.

8. In ensuring that it meets these commitments the University has adopted the [UKRIO Code of Practice for Research](#). Any breach of this code may be considered as misconduct and may be investigated following the University [Procedure for the Investigation of Allegations of Misconduct in Research](#). Researchers are advised to use the [UKRIO checklist](#) as a simple guide to integrity.

2.2 Supervisor (if Principal Investigator is a student or a research assistant)

Name: Dr Jane Creaton
HUMSS

Title /Role: Associate Dean Academic

Department: EDSOC

Faculty: HUMSS

Telephone: 023 9284 3976

Email: Jane.Creaton@port.ac.uk

Names and email of any other supervisors:

Dr Glenn Hadikin, Senior lecturer, SLAL (second supervisor: linguistics specialist)

Dr Bryony Whitmarsh, Associate Dean of Global Engagement, CCI (third supervisor and subject expert)

Has the supervisor attended the researcher development training session on research ethics (NB this is not mandatory)?

Y

2.3 Others involved in the work/research including students and/or external collaborators (name, organisation/course, role in the project)

Professor [REDACTED], Head of School of Architecture

As Head of School. [redacted] is the gatekeeper to documentation and texts needed for initial stage of research.

Third supervisor (Bryony Whitmarsh) is organising a meeting between myself and (Head of School) to discuss access and future research.

Details of Peer Review

This project has been reviewed by my supervisor.

Funding Details

EdD student status internally funded. No other funding.

Sites/Locations

Some data collection may take place in Eldon Building e.g. collecting physical paperwork/texts or meeting with CCI administration staff, online course developers and/or academic to gain access to documentation and/or clarify any ambiguities/duplicates within documentation.

Insurance/indemnity Arrangements

The University of Portsmouth Insurance Policies will cover the research and needs of this research project. This includes research sponsored, managed, designed or conducted by, or on behalf of, the University (including research undertaken by students under supervision).

Insurance for research participants not necessary for initial phase of research.

Aims and Objectives/Hypothesis

7.1 Aims

My aim in this EdD project is to understand the language use, as well as reasons for language choices, of undergraduate architecture students.

7.2 Primary Objective

Identify language choices architecture students make in terms of genre (text types, moves and steps) and vocabulary in academic written texts*

7.3 Secondary Objective(s)

Explore reasons why architecture students make these language choices in academic written texts* (via second phase of research requiring further ethical approval)

**These objectives are deliberately broad in nature due to a more hypothesis-generating rather than hypothesis-testing approach (Hartwick & Barki, 1994) i.e. favouring an 'emic' approach over an 'etic' approach: through deciding (as an outsider) how students use language and searching for these specific language features. (Kuh & Whitt, 1988)*

Justification/Summary of Study (no more than one side)

In my role as English for Academic Purposes module coordinator, I need to prepare my students for a world I don't understand. Most of the students on my module: English for Academic Purposes for Creative and Cultural Industries (EAP for CCI) study architecture at undergraduate level, a subject area and community I have little knowledge or experience of. I need to know more about this world and community to better prepare my students for the language and texts they are likely to encounter and will be expected to produce. Initially, I attempted to understand this academic community through the students I had access to in EAP (mainly first year undergraduate architecture students).

However, these students were new and not yet familiar with their community's practices and/or genres. As a result, EAP students' requests included genres they would not encounter until their second or final year e.g. essays and dissertations. In addition, these genres were often less common and viewed as "academic dinosaurs" (Mey, 2013) by members of this community. As an outsider and in the absence of ethical approval, it was difficult to gain access to and study student texts. Therefore, I needed to look beyond my own institution through researching available corpora, textbooks and research for examples of texts and practices of CCI subjects. Firstly, I investigated corpora including the British Academic Written English (BAWE) corpus but none of the available corpora had CCI texts. Secondly, I searched for appropriate EAP course and reference books. Most EAP course or reference books follow an English for General Academic Purposes (EGAP) approach. EGAP (English for General Academic Purposes) is very similar to academic literacies descriptions of 'study skills models' (Creaton, 2015) which view EAP as transferable language skills suitable for all university study. Some EAP course and reference books follow an ESAP approach which is very similar to academic descriptions of 'academic socialisation' i.e. induction into language discourse practices/genres (Lillis, 2003). However, most ESAP course and reference books feature the same recurring disciplines e.g. business, law, STEM and not CCI subjects. (See (Garnet Education, 2019) for full range). Finally, I also reviewed the available EAP research literature. There were less than 30 papers featuring ESAP at each of the 2017 and 2019 BALEAP ('The global forum for EAP professionals') conferences and fewer than 3 papers on CCI subjects. ESAP research publications feature some CCI subjects but tend to either focus on either graphic design (Lasserre, 2012; Perks & Whittingham, 2017) or fine art (Riley-Jones, 2012, 2017) or focus on interdisciplinary subjects e.g. civil engineering (Heidenreich, 2016). Other EAP research includes specific written genres within specific subjects again often fine art e.g. art history essays (Riley-Jones, 2012, 2017), reflections (Doloughan, 2002) exegesis (short written commentary of artefact) (Paltridge, 2004) and language features within those genres. Other ESAP published research focused on specific genres, often spoken e.g. critiques (Swales et al., 2001) or practices/pedagogies, again often spoken, and less focused on language e.g. studios (Morton, 2012). English for Occupational Purposes offers more published research and course/reference books (Dias et al., 1999; Medway, 1996, 2003; Wiseman, 2014) focuses on professional genres (Parkinson et al., 2017) and language use of architects outside university (Morton, 2016). English for Academic and Occupational purposes corpora, books and research were not hugely helpful in preparing ESAP provision for CCI (mostly architecture undergraduates).

As a profession, architecture has some literature to draw on in terms of practice/s e.g. (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Medway, 1996; Schön, 1991). However, much of this research is either outdated e.g. Medway's investigation of obsolete memos now replaced by emails (Medway, 1996) and/or contested (J. Thompson, 2019). More recent research on language use and practices of architects is available (see: (Caballero Rodriguez, 2003; Medway, 2003; Morton, 2016) but may not reflect language use and practices of architecture students at university. (J. Thompson, 2019) recent research suggests there is a disconnect between what architecture students learn at university and what is

experienced as architects in the profession. This mismatch may also result in considerable variation when comparing genre and language features in a university context and a professional context. Therefore, the specific focus must be on practices and language use for architecture students at university. There is some interesting research available on the pedagogy and practice of architectural education at university e.g. exploring architecture student's identity (Bilikozen, 2015; J. Thompson, 2019) and use of studio learning as pedagogy (Caldwell & Gregory, 2016; Mewburn, 2012). This research provides some insight into practices and some of the principles behind practices but often neglects linguistic practices i.e. language use. Research that focuses on written genres for architecture students is missing. Hyland (2002b) suggests effective language teaching at university level needs to be specific and 'we must go as far as we can' in terms of specificity. In order to go as far as I can, I need to fill this gap in the literature and analyse the written genres and language use of architecture students at university.

Description of Method/ Protocol and Risks

9.1 Please describe your main method(s) or describe your protocol here, although ensure you do not replicate sections 11, 12 or 13.

Initial phase of research involves accessing documentation and texts to find out more about architecture students and their academic written texts. This information will then be used in second phase to guide selection of participants and texts for textual analysis.

Examples include but are not limited to:

school-level, course-level, module-level and assessment-level information e.g. access to module, course, school and external examiners' moodle sites/google drive folders.

school, course and module data e.g. current student population data for school, number of staff, learning hours, completion rates, average grades, employability/destination data

internal school documents and data e.g. module handbooks, assessment deadlines and confirmed module coordinators and teaching staff

internal school reports and texts e.g. Annual Standards and Quality Evaluative Review (ASQER), Module Amendment Request Form (MARF), course/module descriptors, timetable/exam request forms, student surveys (module and course), minutes of student voice and other relevant minuted internal meetings

externally-shared reports and texts e.g. NSS, RIBA accreditation documentation and report, Athena Swan documentation and report, external examiners' reports and external examiners' site/folder

publicly-available texts: university website and course marketing/social media (ethical approval not needed, but access via [REDACTED] School of Architecture may be helpful).

This is not an exhaustive list. If other data sources are subsequently identified but not included above as unanticipated at time of submission then additional formal consent from Oren will be requested.

This collected data will then inform the sampling procedure i.e. how many students from overall population will be invited to participate. The other texts will be analysed to determine which assessments/texts could be included in final data collection phase.

9.2 Anticipated Ethical Issues

Potentially sensitive data e.g. population data, assessment data and other data will request student numbers only, other identifying features removed from data and/or moodle access i.e. anonymised marking turned on.

Possible ethical issues in obtaining consent from students and academics to access completed and marked assessments with feedback. Students and staff may have given consent for these assessments to be shared with external examiners and/or accreditation bodies but may not have provided explicit consent to be used in research. Consent for access provided by head of school.

Access to assessments and data at this initial stage is to inform later stage of data collection. Any assessments collected in later stage and used in research will seek individual consent from associated students and staff.

Where possible all data will be anonymized prior to access through requested use of student numbers only.

9.3 Anticipated other Risks or Concerns

Have all risk assessments as required by relevant Health and Safety policies been completed?	<u>YES</u>
--	-------------------

Risks to participants: No anticipated risks to participant

Risks to researchers/ university staff/students: No anticipated risks to researchers, staff or students

Reputational risks: No anticipated risks as data from initial phase used to inform secondary phase and not to be shared or reported in EdD thesis without consent via secondary phase/

Security risks: no anticipated security risks

9.4 Medical Cover (if applicable)

N/A

Compliance with Laws, Codes, Guidance, Policies and Procedures

This study complies with the ethical codes, policies and procedures outlined within the UK Research Integrity Office's code of practice for research and the University of Portsmouth's ethics policy. This study is also compliant with GDPR 2018.

Recruitment of Participants

11.1 Who are the Research/ Participant Population?

Head of School of Architecture, will be the sole participant. In his role as gatekeeper Oren will allow access to internal documentation, data and texts.

It could be argued the students (authors of some texts) are indirect participants. In his role as gatekeeper Oren will decide if sufficient consent from students has been provided in order for access to student-authored texts to be granted. If insufficient consent from students, consent may be requested in next phase of research.

11.2 Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Oren Liebermann is the sole participant at this stage.

Inclusion Criteria: consent for assessments to be shared

Exclusion Criteria: identifying personal details and/or sensitive data which cannot be removed prior to access

11.3 Number of participants (include rationale for sample size)

Just one participant representing the school of architecture (gatekeeper)

11.4 Recruitment Strategy (including details of any anticipated use of a gatekeeper in host organizations to arrange/distribute participant invitations)

Just one participant: Oren Lieberman who will act as gatekeeper providing or denying access depending on consent provided and/or appropriateness

11.5 Payments, rewards, reimbursements or compensation to participants

No financial incentive or reward

11.6 What is the process for gaining *consent* from participants?

Oren will determine consent for each requested source of data. If additional consent is required then access will be denied, at this point, and consent requested during next stage of research.

11.7 Has or will consent be gained from other organisations involved (if applicable)?
Oren will determine if sources of data are appropriate to be shared i.e. already available in the public domain, already available internally to colleagues external to the school, already available externally in some format e.g. reports, consent provided.
11.8 Arrangements for translation of any documentation into another language (if applicable)?
N/A
11.9 Outline how participants can withdraw consent (if applicable), and how data collected up to this point will be handled. Also stop criteria for specific tests (if applicable)?
Oren will be informed of his right to withdraw at any time: before/after interview, before/after access to information sources and second phase of research and will be made aware of this via participant information sheet, invitation letter and consent form.
11.10 Outline details of re-consent or debrief (if applicable)?
Oren will receive updates on research on request.

Data Management

12.1 Description of data analysis
<p>Some statistical analysis of numerical data e.g. student population and percentage of students with particular characteristics (depending on access to data). Some other statistical analysis including but not limited to averages/frequency e.g. number of learning hours, word counts and grades (depending on access to data).</p> <p>Textual analysis of data sources. Systematic analysis via a grid reporting on academic written texts undergraduate architecture students are required to submit as part of their studies including but not limited to word counts, timeframes, multimodality, reading lists and assessment guidance. Reports and other documentation will aid in understanding texts and assessments and how they may have developed/changed over time. For example, in subsequent stage of research a third-year student's assessment from their first year of study (3+ years ago) may not match current module/course documentation.</p>
12.2 Where and how will data be stored DURING the project?

The data shared during this initial stage will be stored using a google drive folder which is password protected. The data may be discussed with supervisors but texts themselves will not be shared.

12.3 Destruction, Retention and Reuse of Data (often AFTER your project has finished)

The data collected in initial stage will not be shared or made open access and will only be used to inform subsequent stage of data collection.

At this initial stage, collected data will be kept securely and remain confidential and not shared with others, but instead used to guide next stage of research. Texts featuring identifying data e.g. names of individual students/staff will not be used/included unless prior consent is requested and provided. The data, may accidentally identify staff/students e.g. through identifying characteristics: initials, student numbers but data will not be passed to anyone outside the study team (researcher and supervisors) without express written permission. Data will be kept in a password protected research folder on the university's google drive system. This folder and contents of this folder will not be shared with others. The data will be retained for a minimum of 10 years. When it is no longer required, the data will be disposed of securely (e.g. electronic media and paper records / images) destroyed." Note the policy for retention of research data requires retention for between 10 to 30 years and can be accessed from section 7, (and subsections) at the following links:

http://www.port.ac.uk/departments/services/corporategovernance/recordsmanagement/uop_retention/

12.4 Personal Data – How will confidentiality be ensured?

The data collected in initial stage will not be shared with others and will be stored in password-protected google drive folder.

12.5 How will data belonging to organisations (publicly unavailable data) be handled (if applicable)?

Institutional data from the University of Portsmouth will be password-protected and not shared unless consent given through second phase.

12.6 How will security sensitive data be handled (if applicable)?

If security sensitive data is shared in error, then the department (via participant) will be notified and researcher's access to security sensitive data destroyed.

Publication / Impact / Dissemination Plans

No plans to publish or share findings from initial phase of research beyond study team (researcher and supervisor). Any data which may be useful for subsequent stage of research will feature in second ethics form and additional consent requested from participants.

References

- Bilikozen, N. (2015). *Academic literacy development and identity construction of undergraduates at an American university in the UAE*. University of Exeter . Retrieved from <https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/bitstream/handle/10871/21547/BilikozenN.pdf?sequence=1>
- Caballero Rodriguez, M. d. R. (2003). How to talk shop through metaphor: bringing metaphor research to the ESP classroom. *English for Specific Purposes*, 22(2), 177–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(02\)00015-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(02)00015-7)
- Caldwell, E., & Gregory, J. (2016). Internationalizing the art school: What part does the studio have to play? *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 15(2), 117–133. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.15.2.117_1
- Creaton, J. (2015). Marking the boundaries: knowledge and identity in professional doctorates. In Theresa; Lillis, K. Harrington, M. R. . Lea, & S. Mitchell (Eds.), *Working with Academic Literacies*. Anderson: Parlor Press.
- Dias, P., Freedman, A., Medway, P., & Pare, A. (1999). *Worlds Apart*. New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410602336>
- Doloughan, F. J. (2002). The Language of Reflective Practice in Art and Design. *Design Issues*, 18(2), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.1162/074793602317355783>
- Garnet Education. (2019). Category: ESAP Series | Garnet Education. Retrieved March 10, 2019, from <https://www.garneteducation.com/category/english-for-specific-academic-purposes/esap-series/>
- Hartwick, J., & Barki, H. (1994). Research Report-Hypothesis Testing and Hypothesis Generating Research: An Example from the User Participation Literature. *Information Systems Research*, 5(4), 446. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.5.4.446>
- Heidenreich, S. (2016). *Englisch für Architekten und Bauingenieure - English for Architects and Civil Engineers : Ein kompletter Projektlauf auf Englisch mit Vokabeln, Redewendungen, Übungen und Praxistipps - All project phases in English with vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, exercises and practical advice*. Nurnberg: Springer. Retrieved from <https://wordery.com/englisch-fur-architekten-und-bauingenieure-english-for-architects-and-civil-engineers-sharon-heidenreich-9783658139537?currency=GBP>rck=ZGxJV2RqSG0rZ0tTZmt1d1luZXFZMnNnL2xJNG85VmRxdFcrbzRIclJJS0QyVnJGWIlpMzRkU0RuVnI4bnJvVGRwamtyL01TR>
- Hyland, K. (2002). Specificity Revisited: How Far Should we Go Now? *English for Specific Purposes* , 21, 385–395. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00028-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00028-X)
- Kuh, G. D., & Whitt, E. J. (1988). *The Invisible Tapestry. Culture in American Colleges and Universities*. Washington DC. <https://doi.org/ISBN-0-913317-45-4>
- Lasserre, B. (2012). Speaking the critique in graphic design: The role of metaphor. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 10(1), 51–66. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.10.1.51_1

- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from [http://mathed811.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/63103234/Lave-Wenger-Situated Learning-Part I.pdf](http://mathed811.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/63103234/Lave-Wenger-Situated-Learning-Part-I.pdf)
- Lillis, Theresa. (2003). Student Writing as “Academic Literacies”: Drawing on Bakhtin to Move from Critique to Design. *Language and Education*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500780308666848>
- Medway, P. (2003). Imagining the building: architectural design as semiotic construction. *Design Studies*, 24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X\(02\)00055-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X(02)00055-8)
- Medway, Peter. (1996). Writing, Speaking, Drawing: the Distribution of Meaning in Architects’ Communication. In *The New Writing Environment* (pp. 25–42). London: Springer London. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-1482-6_3
- Mewburn, I. (2012). Lost in translation: Reconsidering reflective practice and design studio pedagogy. *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education*, 11(4), 363–379. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022210393912>
- Mey, K. (2013). The gesture of writing. In *Thinking Through Art Reflections on Art as Research* (pp. 217–228). London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203819869-25>
- Morton, J. (2012). Communities of practice in higher education: A challenge from the discipline of architecture. *Linguistics and Education*, 23(1), 100–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LINGED.2011.04.002>
- Morton, J. (2016). ‘Adjacent worlds’: An analysis of a genre at the intersection of academic and professional communities. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 22, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEAP.2016.01.003>
- Paltridge, B. (2004). The exegesis as a genre: an ethnographic examination. In L. . Ravelli & R. A. Ellis (Eds.), *Analysing Academic Writing*. Retrieved from <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=oi1XZ4MwYm8C&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q&f=false>
- Parkinson, J., Demecheleer, M., & Mackay, J. (2017). Writing like a builder: Acquiring a professional genre in a pedagogical setting. *English for Specific Purposes*, 46, 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESP.2016.12.003>
- Perks, S., & Whittingham, N. (2017). Timelines in design: Where linguistics meets design history. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 16(1), 23–32. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.16.1.23_1
- Riley-Jones, G. (2012). Critical thinking as an embodied criticality: The lived experiences of international art students. *Journal of Writing in Creative Practice*, 5(3), 401–421. https://doi.org/10.1386/jwcp.5.3.401_1
- Riley-Jones, G. (2017). There is a disease, and it’s called Goldsmiths. Bristol: BALEAP 2017 conference. Retrieved from <https://baleap2017.files.wordpress.com/2016/01/all-sessions.pdf>
- Schön, D. A. (1991). *The reflective practitioner : how professionals think in action*. Basic Books. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com>
- Swales, J. M., Barks, D., Ostermann, A. C., & Simpson, R. C. (2001). Between critique and accommodation: Reflections on an EAP course for Masters of Architecture students. *English for Specific Purposes*, 20(SUPPL. 1), 439–458. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00020-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00020-5)
- Thompson, J. (2019). *Narratives of architectural education: from student to architect*. New York : Taylor & Francis. Retrieved from <https://www.waterstones.com/book/narratives-of-architectural-education/james-thompson/9780815358817>
- Wiseman, C. (2014). *Writing Architecture : a Practical Guide to Clear Communication about*

the Built Environment. Trinity University Press. Retrieved from
https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=RUbpCAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT7&dq=%22Writing+architecture%22+wiseman&ots=vb5j6B-K1B&sig=1PsfMO_IQ-t2L8MD6s3rsgyRjHc#v=onepage&q=%22Writing+architecture%22+wiseman&f=false

Appendices

Put N/A in version Number column if necessary			
Document	Date	Version No.	Appendix
Application Form	November 2019	1	N/A
Invitation Letter	November 2019	1	A
Participant Information Sheet(s) (list if necessary)	November 2019	1	B
Consent Form(s) (list if necessary)	November 2019	1	C
Advertisement	N/A		
Peer / Independent Review	N/A		
Supervisor Email Confirming Application	N/A		
Evidence From External Organisation Showing Support	N/A		
Terms of Reference for Steering / Advisory Group	N/A		
Survey Instrument	N/A		
Interview Questions / Topic List	N/A		
Focus Group Questions / Topic List	N/A		
Focus Group Ground Rules	N/A		
Script for Oral Consent	N/A		
Questionnaire	N/A		
Observational Data Collection Form	N/A		
Risk Assessment Form(s)	N/A		

Declaration by Principal Investigator and Supervisor (if applicable)

1. The information in this form is accurate to the best of my/our knowledge and belief and I/we take full responsibility for it.
2. I/we undertake to conduct the research/ work in compliance with the University of Portsmouth Ethics Policy, UUK Concordat to Support Research Integrity, the UKRIO Code of Practice and any other guidance I/we have referred to in this application.
3. I/we confirm that all relevant risk assessments and Health and Safety requirements have been made/met.
4. If the research/ work is given a favourable opinion I/we undertake to adhere to the

study protocol, the terms of the full application as finally reviewed and any conditions set out by the Ethics Committee in giving its favourable opinion.

5. I/we undertake to notify the Ethics Committee of substantial amendments to the protocol or the terms of the final application, and to seek a favourable opinion before implementing the amendment.

6. I/we undertake to submit annual progress reports (if the study is of more than a year's duration) setting out the progress of the research/ work, as required by the Ethics Committee.

7. I/we undertake to inform the Ethics Committee when the study is complete and provide a declaration accordingly.

8. I/we am/are aware of my/our responsibility to be up to date and comply with the requirements of the law and relevant guidelines relating to security and confidentiality of personal data, including the need to register, when necessary, with the appropriate Data Protection Officer. I/we understand that I/we am/are not permitted to disclose identifiable data to third parties unless the disclosure has the consent of the data subject.

9. I/we undertake to comply with the University of Portsmouth Data Management Policy.

10. I /we understand that records/data may be subject to inspection by internal and external bodies for audit purposes if required.

11. I/we understand that any personal data in this application will be held by the Ethics Committee, its Administrator and its operational managers and that this will be managed according to the principles established in the Data Protection Act 1998 (and after May 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation).

12. I understand that the information contained in this application, any supporting documentation and all correspondence with the Ethics Committee and its Administrator relating to the application:

Will be held by the Ethics Committee until at least 10 years after the end of the study

Will be subject to the provisions of the Freedom of Information Acts and may be disclosed in response to requests made under the Acts except where statutory exemptions apply.

May be sent by email or other electronic distribution to Ethics Committee members.

13. I/we understand that the favourable opinion of an ethics committee does not grant permission or approval to undertake the research/ work. Management permission or approval must be obtained from any host organisation, including the University of Portsmouth or supervisor, prior to the start of the study.

Principal Investigator Jennifer Sizer.....

Date

17/11/2019.....

Supervisor (if applicable) Jane Creaton.....

Date

07/11/2019.....

17/11/2019

Name: Dr Jane Creaton HUMSS		Title /Role: Associate Dean Academic	
Department: EDSOC		Faculty: FHSS	
Telephone: 023 9284 3976		Email: Jane.Creaton@port.ac.uk	
Names and email of any other supervisors:			
Dr Glenn Hadikin, Senior lecturer, SLAL (second supervisor: linguistics specialist) Dr Bryony Whitmarsh, Associate Dean of Global Engagement, CCI (third supervisor and subject expert)			
Has the supervisor attended the researcher development training session on research ethics (NB this is not mandatory)?			Y
2.3 Others involved in the work/research including students and/or external collaborators (name, organisation/course, role in the project)			
Head of School of Architecture as gatekeeper.			
Bryony Whitmarsh and Nicola Crowson from School of Architecture as link persons and advisors.			
Level 6 BA Architecture students			

3. Details of Peer Review

This project has been reviewed by my supervisor.
--

4. Funding Details

EdD student status internally funded. No other funding.

5. Sites/Locations

Depending on when buildings reopen some data collection may take place in Eldon Building e.g. collecting physical paperwork/texts or interviewing students (room booked in Eldon for this purpose w/c May 26th).
--

6. Insurance/indemnity Arrangements

The University of Portsmouth Insurance Policies will cover the research and needs of this research project. This includes research sponsored, managed, designed or conducted by, or on behalf of, the University (including research undertaken by students under supervision).

Insurance for research participants not necessary for initial phase of research.

7. Aims and Objectives/Hypothesis

7.1 Aims

My aim in this EdD project is to understand the language use, as well as reasons for language choices, of undergraduate architecture students.

7.2 Primary Objective

Identify language choices architecture students make in terms of genre (text types, moves and steps) and vocabulary in academic written texts*

7.3 Secondary Objective(s)

Explore reasons why architecture students make these language choices in academic written texts*

**These objectives are deliberately broad in nature due to a more hypothesis-generating rather than hypothesis-testing approach (Hartwick & Barki, 1994) i.e. favouring an 'emic' approach over an 'etic' approach: through deciding (as an outsider) how students use language and searching for these specific language features. (Kuh & Whitt, 1988)*

8. Justification/Summary of Study (no more than one side)

In my role as English for Academic Purposes module coordinator, I need to prepare my students for a world I don't understand. Most of the students on my module: English for Academic Purposes for Creative and Cultural Industries (EAP for CCI) study architecture at undergraduate level, a subject area and community I have little knowledge or experience of. I need to know more about this world and community to better prepare my students for the language and texts they are likely to encounter and will be expected to produce. Initially, I attempted to understand this academic community through the students I had access to in EAP (mainly first year undergraduate architecture students). However, these students were new and not yet familiar with their community's practices and/or genres. As a result, EAP students' requests included genres they would not encounter until their second or final year e.g. essays and dissertations. In addition, these genres were often less common and viewed as "academic dinosaurs" (Mey, 2013) by members of this community. As an outsider and in the absence of ethical approval, it was difficult to gain access to and study student texts. Therefore, I needed to look beyond my

own institution through researching available corpora, textbooks and research for examples of texts and practices of CCI subjects. Firstly, I investigated corpora including the British Academic Written English (BAWE) corpus but none of the available corpora had CCI texts. Secondly, I searched for appropriate EAP course and reference books. Most EAP course or reference books follow an English for General Academic Purposes (EGAP) approach. EGAP (English for General Academic Purposes) is very similar to academic literacies descriptions of 'study skills models' (Creaton, 2015) which view EAP as transferable language skills suitable for all university study. Some EAP course and reference books follow an ESAP approach which is very similar to academic descriptions of 'academic socialisation' i.e. induction into language discourse practices/genres (Lillis, 2003). However, most ESAP course and reference books feature the same recurring disciplines e.g. business, law, STEM and not CCI subjects. (See (Garnet Education, 2019) for full range). Finally, I also reviewed the available EAP research literature. There were less than 30 papers featuring ESAP at each of the 2017 and 2019 BALEAP ('The global forum for EAP professionals') conferences and fewer than 3 papers on CCI subjects. ESAP research publications feature some CCI subjects but tend to either focus on either graphic design (Lasserre, 2012; Perks & Whittingham, 2017) or fine art (Riley-Jones, 2012, 2017) or focus on interdisciplinary subjects e.g. civil engineering (Heidenreich, 2016). Other EAP research includes specific written genres within specific subjects again often fine art e.g. art history essays (Riley-Jones, 2012, 2017), reflections (Doloughan, 2002) exegesis (short written commentary of artefact) (Paltridge, 2004) and language features within those genres. Other ESAP published research focused on specific genres, often spoken e.g. critiques (Swales, Barks, Ostermann, & Simpson, 2001) or practices/pedagogies, again often spoken, and less focused on language e.g. studios (Morton, 2012). English for Occupational Purposes offers more published research and course/reference books (Dias, Freedman, Medway, & Pare, 1999; Medway, 2003; Medway, 1996; Wiseman, 2014) focuses on professional genres (Parkinson, Demecheleer, & Mackay, 2017) and language use of architects outside university (Morton, 2016). English for Academic and Occupational purposes corpora, books and research were not hugely helpful in preparing ESAP provision for CCI (mostly architecture undergraduates).

As a profession, architecture has some literature to draw on in terms of practice/s e.g. (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Medway, 1996; Schön, 1991). However, much of this research is either outdated e.g. Medway's investigation of obsolete memos now replaced by emails (Medway, 1996) and/or contested (Thompson, 2019). More recent research on language use and practices of architects is available (see: Caballero Rodriguez, 2003; Medway, 2003; Morton, 2016) but may not reflect language use and practices of architecture students at university. Thompson's (2019) recent research suggests there is a disconnect between what architecture students learn at university and what is experienced as architects in the profession. This mismatch may also result in considerable variation when comparing genre and language features in a university context and a professional context. Therefore, the specific focus must be on practices and language use for architecture students at university. There is some interesting research available on the

pedagogy and practice of architectural education at university e.g. exploring architecture student's identity (Bilikozen, 2015; Thompson, 2019) and use of studio learning as pedagogy (Caldwell & Gregory, 2016; Mewburn, 2012). This research provides some insight into practices and some of the principles behind practices but often neglects linguistic practices i.e. language use. Research that focuses on written genres for architecture students is missing. Hyland (2002, p.394) suggests effective language teaching at university level needs to be specific and 'we must go as far as we can' in terms of specificity. In order to go as far as I can, I need to fill this gap in the literature and analyse the written genres and language use of architecture students at university.

9. Description of Method/ Protocol and Risks

9.1 Please describe your main method(s) or describe your protocol here, although ensure you do not replicate sections 11, 12 or 13.

The initial phase of research, which received favourable ethical opinion in December, involved accessing information, documentation and texts to find out more about architecture students and their academic written texts. This gathered information can now be used to guide selection of participants and texts for textual analysis in the final phase of research due to begin in May. This final stage of research will involve online recruitment of level 6 students studying architecture at the University of Portsmouth. Participants will be asked for the following:

Stage 1 (all participants- self-selecting sample from level 6 architecture): Permission to access submitted assessments. This includes electronic submissions via moodle and non-electronic submissions (e.g. models) which can be accessed during assessment and marking period and RIBA accreditation visit (permission from school [Oren: HoS] to access non-electronic submissions has been sought and agreed)

Stage 2 (all participants encouraged, but optional stage): Sharing of other authored texts, which may include but is not limited to: drafts of submitted assignments, plans for submitted assignments, lecture notes, and other texts students feel comfortable sharing and feel may be helpful in understanding process of text production as well as final product: submission. Participants are also encouraged to share and discuss texts they have read, e.g. those from reading lists, which informed their writing in order to develop understanding of intertextuality.

Stage 3 (some participants invited to discuss text via interview, optional stage): All participants invited to interview with the understanding that most participants may be unable/unwilling to be interviewed. Inclusion criteria: sharing of additional texts to provide a more in-depth understanding of process of text production

Exclusion criteria: participants who have yet to submit all assessments/texts as this could cause unnecessary pressure/distress for students and also would mean discussing

'incomplete' data i.e. full textual history. Self-exclusion due to self-identified limited availability and/or interest in participating.

9.2 Anticipated Ethical Issues

Potentially commercially sensitive data e.g. population data, assessment data and other data (e.g. retention and graduate outcomes) will not be included in final public thesis without prior permission of Oren as Head of School). Where possible all data will be anonymized and students provided with pseudonyms.

The nature of interviews i.e. reflecting on textual history and 3-year journey to graduation may trigger uncomfortable and/or negative emotions or memories for some participants. During a 3-year undergraduate course students may experience trauma, loss and/or mental health difficulties which may mean reflecting on the past is difficult/uncomfortable. Although the focus of interview is reflecting on texts rather than events and emotions, it is important to be mindful that some participants may want to share and reflect on experiences that have had an impact on their studies, particularly as a number of participants may want to reflect on the sudden loss of a much-loved lecturer (Martin Pearce) in summer 2019.

The focus of interviews (language used and textual history) will be made clear prior to and during interview. If participants share or reflect on events and/or emotions outside of the intended remit of the interview then they will be reminded of contact details for wellbeing and events/emotions may be explored if of relevance to research project and only if participants are comfortable in doing so. Participants will not be asked to comment on or engage with conversations they feel uncomfortable with. All interviewees will be sent contact details for wellbeing service before the interview via email and reminded of these during the interview.

9.3 Anticipated other Risks or Concerns

Have all risk assessments as required by relevant Health and Safety policies been completed?

YES

Risks to participants: There is a minimal risk, that as a result of interviews, participants may be negatively impacted by discussions and reflections on negative emotions and/or events. As mentioned previously, all participants will be provided and reminded of wellbeing service contact details.

Risks to researchers/ university staff/students: There is a minimal risk that participants report poor practice by other students e.g. academic malpractice and/or university staff e.g. misconduct. Again as the focus of the interview is the student's own textual history, this may be unlikely but is important to keep in mind. If participants do report poor practice of others and this practice raises concerns for the researcher, this will be discussed with supervisor

in order to decide if concerns can/should be passed on anonymously, if possible, and how these concerns may be shared.

Reputational risks: Any reputational risks will be mitigated, as far as possible, by anonymising participants, context and data where possible. The head of school and other colleagues from the school (Nicola Crowson and Bryony Whitmarsh) will receive regular updates on research to further mitigate reputational risks.

Security risks: Only possible security risk is if interview is conducted online. If interviews are conducted online then they will be via google hangouts and using institutional logins to ensure security of discussion.

9.4 Medical Cover (if applicable)

N/A

10. Compliance with Laws, Codes, Guidance, Policies and Procedures

This study complies with the ethical codes, policies and procedures outlined within the UK Research Integrity Office's code of practice for research and the University of Portsmouth's ethics policy. This study is also compliant with GDPR 2018.

11. Recruitment of Participants

11.1 Who are the Research/ Participant Population?

The research population is made up of students enrolled on the BA architecture course at [REDACTED] which currently totals 403 students. This research project will only include a convenience sample of students in level 6/year 3 of this course (115 students).

11.2 Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Participants will be a self-selecting sample from 115 students.

Inclusion Criteria: all 115 students invited to participate in sharing texts - self-selecting sample, consent for access to submitted assessments, additional inclusion criteria for interview: self-selecting, sharing of additional texts

Exclusion Criteria: students who have yet to submit all assessments/texts (e.g. level 4 & level 5 students and students with extensions) as this could cause unnecessary pressure/distress for students and also would mean discussing 'incomplete' data i.e. full textual history. Self-exclusion due to self-identified limited availability and/or interest in participating.

11.3 Number of participants (include rationale for sample size)
Target of approximately 20 for initial textual analysis. Quantitative analysis would suggest a sample of at least 43 based on population of 115 (https://blog.flexmr.net/sample-size-calculator) in order to be representative. As this research is a qualitative study, and not aiming for representativeness, and instead aiming for data saturation from a smaller number of participants, so has a smaller target for participants: 20. Of these 20 participants a smaller self-selecting group will be interviewed about their textual histories 5-10 interviewees.
11.4 Recruitment Strategy (including details of any anticipated use of a gatekeeper in host organizations to arrange/distribute participant invitations)
Participant invitations sent via institutional email with links to consent form, participant information sheet and study promoted by colleagues in online teaching sessions and/or tutorials.
11.5 Payments, rewards, reimbursements or compensation to participants
No financial incentive or reward
11.6 What is the process for gaining <i>consent</i> from participants?
Students asked to complete consent form and indicate interest in/consent for sharing of additional texts and interviews. Participants made aware of consent and consent confirmed at each stage of data collection.
11.7 Has or will consent be gained from other organisations involved (if applicable)?
N/A
11.8 Arrangements for translation of any documentation into another language (if applicable)?
N/A
11.9 Outline how participants can withdraw consent (if applicable), and how data collected up to this point will be handled. Also stop criteria for specific tests (if applicable)?
All participants will be informed of their right to withdraw consent for assessment access, additional text access and interview until the end of the data collection phase (June 2020). Participants will be provided with contact details to inform of withdrawal. If a participant withdraws consent after text collection, their texts will be disregarded from analysis, if a participant withdraws consent after interview, the interview recording will be deleted and not used in data analysis stage.

11.10 Outline details of re-consent or debrief (if applicable)?

Oren (Head of School) will receive updates on research on request.

12. Data Management

12.1 Description of data analysis

Some statistical analysis of numerical data e.g. student population and percentage of students with particular characteristics (depending on access to data). Some other statistical analysis including but not limited to averages/frequency e.g. number of learning hours, word counts and grades (depending on access to data). Textual analysis of data sources. Systematic analysis via a grid reporting on academic written texts undergraduate architecture students are required to submit as part of their studies including but not limited to word counts, timeframes, multimodality, reading lists and assessment guidance. Reports and other documentation will aid in understanding texts and assessments and how they may have developed/changed over time.

Genre analysis and discourse analysis of texts to identify text type (genre) and moves and steps within texts. Participants interviewed about texts and textual histories. Interviews will be recorded and transcribed. Transcripts will be shared with interviewees to check veracity and representation of interview. Transcripts then systematically reviewed and discourse analysis used to analyse discussion points and identify themes.

12.2 Where and how will data be stored DURING the project?

The data shared will be stored using a google drive folder which is password protected. The data may be discussed with supervisors but texts and transcripts themselves will not be shared.

12.3 Destruction, Retention and Reuse of Data (often AFTER your project has finished)

The data collected in initial stage will not be shared or made open access and will only be used to inform subsequent stage of data collection.

At this initial stage, collected data will be kept securely and remain confidential and not shared with others, but instead used to guide next stage of research. Texts featuring identifying data e.g. names of individual students/staff will not be used/included unless prior consent is requested and provided. The data, may accidentally identify staff/students e.g. through identifying characteristics: initials, student numbers but data will not be passed to anyone outside the study team (researcher and supervisors) without express written permission. Data will be kept in a password protected research folder on the university's google drive system. This folder and contents of this folder will not be shared with others. The data will be retained for a minimum of 10 years. When it is no longer required, the data will be disposed of securely (e.g. electronic media and paper records / images) destroyed." Note the policy for retention of research data requires retention for between 10 to 30 years and can be accessed from section 7, (and subsections) at the following links:

http://www.port.ac.uk/departments/services/corporategovernance/recordsmanagement/uop_retention/

12.4 Personal Data – How will confidentiality be ensured?
Personal data will not be shared with others. Complete confidentiality cannot be ensured but all data will be anonymized and identity of participants not disclosed. All data will be stored in password-protected google drive folder. Interview transcripts will use a pseudonym.
12.5 How will data belonging to organisations (publicly unavailable data) be handled (if applicable)?
Institutional data from the University of Portsmouth will be password-protected and not shared unless consent given provided.
12.6 How will security sensitive data be handled (if applicable)?
N/A

13. Publication / Impact / Dissemination Plans

No plans to publish or share findings at this stage. However, during the course of writing up findings opportunities to share and publish findings may present themselves. These opportunities will first be discussed with supervisor and gatekeeper. Participants will be made aware in consent process of publication of thesis and possibility of other publications during/or after thesis publication.

14. References

- Bilikozen, N. (2015). *Academic literacy development and identity construction of undergraduates at an American university in the UAE*. University of Exeter . Retrieved from <https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/bitstream/handle/10871/21547/BilikozenN.pdf?sequence=1>
- Caballero Rodriguez, M. d. R. (2003). How to talk shop through metaphor: bringing metaphor research to the ESP classroom. *English for Specific Purposes*, 22(2), 177–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(02\)00015-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(02)00015-7)
- Caldwell, E., & Gregory, J. (2016). Internationalizing the art school: What part does the studio have to play? *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 15(2), 117–133. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.15.2.117_1
- Creaton, J. (2015). Marking the boundaries: knowledge and identity in professional doctorates. In Theresa; Lillis, K. Harrington, M. R. . Lea, & S. Mitchell (Eds.), *Working with Academic Literacies*. Anderson: Parlor Press.
- Dias, P., Freedman, A., Medway, P., & Pare, A. (1999). *Worlds Apart*. New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410602336>
- Doloughan, F. J. (2002). The Language of Reflective Practice in Art and Design. *Design Issues*, 18(2), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.1162/074793602317355783>
- Garnet Education. (2019). Category: ESAP Series | Garnet Education. Retrieved March 10, 2019, from <https://www.garneteducation.com/category/english-for-specific-academic->

purposes/esap-series/

- Hartwick, J., & Barki, H. (1994). Research Report-Hypothesis Testing and Hypothesis Generating Research: An Example from the User Participation Literature. *Information Systems Research*, 5(4), 446. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.5.4.446>
- Heidenreich, S. (2016). *Englisch für Architekten und Bauingenieure - English for Architects and Civil Engineers : Ein kompletter Projektlauf auf Englisch mit Vokabeln, Redewendungen, Übungen und Praxistipps - All project phases in English with vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, exercises and practical advice*. Nurnberg: Springer. Retrieved from <https://wordery.com/englisch-fur-architekten-und-bauingenieure-english-for-architects-and-civil-engineers-sharon-heidenreich-9783658139537?currency=GBP>rck=ZGxJV2RqSG0rZ0tTZmt1d1luZXFZMnNnL2xJNG85VmRxdFcrbzRlclJjS0QyVnJGWIlpMzRkU0RuVnI4bnJvVGRwamtyL01TR>
- Hyland, K. (2002). Specificity Revisited: How Far Should we Go Now? *English for Specific Purposes*, 21, 385–395. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00028-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00028-X)
- Kuh, G. D., & Whitt, E. J. (1988). *The Invisible Tapestry. Culture in American Colleges and Universities*. Washington DC. <https://doi.org/ISBN-0-913317-45-4>
- Lasserre, B. (2012). Speaking the critique in graphic design: The role of metaphor. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 10(1), 51–66. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.10.1.51_1
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from [http://mathed811.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/63103234/Lave-Wenger-Situated Learning-Part I.pdf](http://mathed811.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/63103234/Lave-Wenger-Situated-Learning-Part-I.pdf)
- Lillis, Theresa. (2003). Student Writing as “Academic Literacies”: Drawing on Bakhtin to Move from Critique to Design. *Language and Education*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500780308666848>
- Medway, P. (2003). Imagining the building: architectural design as semiotic construction. *Design Studies*, 24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X\(02\)00055-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X(02)00055-8)
- Medway, Peter. (1996). Writing, Speaking, Drawing: the Distribution of Meaning in Architects’ Communication. In *The New Writing Environment* (pp. 25–42). London: Springer London. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-1482-6_3
- Mewburn, I. (2012). Lost in translation: Reconsidering reflective practice and design studio pedagogy. *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education*, 11(4), 363–379. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022210393912>
- Mey, K. (2013). The gesture of writing. In *Thinking Through Art Reflections on Art as Research* (pp. 217–228). London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203819869-25>
- Morton, J. (2012). Communities of practice in higher education: A challenge from the discipline of architecture. *Linguistics and Education*, 23(1), 100–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LINGED.2011.04.002>
- Morton, J. (2016). ‘Adjacent worlds’: An analysis of a genre at the intersection of academic and professional communities. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 22, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEAP.2016.01.003>
- Paltridge, B. (2004). The exegesis as a genre: an ethnographic examination. In L. . Ravelli & R. A. Ellis (Eds.), *Analysing Academic Writing*. Retrieved from <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=oi1XZ4MwYm8C&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q&f=false>
- Parkinson, J., Demecheleer, M., & Mackay, J. (2017). Writing like a builder: Acquiring a professional genre in a pedagogical setting. *English for Specific Purposes*, 46, 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESP.2016.12.003>

- Perks, S., & Whittingham, N. (2017). Timelines in design: Where linguistics meets design history. *Art, Design & Communication in Higher Education*, 16(1), 23–32. https://doi.org/10.1386/adch.16.1.23_1
- Riley-Jones, G. (2012). Critical thinking as an embodied criticality: The lived experiences of international art students. *Journal of Writing in Creative Practice*, 5(3), 401–421. https://doi.org/10.1386/jwcp.5.3.401_1
- Riley-Jones, G. (2017). There is a disease, and it's called Goldsmiths. Bristol: BALEAP 2017 conference. Retrieved from <https://baleap2017.files.wordpress.com/2016/01/all-sessions.pdf>
- Schön, D. A. (1991). *The reflective practitioner : how professionals think in action*. Basic Books. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com>
- Swales, J. M., Barks, D., Ostermann, A. C., & Simpson, R. C. (2001). Between critique and accommodation: Reflections on an EAP course for Masters of Architecture students. *English for Specific Purposes*, 20(SUPPL. 1), 439–458. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(01\)00020-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(01)00020-5)
- Thompson, J. (2019). *Narratives of architectural education: from student to architect*. New York : Taylor & Francis. Retrieved from <https://www.waterstones.com/book/narratives-of-architectural-education/james-thompson/9780815358817>
- Wiseman, C. (2014). *Writing Architecture : a Practical Guide to Clear Communication about the Built Environment*. Trinity University Press. Retrieved from https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=RUpC AAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT7&dq=%22Writing+architecture%22+wiseman&ots=vb5j6B-K1B&sig=1PsfMO_IQ-t2L8MD6s3rsgyRjHc#v=onepage&q=%22Writing architecture%22 wiseman&f=false

15. Appendices

Put N/A in version Number column if necessary			
Document	Date	Version No.	Appendix
Application Form	November 2019	1	N/A
Invitation Letter	November 2019	1	A
Participant Information Sheet(s) (list if necessary)	November 2019	1	B
Consent Form(s) (list if necessary)	November 2019	1	C
Advertisement	N/A		
Peer / Independent Review	N/A		
Supervisor Email Confirming Application	N/A		
Evidence From External Organisation Showing Support	N/A		
Terms of Reference for Steering / Advisory Group	N/A		
Survey Instrument	N/A		
Interview Questions / Topic List	N/A		

Focus Group Questions / Topic List	N/A		
Focus Group Ground Rules	N/A		
Script for Oral Consent	N/A		
Questionnaire	N/A		
Observational Data Collection Form	N/A		
Risk Assessment Form(s)	N/A		

16. Declaration by Principal Investigator and Supervisor (if applicable)

1. The information in this form is accurate to the best of my/our knowledge and belief and I/we take full responsibility for it.
2. I/we undertake to conduct the research/ work in compliance with the University of Portsmouth Ethics Policy, UUK Concordat to Support Research Integrity, the UKRIO Code of Practice and any other guidance I/we have referred to in this application.
3. I/we confirm that all relevant risk assessments and Health and Safety requirements have been made/met.
4. If the research/ work is given a favourable opinion I/we undertake to adhere to the study protocol, the terms of the full application as finally reviewed and any conditions set out by the Ethics Committee in giving its favourable opinion.
5. I/we undertake to notify the Ethics Committee of substantial amendments to the protocol or the terms of the final application, and to seek a favourable opinion before implementing the amendment.
6. I/we undertake to submit annual progress reports (if the study is of more than a year's duration) setting out the progress of the research/ work, as required by the Ethics Committee.
7. I/we undertake to inform the Ethics Committee when the study is complete and provide a declaration accordingly.
8. I/we am/are aware of my/our responsibility to be up to date and comply with the requirements of the law and relevant guidelines relating to security and confidentiality of personal data, including the need to register, when necessary, with the appropriate Data Protection Officer. I/we understand that I/we am/are not permitted to disclose identifiable data to third parties unless the disclosure has the consent of the data subject.
9. I/we undertake to comply with the University of Portsmouth Data Management Policy.
10. I /we understand that records/data may be subject to inspection by internal and external bodies for audit purposes if required.
11. I/we understand that any personal data in this application will be held by the Ethics Committee, its Administrator and its operational managers and that this will be managed according to the principles established in the Data Protection Act 1998 (and after May 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation).
12. I understand that the information contained in this application, any supporting

documentation and all correspondence with the Ethics Committee and its Administrator relating to the application:

- Will be held by the Ethics Committee until at least 10 years after the end of the study
- Will be subject to the provisions of the Freedom of Information Acts and may be disclosed in response to requests made under the Acts except where statutory exemptions apply.
- May be sent by email or other electronic distribution to Ethics Committee members.

13. I/we understand that the favourable opinion of an ethics committee does not grant permission or approval to undertake the research/ work. Management permission or approval must be obtained from any host organisation, including the University of Portsmouth or supervisor, prior to the start of the study.

Principal Investigator Jennifer Sizer.....

Date

14/04/2020.....

Supervisor (if applicable) Jane Creaton.....

Date

14/04/2020.....

14/04/2020

Appendix E: Research Ethics Checklist (UPR16)

FORM UPR16

Research Ethics Review Checklist

Please include this completed form as an appendix to your thesis (see the Research Degrees Operational Handbook for more information)

Postgraduate Research Student (PGRS) Information		Student ID:	up667970
PGRS Name:	Jennifer Sizer		
Department:	SELL	First Supervisor:	Glenn Hadikin
Start Date: (or progression date for Prof Doc students)	01/09/2019		
Study Mode and Route:	Part-time <input type="checkbox"/>	MPhil <input type="checkbox"/>	MD <input type="checkbox"/>
	Full-time <input type="checkbox"/>	PhD <input type="checkbox"/>	Professional Doctorate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Title of Thesis:	Architexts: building structure, building texture
Thesis Word Count: (excluding ancillary data)	53335

If you are unsure about any of the following, please contact the local representative on your Faculty Ethics Committee for advice. Please note that it is your responsibility to follow the University's Ethics Policy and any relevant University, academic or professional guidelines in the conduct of your study

Although the Ethics Committee may have given your study a favourable opinion, the final responsibility for the ethical conduct of this work lies with the researcher(s).

UKRIO Finished Research Checklist:

(If you would like to know more about the checklist, please see your Faculty or Departmental Ethics Committee rep or see the online version of the full checklist at: <https://ukrio.org/publications/code-of-practice-for-research>)

a) Have all of your research and findings been reported accurately, honestly and within a reasonable time frame?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
b) Have all contributions to knowledge been acknowledged?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
c) Have you complied with all agreements relating to intellectual property, publication and authorship?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
d) Has your research data been retained in a secure and accessible form and will it remain so for the required duration?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
e) Does your research comply with all legal, ethical, and contractual requirements?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>

Candidate Statement:

I have considered the ethical dimensions of the above named research project, and have successfully obtained the necessary ethical approval(s)

Ethical review number(s) from Faculty Ethics Committee (or from NRES/SCREC):	FHSS 2020-021
---	---------------

If you have *not* submitted your work for ethical review, and/or you have answered 'No' to one or more of questions a) to e), please explain below why this is so:

Signed (PGRS):		Date:	12/11/2025
-----------------------	--	--------------	------------

Appendix F: Participant Information Sheet (Version 5, November 2024)

Title of Project: Understanding language use of architecture students. A textographic analysis to inform English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) practice.

Researcher: Jennifer Sizer (up667970@myport.ac.uk)

Supervisor: Dr Glenn Hadikin (Glenn.Hadikin@port.ac.uk)

Ethics Committee Reference Number: FHSS 2020-021

To complete the consent form please visit:

<https://forms.gle/3oT2C4ArxYa9wvnB9>

More information about this research project, including participant information for students, is also available as a video: [youtube.com/watch?v=eDWvb70umfs](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eDWvb70umfs)

Invitation:

I would like to invite you to take part in my research study. Joining the study is entirely up to you, before you decide I would like you to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. I will go through this participant information sheet with you, to help you decide whether you would like to take part in the interview and answer any questions you may have. I would suggest this should take about 10 minutes. Please feel free to talk to others about the study if you wish. Do ask if anything is unclear.

In my previous role as English for Academic Purposes (EAP) for CCI coordinator at the University of Portsmouth, and my current role as Academic Language and Literacy Liaison for the School of the Built Environment at the University of Reading, my teaching has focussed on discipline-specific support for international students. My research so far has considered how international students can be supported through EAP and this research has highlighted the need for more specialised EAP provision. In order to provide more specialised EAP provision, I need to research the language use of students within a specific school [REDACTED]

Study Summary:

This study is concerned with the language use of architecture students including the texts students are expected to produce as part of their studies. This research is important because there is relatively little research and/or resources to support architecture students with language skills in order to produce academic texts (both verbal and written texts).

Participation in the research at this stage would require you to provide consent via the short consent form: <https://forms.gle/Uq92Kt8bx8Wiw75EA> for me to interview you. The interview will focus on students' text from the author's (former students) and audience's (staff's) perspective and interpretations of the texts. Interview discussions will be fairly unstructured and ask you to reflect on students' textual journeys during 3-year architecture degree with discussions of what language choices are made and what informs these choices based on your perspective, understanding and experience. Interviewees will be provided with relevant students' texts via google drive prior to interview and during interview via links and screen sharing. Interviews will be less structured in order to account for staff/student experience, responsibilities and interests which will influence whether the interview is broad and sweeping covering a number of years, modules, assessments and texts or more focussed e.g. one module, assessment and/or text type/genre e.g. 3rd year dissertations. However, a list of likely discussion/interview topics and themes will be provided in advance of interviews e.g. *texts such as dissertations (language used and choices made within the texts), textual history and textual journey, textual practices and processes, how others texts have influenced work, how context/s have influenced work and discussion about experiences as an architecture student and/or architecture lecturer*. If appropriate, this may include suggestions for possibly more focussed/semi-structured interviews with focus on particular modules, texts, text types/genres and links to text examples via google drive.

What is the purpose of the study?

My main aim in this EdD project is to understand the language use, as well as reasons for language choices, of undergraduate architecture students. I intend to identify language choices architecture students make in terms of genre (text types, structure and texture) in academic written texts. I intend to write up the final research project and submit it as a thesis to be examined as part of my professional doctorate in education.

Why have I been invited?

You have been invited to participate in this study as you have experience of studying and/or working with the [REDACTED] School of Architecture and Design.

The school of architecture was chosen due to the number of students, number of international students, number of undergraduate courses and previous engagement with English for Academic Purposes provision.

Do I have to take part?

No, taking part in this research is entirely voluntary. It is up to you to decide if you want to participate in the study. If you agree to take part, you will be asked to sign the consent form: <https://forms.gle/Uq92Kt8bx8Wiw75EA>

What will happen to me if I take part?

The researcher will invite you to participate in an interview to reflect on and discuss research findings from submitted work and interview discussion about: texts (language used and choices made within the texts), textual history and textual journey, textual practices and processes, how others texts have influenced work, how context/s have influenced work and discussion about experiences as an architecture student. The interview should last around an hour, but may run a little under or over depending on the conversation. The interview will be conducted online, so you will need a reliable internet connection and a digital device with a camera and microphone. The interview will be recorded and transcribed (writing out word for word what was said). Only the researcher will have access to the recordings and transcripts. You can request access to the recording/transcript of your interview if you wish to view these. You can withdraw consent up to 14 days after data collection without giving a reason. The transcripts will be analysed, and written up into a doctoral thesis, during which verbatim comments may be used. You will be assigned a pseudonym (fake name) in all analysis and writing up of interviews. Your data (interview recording and transcript) will be kept in a password-protected research folder on the university's Google Drive system. This folder, and the contents of this folder, will not be shared with others but as previously mentioned, excerpts and/or quotations from this may feature in future thesis and/or other published work. This data will be retained for a minimum of 10 years. When it is no longer required, the data will be disposed of securely (e.g. electronic media and paper records / images) destroyed." Note the university policy for retention of research data requires retention for between 10 to 30 years.

Expenses and payments: You will not incur any expenses by participating in this study and there is a £10 amazon voucher for participating in interviews as a thank you for your time.

Anything else I will have to do? No, thank you.

What data will be collected and / or measurements taken?

Identifying data will be changed or omitted to protect your identity.

Recordings and transcripts of interviews will not be shared with others (unless participants request to access recordings and/or transcripts) but verbatim quotes and images may be used within the writing up of the subsequent thesis. Pseudonyms will be assigned and identifying data omitted to prevent the identification of participants.

What are the possible disadvantages, burdens and risks of taking part?

It is possible, but very unlikely, that as a result of, or during an interview you may feel distressed or anxious particularly when reflecting on a time during your studies and/or career associated with more negative emotions. You will be provided with contact details for University of Portsmouth Wellbeing advisors and prompted to

make contact if the researcher believes support from wellbeing may be beneficial. If during an interview you disclose any sensitive and/or personal data that does not relate to this study, then it will be omitted. However, if it is pertinent, then it may be included but you will be anonymised. If you disclose concerns with regard to your own, or others' professional or academic practice during the interview, the researcher may be duty-bound to share the matter, if serious and warranted, with the identified supervisor and based on advice from this supervisor may also need to refer the matter to relevant internal/external person/s.

What are the possible advantages or benefits of taking part?

The overall research project intends to develop understanding of language use of undergraduate architecture students. This development in understanding should aid the researcher in producing learning materials and resources to better support future architecture students. Sharing findings with colleagues in architecture may potentially change and benefit teaching practice across the school.

Will my data be kept confidential?

Anything you discuss in the interview or is featured in submitted texts may be included in the study. However, you will be anonymised and efforts made to avoid identification such as use of pseudonyms and removal of identifying features in assessments and other data. Any raw data e.g. texts themselves and/or recordings and/or transcripts which may identify staff and/or students, will be kept securely by the researcher and will not be passed to anyone outside the research team without express written permission. Data will be kept in a password-protected research folder on the university's Google Drive system. This folder and the contents of this folder will not be shared with others.

The data, when made anonymous, will be published as a doctoral thesis (and a summary of which and link to shared with participants and Dr Lynne Meshor: Head of School) and may also be presented to others at academic conferences and/or may be published in academic journals and/or other publications such as books.

Anonymous data, which does not identify you, will be publicly shared at the end of the research project and made open access. A CC-BY licence will be applied to this publicly shared data. This will allow anyone else to use the anonymised data, providing they credit the University and research team as the original creators.

The data will be retained for a minimum of 10 years. When it is no longer required, the data will be disposed of securely (e.g. electronic media and paper records / images) destroyed."

If you have any queries about this project please contact Jennifer Sizer (main researcher: J.Sizer@reading.ac.uk) or Glenn Hadikin (supervisor) or if you believe your data has been used unethically or illegally or if you have any queries about how your data or the University's GDPR compliance, please contact the University's Data

Protection Officer, Samantha Hill, using any of the following contact details:
Samantha Hill, 023 9284 3642 or information-matters@port.ac.uk

University House, Winston Churchill Avenue, Portsmouth, Hampshire, PO1 2UP, UK

What will happen if I don't want to carry on with the study?

As a volunteer, you can stop any participation or withdraw from the study at any time before data collection without giving a reason if you do not wish to. You can withdraw up to 14 days after data has been collected. You can withdraw from the study up to 14 days after data collection, but you may be asked if data can be included in the study. If you prefer, the data can be destroyed and not included in the study. Once the research has been completed, and the data analysed, it will not be possible for you to withdraw your data from the study.

What if there is a problem?

If you have a query, concern or complaint about any aspect of this study, in the first instance you should contact the researcher (Jennifer Sizer) if appropriate. If not, then please contact my supervisor (Glenn Hadikin). If your concern or complaint is not resolved by the researcher or their supervisor, you should contact the interim Head of School: Dr Marjorie Huet-Martin marjorie.huet-martin@port.ac.uk (School of Education, Languages and Linguistics)

If the complaint remains unresolved, please contact: The University Complaints Officer,

023 9284 3642, complaintsadvice@port.ac.uk

Who is funding the research? There is no funding for this research and the researcher is self-funding their EdD study.

Who has reviewed the study? Research involving human participants is reviewed by an ethics committee to ensure that the dignity and well-being of participants is respected. This study has been reviewed by the Humanities and Social Sciences Faculty Ethics Committee and been given favourable ethical opinion: Reference Number: FHSS 2020-021

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet and for considering volunteering for this research. If you do agree to participate your consent will be sought; please see the consent form:

<https://forms.gle/Uq92Kt8bx8Wiw75EA>

**COSMOPOLITANISM IN THE POST COLONIAL MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE
IS MOROCCO LOSING ITS IDENTITY?**

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I want to thank everyone who has encouraged me, not only during the course of my studies but throughout my undergraduate degree. I wish to acknowledge the following people.

I want to thank my tutor, xxxxxx who has guided and supported me continuously.

I also thank Simohamed Achak and Abdelmagid Sanat for providing me detailed pieces of information regarding the history of the country.

I appreciate the help of the engineer Mounir Ajlane and the artist Mohamed Hakkoun who enriched my knowledge from an architectural perspective and provided an artistic insight for this dissertation.

Thank you to my friend and course mate Olivia Jones for her support and for help throughout this study.

I owe a debt of gratitude to my parents, xxxxxxxx and brothers, xxxxxxxx for their strong support and advice, and for always believing in me

TABLE OF CONTENTS:

INTRODUCTION	1
METHODOLOGY	2
MOROCCO GENERAL INFORMATION	3
WHAT IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE?	4
ANCIENT ARCHITECTURE	5
BERBER STYLE	5
PORTUGUESE INFLUENCE	6
THE ARAB-ANDALUSIAN TRADITION	6
COLONIAL ARCHITECTURE	7
CONTEMPORARY STYLE	8
FINAL DEFINITION	9
CASABLANCA	10-11
COSMOPOLITANISM	12
CASE STUDY 1	13-14
CASE STUDY 2	15-16
CONCLUSION	17
TARIQ OUALALOU	18
ILLUSTRATION LIST	19-20
BIBLIOGRAPHY	21

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary architecture is, to some extent, "Cosmopolitan Architecture," and it is part of a complex totality encompassing the conditions of its production, entertaining relationships with economy and politics. The framework provides the basis for understanding what contemporary architecture is and where it started from.

The architecture of colonialism in Morocco motivated the current contemporary vision. This was driven by the ideology and politics of the time.

"This type of style is one of the most spectacular manifestations of state manipulation of visual culture in the twentieth century. It was part of the means of imposing French hegemony upon a non-industrialized society."
(EL MALI, MOHAMMED, 1983)

This dissertation discusses the major issues caused by the entry of a "New" style in order to illustrate the contemporary architecture and town planning in Morocco.

Fig. 1 New buildings in Casablanca

Morocco is my Homeland. I feel very passionately towards the country and the architectural culture; this is the reason why I decided to carry on a study and to base my dissertation around it. Upon my recent visit to Morocco, I started to notice that it was starting to gradually lose its identity due to the new buildings and the different structures established within the country.

This phenomenon is evident in the City of Casablanca, which is losing its authentic Moroccan styles and designs. Casablanca is known for its traditional history of many different rulers which have gradually left their mark on the architecture in the city. The main purpose of this thesis is to examine the loss of identity within Morocco, especially focusing on Casablanca due to the impact of a cosmopolitan architecture. A modern architecture that oscillates between the national and international. I want to be able to reach out to the Moroccan community and the community of architects to remind them of the original use of Moroccan style architecture and emphasize the loss of identity as a country.

I want to make a difference and implement both modern and traditional architecture in Morocco together, in order to maintain the beautiful essence of my country.

METHODOLOGY

Morocco, specifically in Casablanca, is a country that hosted numerous "populations". These brought to the country multiple architecture styles which determined the Moroccan style.

The first part of the thesis will define what Moroccan architecture is and where it is originally stemmed from. It will be discussing the different layers that emerge with this specific type of architecture and define them in one single definition.

I will be analysing in depth the contemporary architecture in Casablanca and its cosmopolitanism with its major sponsors, and how it contributed to the loss of identity.

Additionally, I will be examining two case studies of which will be on the use of Moroccan style architecture and one of which will be focused purely on modern/ cosmopolitan architecture. Once I have completed this study and research, I will be able to evaluate which is the most suitable and has a positive impact on Morocco (Casablanca).

MOROCCO:

GENERAL INFORMATIONS

Morocco is a country in North Africa. It borders with Algeria on the east, with Mauretania on the south, with the Atlantic Ocean on the west and with the Mediterranean Sea on the north.

Surface: 710.850 Km² (including the disputed territory of Western Sahara covering 252.120 Km²)

Capital: Rabat (1,885,000 inhabitants)
Other major cities: Casablanca (3,356,000 inhab.), Marrakech (953,000 inhab.), Fez (1,072,000 inhab.), Tangier (794,000 inhab.), Kenitra (418,000 inhab.).

Population: 32.360.000 inhabitants (IMF estimates for 2012)

Fig. 1 Map of Morocco

Most of Morocco's population is made up of 65% Arabs and Berbers who have been able to adapt and preserve with the Arabic language and the Moroccan culture and from the south the Sahrawis. The conquest and Arab occupation have, in fact, profoundly influenced the characteristics of the pre-existing Berber society, of which the language, tradition, customs, and art that manifests itself in the geometric decoration of carpets and pottery and the manufacture of objects. The Arabic language and Islam is the religion that is practised in Morocco have gradually spread from the plains to the first slopes of the mountains, where the populations have become bilingual. Arabic is the most common used language in Morocco (63% of Morocco's residence speaking it as their first language). Furthermore, the remainder of Morocco speaks the language of Berber. The second language also spoken in Morocco is French and Spanish. When it comes to discussing the Religion that is practised in Morocco, Islam strikes first as 98.7% of the population follows it, and the remaining 1.1% are Christians, as well as a small community of Jews whom primarily reside in Casablanca.

Finally, the Currency used in Morocco is Dirham (MAD), Divided into 100 cents.

(Nevill BarbourL. Carl BrownWill D. Swearingen-Susan Gilson MillerAbdallah Laroui,2019).
(Anne,Allan Findlay 1995).

WHAT IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE?

Morocco is often viewed as an African Landmark that is surrounded by mystery, seduction and beauty. These opinions are reflected in the breath-taking architecture of Morocco. With the introduction of modern architecture in recent years, there has been a reform to traditional Moroccan architecture, which has come with the loss of architectural marvels. The architectural background of Morocco can still be seen in the modern buildings that are constructed today. -Architecture in Morocco is a mixture of black African and Islamic design styles, with the Islamic styles dominating in this combination. This can be noticed not only in the building itself but the lavish gardens, extravagant decorations and elaborate use of acute and contrasting colour. -There are quite a few dominant characteristics in regard to the architecture of Morocco. Most buildings feature large archways and beautiful domes that complete them. It is also common to find courtyards, sprawling gardens and the use of ornaments to decorate the exterior of the building. Moroccan architecture also makes use of calligraphy as decoration as opposed to pictures. Geometric patterns are also commonly found.

Morocco is known to be an open-air architectural museum, which its collection starts from roman architecture till contemporary architecture.

There are six architectural styles.

(Christopher Muscato, Moroccan architecture:style & elements)

WHAT

IS MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE?

1. ANCIENT ARCHITECTURE

The oldest traces of human life date back to an ancient phase of the lower Paleolithic era. In ancient architecture (or what's left of it) has left its mark in the northern area of Morocco Volubilis (Unesco heritage since 1997) and Chellah (located in Rabat) are the main cities that most represent the ancient culture within Morocco including; thermal baths, triumphal arches, Riyadh and houses. Such structures are finally decorated with mosaics showcasing an exquisite interior craft, colour, texture, architectural detail and decorative flourishes with mysterious lights.

2. BERBER STYLE

The Berbers are an ethnic group, native to Morocco, who have developed the first major architectural traditions of the region. Of these traditions, few have survived as well as the aesthetic created through the Berber use of mud brick as the most used architectural material. This is known as pisé in French, this material can be found across Morocco, even if the actual use of mud brick is not as common anymore. Berber architecture has left a memorable mark on the lands of southern Morocco, of which it is the symbol of Ksour (fortified villages), Kasbah (fortified houses) and agadir (fortified granaries) decorated with traditional geometric patterns that illustrates the magnificence of the Berber style. These castles of land and reeds represent the old history of Morocco which could disappear forever, due to the use of fragile materials.

Fig. 4 Volubilis, Morocco

Fig. 5 Chellah, Rabat

Fig. 6 Berber Architecture Ouarzazate, Morocco

3 PORTUGUESE INFLUENCE

The Portuguese influence was primarily limited in the coastal towns and cities, mostly located in the west of Morocco. For instance: El Jadida, Essaouria, Asilah, Azemmour and Safi all have in common their architectural heritage linked to the Lusitanian presence on Morocco soil. Witnesses of 354 years of Portuguese lust, the defensive fortifications, erected facing the blue waves of the Atlantic, recall a time when Mazgan (know as El Jadida in present day) and Mogador (Most commonly know as Essaouri) housed in military enclaves. If the “Algarve beyond” are well and truly over, these Moroccan cities retain superb examples of Portuguese architecture punctuated by long sandy beaches flooded with light.

4 THE ARAB-ANDALUSIAN TRADITION

The Arab-Andalusian style is the approach that one immediately thinks of when evoking the Cherifian Kingdom. Minarets, mosques, caravanserais, fortifications, monumental doors and palaces covered with calligraphy and arabesques evoke the richness and refinement of this city tradition inherited from Al Andalus.

Of the many influences on Moroccan architecture none have been as significant as those of Muslim Arabs. Islamic architecture is the most visible style of Moroccan architecture to this day. When looking for Islamic influences, you will be stricken with the intricate geometric patterns, ornate tile or woodwork and decorative calligraphy. Its highly decorative but also very consciously laid out. The courtyard layout is common in both ancient palaces and everyday homes, reflecting a clear division of public and private interaction. Apart from these elements, many common Islamic buildings have long been ubiquitous of Moroccan skylines. Mosques are found in every city. These features include Islamic-style domes and sky high minarets or towers. With water fountains readily built inside all Islamic buildings (Mosques, Palaces, Ryads and Government buildings).

Fig. 7 Essaouira, Morocco (Portuguese influence)
Fig. 8 Al Attarine, Fes (Arab-Andalusian architecture)
Fig. 9 Abu al Hassan, Sale, Rabat

5 COLONIAL ARCHITECTURE

The colonial architecture of Morocco flourished in the first half of the 20th century. Casablanca and Rabat, in the era of the French protectorate, saw the growth of new urban space under the leadership of Marshal Lyautey, the general at the time.

“From the 1930s on, colonial North Africa was transformed into a laboratory for European modernization fantasies. Casablanca was seen as a test case for the ‘city of tomorrow’, radical redevelopment plans included”.

(MARION VON OSTEN, 2008)

Colonial houses, Art Nouveau buildings, Art Deco buildings, and a neo-Moorish or Bauhaus-style were injected through European districts alongside the old centres called “Medinas”. Casablanca, “Deir Beida”, was the home of the craziest urban and architectural experiments of the time, the white city was then able to compete with the Haussmannian ensembles of Paris.

“For European modern architects colonial territories became laboratories in which they could realize their architectura: and urban concepts”

(ANNARITA FERRANTE, 2011)

The same architectural overview was happening in the cities of northern Morocco, marked by Spanish colonial architecture. At the start of the 20th century, the North African port and industrial town of Casablanca was strategically developed by Europeans for Europeans

Colonial housing and settlement policies radically changed cities, modes of living, and architectural discourse in North Africa and Europe alike.

Threatened by the indifference of the authorities and the real estate speculation which rages in the big urban centres, the colonial heritage is at the centre of attention of the associations of safeguarding the heritage.

Fig. 10 Cinema, Casablanca

Fig. 11 Colonial architecture, Casablanca

Fig. 12 Colonial architecture, Tangiers

6 CONTEMPORARY ARCHITECTURE

“The colonial architectural legacy has been a main source of inspiration to the foundation of a nationalist discourse on architecture. This nationalism is clearly both a discursive entity created by narrativity (and marked by a distinction between the political realm of nationalism, which is influenced by metropolitan precedents, and the cultural realm, where different Nationalist patterns are perpetuated”.

(PARTA CHATTERJE 1986 and 1993)

Contemporary architecture is not the style you always think of when you talk about Morocco. This may change the face of the Kingdom in the years to come.

Morocco started its journey to contemporary architecture from the colonial era, which introduced new styles to the country. These experimental styles guided the state into a process of full experimentation, specifically in the city of Casablanca.

This phenomenon has advantages and disadvantages, in some cities you don't feel in Morocco anymore due to this super modern landscape that has been created.

The Morocco Mall (Casablanca), the National Library (Rabat), and the headquarters of Maroc Telecom (Rabat) are some of the new architecture brought to the country. The great CasArts theater in Casablanca (signed Christian de Portzamparc and Rachid Andaloussi), the great theater in Rabat (signed Zaha Hadid), and the tallest tower in Africa, which should find its mark in the Bou Regreg valley in Rabat are the projects on their way to being completed.

Does this architecture represent the current society in its totality?

Fig. 13 Morocco Mall, Casablanca

Fig. 14 Maroc Telecom, Rabat

Fig. 15 The Great Theater, Zaha Hadid

HOW CAN MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE BE DEFINED?

"Morocco is a mosaic of different cultures and with-it different architectural styles"

(MOHAMED HAKOUN).

All these styles combine in one and form the Moroccan style; a combination of ancient architecture, Berber architecture, Portuguese history, Arab-andalusian architecture and, colonial architecture.

Moroccan architecture can be defined as an architecture that reflects the long and complex history of Morocco, a country that's been a crossroads of culture for centuries. This has created a unique culture that can't be found anywhere in the world.

Morocco is filled with exquisite architectural gems that tell the intriguing story of a country that has been continuously welcomed and absorbed by different cultures, lifestyles and beautiful designs.

Casablanca is the city that best represent this concept of mixture as an architectural style, and it is also the city where a metropolitan influence is currently taking place.

Morocco is filled with exquisite architectural gems that tell the intriguing story of a country that has been continuously welcomed and absorbed by different cultures, lifestyles and beautiful designs.

CASABLANCA: A DEFINITION OF MOROCCAN ARCHITECTURE

"Casablanca presents one of the best models of modernism as a way to build and house a city that combines order and excitement, mixed cultures, and offerors a dream of metropolitan possibilities".

(*"Casablanca presents one of the best models of modernism"*, AARON BETSKY, Dezeen, 2018)

However, does Casablanca continue to maintain its identity and true sense of place?

"The city can be big, it can be repetitive, it can be a bit of a mess, and it can be quite abstract in its form, and still – or rather, because off that – fell like the kind of place you as a human want to be in, because it will energise and frame you at the same time."

(*"Casablanca presents one of the best models of modernism"*, AARON BETSKY, Dezeen, 2018)

This thought was expressed by a tourists that visited the country, but what is the general opinion of the population?

A significant change is happening in Casablanca, enormous and super modern structures have been introduced. They are slowly changing the city, making it feel like a city that can be anywhere in the world due to striking resemblances in its architectural styles to cities like Dubai.

This can be viewed positively, as the city is becoming more international, but equally, it is losing its atmosphere and characteristics.

Casablanca is a city made of different neighbourhoods and areas defined by different usage and styles.

"Elle est divisée en trois quartiers : le Tnaker, au nord-ouest, occupé par les ruraux vivant dans les noualas (huttes en roseaux) ; le Mellah, au sud-ouest, aux constructions modestes, réserve à la population israélite ; enfin la partie la plus structurée de la cité, le long du port et sur la rive sud-est de la muraille où s'ouvre la porte Bab Souk vers l'intérieur du pays. C'est là que se concentre les bâtiments occupés par les étrangers (consulats, agences bancaires, hôtels et pensions), les maisons difiées par les négociants marocains, ainsi que les équipements publics."

(*"Une médina cosmopolite"*, e-taqafa.ma)

Casablanca is divided into three districts: the Tnaker, the Mellah and Bab Souk.

Tnaker is situated in the north-west, and it is the rural area of the economic capital. Mellah, in the south-west, is the Jewish part of the city characterized by modest housing and at the end Bab Souk which is the area occupied by the "foreigners" whose buildings consulates, banks, and hotels.

Its evident those in a position of power are focused on protecting the colonial architecture (experimental) rather than the existing structures that form part of Casablanca. There has been less focus or rather, a lack of attention on the districts that form-Casablanca. Parts of the old Medina will be destroyed to give space to new projects.

A group has been created to protect the colonial architecture in the city (Casamemoire), but what about the other architecture that makes up the Moroccan "touch"?

Currently, modern day Casablanca is seemingly carrying forward the sense of experimentalism left by the colonies, and is on its journey of becoming a Cosmopolitan city.

Casablanca “is a place where a particular mix of colonial importation and control, local initiative, and just plain good design created a city core that, though it has seen few major additions since 1950, looks as new as promising”.

(“Casablanca presents one of the best models of modernism”, Aaron Betsky, Dezeen,2018)

However the term “new”, in the 50s era , was a style of architecture that was highly influenced by existing Moroccan architecture at that time. It incorporated and merged the details of influences such as, Arab -andalusian. This is a clear contrast to the current and upcoming architecture in Casablanca, as there is no link or influence from the architectural background in the city due to its experimental and globalised nature.

Fig. 16 colonial experimental architecture, Casablanca

Fig. 17 arched street view, Medina, Casablanca

Fig. 18 Map of Casablanca

WHAT IS COSMOPOLITANISM?

“Cosmopolitanism can be defined as a global politics that, firstly, projects a sociality of common political engagement among all human beings across the globe, and, secondly, suggests that this sociality should be either ethically or organizationally privileged over other forms of sociality.”
(JAMES PAUL 2014).

This definition can also be adapted to architecture: cosmopolitanism is an address of thought that attributes to each city or country the citizenship of the world, deeming irrelevant the cultures, architectural styles or religious distinctions between nations.

These definitions yield cosmopolitanism as a positive phenomenon, simply because they give a balanced view of this process happening.

HOW DOES COSMOPOLITANISM RELATES TO MOROCCO?

Cosmopolitanism relates to Morocco, specifically, Casablanca, as the city in the last decade has started to look and feel more international and less Moroccan.

On one hand, this has a positive impact as the country is moving closer and establishing a connection with the rest of the world.

Nevertheless, this process in Morocco is not happening in a balanced way, but rather a quick and drastic manner. A large number of buildings have been built with an utterly distant style and in areas where they do not suit.

In Casablanca, if this process cannot be stopped, the city will risk becoming one of those popular cities around the world with a loss of authenticity and original values, with little cultural influence.

Today, globalization has taken over cosmopolitanism, which, if it represents the independence of economic and political processes, in reality, is a reduction of universalistic vocations to the homogenization of the world market.

Morocco is seemingly on the brink of becoming part of this Homogenized market...

Fig. 19 Cosmopolitanism

CASE STUDY 1

CASABLANCA MARINA

WHERE: Boulevard Des Almohades, Casablanca

FIRM:WATG

TYPE:Commercial , Retail, Hospitality, Sport, Bar/Nightclub, Hotel, Restaurant, Transport , Infrastructure,- Marina and Ports.

(ACHITIZER, 2012)

It is a project that is willing to create a new dynamic and modern marina in Casablanca for the locals and the visitors alike and to reconnect a part of the city back to its ocean frontage.

The architects created a place that embraces and celebrates the future of Casablanca. This concept has been applied by creating an animated marina edge which included a luxury hotel, boutique retail, cafes and restaurants. The tower hotel mainstay the project site and designs a visual mark to the rest of Casablanca. This is linked to a convention centre which provides scenery to a new public square. A four-star hotel provides a seamless connection with the adjacent retail centre.

Fig. 20 Part of th "Casablanca Marina"project

Fig. 21 Panoramic view of Casablanca Marina

"This new urban centre development will help propel Casablanca into the 21st century".(ACHITIZER, 2012)

This project has been conceived uniquely to drive Casablanca into the 21st century and make the city stand out globally. However, this raises the question of its connections with the area it has been built as well as its incorporation of the Moroccan Style?

Casablanca Marina is a project that can be realized in mostly all balneary cities around the world; this categorises the project as a homogenized version of architecture that has a loss in its originality.

Most of the buildings belonging to this project complex don't embrace, or better, adapt to the surrounding area its situated in.

The site is located between the harbour and the Hassan II mosque, as well as facing the Atlantic Ocean, it overlooks the old Medina on the other side.

The old Medina, characterized by robust stone walls, small shops and narrow streets is now hidden by the concrete and glass of the new Marina that already changed Casablanca's skyline.

CASE STUDY 1

CASABLANCA MARINA

Fig. 22 View of Casablanca Marina

Fig. 23 View of Casablanca Marina

Fig. 24 View of Casablanca Marina

CASE STUDY 2

THE GREEN QUARTER OF ANFA

WHERE: Anfa, Casablanca.

FIRM: Reichen & Robert & Associés

TYPE: mixed use

The Anfa quarter in Casablanca is destined to become a mixed-use quarter with a central park. The project extends over the City's old airport and preserves its old runway which has been used to accentuate the perspective views and guide the eye towards the sea and the Great Mosque.

The new Anfa quarter is established around a central 50-hectare park attached to the airport runway.

"The creation of a wooded park of this scale in Casablanca's Mediterranean climate requires the strategic management of water reserves. This 'Central Park' is thus "endowed with transversal branches forming a veritable ecosystem network. Its western sections are filled with fresh, shaded gardens planted with hydrophilic varieties that collect rainwater and make maximum use of the rainy periods. Organised in this way, the green canvas is able to receive the buildings of the new urban quarter".

(AGECETER, 2012)

The outside of the buildings is defined by green areas, secure design paths and delimited by common fences and a playground for children in the heart of the island, which allows a high quality of life together in the residence.

Visual comfort is provided by the appreciable views and the maximum natural brightness thanks to the studies of the architect Omar Alaoui.

The Anfa project has single-handedly given rise to a city with a population of 100,000, and thus created 100,000 jobs. The first operational phase has now been built while the public spaces are being designed.

"Anfa plays a special role within the City of Casablanca: it is a modest urban project by comparison with the immense territories open to urbanisation, and at the same time it is Morocco's flagship project, destined to be the symbol of urban renewal in the country".

(Reichen & Robert & Associés)

Green Anfa will also change the dynamics of the enormous city of Casablanca, as it will be a central location and meeting point for the society.

Fig. 25 Masterplan, Green Anfa

Fig. 26 render Casa Anfa

Fig. 27 Panoramic view Anfa

CASE STUDY 2

THE GREEN QUARTER OF ANFA

The Anfa Quarter in Casablanca, also, even if quite modern, merges quite well with the context. The designed towers are not too high, and they don't disturb the visitor's views. Traditional Moroccan geometric patterning is used for the membranes that cover the towers and Moroccan brick as well for some aspects of the project. These small touches may not be initially noticeable, but they really make a difference, and they adapt the project to the country's history. Furthermore, they create a sense of identity and connection with the rest of the city and its heritage, especially the Medina.

Fig. 28 Traditional patterning
Fig. 26 render Casa Anfa
Fig. 27 Panoramic view Anfa

CONCLUSION

To conclude Moroccan architecture is clearly taking a giant leap away from traditional styles that form part of the country's heritage and is evidently moving towards a more globalised or cosmopolitan approach in the formation of its new structures. As a result, the views of the general population are divided in their needs versus wants of maintaining a traditional approach in the design of newly established structures, in favour of preserving Moroccan culture, or incorporating a completely new contemporary design style to accelerate the development of its major cities.

Many architects incorporate aspects of landscape and urban design in the process of designing and shaping physical features of cities and consolidate this with a clear background understanding of traditional architecture that form the country's heritage. It is evident there has been a shift in the masterplans of architects from the 1940s, compared to the 1980s, as indicated by

"During the tours we encourage people to find something within the architecture that relates to our Moroccan culture – interior courtyards, the use of traditional crafts like zellij, ceramics, and how respect for the climate was incorporated into the builds".

(Mandy Sinclair, 2018).

This thought was of key importance around the 1900s, as conservation and the negation of historic buildings was first introduced to Morocco in this period by Lyautey. However, very few works of conservation took place during this period, and the few works of conservation that had successfully been carried out did not take into account international norms. The buildings were reconstructed with little attention to conserving prior works and upkeeping cultural character to the building.

In order to avoid a loss of identity to Moroccan architecture, both in present-time and in future, awareness to these matters must be created at the root of the problem; upcoming architects. First and foremost, the country's architects and its citizens must not deny its loss of architectural identity, but rather accept the progressive loss of heritage in its newly established buildings (particularly in Casablanca). Moving forward, we must acknowledge how a shift in architectural styles to modern approaches have led to a loss of identity and a result, instability in the nation. In this regard, we must follow the trend started by Marrakesh of mixing vernacular architecture and modern style. This could be adopted also in Casablanca by using the character of the old Medina and the Casablanca art deco with the contemporary style.

***“LE MAROC EST UNE INTERSECTION. TOUT CE QUE
L’ON Y CONSTRUIT A UNE RÉSONANCE TANT SUR LE
CONTINENT AFRICAÏN QU’EN OCCIDENT”***
(TARIK OUALALOU, 2019)

This is a message for the moroccan architects and the architects that work in Morocco. Creating spaces and projects in the country is a big responsibility and work that will influence the other countries.

ILLUSTRATION LIST:

Figure 0	Panoramic view of Casablanca	title page	Primary source
Figure 1	New Buildings in Casablanca	page 1	Retrieved from https://redac.leconomiste.com/flash-infos/casablanca-mais-que-devient-la-marina?page=1
Figure 3	Map of Morocco	page 3	Retrieved from https://www.shutterstock.com/image-vector/morocco-western-sahara-map-hand-drawn-147728906
Figure 4	Volubilis, Morocco	page 4	Retrieved from https://www.viator.com/it-CH/tours/Fez/Private-Day-Tour-to-Mknes-and-Volubilis-from-Fez/d221
Figure 5	Chellah, Rabat	page 4	Primary source
Figure 6	Berber architecture in Ouarzazate	page 4	Retrieved from https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/ber_architecture_in_the_town_of_Ouarzazate,_Morocco
Figure 7	Essaouira, Morocco	page 5	Retrieved from https://www.adventurous-travels.com/posts/essaouira
Figure 8	Al Attarine, Fes	page 5	Retrieved from https://photo.wn.com/Hathazari_Madrasa
Figure 9	Abu Al hassan, Sale, Rabat	page 5	Primary source
Figure 10	Cinema, Casablanca	page 6	Retrieved from https://www.awl-images.com/stock-photo-french-colonial-architecture-casablanca-morocco
Figure 11	Colonial architecture, casablanca	page 6	Retrieved from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/-pin/122089839869776829/?lp=true
Figure 12	Colonial architecture, Tangiers	page 6	Retrieved from https://www.alamy.es/imagenes/louvre.html
Figure 13	Morocco Mall, Casablanca	page 7	Retrieved from https://www.arup.com/projects/morocco-mall
Figure 14	Moroc Telecom, Rabat	page 7	Retrieved from https://www.glassdoor.co.uk/Photos/Maroc-T%C3%A9l%C3%A9com-Office-Photos-IMG1045555.htm
Figure 15	The Great theatre, Zaha Hadid	page 7	Retrieved from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/-pin/505951339381758473/?lp=true
Figure 16	Casablanca, experimental arc.	page 11	Retrieved from https://www.ratpdev.com/en/references/morocco-casablanca-tramway
Figure 17	Medina, arched street view	page 11	Retrieved from https://www.tripadvisor.com/AttractionProductRe-
Figure 18	Casablanca, map	page 11	Retrieved from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/-
Figure 19	Cosmpolitanism	page 12	Retrieved from https://twitter.com/donapadan
Figure 20	"Casablanca Marina" project	page 13	Retrieved from https://www.meetingsbooker.com/ve-
Figure 21	Panoramic view of Marina Casa	page 13	Retrieved from https://Int.ma/casablanca-mort-bles-
Figure 22	Views of Marina, Casablanca	page 14	Retrieved from https://www.google.com/search?q=casablanca+mari
Figure 23	Views of Marina, Casablanca	page 14	Retrieved from https://www.behance.net/gallery/3639039/Casablanca-Marina
Figure 24	Views of Marina, Casablanca	page 14	Retrieved from https://www.shutterstock.com/-search/casablanca+marina

ILLUSTRATION LIST:

Figure 25	Masterplan Green Anfa	page 15	Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&source=images&cd=&ved=2ahUKEw
Figure 26	Render GreenAnfa	page 15	Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&source=images&cd=&ved=2ahUKEw
Figure 27	Panoramic view Anfa	page 15	Retrieved from https://www.shutterstock.com/image-vector/morocco-western-sahara-map-hand-drawn-147728906
Figure 28	Traditional patterning	page 16	Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&source=images&cd=&ved=2ahUKEw
Figure 29	Render GreenAnfa	page 16	Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&source=images&cd=&ved=2ahUKEw
Figure 30	Panoramic view Anfa	page 16	Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&source=images&cd=&ved=2ahUKEw

BIBLIOGRAPHY AND ONLINE SOURCES:

- Nadia KHROUZ et Nazarena LANZA. (2015). Migrants au Maroc: Cosmopolitisme, présence d'étrangers et transformations sociale.
- Susan Gilson MILLER.(2013). A History of Modern Morocco.
- Hamid IRBOUH.(2005). Art in the service of Colonialism. French art education in Morocco 1912-1956.
- Stanford's travel CLASSICS.(1920). In Morocco.
- Ann M. FINDLAY, Allan M. FINDLAY.(1995). Morocco.
- Sater, JAMES. (2010). Morocco: challenges to tradition and modernity.
- EL MALTI, MOHAMMED. (1983). The architecture of colonialism, Morocco, 1912-1932: an enquiry into the determinants of french colonial architecture. Retrieved from <https://repository.upenn.edu/dissertations/AAI8326283>
- Nevill Barbour L. Carl Brown Will D. Swearingen Susan Gilson Miller Abdallah Laroui.(2019). Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/search?query=Miller,%20Susan>
- Christopher Muscato, Moroccan architecture: style & elements. Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/moroccan-architecture-style-elements.html>.
- Marion VON OSTEN. (2008). In the desert of modernity. Colonial planning and after. Retrieved from https://www.hkw.de/media/en/texte/pdf/2008_3/projekte_1/wueste_1/desert_exhibition.pdf and <https://www.e-flux.com/announcements/39015/in-the-desert-of-modernity-colonial-planning-and-after/>
- Annarita FERRANTE. (2011). Retrofitting and Adaptability in Urban Areas. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/35131879/Retrofitting_and_Adaptability_in_Urban_Areas
- Partha, CHATTERJE. (1986), Nationalist Thought and the Colonial World: A Derivative Discourse? Retrieved from <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/cgi/t/text/text-idx?c=acls;cc=acls;view=toc;idno=heb02425.0001.001>
- Mohamed HAKOUN.(2020). Primary source.
- AARON BETSKY.(2018). Casablanca presents one of the best models of modernism, Dezeen. Retrieved from <https://www.dezeen.com/2018/05/17/opinion-aaron-betsky-casablanca-modernist-architecture/>
- ADAM AYADI. (2015). Une médina cosmopolite. Retrieved from <http://www.e-taqafa.ma/node/1456>
- James, Paul (2014-05-16). "Political Philosophies of the Global: A Critical Overview". Globalization and Politics Vol. 4: Political Philosophies of the Global. retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cosmopolitanism#cite_note-6
- ACHITIZER, 2012. Casablanca Marina. Retrieved from <https://architizer.com/projects/casablanca-marina/>
- Koenrad BOGAERT. (2018). Globalized Authoritarianism: Megaprojects, Slums, and Class Relations in Morocco. Retrieved from <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=TCp0DwAAQBAJ&pg=PT15&lp-g=PT15&dq=marinca+casablanca+et+la+medina&source=bl&ots=K1ewH5n3DE&sig=ACfU3U0zoAf8BNfu7Ou856gdBY4tdksPlg&hl=it&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwirx728lu7mAhNTxUIHTA3AzcQ6AEwBXoECAoQAQ#v=onepage&q=marinca%20casablanca%20et%20la%20medina&f=false>
- Tarik OUALALOU.(2019). Tarik Oualalou, l'architecte franco-marocain qui invite à réhabiliter le monde. Retrieved from <https://www.jeuneafrique.com/mag/805665/culture/tarik-oualalou-larchitecte-franco-marocain-qui-invite-a-rehabiliter-le-monde/2019>
- Agente TER. (2012). Retrieved from <https://agenceter.com/en/projets/casablanca-quartier-vert-danfa/>

How can architecture in the polar regions inform us
about
extreme climate, building technologies and the
sociality of isolated living?

Date 29.01.21

Word count 5089

“Arctic Architecture”

Figure 25

Contents

Figures list	I - II
Acknowledgements	III
Abstract	IV
Introduction	1 - 2
Chapter 1 Climate/location	3 - 4
Chapter 2 Community	5 - 6
Chapter 3 Settlements	7 - 8
Case Studies	9 - 10
Discussion - Conclusion	11
Final Remarks	12
Bibliography	13, 14 ,15, 16
Appendix	17 - 18

List of Figures

Figure	Image title	Page number	Reference/source
1	Airship Italia	1	The Italia. [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from https://welweb.org/ThenandNow/zeppe-lincoln/norway.html .
2	La Tenda Rossa film poster	1	The red tent. (1971). [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from https://ffffmovieposters.com/shop/red-tent-the-13/ .
3	Venn diagram	2	Authors diagram (primary source)
4	Arctic landscape	2	Arctic Landscape. (2021). [Image]. Retrieved 25 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/152911349837630954/ .
5	Arctic circle infographic	3	Arctic circle location and geography. (2006). [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from http://polardiscovery.who.edu/arctic/geography-en.html .
6	Koppen Geiger classification	3	Koppen Geiger Classification. [Image]. Retrieved 25 January 2021, from http://stream1.cmatc.cn/pub/comet/MountainMeteorology/SnowpackanditsAssment/comet/afwa/snowpack/navmenu.php_tab_2.1.6.htm .
7	Arctic Walrus	4	Arctic Walrus. [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from https://oceana.org/marine-life/marine-mammals/walrus .
8	Arctic blizzard	4	Olson, B. (2017). The Gallahan shelter is bombarded by a late-winter blizzard [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from https://www.adn.com/alaska-life/we-alaskans/2017/03/19/when-arctic-winds-blow-from-nome-to-kivalina-on-fat-tire-bikes/ .
9	High Albedo	4	Arctic Albedo. [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from https://arctic-council.org/en/projects/arctic-black-carbon-case-studies-platform/ .
10	Inuit Hunting	5	Cheek, J. (2009). Inuit men hunting in traditional dress, Nunavut, Canada [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from http://www.sciencepoles.org/article/examining-indigenous-sea-ice-knowledge-and-use .
11	Inuit kayak	5	Traditional Inuit Kayak. [Image]. Retrieved 16 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/322711129528566302/ .
12	Station Nord Soldiers	5	Kingsley, J. (2019). Soldiers eat lunch next to an iceberg [Image]. Retrieved 15 January 2021, from https://www.nationalgeographic.co.uk/environment-and-conservation/2019/08/arctic-science-base-life-anything-lonely .
13	Rothera Research Station	6	Clark, P. (2018). The British Antarctic Survey's Rothera base, surrounded by icebergs [Image]. Retrieved 27 January 2021, from https://www.ft.com/antarctica .
14	Construction workers at Rothera	6	Institute of materials, minerals and mining. (2021). Construction team clearing snow to start work on building the new scientific support facility © BAS [Image]. Retrieved 26 January 2021, from https://www.iom3.org/resource/construction-in-extreme-environments-at-rothera-research-station.html .
15	Rothera Yoga class	6	Clark, P. (2018). An outdoor yoga class at Rothera [Image]. Retrieved 27 January 2021, from https://www.ft.com/antarctica .
16	Norilsk Building landscape	7	Norilsk Russia. [Image]. Retrieved 16 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/747034656924405474/i
17	Norilsk Building	7	Chernyshova, E. (2015). Norilsk Architecture [Image]. Retrieved 16 January 2021, from https://meduza.io/en/galleries/2015/04/02/life-in-norilsk .
18	Community of Igloos	8	Igloo village with eskimos greeting an explorer. [Image]. Retrieved 26 January 2021, from https://www.sciencephoto.com/media/320719/view .

19	An Inuit's igloo	8	Inuit's standing outside an Igloo. [Image]. Retrieved 27 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.ca/pin/133771051405296329/ .
20	Antarctica Halley VI research facility	9	Halley VI British Antarctic Research Station. (2013). [Image]. Retrieved 16 January 2021, from https://hbarchitects.co.uk/halley-vi-british-antarctic-research-station/ .
21	Interior of Halley VI	9	I. Hamilton, W. (2013). The recreation area's was chosen to invigorate or calm [Image]. Retrieved 27 January 2021, from https://www.interiordesign.net/slideshows/detail/7459-come-in-from-the-cold-hugh-broughtons-antarctic-re/ .
22	Inuit building an igloo	9	Inuit building an igloo. [Image]. Retrieved 26 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/619596861233204567 .
23	Construction of a module of Halley VI	10	Grozdanic, L. (2014). Construction of a module [Image]. Retrieved 26 January 2021, from https://in-habitat.com/halley-vi-the-worlds-first-modular-research-station-in-antarctica-can-climb-through-snow/halley-vi-antarctic-reasearch-station-hugh-broughton-architects-7/ .
24	Inside an igloo	10	Inside an Igloo. [Image]. Retrieved 16 January 2021, from https://www.dkfindout.com/us/history/native-americans/inuit/ .
25	Arctic iceberg from above		Schauer, M. Ice bergs in the Arctic ocean [Image]. Retrieved 26 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/665055069955340508/ .
26	Iceberg	IV	Iceberg. [Image]. Retrieved 28 January 2021, from https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/468304061239565374/ .

Acknowledgements

I must say in the past few months of writing this dissertation I have thoroughly enjoyed it, the arctic landscape and architecture has intrigued me from the beginning and through to the end. I must at this point give my thanks and admiration to xxxx, my dissertation tutor, his truly great advice and ability to always have the right answer. His help has been very much appreciated.

CONFIDENTIAL

Abstract

The polar regions of the world to many people is just a place that is very cold and full of snow. How wrong they are, the Arctic and Antarctica are incredible places full of diversity and life. Many explorers have ventured to far corners of the earth and come back with more than just stories.

However, very little has been created in terms of architecture. As to create architecture in the polar regions you can not just place a structure in an arctic location. First you must take into account the environment and location and the challenges that one will face. Secondly, the human aspect of comfort must be understood, and natives must be respected. Thirdly, one shall have to examine what settlements already exist to learn what is successful. Lastly, architecture and building technology are important to consider before one would embark on building in the arctic. Once these factors have been studied then a discussion will take place to evaluate if one should consider the arctic or Antarctica as a sustainable and smart decision to create architecture.

The arctic, the final frontier

The arctic, the final frontier. A Largely unexplored place compared to other regions of the Earth. Questions have risen before from explorers if the arctic was habitable. There has been thought on what needs to be provided for sustainable living in such a harsh climate. An everchanging place with global warming melting most of the arctic's land. One could imagine there would be many challenges that one would face if they were to build a small settlement. What would be the solutions for energy conservation, the lack of food and the sunless months in the winter? Could a building help improve the local ecosystem rather than disturb it? Indigenous people have shown that it is possible to survive the extreme environments of the arctic. However, there is a key difference between surviving and living.

The well-known case of Umberto Nobile's expedition can be considered here as a case study that allows us to identify key aspects of the polar regions. Umberto Nobile's airship floated to the north pole within 24 hours from the Svalbard islands his crew dropped an Italian flag to mark the achievement. Flying his airship on return from the North Pole approximately 30km from the finish the arctic weather took a vicious turn as the strength of the wind and snow started to batter the thin exterior of the airship. Then the over the next two minutes Umberto Nobile and his crew of 16 plummeted down into the frozen ice below. Analysed today, this story has a lot to teach us about architecture as a mediation between man and habitat. The story of Nobile, who, for the technologies of the time, can correspond to today's attempt to terraform deserts or a trip to the moon, is a lesson in architecture because what can be done (or can not be done) in extreme conditions it is even more valid in environmental conditions closer to our thermal and psychological comfort.

As the only existing "architecture", the cockpit, was completely destroyed the eleven who survived two of which were severely injured faced an ordeal before them which they would have prayed to never be possible. Stranded in the arctic, with a radio and minimum food supplies survived the crash. For the next forty-eight days, the men had to ration out food, keep sane and hope for rescue. The men re-discovered the basic rules of survival. A few of them killed a bear gifting the crew with meat for food and fur for warmth.

Figure 1

This was the first of the numerous dangers of the arctic. Which demonstrates that, reduced to minimal terms architecture, as a system of mediation with the habitat, lays its foundations, before technical aspects, on the idea that humanity is able to survive only if it is part of a cohesive and supportive community. (see Appendix A)

Figure 2

Ingenuously the survivors in the Arctic had created a tent structure from a white curtain and covered it in aniline giving it a red colour. Better known as the red tent. Which the film by Mikhail Kalatozov, La Tenda Rossa was based on. The red colour made it more detectable to any rescue planes flying over the white snow.

The harsh environment and deafening silence pushed the men to their mental limits. After a few days sensory deprivation started to set in making it harder for them to concentrate and communicate within the group. Visually all the survivors could see was featureless landscapes with only the wind and the silence of the snow to add to the feeling of isolation. Their brains were starved of visual stimulation which allowed the brain to start to create hallucinations. In this case, experience describes another fundamental need of architecture which, taken to the extreme consequences of the Antarctic, becomes paroxysmal. It is not enough for architecture to respond positively to the primary needs of humankind. The colours, the landscape and the context, as well as essential for communicating and as tools for representing one's identity, which evidently highlights the ancestral needs of the community (The Red Tent), also demonstrates that the absence of sensory qualities, in our habitat, leads us to alienation and self-destruction. Therefore, a rational architecture is not enough, if its reductionism does not fulfil our deepest, unconscious and metaphysical needs.

My curiosity directed me to the arctic as a field of life and research. I feel much about the arctic is unknown and only recently with in the past 100 years has significant studies taken place. I want to discover what it would take to create a long-lasting architecture project in the extreme environment. Could a large settlement be created to support humans and other life forms? Additionally, I am intrigued to understand just how extreme the climate is, what is unique about this place that makes it challenging. With climate change and global warming becoming more important, it is key to understand what is happening and how would it impact the future of architecture in the arctic.

Furthermore, how have Innuits survived there for as long as they have and why do non-natives struggle mentally and physically. Not many architects have ventured as far north as my research will take me to where there is a gap in knowledge concerning the type of design strategies that one would use. (see appendix B)

Figure 3

In the future a study of which I am about to undertake could be the inspiration or generate thought into living in extreme environments around the globe and other planets. In a current study, scientists have been placed in Antarctica to record what isolated living is like whilst working with astronauts on the ISS to compare data sets and observations. This could also encourage innovation in technological advancements for architecture as new constructions methods and materials could be developed to adapt to these known harsh environments.

Figure 4

Chapter 1 - Climate/Location

After the crash of Nobile's airship, the men had to face the environment of the arctic a place not easy for survival with limited resources. The study of the Arctic (and Antarctica) is considered extremely relevant for scholars because it offers insight into the most extreme conditions on our planet, which can be studied to understand the limits of human survival. Research stations such as Rothera Research Station have been built to investigate questions of the environment, climate and to observe how humans deal with isolation. (Bliss, 2020) Furthermore, being a habitat with a limited urban presence, it can offer useful data on the ecology of the planet and constitute a useful reference as a seismograph of the health of the earth.

The location of the arctic can be difficult to define as it does not describe one land mass but rather an ocean with moving land. Sir David Attenborough described the Arctic as "A frozen ocean ringed by land." (2019) as it is the region above the Arctic Circle at the top of the planet (66° 34' N). Other scholars also describe the arctic circle as the place where no trees or plants grow because of the frozen landscape where the daily average summer temperature does not rise above 10 degrees Celsius. ("What is the Arctic? | National Snow and Ice Data Center", 2020).

According to the widely accepted Köppen - Geiger climate classification, ("World Maps of Köppen-Geiger climate classification", 2019) the arctic is classified as zone E, a polar zone, which is then divided further into tundra regions or snow and ice regions. (National Geographic Society, 2019;(Serreze & Barry, 2005, p. 39; Arnfield, 2020). The exact size is also hard to define as the ice is constantly growing and melting. It is estimated that during the winter months the total land mass is 5.8 million square miles and in the warmer summer months the number shrinks down to 2.7 million square miles. ("Arctic vs. Antarctic | National Snow and Ice Data Center", 2020). It acts "like a lung the sea ice breathes over the top of the earth going forward then retreating", Sir David Attenborough (Lanfeair, 2019).

Figure 6

With the arctic being so far north the earth's tilt and orbit have a large influence over the seasons. This region receives less solar energy and heat from the sun as it is set much farther back. Which leaves the polar regions with only two seasons, being summer and winter. ("Dive and Discover : Antarctica : Seasons", 2020). The vertical line of the north pole is tilted 23.5 degrees away from the sun. This angle and rotation are maintained throughout the year. During the summer solstice the length of the days will increase dramatically to a point where the sun will not move below the equator and will be visible for 24 hours. (Gedney, 1984). This is often known as the midnight sun, as it best describes the sun appearing at midnight. (Tours, 2019). In contrast the winter solstice, starting on December 22nd the days with sunlight will become incredibly short and soon disappear. As the sun cannot reach the arctic due to the angle of the tilt. ("Winter Solstice", 2005). The north pole 90°N will then be plunged into total darkness for 163 days. ("Day Length", 2020). An important characteristic of this environment when planning for long term settlement. The seasons will raise questions on how to adapt building technology to compensate for the lack of light in the winter months.

As well how humans will be able to physically and mentally survive with the extreme versions of the two seasons of winter and summer.

The majority of arctic land and sea ice has a snow covering for over half a year. The snow is a key climatic variable as it performs three significant functions for the environment. The insulating effect it has on sea ice which allows ice to be maintained and for land mass to be created. Its high albedo of the white colour which reflects solar waves and prevents the snow from absorbing solar radiation. The third being the snows role in storing precipitation over physical regions. (Serreze & Barry, 2005) The arctic winds are a prominent feature to consider as they can greatly influence the temperature of the regions. (see appendix C)

Figure 9

The snow covering in the arctic has great impacts not just for the polar regions but for the planet. If the sea ice was to shrink, then the albedo effect would accelerate global warming. As “the darker oceans and land will absorb 90% of that heat” as said by Peter Wadhams, professor of ocean physics. However, when sea ice melts it floats but when land ice melts it causes sea levels to rise greatly. Which poses a great risk to any person living on a coastal city anywhere in the world. (Potenza, 2018)

Figure 8

The life in this region survives some of the harshest extremes on the planet in terms of light and temperature. In the arctic a complex ecosystem exists which hosts an abundance of life with a delicate but balanced food chain. This system is also key to recycling carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. As carbon cycles from the atmosphere to the seawater. Once in the water phytoplankton and algae can convert it into an organic carbon of their tissue. (Ashjian, 2020). In a way they can extract a heat-trapping gas from going to the atmosphere and keeping it at the bottom of the sea. A distribution of this ecosystem can have grave consequences as “They are responsible for half of the photosynthetic activity in earth” (Agar, 2019) This food chain is directly accessed by humans who consume the fish which have eaten the phytoplankton, if you were to kill of the start of the food chain then rest would fall apart.

Figure 7

The arctic has a rich marine ecosystem with the ocean being the least salty due to the low evaporation and vast influxes of freshwater from rivers and glaciers. Rivers deriving from Russia and North America, which flow to the arctic via the transpolar drift stream. (Freshwater circulation in the Arctic Ocean, 2020).

Chapter 2 - Community

Nobile and his team had to work together as a community in order to survive. The polar regions of the Earth may seem inhospitable to many but there exists a population of Inuit natives that have lived for 5,000 years. Their territories cover the shores of Russia, Alaska, Canada, and to the southern coast of Greenland. (5000 Years of Inuit History and Heritage, 2004) Many non-natives such as explorers, scientists and soldiers have only started living there in a very small capacity as recent as 100 years. Both natives and non-natives deal with the same extreme conditions but with different, various methods. This chapter analyses how natural resources are used, how group dynamics can influence the chance of survival and what effect the environment can have on mental health.

There are many indigenous cultures of the polar region, such as the Yupik and Inupiat of Alaska and Russia and Inuit from Greenland and Canada. (5000 Years of Inuit History and Heritage, 2004) Traditionally the indigenous Inuit people would usually live on coastal areas with access to open waters and land. As here a “food supply would be obtained by hunting and fishing” (Sugden, 1982), having two areas for resources prevents the people from being reliant on just one food source. Most of the food hunted and consumed by native people include marine wildlife such as seal, fish, whale and land animals, polar bear, caribou etc. The term Inuit derives from native American Indians meaning ‘eaters of raw meat.’ (Sugden, 1982) Consistently, natives will consume animals raw as they believe it “is effective in keeping the body warm, making the mind strong, keeping the body fit” Searles, E. (2010) Their diet reveals a deep understanding of the available resources in the extreme environment. They rely heavily on hunting skill to survive as the icy conditions prevent any fruit or vegetables to be cultivated and gathered. Which is a key factor that separates this culture of people from other hunter groups from around the world. As resources are very sparse, the animals caught are not just used for food but also for clothing. They convert sealskin into a waterproof for water travel in kayaks. (Sugden, 1982) The native people of the arctic appreciate and can successfully use resources of the environment which make surviving more manageable.

Figure 10

Their response to the two extreme seasons has influenced culture as it brings annual migrations across the arctic. “The dominant movements of the Inuit were in response to the annual rhythm and were concerned with the search for food and clothing” (Sugden, 1982) The local knowledge of areas to move to and from at certain times of the year demonstrate necessary awareness for survival in a polar environment. (see appendix D)

Figure 11

Whilst Antarctica is a protected land where no one country can claim ownership the Arctic is more complicated. Which has led to many army bases being set up to claim parts of the land for strategic reasons. (see appendix E)

Denmark has set up Station Nord a military outpost 575 miles from the North Pole. Six specialists, soldiers live here for 26-months at a time and will also be the only ones in the winter months to keep the base running. (see appendix F)

Figure 12

Natives are not the only group of people who have ventured and settled as far north as the arctic circle, the region is seen by many scientists as a place of very little urban disturbance. Often teaming up with national armies, who provide support, numerous experiments and research projects have taken been conducted.

Open all year round the Rothera Research Station in Antarctica provides a good insight for the human aspect of how difficult isolated living can be. During the winter months of April to October, the station will have 22 members that will continue science projects and maintain the infrastructure. There is variety of roles for the wider project to be functional for example, staff include a chef, doctor, electrician, plumber, carpenter, terrestrial biologists, meteorologists and field assistants. (“Rothera Research Station - British Antarctic Survey”, 2020) Many workers depict an isolated feeling or ‘cabin fever’ once the sun sets and the permanent darkness takes over the flat barren landscape. The cause for the stress can be categorised into three parts, isolation, confinement and environment. (A. Palinkas, 2000) Aurelia Reichardt a scientist at the station describes the situation, “I remember some winter storms lasting over a week, with visibility of just 10 metres, howling wind and utter, utter darkness. In these conditions, after a few days, I found myself irrationally annoyed, or stressed and on edge for no apparent reason.” This small quotation shows the start of a change in mentality; the stress is a key indicator that the environment is not as comfortable as it could be.

Figure 15

Figure 13

Figure 14

The negative effects can also affect the quality of work being done which could produce inaccurate data. Reichardt also notes that “Having a private room massively helps and provides a safe haven to retreat to,” which could suggest that architecture can influence the mental stability of the environment. One comfort that scientists have is the ability to have food supplied and delivered throughout the year, instead of having to hunt and live off the land. The supplies can also be tailored for dietary requirements and there is a full-time chef on the station to cook for them, this factor could make the experience easier.

Clearly in the polar regions the effects of the environment are known and have been documented. It also interesting to know how different places have put procedures and strategies in place to reduce the negative effects. The planning for the trips to these intense environments is very thorough which shows the complexity and huge potential danger to the lives of the workers. The natives who have grown up with the snow and low temperatures are much more adapted and will not feel the impact of the surroundings as severely as non-natives.

Chapter 3 - Settlements

The team of men from the crash created a small temporary settlement with the red tent being the at the centre as the only form of shelter from the elements. There is an extensive history of various settlements being created by different groups of people. In ancient times Europeans from Norway have places such as Greenland and Iceland as a point of exploration and home. Whilst natives have continuously had non-permanent settlements until recently when the intervention of the western world changed their ways. Urbanisation has also had its influence on regions in Canada, Alaska and Russia as the Arctic has many natural resources hidden beneath the surface. This research will provide the wider context to large scale living in the arctic and inform me about any characteristics or systems that exist and if it is successful.

Figure 17

One of the major cities that exists in the Arctic Circle is the city of Norilsk, Russia. The whole population of 175,300 all works for the largest steel and iron foundry in the world. The city is one massive industrial mining complex for Norilsk Nickel, so large in fact that it makes up 2% of Russian GDP. The layout was designed in the 1940s by architects who were either exiled or imprisoned. The aim was to create a coherent and logical plan. (Zoo, 2016) A fascinating detail is the very narrow alleys and gaps between buildings which prevent the high winds from disturbing the people on the inside.

Figure 16

This city demonstrates the most industrial approach to the arctic partly due to the socialist modernism movement of the time. However, even though the conditions here are unique, the buildings are still similar to other Russian cities from the 1940s era. Proving that an arctic settlement can be very simple. This city however does suffer terribly from the pollution due to the mining which has frequently caused acid rain and dense smog, it can be very harmful to anything living there. (Love, 2014)

Inuit's traditionally utilize an alternative approach to creating settlements and villages in the arctic. As they are nomadic people, they create summer and winter camps and migrate to wherever there is food. Therefore, their homes are temporary and easy structures to deconstruct and build quickly. In the summer months tents would be made from animal skins and use driftwood as poles. As building materials such as timber were scarce, they were guarded heavily. Families would join each other to create small villages to share resources; some could have up to 30 people. This way of community living is very traditional and is reminiscent of how early man lived. It also gives insight as to why the architecture is the way it is for the summer months. In the winter individual families would disperse across the land, and the accommodation would also change.

Figure 19

Igloos would be created from the only available material, snow. Large igloos could accommodate up to 20 people and would be used for the duration of the winter stay. If the Inuit's were hunting and sensed a storm, they would create smaller igloos to protect them. ("The Arctic People - Environment / Housing", n.d.)

Figure 18

Adapting to the climate the Inuit once again provide evidence of how they have survived for as long as they have in the wilderness. The two distinct settlements here provide a stark contrast in how people could live in the arctic. Furthermore, it shows how modern technology has influenced ways of living and the types of buildings constructed.

Case studies

Nobile's red tent was perhaps not the best example of architecture in the arctic, but it was a shelter, nevertheless. Building on from a climatic, social and settlement investigations I shall examine more critically specific polar architecture projects. I have chosen these two case studies as there is a stark contrast between the igloo which is a traditional temporary structure for shelter for Inuit people and the research station a permanent structure for scientists using the latest technology available at the time of design. By comparing these two it will deepen my understanding of what is possible in terms of architecture technology and materials in the polar regions.

Previously I touched upon the igloo and how it is used within Inuit settlements for survival in winter throughout the Arctic. This pioneering piece of architecture is exceptionally resourceful. In Antarctica, the Halley VI Research station is home to a research team throughout the year. The research facility design principles focus on "survivability, maintainability, and liveability" ("Halley VI Research Station", 2020) The structure is split into eight individual modules which are interlinked. Each module serves a function such as offices, bedrooms, laboratories, and energy plants. The central red module is two-storey which provides a social space. Each half has its own energy centre and is self-sustaining.

The stability of the igloo relies heavily on the material used to construct it. Which is older solid snow as freshly laid surface snow being too powdery to create a stable structure. (keartes, 2017) The round dome shape uses the same idea as an arch in the use of compression to be stable. Using compressed snow blocks as bricks is considerably better than sculpting solid ice for insulation. The snow is 95% air trapped inside tiny crystals, which prevents any circulation which in turn traps heat. (Greenway, 2019)

Figure 21

Figure 22

Thus, this structure has no need for an external energy source to provide heat. The body heat of humans and maybe a small oil lamp can heat these homes up to 40 degrees above the outside temperature.

Figure 20

Figure 23

Alternatively, the designers and engineers for Halley VI used advanced energy-saving technology such as translucent nano-aerogel panels. These panels have an extremely high thermal efficiency and when incorporated can reduce heat loss greatly in the cold environment just as the snow bricks of the igloo do. Another high-tech design feature of the facility to note is it can be hydraulically raised to be above the heavy snowfall of the winter months. The hydraulic legs are connected to giant steel skies, which allows the individual modules to be towed across the icy deserts to avoid the facility from being isolated on icebergs. (Slavid, 2013)

An igloo because of the materials used does not have to be moved for the inhabitants to survive instead Inuit's can just relocate themselves and build a structure wherever they want. Using the snow also has a very low impact on the natural environment as nothing was destroyed to create the igloo.

Inside the igloo the floor is cut into terraces creating three levels. The upper level for rest and sleep, the middle level for a fire and the lowest level used as a cold sink. Naturally, heavy cold air will fall and stay on the lower level whilst lighter warmer air will rise. (keartes, 2017)

The door of the igloo is placed at a right angle with an attached tunnel to crawl through this prevents any direct powerful winds from blowing directly into the home. The station is similarly strategically laid out in a straight line perpendicular to the prevailing wind allowing snow to move past the station with ease.

Figure 24

The igloo is a great example of how resourceful humans can be when they are in an environment with very little to offer. The use of snow to combat the snow is an ingenious solution to the weather. Also, the interior layout uses fundamental principles of air flow and temperature to create a comfortable shelter. A possible limitation would be the lack of windows to observe potential dangers such as polar bears roaming the landscape. The research facility's innovative approach demonstrates how modern technology can be utilised to create a comfortable living space. However, the use of modern materials requires a high skill maintenance and more complex problems could easily arise.

Discussion and Conclusion

This discussion of my research aims to evaluate if a large settlement should or not be created in the Polar regions. I have stated a claim that 'we should start to develop large-scale modern settlements in the Arctic', to allow comparison of all aspects of my research.

As demonstrated humans could utilize this opportunity to increase their knowledge of the arctic environment. As well as improve the eco-system by strengthening the local habitat allowing for animal populations to rise a safe level.

The harsh conditions present many challenges to constructing structures and living in the Arctic. The freezing temperatures, extremely fierce winds and snowstorms create a very inhospitable location. Furthermore, with global warming increasing every year the arctic is melting much faster and modern human presence could only speed that up. This would have much more disastrous effects worldwide for rising sea levels and flooding. The creation a large settlement could profoundly disturb the environment if the right precautions were not taken seriously. I think the risk to the wider world of global warming proves to highly of a threat to warrant commercialisation of the Arctic. The excess heat and CO2 of each human could be extremely dangerous to provide sustainable living.

If we were to analyse the social aspect, it could give people a chance to have an adventure and explore a completely unique and serene place on earth. The community's bonds would grow strong as demonstrated by soldiers at Station Nord. The Inuit's were able to balance populations across the arctic landscape enough to reduce their impact and increase the survivability rate. The importance of being nomadic may prove useful and provide a solution for sustainable living.

However, I feel if you were to move to a large settlement then you would need a job or a task to keep you occupied in the desolate area. For example, a retirement plan would be unsustainable as you would be doing very little in an already hugely isolated area. If you are a non-native, then the feeling of isolation and confinement can be very damaging to your mental health. The human need for social people would make the transition easier. Which if a large-scale settlement were to be introduced it could easily be supported. The need for resources such as food and energy to fuel homes would increase on the region, a region that would struggle to do so. A high the population would increase imports in turn increasing costs and carbon footprints. Politics could also cause some complications as many countries claim specific parts of the land. Conflicting laws, currency and language would play a role in how the people would be able to live. Food supply chains and trade could be created with countries to make it easier to live there as it would be problematic to cultivate food.

There is both modern and traditional building technology that gives evidence of successful architecture in the Arctic. The Inuit's with snow to create the igloo for shelter, but in the future the idea of snow as a material could be expanded. The Halley VI Research Station also supports the fact that a good thought out design and system can support comfortable living.

The most fundamental issue for actual buildings and architecture would be the maintainability and the difficulties. Would it require specialists to sustain or should the design of the architecture be robust enough to survive 50 years? Transporting the building materials to the arctic may also prove difficult and expensive. Creating sustainable clean energy to power the settlement could additionally prove another limitation. As the environmental conditions will not always be suitable, case in point solar panels would be useless in the total darkness of the winter months.

Final Remarks

As a conclusion of my research, I believe there is a bright future in the polar regions especially the arctic. If climate, communities, settlements and building technology were all taken into consideration then the polar regions may be the place of the future. I believe architecture in the Arctic can be built, providing places to work, live and relax. A large community of non-native and natives would be successful as long as they could exchange knowledge. With the correct support people could adapt over time to the environment and sociality of the location. A limitation with this field of research to note is the small amount of architecture in the polar regions to compare and contrast to build up a much bigger picture of what exists there. I feel one would have to have a large imagination to envision the large scale sustainable arctic living. As well how long can it realistically last before the icy deserts consume the architecture. There is huge potential to learn so much about the world and where architecture can go in the polar regions that is just waiting to be fully unlocked.

Bibliography

What is the Arctic? | National Snow and Ice Data Center. Nsidc.org. (2020). Retrieved 4 May 2020, from <https://nsidc.org/cryosphere/arctic-meteorology/arctic.html>. <https://nsidc.org/cryosphere/arctic-meteorology/arctic.html>

World Maps of Köppen-Geiger climate classification. Koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at. (2019). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>.

Society, N. (2019). Köppen Climate Classification System. National Geographic Society. Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/koppen-climate-classification-system/#:~:text=The%20K%C3%B6ppen%20climate%20classification%20system%20categorizes%20climate%20zones%20throughout%20the,biome%20research%20conducted%20by%20scientists.>

Arnfield, A. (2020). Koppen climate classification | Definition, System, & Map. Encycloped
ia Britannica. Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://www.britannica.com/science/Koppen-climate-classification>.

Arctic vs. Antarctic | National Snow and Ice Data Center. Nsidc.org. (2020). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://nsidc.org/cryosphere/seaice/characteristics/difference.html>.

Sugden, D. (1982). Arctic and Antarctica (1st ed., p. 56). Basil Blackwell Publisher Limited

Arctic vs. Antarctic | National Snow and Ice Data Center. Nsidc.org. (2020). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://nsidc.org/cryosphere/seaice/characteristics/difference.html>.

Outdoor comfort criteria - CPP Wind. CPP Wind. (2020). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://www.cpwind.com/outdoor-comfort-criteria/>.

Dive and Discover : Antarctica : Seasons. Divediscover
.whoi.edu. (2020). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://divediscover.whoi.edu/archives/ecosystem/informod.html>.

Gedney, L. (1984). The Shortest Day | Geophysical Institute. Gi.alaska.edu. Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://www.gi.alaska.edu/alaska-science-forum/shortest-day>.

Winter Solstice. Athropolis.com. (2005). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from Day Length. Arctic.uoguelph.ca. (2020). Retrieved 4 December 2020, from http://www.arctic.uoguelph.ca/cpe/environments/sky/features/sun_moon/daylight.htm. <https://www.athropolis.com/arctic-facts/fact-solstice-winter.htm>.

Tours, F. (2019). The Midnight Sun Explained. Fjord Tours. Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <https://www.fjordtours.com/inspiration/articles/midnight-sun-explained/>.

Lanfear, S. (2019). Our Planet - Frozen Worlds [Film]. United Kingdom; Silverback films, World Wide Fund for Nature.

Ashjian, C. (2020). Polar Discovery :: Arctic Ecosystem. Polardiscovery.whoi.edu. Retrieved 4 December 2020, from <http://polardiscovery.whoi.edu/arctic/ecosystem.html>.

Psc.apl.washington.edu. 2020. Freshwater Circulation In The Arctic Ocean. [online] Available at: <[http://psc.apl.washington.edu/switchyard/overview_pages/circulation.html#:~:text=The%20Arctic%20Ocean%20is%20a%20very%20fresh%20ocean.&text=Eventually%2C%20this%20freshwater%20\(both%20liquid,Fram%20Strait%20northeast%20of%20Greenland.](http://psc.apl.washington.edu/switchyard/overview_pages/circulation.html#:~:text=The%20Arctic%20Ocean%20is%20a%20very%20fresh%20ocean.&text=Eventually%2C%20this%20freshwater%20(both%20liquid,Fram%20Strait%20northeast%20of%20Greenland.)> [Accessed 4 December 2020].

Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research. (2013, September 25). The deep Greenland Sea is warming faster than the world ocean. ScienceDaily. Retrieved December 3, 2020 from www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2013/09/130925102833.html

Muirhead, E., 2020. Arctic Marine Mammal Adaptations. [online] Animals.mom.com. Available at: <https://animals.mom.com/arctic-marine-mammal-adaptations-7282.html> [Accessed 4 December 2020].

Serreze, M., & Barry, R. (2005). The Arctic climate system (1st ed., pp. 37,38). Cambridge university press.

Bliss, D. (2020). Isolation at the extreme: What life is like spending winter in Earth's most inaccessible research stations. National Geographic. Retrieved 11 December 2020, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.co.uk/science-and-technology/2020/04/isolation-extreme-what-life-spending-winter-earths-most-inaccessible>.

Vaughan, D. (2020). Our science strategy - British Antarctic Survey. British Antarctic Survey. Retrieved 11 December 2020, from <https://www.bas.ac.uk/science/our-research/our-strategy/>.f

Potenza, A. (2018). Here's what vanishing sea ice in the Arctic means for you. The Verge. Retrieved 11 December 2020, from <https://www.theverge.com/2018/5/10/17339046/arctic-sea-ice-decline-albedo-effect-climate-change-global-warming#:~:text=But%20warmer%20temperatures%20in%20the,levels%20would%20soar%20%20feet>.

Agar, R. (2019). Importance of Phytoplankton. Sciencing. Retrieved 11 December 2020, from <https://sciencing.com/importance-phytoplankton-5414740.html>.

Bottomley, F. (2019). How your environment affects your mental health. NCS. Retrieved 11 December 2020, from <https://nationalcounsellingsociety.org/blog/posts/how-your-environment-affects-your-mental-health>.

Sugden, D. (1982). Arctic and Antarctica (1st ed., p. 225, 231, 233). Basil Blackwell Publisher Limited.

Searles, E. (2010). Inuit identity in the canadian arctic. *Ethnology: An international journal of cultural and social anthropology*, 47, 239-255.

5000 Years of Inuit History and Heritage. (2004). [Ebook] (1st ed., p. 2). Retrieved 12 December 2020, from https://www.itk.ca/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/5000YearHeritage_0.pdf.

Callebs, S. (2015). On Thin Ice: The People of the North [Film]. Canada; American arm of China Central Television.

Rothera Research Station - British Antarctic Survey. British Antarctic Survey. (2020). Retrieved 13 December 2020, from <https://www.bas.ac.uk/polar-operations/sites-and-facilities/facility/rothera/#about>.

Bliss, D. (2020). Isolation at the extreme: What life is like spending winter in Earth's most inaccessible research stations. National Geographic. Retrieved 13 December 2020, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.co.uk/science-and-technology/2020/04/isolation-extreme-what-life-spending-winter-earths-most-inaccessible>.

A. Palinkas, L. (2000). On the Ice: Individual and Group Adaptation in Antarctica [Ebook] (1st ed., p. 3). University of California. Retrieved 13 December 2020, from https://web.archive.org/web/20120623024832/http://www.sscnet.ucla.edu/anthro/bec/papers/Palinkas_On_The_Ice.pdf.

Ingold, T., & Armstrong, T. (2019). Arctic | Definition, Climate, People, & Facts. Encyclopedia Britannica. Retrieved 13 December 2020, from <https://www.britannica.com/place/Arctic>.

Kingsley, J. (2019). At this Arctic science base, life is anything but lonely. National Geographic. Retrieved 13 December 2020, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.co.uk/environment-and-conservation/2019/08/arctic-science-base-life-anything-lonely>.

Zoo, A. (2016). The Brutal Beauty of Life in an Arctic Mining Town - Feature Shoot. Feature Shoot. Retrieved 17 December 2020, from <https://www.featureshoot.com/2016/10/the-brutal-beauty-of-life-in-an-arctic-mining-town/>.

Love, R. (2014). Haunting Photographs of the Siberian City of Norilsk Contrast Colorful Architecture with Devastating Industrial Pollution. Fstoppers. Retrieved 24 December 2020, from <https://fstoppers.com/aerial/haunting-photographs-siberian-city-norilsk-contrast-colorful-architecture-14962>.

The Arctic People - Environment / Housing. Firstpeoplesofcanada.com. Retrieved 1 January 2021, from http://firstpeoplesofcanada.com/fp_groups/fp_inuit2.html.

Halley VI Research Station. Aecom.com. (2020). Retrieved 4 January 2021, from <https://aecom.com/uk/projects/halley-vi-research-station/>.

Slavid, R. (2013). Halley VI British Antarctic Research Station | Hugh Broughton Architects. Hbarchitects.co.uk. Retrieved 4 January 2021, from <https://hbarchitects.co.uk/halley-vi-british-antarctic-research-station/>.

Greenway, T. (2019). How Does an Igloo Work?. Transun.co.uk. Retrieved 5 January 2021, from <https://www.transun.co.uk/blogs/how-does-an-igloo-work#:~:text=Igluos%20are%20built%20from%20compressed%20snow.&text=While%20it%20looks%20solid%2C%20as,heat%20gets%20trapped%20in%20there>.

keartes, S. (2017). How An Igloo Keeps You Warm [Video]. Retrieved 5 January 2021, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1L7EI0vKVuU>.

Appendix

This appendix was created as some paragraphs of the dissertation were too long for the word count however the information was too important to lose. So below are extended pieces of text to further explain specific parts of the text.

Appendix A

The physical, political and social of a settlement

It is precisely on this idea that we know that the birth of the city is based, which in fact, takes the name polis, (which in Greek combines the physical dimension with the political and social dimension of the settlement.

Appendix B

Motivating factors

One significant motivating factor for this section of the earth is the passion to educate myself on the current state of the polar region. To discover if there is potential and reason to build in the arctic or should we leave it alone?

Appendix C

Arctic winds

The arctic winds are a prominent feature to consider as they can greatly influence the temperature of the regions. "The lack of trees and the generally smooth ice surfaces over the sea and on land mean that winds are not greatly retarded by friction at ground level." (Sugden, 1982, p. 56). The smooth surface allows for a higher wind velocity and a greater reduction in temperature. Frequently the wind speeds can reach up to 64 miles per hour if a polar low has formed, which is a small intense cyclone. ("Arctic vs. Antarctic | National Snow and Ice Data Center", 2020). A highly distressing situation for any human as any wind speed faster than 22 miles per hour is classed as uncomfortable. ("Outdoor comfort criteria - CPP Wind", 2020). An important factor of the environment to consider for if a settlement was to be created. The highly uncomfortable wind could deter people and have a negative influence on their mental health as it can cause unwanted stress especially if the extreme weather is a danger to your life. (Bottomley, 2019)

Appendix C

Nomadic natives

The natives would survive and migrate around the arctic following different routes throughout the year to increase their survival chances. Inuit settlement populations had to be balanced with averages numbers of people at 25 - 30 which would allow for more security and communal hunting but there was simultaneously a significant risk of running out of sparse resources. (Sugden, 1982) With such a harsh landscape native, groups would often communicate and work together and look after each other. To survive "The whole community was one whole unity family" Caroline Cannon (2015), a native of Point Hope, Alaska. The sharing of knowledge and technology they had developed led to successful survival for many years.

Appendix D

Politics of Antarctica and the Arctic

Eight countries including Russia, Canada, Denmark (Greenland), Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland stake a claim in the Arctic. (Ingold & Armstrong, 2019) Denmark has an internationally recognised sovereignty claim over Greenland but for political reasons must show its presence to legitimise its claim. (Kingsley, 2019) During the summer months that population can grow to 60 people. The post is used primarily for scientific reasons to conduct research on climate change, taking information from the atmosphere and the ice. The post has 25 buildings and could be compared to a small village. Despite the long active service time the personal atmosphere here is much lighter and people enjoy this place more.

Appendix E

Home from Home

Mads Adamsen, a soldier, states that it is like “Coming home to your family from another place”. (2019) The different buildings and larger number of people helps to create a community which can partly take away the feeling of isolation. The fact that the buildings are spread to prevent a fire from destroying the whole base makes gives people more space to traverse when moving around the base which gives the feeling that they are not so confined. Dogs are also employed on the base which are “critical to soldiers’ emotional well-being” Jesper Juul Hansen the station leader has stated.

Appendix I: Yellow 2/3 dissertation

History and Theory Dissertation
U30652

The Futuristic Image of Architecture: Computational Design Evolution

Figure 1

In Memory of Zaha Mohammad Hadid

One of architecture's most cherished figures, an Iraqi-born architect with extraordinary achievements and honours. Zaha Hadid's groundbreaking career ranks her among the world's most talented and influential.

Acknowledgement

Writing my dissertation has given me a lot of knowledge in computational and parametric design that I have been able to implement into my architectural projects. In a recent project for an urban development in Peckham I have been inspired to use Rhino and Grasshopper 3D to incorporate Parametricism into the urban proposal to tackle: Population Growth and Urban Decay, putting a key focus on the environment, the poor community and crime.

Throughout the months of intense research, investigation and writing my dissertation, I would firstly like to thank my dissertation tutor, xxxx for her advice and opportunities offered to me from start to finish. You provided me with valuable tools and guidance in steering my dissertation in the right direction right up until the end.

I would like to thank xxxx for his time and input into my research. You had a strong influence in guiding my dissertation and were a great reference for me as a specialist in the application of computational form finding techniques for Zaha Architects.

	Contents	Figures	Page
Acknowledgements	2-3	Fig.1: Zaha Hadid at the Heydar Ailyev Cultural Center, November 2013	2
Abstract	6-7		
Introduction	8-9	Fig.2: Beijing Daxing International Airport / Zaha Hadid Architects.	7
Literature Review	10-13		
Methodology	14-18	Fig.3-5: Diagrams of Parametricism	8
Discussion and Results	19-23	Fig.6: Primary Data	8/12
Conclusion	24-25	Fig.7: Construction Workers on Site	10
Bibliography	26-28	Fig.8: Primary Data Timeline	13
Apendix	29-31	Fig.9: Sagrada Familia Model	14
		Fig.10: Shanghai HQ	15
		Fig.11: TMD Studios	16
		Fig 12: Computational Design Framework of Sustainability	18
		Fig 13: Zaha Hadid Architect	19
		Fig 14-15: Sagrada Familia	20-21
		Fig.16: Relevance Photomontage	25

Abstract

We live in a digital era in which technology is at the forefront of the world. As a result of COVID-19, the whole world is more than ever, reliant on technology to function.

Computation-based design approaches have emerged in the last decades and are becoming increasingly popular among architects and other designers because of the world's current state.

This text summarises digital design's origin and development through design pioneers such as Zaha Hadid, Antoni Gaudi, Le Corbusier, Walter Gropius and Mies van der Rohe. It further goes on to intensely discuss the evolution of computational architecture; and the future image of the design and the built environment, citing key authors and projects. This document also further explains the origin and development of a computational design by analysing history, global transitions, and advancements in technology mentioned in an extensive literature review. Different definitions by various authors were collected, analysed, and compared. The text then uses this information to drive an interview with a leading professional in computational form-finding for Zaha Hadid Architects (the most well-known and influential pioneers of parametric design) on computational design evolution the future of architecture and approaches towards sustainability (the full interview can be found in the appendix).

The document concludes with reflections on digital architecture's current state and its role in contemporary design and improving the world's future through computational architecture.

Keywords: Parametricism, computational design, parametric design and contemporary history.

Figure 2

Introduction

Computation-based design approaches have emerged in the last decades and have rapidly become popular among architects and designers. One of this text aims to address why this design technique is becoming favourable and its benefits. The reasons can be summarised into three main points; global transformation as of recent events globally, including COVID 19, population growth, environmental issues, and the changing of human ideologies behind these factors that influence designing strategies. Another main factor that will be addressed is the improvement in digital technology and the opportunities that can come from this. Furthermore, historical influence and how the past can help inform a future design create successful innovative strategies and techniques. Incorporating digital design tools in architecture results from a long development process and has a fascinating recent history.

The concept of using machines to complete tedious tasks arose in 1920 originating the birth of computer science (Menges & Ahlquist, 2011). Computation design refers to 'the study and practice of design activities through applying and developing novel ideas and techniques in computing' (Caetano, Santos & Leitão 2020). This method of designing has developed and succeeded Modernism into a new key design movement, Parametricism. Parametric Design 'is the architects' use of computational and communication technologies. This design has three main principles: soft forms, differentiation, and correlation. It rejects rigid forms, repetition, and pure difference; all the elements found in modern architecture. The Parametricism mentality was created within a transitional period of Modernism' (Caetano, Sthreentos & Leitão, 2020). Parametricism has been refined over the last 15 years to become a dominant computational design style because of famous firms such as Zaha Hadid Architects that have utilised this movement to establish innovative manifesto projects. (Schumacher, 2019) (Tenorio, 2014).

8 Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Architecture is evolving around us into more complex schemes that aim to tackle worldwide environmental and population growth issues. Thus, throughout the past few years, the invalidity of traditional design approaches such as Modernism and classical architecture has been evident (Valencia, 2020). The main factor that has brought attention to this is COVID-19 the pandemic of 2020, which has made it clear that the world is becoming increasingly dependent on digital technology. When it comes to architecture and design, the rise of Computation design is inevitable. Michael Spence -Nobel Prize Laureate in Economic Sciences-, suggested 'higher risk aversion, increasing investment in digital technologies, and the diversification of supply chains will equate to a rapid expansion of smart cities' in response to being questioned about the major changes in the global economy likely to occur in the aftermath of COVID-19 (Guerrero, 2020). From this, its inferred that three main factors will influence a design shift moving into the future. These primary factors are global transformations, technology, and history. The computational design will shift to become the forefront for architectural design as the dominant style in architecture in this envision of a future world. These factors are strong influencers of this when heading into a future world.

Figure 6: Primary Research

Figure 6 simplifies the causes of design evolution into three main factors: global transformation, advancements in technology and historic influence. Throughout this text these factors will be expanded to assess how much influence they have on design evolution and how they influence shifts in design heading into a future world.

Literature Review

Research Question:

How has the evolution of computational design influenced architecture's future image through the Lens of Zaha Hadid Architects?

Transitions in global ideologies are not the only deciding factor when it comes to global transformation. Before the recent pandemic, the field of construction was already facing a series of global transformations. As the world's population predicts reaching the 11-billion milestone before 2100 (UN,2019), the construction sector was under pressure to understand and adapt to the transformations that are reshaping the globe (Valencia 2020). Architecture and construction are critical sectors in developing the world for the future. Moreover, the construction industry that is deeply rooted in human interaction is facing a new reality and when it comes to COVID-19. The digital landscape has taken over the field, and these ongoing businesses are forced to evolve to keep up with these more recent global transformations.

Figure 7

Parametricism is a design style that has been developed over the last 15 years being derived from Modernism (Schumacher 2008). The main driving force that developed modernism architecture into this more complex and fluid design style is computational design. Over the twenty-first century, the design process has been enhanced by new technological methods that have allowed designers to create sophisticated and unique geometries (Guerrero 2020). These geometries are most successfully evident in Zaha Hadid Architect buildings as a globally influential use of Parametricism. It is almost impossible to compete within the contemporary design scheme without mastering these new technology-driven design methods. The reason for this is for the demand for computational design to create design strategies that are directly adaptable to the changing world. With the computational design, techniques can be used to create the most efficient proposal for a project.

The architects who are well known to be the leading competitors of this design method are Zaha Hadid Architects. In the interview with Dr Pierandrea Angius, a lead associate of Zaha Architects, about the profession of applying computational design — he states that 'Computational techniques are now part of the "deep DNA of the company"'. Any project of Zaha Architects in the last 15 years has in different ways used instrumentally different kinds of computational techniques. It is one of our strengths and core focuses' (Angius, 2020). Designers in this generation are almost entirely dependent on technology to design these future proof projects because there is so much more potential for the computational design that can emit incredible results that can easily pose a challenge to a single designer. Technology has also made it possible to design more complex projects and push forward new movements and trend design into different design trends, such as Parametricism.

Development of futuristic design movements is influenced by global transformations, technology, and history. (Figure 6) These factors can induce transitions in architectural trends and create a new design trend that influences designers' ideologies, workflow, and inspiration.

Transitions in architecture are essential as different methods in building design mark transformations in human thinking and society. For example, in this generation, humans are becoming more concerned about environmental problems because of the consequences of pollution. More recent global issues such as rising seawater levels, global warming and many more changed in our environment have resulted in a transitional shift in designer ideologies towards a more responsible lifestyle and a more sustainable way of living. The approach is evident in recent building proposals from influential architectural firms like Zaha Hadid Architects. Designers are starting to act and address these problems subsequently, and there has been a rise in the number of architectural projects that are focalised around sustainability aspects. Zaha Hadid is one of the most famous and successful female architects in history who made fundamental progress in her design according to sustainability aspects. The firm she built on a foundation of her famous curved forms influenced by Parametricism has most definitely challenged many architects' ideologies regarding design, - she states that 'sustainability is a defining challenge of this generation' (Hadid 2015 & AJ Contributor 2015). This challenge can be seen meeting in Zaha Hadid Architects headquarters building proposal for the China Energy Conservation and Environmental Protection Group (CECEP). This building successfully shows the evidence of putting sustainability at the proposal's foundation using computational tools to study the building's massing and orientation to ensure that the passive design is exceptionally efficient (Stamp 2020). These kinds of Projects influence ideologies and push forward new and improved design methodologies as more firms must compete now to keep up with these successful strategies.

Figure 6: Primary Research

Assessed throughout the text, computational design is a technique that has becoming more influential in recent years and will be moving into the future of architecture because of global transitions, advancements in technology and historical influence, but when did this evolution of architecture begin?

Throughout this text, factors of design evolution; global transformation; advancements in technology; and historic influence will be explored to assess how much influence they have on design evolution on Parametricism and computational design. The text will also show how their impact creates shifts in design, heading into a future world. Future possibilities of design will be explored through case studies with a particular focus on how:

the evolution of computational design has influenced the future image of architecture through the Lens of Zaha Hadid Architects, one of the most evolutionary and famous architects in Parametricism and computational design?

Through research and by conducting a qualitative interview with a leading associate of Zaha Hadid Architects about the future of architecture I aim to gain insight into a critical influential pioneer architecture firm and their vision of a future world. This method is limited by myself as I am the primary instrument of the data collection and analysis (Ochieng 2009); therefore, the information mediated could be misinterpreted. However, in this circumstance, it is appropriate because the answers to the questions will not prevent discovery in learning how a vital member of the company perceives the future of architecture.

Figure 8: Primary Research
This timeline shows some key influencers that pioneered design evolution throughout history into Parametricism.

Methodology

How has the evolution of computational design influenced architecture's future image through the Lens of Zaha Hadid Architects?

Throughout the past ten years, it is evident that the future world is becoming increasingly digital, and this is also seen in the design and the built environment (F. Guerrero 2020). Nevertheless, how and to what extent can computational design benefit the environment? Many studies have researched the recent benefits of computational design concerning sustainability. In contrast, few researchers have considered how Building Information Modeling (BIM) can embed sustainable information into a project. This text wishes to draw in some analogical insight from computational design and show how this can be relevant in this generation and move into the future.

Figure 9:

History and advancements in technology and materials (N. Valencia 2020)

It can also be suggested that 'history drives the methodology of the new and unseen architecture and design of today's era'. Pierandrea Angius suggests that this concept goes the other way; 'glimpses of parametric principles can be seen in historical precedents' (Angius, 2020). This infers that our history of architecture is steppingstones across the river towards the futuristic conception of architecture. These steppingstones were paved by fundamental architects that influenced vital design movements. For example, architects who influenced Modernism design movement, including Walter Gropius, Mies van der Rohe, and Le Corbusier during the Industrial Age, demonstrated modernism concepts that invoked the transition into modernism architecture dominated the discipline for over 70 years (P. Schumacher). This can be seen in the work of Antoni Gaudí, a Spanish architect. His freedom of form, voluptuous colour and texture and organic unity is famously found throughout Barcelona. His work in the church of Sagrada Família's design consisted of the creation of an upside-down model, using strings being weighed down by birdshot. A mirror placed below the model showed what the chapel would look like the right side up. (Akande, 2016) This model demonstrates the principles of Parametricism. A set of parameters, the length of the string, anchor point location, and the birdshot weight. A set of outcomes were the various vertex locations of points on the strings, and these outcomes were derived from mathematical functions, Newton's Laws of Motion. This approach underwent many transitions over time that developed Modernism into several different movements in architecture. However, at the same time when analysing some of these designs, some snippets of Parametricism can be seen.

Figure 9: Shows Antoni Gaudí's the physical parametric model of the Sagrada Família. The model demonstrates a historical approach towards Parametricism before the introduction of computers and the digital age in the creation of an innovative design.

Sustainability and changes in ideologies

Sustainable architecture is a critically influential factor when considering an environmentally positive future. Only by living more economically with our resources can we protect our environment. Computation has become an efficient and easy to access tool that has been gaining more and more ground in the construction industry as a means of design. Nevertheless, how can this technology be used to create responsible architecture towards sustainability?

Zaha Hadid Architects proposal for the new HQ of the CECEP is a great example that shows not only the use of computation as a powerful analogical tool to instrumentally define the elements and spaces of a building, contextualised to sun paths and geometrical, mathematical rule sets to create an extremely efficient passive design (Stamp 2020); they also successfully push Zaha Hadid's ideology of sustainability being the defining challenge of this generation (Hadid & Contributor 2015) by creating an innovative design that is that achieved the highest score ever achieved in China's Three Star Green Building Rating System (Stamp 2020). This ideology is pushed further, having won the competition to design the new Shanghai HQ boasting the significance of sustainable technology and boosting this trend in design for other firms to compete with them.

Figure 10:

Throughout the past ten years, it is evident that the future world is becoming increasingly digital, and this is also seen in the design and the built environment (Guerrero 2020). However, how and to what extent can computational design benefit the environment? Many studies have researched the recent benefits of computational design concerning sustainability. In contrast, few researchers have considered how Building Information Modeling (BIM) can embed sustainable information into a project. This text wishes to draw in some analogical insight from computational design and show how this can be relevant in this generation and move into the future.

TMD Studios LTD (TMD 2020) is a practice that 'embraces sustainable and technological techniques to the designing framework that adopts the latest advancements in building technology and being focused on Big Data to offer unique and innovative solutions.' (TMD & Ondrej Cudy) TMD offer creatives who want to respond to future challenges using their fields to serve better quality of living for all. They go onto theories that there are three concerns when designing buildings with better considerations towards the environment. They derive these factors like people, earth, and cost. They later go onto state that there are three overriding ecological concerns when designing buildings. 'The first is the material used for construction; the second is the building's energy efficiency and the last is the location of the building.'

Figure 11:

Computational Sustainability (CS) (C. Gomes & Yang, 2011) on the other hand, is a novel research field that attempts to employ computer science technologies such as Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to 'address broad sustainability problems integrating environmental, economic, and social dimensions. These CS problems are classified according to the relevant computer application that is utilised to address the problems' (C. Gomes & Yang, 2011). CS framework categorises their field including, computational simulation, constraint optimisation and machine learning, data mining, planning control and scheduling, policy, and action learning. Since the nature of such problems is complex and concerns various disciplines, they often require multidisciplinary approaches (Silva & Analide, 2019)

(Figure 12 Computational Design Framework of Sustainability Towards the environment, sociological and ecological)

From this, it can derive that their methodology in designing a sustainable building has a deep analogical computing system that is viable today. CS uses computation as a prosthetic device for calculations, allowing them to embed intelligent information about the whole project. Opposed to TMD, they use various backgrounds to create a concept in constructing a sustainable building.

Discussion and Results

I conducted an interview to understand the future image of architecture and to acknowledge how to design using computational methods to create a more future proof design. To achieve this, I set out to attain qualitative data to tackle my research question using primary data I gathered in an interview. I contacted architect Dr Pierandrea Angius, a lead associate of Zaha Architects in the profession of applying computational design. I sent an email with three questions about the computational design benefits and how computational design was utilised within Zaha Architects firm to conduct this interview.

Figure 13:

How has the evolution of computational design influenced architecture's future image through the Lens of Zaha Hadid Architects?

When asked about computational design history, Pierandrea Angius mentioned a list of precedents where glimpses of Parametricism can be seen. the key building that shows Parametricism is Antoni Gaudi, Sagrada Familia mentioned previously. It demonstrates parametric design principles through the development of creating the concept (parameters, anchor points and outcomes). Compared to what we see currently as a 'highly technological enhancement offered to an old methodology' (Angius, 2020) the Sagrada Familia is the most successful precedent that demonstrates Parametricism before the evolution and development of technology. Methods of Parametricism through computation give more advanced, unthinkable, and unpredictable results of then Parametricism without computation. This is because the computers offer so much enhancement through software, hardware that the human brain and body cannot compete with (Moravec, 1998). The transition between analogical-physical models such as the Sagrada Familia and digital parametric can show various similarities in the techniques used to design.

Figure 14:

Figure 15:

However, the differences are apparent when buildings designed using analogical-physical models are assessed against computational parametric buildings. A project that shows an evident success in evolution is Zaha Hadid Architects proposal for the new HQ of the CECEP that uses computation as a powerful tool in the design scheme to develop a record-breaking efficient passive design using analogical computing (Stamp, 2020). This example is a perfect demonstration of what can be achieved when utilising computational methods. Computation has become influential in creating responsible designs towards sustainability because of its compatibility with analogical computing with sun paths or lunar phases or any geometrical rule set that can be embedded to contextualise and test any architectural element's behaviours.

When questioned about how computational design can help contribute a sustainable future, Dr Angius went on to add that computationally driven processes can contribute on both qualitative and quantitative aspects of any project that aims to address environmental sustainability, circularity and in the general economy means. I can infer from this that not only can these techniques be used to create a sustainable project towards the environment but also future proof the building towards any economic and social context. Being able to test these theories and scenarios has most definitely defined the future image of architecture by creating buildings that are more resilient and adaptable to change within their context. This is shown in figure x of a diagram explaining how to design sustainably to make long-lasting buildings for the future using computational design sustainability framework used by Computational Sustainability (CS) (C. Gomes & Yang, 2011). This diagram explains how computation can be used as a 'tool', a prosthetic device for calculations which allow handling multi-strata data and algorithms (Angius) to manage complex problems such as sustainability towards the environment, sociology and economically. Pierandrea Angius also adds that this multi-stratum of data has lots of variety.

This includes holistic form-finding; processes using environmental inputs to mere dimensioning of façade layers; and the embedment of intelligent time-based behaviours that not only just aid in designing the building for construction, but also design the buildings entire life cycle from construction to demolition using architectural construct (BIM 4D, 5D and 6D). The use of these schematics is the key to designing a future proof building.

All in all, sustainability is the key factor for this generation in creating a building that is future proof (Hadid & Contributor 2015), and the CECEP case study is a clear example of how computational design can be used to successfully accomplish this, as well as showing a clear superiority to non-computational techniques through its successful framework. Evolution of computational design over the years has most definitely influenced many architects and their techniques in creating sustainable, innovative projects to the extent that it is almost impossible for a firm to compete in architecture without having this knowledge. Pierandrea Angius himself also said in the interview that computational techniques are now a part of the 'deep' DNA and are the strength and core focus of the company of Zaha Hadid Architects which shows that the firm is dependent on technology.

Zaha Hadid Architects are currently the most advanced and experienced company on computational techniques applied to architectural design and use its framework to their advantages in relation to the technical development of highly complex, large scale projects (Angius, 2020); as result of pioneering firms and architects such as Zaha Architects, Antoni Gaudi and many others, other architects have been inspired to tack the same approach. Firms such as TMD Studios LTD (TMD, 2020) utilise computational to 'embraces a sustainable and technological approach to design' (TMD, 2020). They narrow sustainability towards the environment to three main factors: people, earth and cost. (TMD & Ondrej Cudy, 2020). Trends in growths in firms and architects with similar ideologies to this are evident in recent years because of Parametricism's success.

Conclusion

This research aimed to identify the causes of computational design evolution and its impact on the image of architecture for the future, specifically putting a key focal point on Zaha Hadid Architects as the most advanced and experienced companies on computational techniques applied to architectural design. Based on a qualitative interview with a leading associate of Zaha Hadid Architects (the original interview can be found in the appendix) and an analysis of case studies and theories related towards the evolution of computational design with a responsible approach towards sustainability. The results concluded that evolution of digital architecture will subsequently adapt the future world through advanced methods of design with a broad approach of sustainability towards, the economy, sociology, and the environment. The significance of computational evolution is paramount because it is a tool that can be utilised when creating a resilient design that is adaptable for the future.

The research carried out in the interview clearly illustrates the direct influence that computational and parametric design has on Zaha Hadid Architects and the individual architects that work for the firm. However, it also raises questions of a scenario where the world has run out of fossil fuels due to the constant growing population. To make a better understanding of the future image of architecture, these scenarios should be addressed. As discussed throughout the text, if a building is being designed for the future; the building needs to be designed to make it resilient to change. Further studies could address the growing population and the limitation of fossil fuels when discussing the image of a future city and analyse how computational design could be used to address these future issues. I believe this to be a crucial gap in knowledge that lets down this document.

Other issues that arose in this document and were left undiscussed were other scenarios that revolved around global transformations. This document would have been more relevant if these current issues were discussed, this is because we are currently transitioning into a world where digital media is taking over because of global transformations such as coronavirus (Guerrero, 2020) and within the field of architectural design and the built environment, this is no exception. An industry that is built on human interaction is difficult to adapt to the realities of COVID-19 and similarly to everyone in the world; designers are finding themselves in online zoom conferences virtually instead of being present physically. Reality is becoming more digital by the day as technology improves and restrictions are worsened which poses difficult questions for designers of the built environment moving forward such as: How do we evolve from designing for this uncertain future? And how will significant changes in the world influence design for the future?

Throughout this dissertation, I have answered these questions with intense research through intensive literature and case studies putting a key focus onto the history and influence of computational architect pioneers throughout time, advancements in technology and global transformations.

Figure 16:

Bibliography

- Achim. M. S. Ahlquist, 2011, 'Computational Design Thinking', John Wiley and Sons, pp 3-9
- Caetano, I., Santos, L., Leitão, A. (2020). "Computational design in architecture: Defining parametric, generative, and algorithmic design." *Frontiers of Architectural Research*, pp 287-300
- Contributor, A., & Contributor, A. (2021). Hadid: 'Sustainability is a defining challenge of our generation'. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://www.architectsjournal.co.uk/news/opinion/hadid-sustainability-is-a-defining-challenge-of-our-generation>
- Data, U. (2021). Growing at a slower pace, world population is expected to reach 9.7 billion in 2050 and could peak at nearly 11 billion around 2100 | UN DESA | United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://www.un.org/development/desa/en/news/population/world-population-prospects-2019.html>
- Eaton. E, Gomes. C, Williams. B, 2014, 'Computational sustainability', *AI Magazine*, 35, pp. 3-7
- Gomes, C, 2019, 'Computational sustainability: Computing for a better world and a sustainable future', *Communications of the ACM*, 62, pp. 56-65
- Gomes, C and Yang, Q, 2011, 'Introduction to special issue on computational sustainability', *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology*, 2, pp. 119-121
- Haris, S. (2021). Algorithms are designing better buildings. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://theconversation.com/algorithms-are-designing-better-buildings-140302>
- Kennicott, P. (2021). Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://www.washingtonpost.com/magazine/2020/07/13/pandemic-has-shown-us-what-future-architecture-could-be/?arc404=true>
- LTD, T. (2021). Emerging Trends That Will Shape the Future of Architecture. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://medium.com/studiotmd/emerging-trends-that-will-shape-the-future-of-architecture-356ba3e7f910>
- Moravec, H. (1998). When will computer hardware match the human brain. *Journal of evolution and technology*, 1(1), 10.
- Ochieng, P. A. (2009). An analysis of the strengths and limitation of qualitative and quantitative research paradigms. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 13, 13.
- Patrik Schumacher. (2021). Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://www.patrikschumacher.com/index.htm>
- Patrik Schumacher. (2021). Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://www.patrikschumacher.com/Texts/Parametricism%20-%20A%20New%20Global%20Style%20for%20Architecture%20and%20Urban%20Design.html>
- PM, F. (2021). Michael Spence, Premio Nobel de Economía: "Es innegable que esta experiencia va a cambiar la forma en cómo funciona la economía mundial" - *La Tercera*. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from https://www.latercera.com/pulso/noticia/michael-spence-premio-nobel-de-economia-es-innegable-que-esta-experiencia-va-a-cambiar-la-forma-en-como-funciona-la-economia-mundial/ZG5HRLKEMZD7NIOIVKVQGWEDRM/?utm_medium=website&utm_source=archdaily.com

Bibliography

Silva, F and Analide, C, 2019, 'Computational sustainability and the PHESS platform: Using affective computing as social indicators', *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 92, pp. 329-341

Shafiee, S. & Topal, E. (2009). When will fossil fuel reserves be diminished?. *Energy policy*, 37(1), 181-189.

Schumacher, E. F. (2011). *Small is beautiful: A study of economics as if people mattered*. Random House.

Schumacher, P. (2021). *Parametricism - A New Global Style for Architecture and Urban Design*. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from <https://www.architecturaldigest.com/story/zaha-hadid-architects-design-shanghais-greenest-building>

Valencia, N. (2021). What Are the Megatrends Reshaping the Architecture Field and the Construction Industry?. Retrieved 29 January 2021, from https://www.archdaily.com/948366/what-are-the-megatrends-reshaping-the-architecture-field-and-the-construction-industry?utm_medium=email&utm_source=ArchDaily%20List&kth=5,472, 165

Apendix

Interview with Pierandrea Angius Associate Architect for Zaha Hadid Architects

Q) How can computational design help create a light footed and environmentally friendly project and contribute to the sustainability of future architecture?

A) Computational design, as design category and as currently intended, incarnates an inevitable advancement (and not the latest advancement, see machine learning, AI, etc...) in the long development trajectory defined by computer aided design methodology. Computation has become a powerful and easy to access tool, therefore its impact nowadays is exponentially growing compared to the past. Computation can be as well the analogical computing of sun path or lunar phases, or any kind of geometrical, mathematical rule set. An extremely high number of rule sets can now be easily embedded on any digital model, modified, and contextualised to any need, and used instrumentally to define and test the behaviour of any architectural element.

A computationally driven design process can surely contribute on both qualitative and quantitative aspects of any project that aim to address environmental sustainability, circularity and in general economy of means. Computation is just a "tool", a prosthetic device for calculation which allow to handle a multi-strata of data and algorithms, and that is way its contribution is necessary to manage complex problems such as environmentally sustainable design. This contribution ranges from holistic form-finding processes using environmental inputs to mere dimensioning of façade layers. Computational design allows as well to compute time-based behaviours and to embed intelligent information about the life cycle of the architectural construct, such as BIM 4D, 5D, 6D, which is surely an important step forward on the validation process of the design intent.

Q) How has evolution of computation contributed to the design work of ZHA Architects?

A) Computational techniques are now part of the “deep” DNA of the company. Any project we have worked on in the last 15 years has in different ways used instrumentally different kinds of computational techniques. It is one of our strengths and core focus. We are currently one of the most advanced and experienced company on computational techniques applied to architectural design and we experience daily the relevant advantages in relation to the technical development of highly complex, large scale projects. A computationally driven or a rule based architectural model allows to make changes and intervene on the geometrical and mathematical rules at any time without having to rebuild the model from scratch. It allows to create an adaptive model to both predefined and varying inputs. We use as well computational techniques to optimise geometry and test structural configurations. We constantly adapt to the new computational tools and techniques as they offer new opportunities and capabilities; the development of the architectural discipline is very much bound to the developments of its tools, hence our interest on “evolving” in parallel to the evolution of the computational tools.

Q) ZHA Architects are certainly the pioneers and are still today the most influential representatives in Parametricism in architecture. But if you were to identify a historical origin of this new trend, what are the architects that we could consider in the past?

A) I would surely investigate the history of architecture for any rule-based architecture or design process, both driven by intuitive and explicit principles. Someone sees in Palladian architecture a clear representation of rule-based design. Jantar Jaipur’s buildings in India are a clear representation of parametrically driven spatial configuration. Corbusier’s Ville Radieuse can also show a glimpse of parametric principles as well as Mies’ courtyard houses and Tschumi’s folies. Corbusier’s and Xenakis’ Philips’ pavilion but as well Moretti’s stadia designs are all relevant precedents. Parametricism as a methodology can be seen in the work of many past, recent and less recent, architects. What we see currently is a highly powerful technological enhancement offered to an old methodology. This has led to an evolution and development of the old methodology into something completely new and unseen. Outcomes become unthinkable and unpredictable, emergent, because the complexity and the number of parameters in play. Frei Otto’s work is surely seminal and it embodies the transition between analogical-physical and digital parametric design. One of its contemporary and first proofs of concept, in the digital realm, is the design and construction of the Swiss Re in London by Foster, using Generative components, a proto-Rhino Grasshopper tool that allowed to create a highly complex associative, component-based model. After this project, many others followed moving from small scale to large scale urban highly sophisticated experimentations.

HISTORY (M36052) DISSERTATION COURSEWORK

INTRO :

PUBLIC ART – WHAT MAKES THEM PUBLIC
ART AND HOW DOES IT HELP PUBLIC ART
SERVING ITS PURPOSE ?

TABLES OF CONTENT :

COVER

TABLES OF CONTENT

PREFACE / ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

INTRODUCTION

[P. 03] _____ 1) INTRO

[P. 03] _____ 2) DEFINITION OF ART

[P. 03 – P. 04] ____ 3) DEFINITION OF PUBLIC AND TERM PUBLIC ART

BODY

[P. 05] _____ 4) BRIEF HISTORY OF PUBLIC ART

[P. 05 – P. 07] ____ 5) FORM VS FUNCTION IN PUBLIC ART

[P. 07 – P. 11] ____ 6) FORM EXAMPLE 1 : JAMES TURRELL

[P. 11 – P. 13] ____ 7) FORM EXAMPLE 2 : HEART-SHAPED INSTALLATION

[P. 14 – P. 16] ____ 8) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 1 : PARC DE LA VILLETTE

[P. 17 – P. 18] ____ 9) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 2 : RACHEL WHITEREAD

CLOSING

[P. 19] _____ 10) CONCLUSION

BIBLIOGRAPHY

[P. 20 – P. 21] ____ 11) BIBLIOGRAPHY

PREFACE / ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This dissertation was written in conjunction to the History coursework submission . This dissertation was written with help from mixed resources being both printed and electronic . These resources , whether it came in interviews or independent journals , whether it comes in paper or found via Internet , were beneficial for this essay . There were also photos that can help in supporting the points I am looking to bring up .

The research and writing process also benefits me in a way it exposes me to newer methods of exploring certain subject area in both efficient and detailed manner . These aspects will be useful for me to use in the future .

1) INTRODUCTION

What is public art ? Or better yet , what is the definition of the terms “public” and “art” and how does their individual definitions correlate to the combined terms ? Considering the “public” in public art , what does it do to involve “public” and “art” in itself ? Also , how does “form” and “function” play a role in shaping these variants of public art ?

In addition to these , we will also be looking at variants of public art which will be classified by how much form and function is influenced in the design process and to serve its artist’s intent .

2) DEFINITION OF ART

Thomas Adajain (2018) has explored various examples of art definitions from different perspectives , and based on his observations , the definition varies by time and perspectives from different groups . By following the traditional views of art , art always been correlated to aesthetics ; especially with Monroe Beardsley takes account onto “arrangement of conditions” when defining artwork . On the other hand , institutionalists had always equated art to subjects , point of view and engagement with the audience . There were also hybrid definitions (meeting the middle ground) which satisfies both aesthetic and substantive aspects and appealed to the likes of functions and institutions .

This issue of defining art was also acknowledged by British philosopher Richard Wollheim (1980) . He discovered that defining art will develop into finding the meaning of the meanings of art (art → works of art → examples [poem / painting / sculpture]) and even considered abandoning hope of anything but a complex conception of art (pg. 2) . He would concede by overlapping the potential answers of meaning of art instead of waiting for a unitary answer (pg. 3) .

In an attempt to find a unitary answer , Thomas Adajain (2018) concluded by connecting “art” to both aesthetical (historical) and public engagement (institutionalists) aspects . For public art’s case , both traditional and institutionalists’ definitions will be considered given their purpose as will be shown later .

3) DEFINITION OF PUBLIC AND TERM PUBLIC ART

In conjunction to this , the term “public” can be defined as people in general or community (noun) or concerning people as a whole (adjective) . Being used as an adjective in this case , and by combining the “art” definition found by Adajain , the term “public art” can be defined as “an arrangement of conditions” (Adajain , 2018) that serves in both aesthetic and subjective matter to general people .

To put it simply , public art was made to serve its broad audience (public) in spreading the ideas from its artist . However , there was another definition coined by Bach from his work “New-Land-Marks” in 2001 which is art placed in a space easily accessed and enjoyed by public . This was found by Cher Krause Knight (2011 , Preface) who addressed the definition lacking further connection between content and audience or “art coefficient” from “The Creative Art” by Marcel Duchamp (1957) [FOUND BY KNIGHT] .

The term “art coefficient” was used as an indicator of public art on the gap between the intentions of an artist and the realization as stated by Duchamp (Knight , 2011) where viewers must contemplate the art in order to fulfil the artist’s intent . Without viewer’s interactions or reactions to art , regardless of whether the reception is positive or negative , the artistic process remains unfulfilled . Duchamp also stated that art by artists , regardless of their source material , will be discerned by the public depending on their viewpoints and will become more prevalent as the public size increases (Knight , 2011) .

That being said , the term “art” can be very loose and questionable , even when given context . When Knight (2011) quoted Penny Bach’s definition of public art simply being located to the public , she brought up an argument from Hilde Hein (1996) where “art-out-of-doors or in a bus terminal doesn’t make it art , similar to putting a tiger in a backyard doesn’t make it an animal” .

In addition to that , when interviewed by Judith Findlay , two artists Matthew Dalziel and Louis Scullion (Kearton , 1996 , pg. 23) hinted the importance of art coefficient when discussing the terms and use of “art” . There , Dalziel argued towards not labelling “art” as it doesn’t have to be explicitly art and will still serve the public as “art” (do not need to know its art) based on their own terms . This goes together with Hein’s argument where “art” isn’t defined by how explicitly “artsy” it is . This statement also applies to public art , if the “art coefficient” was met (Knight , 2011) .

One of the works of Dalziel and Scullion that does not directly tell that its art is their Rain Pavilion (Thuwal) in King Abdullah University of Science and Technology built in 2015 . According to them , this pavilion simply takes the shape of the sphagnum moss which represents the opposite of the regional climate . This was done in conjunction to their premise to emulate different rain sounds where rain is scarce in Saudi Arabia . There , no aesthetically explicit changes were made other than to present itself as the oddball of the Arabian climate .

4) BRIEF HISTORY OF PUBLIC ART

Figure 1 - Rain Pavilion (Thuwal) in King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (Dalziel + Scullion , 2015) . This pavilion is shaped like a sphagnum moss and was designed around the contrasting climate by emulating different rain sounds .

When Knight (2011) started delving into the origins of the “public art”, she focused on the public support of art, leading to an idea of an official art patronage of the United States despite the clear definition of public art not yet discovered. This took off initially as reinforced agendas (portraits etc.) made in a way to be seen in public. There, its notion in public art as a service remained a concept. Following the starting stage, art philosopher Carol Duncan insisted public art as an “evidence in political virtue”, where the government serves its people while preserving its past accomplishments (Knight, 2011). This emphasises the importance of public art as a “messenger” to the public; cementing its purpose in process and aligning with the “art coefficient” as coined by Duchamp.

This in turn leads to the discussion of form and function in public art and whether the form aspect (aesthetics) or function aspect (subject matter) has more importance in public arts.

5) FORM VS FUNCTION IN PUBLIC ART

One of the most popular terms in architecture are “form” and “function”, especially when associated with the design or architectural aspect of topic. The phrase “form follows function” coined by Louis Sullivan in 1896 was commonly followed by architects and designers, but for those who were in charge of public art, where “art” has to be displayed to a broader audience, this phrase could come off as contradictory.

In theory, public art was given more leniency than other typical buildings due to not being tied to building regulations. However, these artworks were still dependent on all parties involved including the artist, sponsor and the public. And considering the sensitivity of the public towards artworks created to and for them, function still has to be considered.

There are two types of public art which I will be looking to explore: the “form” dependent and the “function” dependent variants. “Form” based public art was built mostly for leisure and entertainment purposes. These artworks, as classified earlier, relied on aesthetics based on the historical definitions of art (Adajain, 2018). The form of these public arts can be manipulated in various factors such as shape and size.

Figures 2 and 3 showcased a few examples of form-dependent city arts, including the Thermo Photovoltaic Energy Converter by Panamarenko (1967) and “Memorial to the Unknown Artist” by Hermann Pitz (2003).

Figure 2- Thermo Photovoltaic Energy Converter by Panamarenko (Artnet , 2001) . This vehicle was given a streamlined shape to give the impression that it's useful for land , water and air transport .

Figure 3 - Memorial to the Unknown Artist II by Hermann Pitz (Matzner , 2003) .

“Function” based public art , however , served as a memorial of a serious topic , aiming to remind and teach the users (more in-depth interactions) . This coincides with the institutionalists’ definition of art which was also explored by Adajain (2018) .

A good example of “function” , or “function over form” variant of public art is the Cashier’s Booth II designed by Stephen Craig . When he designed the booth , he envisioned it as the simplest interpretation of the fair to work as a metaphor of the city . This was done by simply reducing the form of the fair to the minimum (cashier booth) (pg. 33) . By doing so , he emphasised the cashier booth as just “nice , colourful , little houses” as shown in Figure 4 which functions as a lead to the secondary existence (fair) (pg. 34-35) . He also quoted that “everything else is there because the cashier’s booth is there” .

Figure 4 – Cashier’s Booth II by Stephen Craig (Galerie Bob Gysin , 2002) . This booth was Craig’s sculptural interpretation of shrinking the fair to the simplest possible unit (Craig , pg. 33) .

That being said , form and function in public art are not mutually exclusive and public arts can serve one aspect without compromising another aspect . A public art can also sit in the middle of both aspects and in turn can blur the fine line between form and function . The form manipulation of these public arts can bring an impact on both the public user and the intentions of the artist . This coincides with Richard Wollheim’s suggestion of overlapping where an art works as more than either eye candy or memorial .

In fact , the form and function categorised examples shown earlier has some “cross” influences . The works of Panamarenko and Pitz were said with an intention to change the city (2003 , pg. 21) . When Panamarenko designed that said vehicle , he envisioned its versatility for land , water and air transport (2003 , pg. 115) . On the other side , Craig’s cashier booth was still lit in colours to turn into a focal point (form manipulation) (pg. 33) .

6) FORM EXAMPLE 1 : JAMES TURRELL

We will be looking at the two notable examples of form-based public art and the function-based public art and explore into what makes these artworks (or artists) notable in communicating the audience with their artistic intentions akin to the art coefficient , whether it be factors of forms (shapes) , functions (message) or a mixture of both factors .

Starting with artist John Turrell , who was well known for his interconnections with the manifolds of visual perception by manipulating light and space in his works (Adcock & Turrell , 1990 , 1-2) . There , his main intentions of playing with these two spatial factors in his artworks was to create an experience of wordless thought , to make the quality and sensation of light itself seem tactile .

He has plentiful examples of public arts that visualized his quote stated earlier . These include , but not limited to Colome Winery and Estate in Argentina , Culiacan Botanical Gardens in Mexico and Rice University in Houston , USA (Rellihan , 2018) which were among the more publicly accessible artworks of his . Following the list provided , Rellihan touched on his signature style of his artworks , which is typically “an observatory with an aperture in the ceiling open to the sky” . In other words , the observatory focuses on the skylight cut-outs and implements them in lighting effects to maximise impact towards observants .

Figure 5 – Unseen Blue (built in 2002) , one of James Turrell's works in his own museum located in the Colome Winery and Estate (Rellihan , 2018) .

The first two examples stated (Colome Winery and Culiacan Botanical Gardens) used that stated principle of complimenting skylight with his artificial lighting effects . Both places were made as “space for introspection” for viewers (Rellihan , 2018) and have relatively specific requirements for best viewer experience . These requirements include silence and timing being dawn or sunset which were highly advised to give the desired intoxicating and dizzying effect (Rellihan , 2018) which goes together with Turrell’s intentions (Adcock & Turrell , 1990) .

Figure 6 – Encounter by James Turrell located in Culiacan Botanical Garden , Mexico (Rellihan , 2018) . To get the best experience of the skylight scenery , silence and desired time setting is highly recommended .

His other public art , the Twilight Epiphany Skyspace located at Rice University , also utilised the similar concept as his two works of art mentioned earlier , albeit not as fully prioritised . There , James Turrell has made use of colour changing of his artificial lighting in conjunction to the time setting . This aspect , while present in most of his other works , was the focus of the skylight pyramid structure .

Figure 7 – The Twilight Epiphany Skyspace Pavilion (built in 2012) located at Rice University (Designboom , 2012) . This image shows the closeup up the pavilion where the attendants can experience the lighting effects from both inside and outside the pavilion .

The images above and below showcased how the colour changing of the LED lightings synced with the time of the location . The picture above showed the blue LED lights accenting the sunrise whereas the picture below illustrates the pink lighting complimenting the evenings . These alterations of colours in accordance with time settings can be experienced from both inside and outside the structure as shown in Figure 8 .

Figure 8 – Twilight Epiphany Skyspace changing colour to pink when approaching evening , syncing with the location time setting (Designboom , 2012) .

In terms of functional aspect of Turrell’s works , his lighting effects has created a form of relaxation for people to access and in turn , provided a soothing and therapeutic feeling for people . This fits the function purpose of Turrell’s public arts , coinciding as the result of “an experience of wordless thought” that Turrell envisioned (Adcock & Turrell , 1990) . That being said , these benefits were not explicitly stated by Turrell or part of his intent , meaning the “function” aspect of his public arts were subtle and worked as side effect of his form manipulation .

7) FORM EXAMPLE 2 : HEART-SHAPED INSTALLATION

The second example of public art is the Heart Shaped Installation built by MODU Architects and Eric Forman which sits in an awkward position as it heavily relies on form factor to serve a function (both form and function) . The goal of this sculpture was to celebrate both love and diversity of the city of New York as commissioned by Times Square Arts (Harrouk , 2020) .

Figure 9 – The Heart Shaped Installation by MODU and Eric Forman (Harrouk , 2020) . This sculpture heavily relies on certain perspective by viewer to showcase its true shape .

The designers from MODU and Eric Forman Studio quoted to “celebrate the essential New York – bringing together people of all backgrounds , ethnicities , orientations and walks of life” through this sculpture . To achieve this premise , the designers made use of two different aspects of the public art sculpture : material and shape .

The Heart Shaped Installation was described by Eric Forman as an “abstract anatomical heart from a cubic steel lattice” (Harrouk , 2020) . The “love” aspect of this can be clearly seen from its name through the pixelated shape . In addition to the shape , the “cubic steel lattice” construction helps in giving it a pixelated aesthetic through steel frames .

Lighting and reflections through mirrors were also used “as an amplifier of this togetherness” as the designers described (Harrouk , 2020) . Eric Forman stated that this effect manipulation , accompanied with the material choices , gave the structure “a balancing act between structure and air , buildings and sky , people and city , and movement and slowness” . Plus , the way this structure was built gives the viewers a “sweet spot” perspective which displays its shape , “giving people a new way to see the city – and together” .

Figures 10 and 11 showcased the importance of points of view from viewers in fulfilling the artistic potential of the sculpture .

Figure 10 – Heart Shaped Installation in a not-so-ideal point of view .

Figure 11 – Heart Shaped Installation in an ideal point of view , where the mirrors reflected onto the surroundings and create a heart shape .

These two examples of form-based public arts shown earlier share one thing in common , which is the dynamic nature . This was mostly due to these works of art presented in a way that requires a more specific approach of appreciation . For example , the . As for Eric Forman’s Heart Shaped Installation , a specific viewpoint (point of view) was needed to “tie” the unity-based shape . James Turrell’s public arts are more prevalent in terms of dynamic nature incorporations .

This helps in making these public arts sticking out in the crowd instead of appearing as a replaceable monument , as addressed by Bogomir Ecker (2003) . Ecker criticised the static nature of sculptures and how by leaving it as it is , “even huge pillars made of stone , horseback riders cast in bronze and lots and lots of modern art sculptures could quickly be brought up from the underground and then disappear again after a time” (pg. 40) . He added with how these sculptures would no longer pervade space , but instead would be submergible , not occupying space – like the ghosts of a lasting memory (pg. 40) .

8) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 1 : PARC DE LA VILLETTE

Now that the form-oriented public arts were covered , we'll be moving to the function-oriented public arts , where the motives of the artists were driven by subject matter (messages and intents) , similar to the institutionalists' view of art brought up earlier (Adajain , 2018) .

The first example of a function-driven public art in discussion is the Parc De La Villette designed by Bernard Tschumi in 1987 . When Bernard Tschumi entered and won the design competition for the "Urban Park for the 21st Century" in 1982 , his design envisioned the integrated nature of government policies in economic , social and physical planning (Lee , 1991 , pg. 313) . His winning design proposed the park to be less of an escape from the city akin to Frederick Law Olmsted's Central Park of New York , but to work as a continuation of the city .

Figure 12 – Parc De La Villette designed by Bernard Tschumi (Comberg , 2018) . This park was built in a way to act as transition area across the city instead of embracing escapism from city life as shown with the wide walking spaces and pedestrian bridges .

This urban park proposal relies on the theory of three systems being points , lines and surfaces (pg. 314) . This theory is similar to Kevin Lynch's theory of 5 elements of the city . Going back to the Tschumi's proposal , this proposal aligns with Tschumi's intent of reshaping the urban parks as shown by not conforming with the tropes of the traditional urban parks . There , the points worked as red follies evenly distributed across the project , the lines represent the varying connecting pathways , and the surface acts as planar spaces open to various activities (pg. 314-315) .

The functional element was the priority of this proposal thanks to Tschumi considering pedestrian factors into the development of the plan . Examples include the points or follies as breaking points for pedestrians to relax and the lines forming interesting pathways to prevent monotony . The surface aspect of the park translates to flexibility and adaptability since it is open-ended and has no specific purpose .

Figure 13 – The exploded axonometric diagram of Parc De La Villette (Williams , 2019)

TOP ROW – LINES (connections)

MIDDLE ROW – POINTS (follies)

BOTTOM ROW – SURFACE (open space)

The follies of the park (or the points) , while functions as breaking points , also behaved as the most form-influenced aspect of the park . This was thanks to the follies being painted red as shown in Figure 14 , therefore they stick out of the whole park . This also comes in handy for pedestrians , indicating the available spots to take

a break from walking across the park . This scenario showcased how the form aspect of the proposal can help contributing to the functional aspect of the project .

Figure 14 – Parc De La Villette with the red structures / follies as points and the pedestrian bridge as one example of lines (Comberg , 2018) . The red colour of the follies were the key points of the park and serves as resting space and even a rooftop platform .

Despite the elaborate and complex shape of the urban proposal , Tschumi quoted “There is no obvious focus of the overall concept , since spatial importances change according to usage” (Lee , 1991 , pg. 315) . This was because Tschumi went against the site history to make a park a “non-place” , where people behave in their own terms and were not limited by positions of other amenities in a typical urban park (Comberg , 2018) .

According to Comberg (2018) , Tschumi’s park design shares the same principles as Georges Seurat’s painting “A Sunday Afternoon of the Island of La Grande Jatte” where relaxation was prioritised . The difference , however , was Tschumi also incorporated social interaction into his design via points (follies) and surfaces (open spaces) . Through this comparison , Comberg (2018) used Parc De La Villette as the catalyst for the upcoming urban park works , where they function as “space for cross-cultural , inter-neighbourhood contact in the increasingly digital and segregated world” .

9) FUNCTION EXAMPLE 2 : RACHEL WHITEREAD

The next example(s) will go to the works of Rachel Whiteread, who is a renowned artist in terms of incorporating deeper connotations into her artworks. She was famous for her sculptures being made as memorials of the past events and casted in bare concrete. The intentions and material of choice for her sculptures aligns well with the brutalist nature of architecture which relies on the pure human nature (no frills) and the quality of material such as the woodness of wood as quoted by Peter Smithson (Campbell, n.d.). Hence, I believed the brutalist approach to sculptures by Whiteread helped in shaping the message to the public.

This is where both form and function helped her in designing these memorials, as the form factor (brutalist-like nature and materials) contributed to the functional aspects of her sculptures. The two public art examples from her which perfectly highlights the importance of function and form in resonating with the audience, being "House" in East London and the Holocaust Memorial in Vienna.

The "House" was one of her first precast concrete contraptions and it was what puts her in a spotlight as both the best and worst artist of Britain in 1993 (Cohen, 2018). She used her experience of casting from her earlier work "Ghost" where she casted a house in North London with plaster of Paris. This helped to serve her childhood memories, with the said material giving the neo-classical look and strengthening the nostalgic factor (Cohen, 2018).

Figure 15 – The "House" sculpture built by Rachel Whiteread in 1993 (Cohen, 2018)

Figure 16 – Rachel Whiteread casting "Ghost" house in 1990 with plaster of Paris. This method is also used for her "House" except with concrete (Cohen, 2018).

Her “House” work , however , goes beyond personal connections as it serves as “a lighting rod for all kinds of public house debates” (Cohen , 2018) , or in other words , tackling the gentrification topic . Whiteread made “House” by using the remaining dwelling house to be demolished as a mask and did so with concrete . As a result , the “House” became a subject for debate among locals with positive responses from the tourist side and negative reception from the victims of gentrification .

In terms of form and function , by using the traditional dwelling house architecture as casting , it not only shaped the past of the location , bringing out nostalgia factor (form) but also helps enforcing the relevant message to the public and authorities .

Figure 16 – The Holocaust Memorial by Rachel Whiteread in Vienna (Searle , 2000) .The stacked-slab like façade was formed from the dated books in the library

The Holocaust Memorial , built in Vienna in 2000 , is the more prominent example of Whiteread’s public art efforts . Built in conjunction to remember the lost lives of the Holocaust , she prioritised on the unapologetic and uncomfortable presence to remind the public about the horrors of the past incident (Searle , 2000) . The single-storey , fully enclosed building was “engraved” with old books listing the names of the Death Camps to effectively resonate with the public , bringing awareness in the process .

In terms of form aspects , Whiteread’s signature construction method is prevalent with indoor casting of concrete inside the nameless library . As a result , the casted concrete has left the scars off the aging and used books (Searle , 2000) . In addition to that , Searle (2000) stated that Whiteread wanted to use a more porous (wetter) concrete to give a sorrier appearance given that the memorial was built to commemorate such tragedy , but never materialised . This shows another example of how form is as equally important as function in dictating the message the artists wanted to send to the audience .

10) CONCLUSION

Based on these examples of easily accessible artworks and further exploration , there are various instances of how form and function helped in shaping and influencing the public arts that graced the public spaces . For instance , James Turrell aims to bring refreshing ways of experiencing lighting effects to his audience , whereas Rachel Whiteread stands to her purpose of tributing to tragic events of the past . With that being said , both form and function can contribute to each other on serving their purpose , since these elements are not mutually exclusive . A skylight enclosure from Turrell can help people in relaxing and therapeutic manners while a memorial by Whiteread relies on casting of traditional architectural styles (form) to evoke reactions from the public .

Short answer : form plays a bigger role in shaping public art . Long answer : the artist's intents are the main driving force of their public art and the forms and functions behave more as catalysts than deal-sealers of their design .

In addition to that , Duchamp's term "art coefficient" also have to be considered when determining public art based on connecting artist's intents and public interactions (Knight , 2011) regardless of their response ; hence the word "public" in public art . This also means that "art" does not necessarily have to be explicitly brought up akin to both Dalziel and Scullion said on how art shouldn't have to conform to the traditional viewpoint of art (Kearton , 1996 pg. 23) .

To put it simply , public art puts more emphasis on "public" than "art" , despite both terms important in the making of public art . As long as the sculpture satisfies the form or function based purposes and involves public engagement , referring to them as public art could be more legitimate .

(4750 words including citations)

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adajain , T. (2018). “The Definition of Art” . Found here : <https://plato.stanford.edu/>

Adams , K. , Bourgeois , L. , Craig , S. , Ecker , B. , Eliasson , O. , Erkmén , A. , Genzken , I. , Golz , D. , Grosch , W. , Metzger , F. , Haacke , H. , Herz , R. , Huber , S. , Julius , R. , Kabakov , E. , Kabakov , I. , Korpys , A. , Löffler , M. , Van Lieshout , A. , Kuball , M. , M+M , Manz , J. , Nicolai , O. , Opie , J. , Panamarenko , Pitz , H. , Potrc , M. , Rehberger , T. , Ruff , T. , Baudrexel , F. , Ulrich , J. , Signer , R. , Theis , B. , De Vries , H. , Winter , W. , Horbert , B. (2003). “No Art = No City : Urban Utopias in Contemporary Art” (Bilingual edition) , Bremen : Hatje Cantz Verlag Pub.

Adcock , C. E. ; Turrell , James (1990). “James Turrell : The art of light and space” , California : University of California Press . Retrieved from : https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/James_Turrell/RN-NiMBuD7MC?hl=en&gbpv=0

Artnet (2001). “Thermo Photovoltaic Energy Converter” . Retrieved from : <http://www.artnet.com/artists/panamarenko/thermo-photovoltaic-energy-converter-9U8AtYB5cXk-1vwillxapw2>

Campbell , T. (n.d.). “Brutalist Architecture : The Defining Style of the 20th Century ?” . Retrieved from : <https://magazine.artland.com/brutalist-architecture-the-defining-style-of-the-20th-century/>

Cohen , A. (2018). “Rachel Whiteread’s ‘House’ was Unliveable , Controversial and Unforgettable” . Retrieved from : <https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-rachel-whitereads-house-unlivable-controversial-unforgettable>

Comberg , E. (2018). “How the Parc De La Villette Kickstarted A New Era in Urban Design” . Retrieved from : <https://www.archdaily.com/899597/how-the-parc-de-la-villette-kickstarted-a-new-era-for-urban-design>

Dalziel + Scullion (2015). “Rain (Thuwal) . Retrieved from : <https://dalzielscullion.com/works-entry/rain-jedda/>

Designboom (2012). “James Turrell : Twilight Epiphany Skyspace at Rice University” . Retrieved from : <https://www.designboom.com/art/james-turrell-twilight-epiphany-skyspace-at-rice-university/>

Galerie Bob Gysin (2002). “Stephen Craig : Kasse II” . Retrieved from : http://old.likeyou.com/archives/stephen_craig_gbg.htm

Harrouk , C. (2020). “Heart Shaped Installation , Designed by MODU and Eric Forman , Opens in Times Square” . Retrieved from : <https://www.archdaily.com/933212/heart-squared-installation-designed-by-modu-and-eric-forman-opens-in-times-square>

Kearton , N. (1996). “Art & Design : Public Art” Vol 11 No. ½ , Munich : DTV Verlagsgesellschaft .

Knight , C. K. (2011). “Public Art : Theory , Practice and Populism” , Blackwell : Wiley . Found here : https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/Public_Art/qkxClDeTCbQC?hl=en&gbpv=0

Lee , J. (1991). PARC DE LA VILLETTE: A VIEW TO THE FUTURE. *Landscape Australia*, 13(4), 313-319. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/45144064>

Matzner , F. (2003). “Stadtutopien in der zeitgenössischen Kunst” . Retrieved from : <https://www.staedtischegalerie-bremen.de/archiv/archiv-2003/no-art-no-city/>

Rellihan , K. (2018). “How to find James Turrell’s art in the most unlikely corners of the Earth” . Retrieved from : <https://www.architecturaldigest.com/story/james-turrell-art-around-the-world>

Searle , A. (2000). “Austere , Silent and Nameless – Whiteread’s Concrete Tributes to Victims of Nazism” . Retrieved from : <https://www.theguardian.com/culture/2000/oct/26/artsfeatures6>

Williams , A. (2019). “Parc De La Villette , Paris” Retrieved from : <https://www.udg.org.uk/publications/articles/parc-de-la-villette-paris>

Wollheim , Richard (1980). “Art and Its Objects” Cambridge University Press . Retrieved from : [https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/Art and Its Objects/NBmYGQDjM6sC?hl=en&gbpv=0](https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/Art%20and%20Its%20Objects/NBmYGQDjM6sC?hl=en&gbpv=0)

Caring for older people: How are Portsmouth's public spaces doing?

Abstract

How can we as urban designers take better care of older citizens? Rapid urbanisation and ageing populations are two trends that significantly impact today's society. More people over 60 years old than ever before live in cities. However, the spatial qualities of these urban landscapes can overlook the needs of the aging, which enable them to live a fulfilling life. With trends in changing demographics, the well-being of older persons should be increasingly considered for creating a healthy and happy society. Research has shown that the quality of urban landscapes have a significant impact on a person's well-being.

Aims: This study aims to explore how an urban outdoor space can actively care for older people. By linking the quality of Portsmouth's outdoor public spaces and their elements to older people's physical and mental well-being it aims to argue that this is significant to the urban users' quality of life as they grow old. This exploration aims to identify the qualities that are important for promoting well-being and suggest ways to increase levels of care in existing environments.

Methodology: In response to relevant research, this study has created categories named "acts of care". These categories include opportunities for positive diversity, healthy and active lifestyles, social engagement and a fair chance to interact with resources. In order to explore the quality of how a space can exhibit these acts of care, there will be an analysis of existing examples of each act. The aspects allowing these examples to successfully care for older people will be highlighted through maps and key notes. The aims will be explored by looking at the case study of Commercial Road, the heart of Portsmouth. Visual exploration of the site will measure the qualities of each "act" on Commercial Road by scoring each out of 10. This will be done considering the lessons learnt from the examples and research explored. A visual and written response will then propose improvements aiming to produce a caring renewal of Commercial Road and other urban outdoor spaces.

Findings: Certain organisations and researchers have begun to think about how the urban environment can care for older people. However the findings make it clear our cities still have a lot of improvements to make in order to become intentional at creating spaces that care for the well-being of those who have come to the end of their careers and are beginning to experience signs of ageing. There are several qualities of an urban outdoor environment that indicate the level of care when designing that environment. Currently, there is a disconnect between the well-being of the aging and the most frequented urban outdoor areas. Lessons can be learned from certain examples of the "acts of care", suggesting how urban professionals can optimise spaces for aging populations. In conjunction with lessons from successful environments and research on the effect of environments on well-being urban planners need to develop areas of neglect that are present.

Key words: Urban ageing, care, well-being, urban outdoor spaces, older people

Contents list

i. List of figures

1. Why should we care?

2. Acts of a caring city

3. How caring is Commercial Road?

4. A caring urban outdoor space

5. References

List of figures

- Figure 1** Age UK statistics on the changes in older population (2013)
- Figure 2** Age distribution of world population by sex from 1950 to 2100
- Figure 3** Median age of population in UK
- Figure 4** Changes in percentage of urban population in different contents
- Figure 5** Dictionary definitions of care
- Figure 6** Average personal well-being ratings by age 2012-2015 UK
- Figure 7** Influences of Person-Environment Fit on Residential Satisfaction and Psychological Well-Being of Aged Community Dwellers
- Figure 8** Global Age-friendly Cities: A Guide - Outdoor spaces and buildings
- Figure 9** Acts of a caring city
- Figure 10** Example of Diversity - Mount Sterling, Illinois, USA
- Figure 11** Proportion who have been victim of crime and their perception of likelihood of being a victim by age group 2016, England and Wales
- Figure 12** Example of positive people to people interaction - Songzhuang Micro Community Park
- Figure 13** Changes in walking speed with age
- Figure 14** Example of accessibility - Stadshart, Zoetermeer, The Netherlands
- Figure 15** Example of enabling healthy lifestyles - Steepleton, Tetbury, Gloucestershire
- Figure 16** Acts of care and areas of neglect on Commercial Road
- Figure 17** Photograph of positive and diverse stimulation on Commercial Road
- Figure 18** Photograph of people to people interaction on Commercial Road
- Figure 19** Photograph of access to amenities on Commercial Road
- Figure 20** Photograph of healthy resources on Commercial Road
- Figure 21** A caring urban outdoor centre

Age UK statistics on the changes in older population (2013)

The number of over 65 year olds has risen from 885,000 to 967,000.

Annual spending for older households has gone up by £12 billion.

Around 4.9 million over 65 year olds volunteer or civically engaged (more than half of that age group) in England.

Older people contribute up to £50 billion in unpaid family care for their family members.

In England and Wales the number of over 65 year olds projected to increase by 65 per cent to more than 16.4 million in 2033.

The number of over 85s in the UK is double by nearly 2040

Britain's population more than before. number and ethnic aged is d to 11

over 2006

Figure 1

of over 85s set to 2030 and treble by

older on is diverse ever

The of black minority people over 70 project increase times

from to 2051

Why should we care?

Everyone grows older - it is a part of life. Globally the percentage of older people is beginning to match the percentage of the youngest people (Ball, et al., 2012). Figure 2 shows the global demographic change. There is an increase in the amount of people living longer from 1950 and the UN's predictions into 2100. By 2030 at least one quarter of the urban population will be 60 years plus (Phillipson, 2011). Meanwhile, Figure 3 shows the upwards trend of median age in the UK from 2001 to 2020. In response to the growing field of gerontology (the study of the

Age distribution of world population by sex from 1950 to 2100

Figure 2

Median age of population in UK

Figure 3

Changes in percentage of urban population in different continents

Figure 4

process and issues that come with aging) the UK Government aims to make the UK the best country to grow old in, in Europe (Age UK, 2013). However, it acknowledges that there is still work to be done to achieve this (Government Office for Science, 2016). Figure 4 shows the move of our societies into urban environments by showing percentage change from 1950 to 2020. By 2030 two thirds of the global population will live in urban environments (Phillipson, 2011). Urbanism is a key outcome of the advances of the twentieth century that have drastically changed lifestyles. It has redefined how people live in built communities and how people can play a role in the ever increasing globalisation of culture and economy (Ball, et al., 2012). It is significant to note that a lot of urban planning is centred around young families with children and most planning with older adults in mind has been within specialized age-segregated retirement and care communities (Ball, et al., 2012). This essay is a prompt to "us" as urban designers and planners to continue to discuss how urban spaces can care for urban livers by ensuring they can grow old in environments that enable them healthy and happy lives. Within this essay when referring to "we", it is a reference to the professionals who create these environments.gap in literature targeted at exploring the support of the well-being of this age group through the outdoor built environment.

Urban outdoor spaces can be outlined in different ways and when referencing these spaces this paper uses definitions provided by Woolley and Gehl. In the tangible sense, Woolley (2003) describes it as an urban area not covered by buildings, including that area's space and light. He suggests a sense of fluidity into and out of the city. In the conceptual sense,

Dictionary definitions of care

Gehl (2011) defines it from a user's perspective, noting that these spaces allow for different types of activities - necessary, optional and social. These spaces have been chosen as this is where many city dwellers convene and use daily life. A majority of the literature on this subject is on urban environments adjacent to neighbourhoods of older people from the idea of "aging in place" (Smith, 2009). Although the urban outdoor spaces most used by older people will be the ones they live near, this essay is taking the approach that eventually all urban outdoor spaces will be frequented by older people. Therefore, all urban outdoor spaces should consider the well-being of this age group. The age-friendly cities movement is a recent advancement in urban care for older people. It has a particular focus on accessibility and "active-aging" as covered by the World Health Organisation (WHO) definition. WHO defines an age-friendly city as a place that has services and structures that are accessible to older people and their varying needs. This then allows them to participate in all aspects of life (World Health Organisation, 2007). Although accessibility is key when providing spaces for older people, there is a gap in literature targeted at exploring the support of the well-being of this age group through the outdoor built environment. While this essay has taken aspects of existing criteria on what it means to be age-friendly this essay aims to take a new perspective. This study looks at not just how we can be inclusive but how our city spaces can directly seek to look after older people's well-being.

"Serious attention or consideration applied to doing something correctly or to avoid damage or risk" (Lexico, 2021)

"The process of protecting someone or something and providing what that person or thing needs" (Cambridge University Press, 2022)

"If you care about something, you feel that it is important and are concerned about it" (Collins, 2022)

Figure 5

Average personal well-being ratings by age 2012-2015 UK

Figure 6

The definitions in Figure 5 have been taken from well-known dictionaries to reflect how our general western society views the concept of care. When looking at these sources "affection" is mentioned. While many of these definitions show an aim to place importance on someone or something and fulfilling certain needs, there is a more humane and emotional connection that appears missing. The first definition particularly highlights the idea of a rigid intentionality in order to "get things right". This can be seen in the ideals of modernist design and today's societal attitudes. There is a danger that we might take this approach to designing urban spaces and design out of efficiency rather than out of wanting the best for users in an affectionate way. This could be why many places lack care for older adults because we have focused on certain aspects of society that appear to be most lucrative. In disruption to this way of thinking, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought to light a need to care for those in our communities that are most vulnerable. This essay will explore what it means for our cities' public spaces to look after older people because they have been highlighted as most sensitive to the challenges that urbanism presents.

In order to care for this diverse age group, we need to understand who they are and what their priorities are so that they can live full lives. Figure 1 includes UK statistics that challenge stereotypes

of those who are older but also gives more context as to their place in this nation. When identifying this age group, the Department of Health (2001) identifies that older age can begin from a stage called "entering older age", going on to the "transitional phase" between health and frailty and finally the state of frailty. This way of looking at age presents two aspects: frailty and lifestyle change. "Entering old age" is defined as when a person has completed or is coming to the end of their career in child rearing and/or paid employment. It can begin from different ages and changes in life expectancy have increased the UK's retirement age to 68 (Gov.uk, 2021). However it is possible to choose to decrease work amount or stop working from around 55 (Standard Life, 2021). When referencing older people this essay includes those who are coming to the end of their career because of age until the end of their lives as well as those experiencing the health impacts of aging.

Retirement and levels of health are a significant change to lifestyle that impacts

Influences of Person, Environment, and Person-Environment Fit on Residential Satisfaction and Psychological Well-Being of Aged Community Dwellers

Figure 7

how one interacts with the city and therefore their well-being. The CDC (2018) defines well-being as integrating mental health and physical health in a balance of subjective and objective measures. ONS data (2018) reveals that perception of personal well-being is at its lowest during a person's midlife; it then rises from 60 to 64 years, until its highest around 65 to 75 before starting to decrease with age. Figure 6 represents ratings of well-being from 2012-2015 by age in the UK. In order to look after older people we should design urban spaces in a way that can prevent the decrease of well-being as urban dwellers grow old. Poignantly, a study showed that outdoor environments can play a significant role in an older person's quality of life. This is because they provide important opportunities for daily lives and activities of the elderly. On the other hand, they can also create barriers that might prevent older people from going outside (Sugiyama & Thompson, 2005). Figure 7 shows how the relationship between the individual and the environment they are in can impact satisfaction and psychological well-being.

This study investigates the idea that to look after older people we need to actively promote their well-being. In comparison to age-friendly guides this study focuses less on physical characteristics and more on the opportunities provided as well as the experiential qualities that allow for increased levels of well-being for older people. Four key "acts of a caring city" have emerged; these acts of care include: diverse and positive stimulation, positive people to people interactions, accessibility and healthy lifestyles. While these acts are beneficial to all urban participants, the health challenges that increase with age mean that older people are more likely to find these categories as barriers to leading healthy and happy lives. As people get older there are key issues that are prevalent including depression, isolation, cognitive health, falling, urinary incontinence, pain in their body and social isolation (Kernisan, 2016). All of these issues make older people more sensitive to barriers to social engagement, accessing resources, remaining active and healthy and enjoying an environment sensorily.

The investigation will include looking at Commercial Road, which is considered the city centre, as a representation of how well Portsmouth's urban outdoor spaces are currently doing. To compliment each act of care and demonstrate how they can be implemented four significant examples of care responding to the needs of older people have been selected. In response to the research on the care of older people in an urban outdoor space and the examples, Commercial Road will be analysed and scored on each "act of care". In order to do this a visual exploration of maps and images and an in person visit will identify aspects of care and areas of neglect. From this analysis suggestions of redevelopment to Commercial Road will be used to propose how to create a caring urban outdoor space.

Global Age-friendly Cities: A Guide - Outdoor spaces and buildings

Figure 8

Figure 9

Acts of a Caring City

As mentioned previously, outdoor environments can be great resources for older people but can also prevent them from leaving their homes. In a study conducted by Kahana et al. (2003, p. 435) on residential satisfaction of older people, they suggest that how well an environment relates to the individual can impact their levels of chronic stress. This can have serious effects on personal well-being. Based on reviewing existing literature, these four acts have been created in response to the gap concerning older people's well-being. In conjunction with this subject, WHO has developed key characteristics of an age-friendly city based on accessibility relating to outdoor spaces (see Figure 8). WHO's guide of physical characteristics indicate how easy it is for an older person to utilise an urban space. It can be used to indicate whether these four acts are present in an outdoor space and have been designed to include older people in urban life. Notably, these four acts have a specific focus on the experience and opportunities in urban outdoor spaces which largely impact the well-being of older people and reach broader than physical navigation of space. The categories work in tandem and can overlap in different ways. The four key "acts" are represented in Figure 9:

In order to explain each category clearly a exemplar case study has been selected and analysed for only one category - this does not mean there is an absence of the other acts of care.

Diverse and positive stimulation

Does the urban outdoor space provide varied sensory, active and social stimulation for older people? Diversity in an urban environment promotes a range of people and amenities within an area (Friedman, 2018). Because aging people are at risk of being socially isolated, being in diverse spaces, offering a full and active daily life can help maintain high well-being (Arup 2015). Interestingly, older people with a preference for more stimulation are likely to find less complex environments unrewarding and this will decrease their perception of their quality of life. Environmental planners highlight physical amenities as important in designing for older people. These amenities can include qualities such as the presence of plants (Kahana et al., 2003, p. 443). Contact with nature is a key example and research shows that visual contact and activity within green spaces can help mitigate the common impacts of aging. It is linked with increased cognitive function, sense of achievement, satisfaction and better quality of sleep (Sugiyama and Thompson, 2007, p. 1946). The resources and facilities in a space also add to its diversity. Kahana et al. (2003, p. 444) note that the undersupply of resources is likely to have a stronger effect than oversupply because those not wanting to will simply not use those resources. However if the resources are hard to access for older people it can greatly impact their quality of life. These resources can include daily establishments such as the sale of goods and provision of services. Diversity also includes the ability to find stimulation and tranquility (Kahana et al 2003, p.445). As people age they are more likely to be sensitive to overbearing and unpleasant sensory experiences (touch, sight, hearing, smell and taste) and they should be able to find a suitable balance for their needs and preferences. The quality of recreational facilities is another aspect contributing to diversity and can have an impact on the social environment and either support or deter an older person's physical activity. Such places

Elements adding diversity:

- + Renovation of historic buildings for retail
- + New building houses an independent food market
- + Streetscaping new sidewalks, street trees, landscaping / flower beds, new light

- poles, banners, and areas for sidewalk cafes.
- + Renovated Hagel building as restaurant
- + Preserved post office's facade
- + New lighting scheme for old courthouse
- + Restored water tower
- + New civic plaza

Example of diversity - Mount Sterling, Illinois, USA

Figure 10

should be clean and safe with adequate lighting in order to encourage use (Friedman, 2018). Providing diverse stimulation may include and lead to social interaction, physical activity and also access to facilities.

Positive people to people interactions

As Gehl suggests, urban outdoor spaces provide somewhere for activities. An example is social engagement such as greeting others, engaging in conversations and seeing other people. These activities enable older people to feel part of a community. Research has shown that environments that are pedestrian-oriented are mixed used and also create opportunities for older people to interact and connect (Sugiyama and Thompson, 2007, p. 1946). Moreover studies have shown that older people with more social interaction show less signs of depression and frequent participation in social activities decreases the risk of dementia (Sugiyama and Thompson, 2007, p. 1946). When linking social engagement to space Kahana et al (2003, p. 447) note that feeling a sense of community is valuable when predicting satisfaction. There is also a need for balance between positive interaction between other people and the ability to find privacy as not all older people will want to be around others all the time. As mentioned, isolation is a key issue impacting the well-being of older people but so is their perception of experiencing crime. Figure 11 shows that older people are more disproportionately afraid of experiencing crime than their experience of crime compared to younger age groups. An older person's perception of safety can also be a deterrent or encouragement to using a certain space and is particularly important for older people with more safety concerns (Kahana et al 2003, p. 445). Crafting the social aspects of an environment contributes to making it positive and inclusive. Social infrastructure should be prioritised in order to create links within communities and across generations (Arup, 2015).

Proportion who have been victim of crime and their perception of likelihood of being a victim by age group 2016, England and Wales

Figure 11

Elements creating positive people to people interactions:

- + Careful spatial configuration
- + Green zone with native plants creating natural buffer to parking lot
- + Preforated wall with integrated seating in designated social "rooms"
- + Trees and bushes create visual

- barriers marking where the park starts
- + Rooms provoke series of activities + unrestricted uses
- + Bright pathway connects "rooms" visually and physically and links different public areas
- + Different levels of enclosure and boundary
- + Seating in front of child's play room
- + Well placed lighting throughout park

Example of positive people to people interaction - Songzhuang Micro Community Park

Figure 12

Accessibility

An older person's ability to move around the city is directly linked to their quality of life. Age-related physical and cognitive impairment can impact mobility. Therefore transport systems (Arup, 2015) and the distribution and nearness of urban amenities (Kahana et al, 2003, p. 444) such as parks and services (Friedman, 2018) should consider the support older people may need. This is directly linked to the design of the built environment. Built environment includes street pattern, layout of building blocks and the density of an area. These factors will impact travel distances, how available green spaces are, street connectivity and building typologies. Accessibility is also connected to transport systems available and whether they are accessible for older users by providing adequate station stops and links to the facilities that older people frequent such as services, hospitals, parks and public centres. There are certain aspects of the city such as the exclusion of pavement, benches and street trees that have a negative impact. As the ability to walk for longer amounts of time decreases, accessible walking surfaces as well as places to rest that are sheltered and provide a chance to enjoy natural light are important for an aging population. Walkable areas with higher densities, a greater mix of uses, and efficient public transport are important to provide users with healthy lifestyles (Friedman, 2018). When amenities are in close proximity older users are more likely to utilise them. Incidentally, research shows older people travel less than younger people because of the lack of the need to travel out of necessity for work (Arup, 2015). They are also more likely to replace driving with walking or public transport. An older person's walking speed reduces with age as well as the comfortable distance they are able to walk for. Figure 13 shows how walking distance shortens with age. Urbanism supports environments that are compact which can be supportive for older people who have a decreasing life space and who value the availability of shops and services as well as public transport (Friedman, 2018). Accessibility is essential to the well-being of older people because limits to accessing the services, social spaces and activities of leisure will decrease their ability to enjoy life.

Figure 13

Elements making the space accessible

- + Evenly paved slabs on flooring
- + Underground public transport
- + Ability to park mobility aids
- + Walkable space
- + Special bus service for older people 'Ouderenbus'

- + Most streets are covered or provide protective overhangs against precipitation
- + Pavements & bus stops have dropped kerbs
- + Entrances to buildings don't have thresholds

Example of accessibility - Stadshart, Zoetermeer, The Netherlands

Figure 14

Healthy lifestyles

Public space within the built environment should offer an opportunity for an active lifestyle for all ages (Friedman, 2018) these include moderate and accessible activities such as walking (Sugiyama and Thompson, 2007, p. 1945). By participating in regular physical activity it can create many benefits for the health and functioning of older people. It has been found to minimise psychological changes that come with ageing and prevent common chronic diseases such as diabetes, arthritis and osteoporosis. It can also enhance muscle strength, sleep quality, aerobic capacity, balance, and flexibility and can help reduce the possibility of falling, a major cause of disabilities in later life. Regular physical activity can significantly support independent lifestyles in older people. (Sugiyama and Thompson, 2007, p. 1944). This lifestyle can enable older people to mitigate their cognitive decline. Physical activity like long walks, exercise, and swimming has a protective effect against depression which is prevalent in older age (Sugiyama and Thompson, 2007, p. 1945). Interestingly, using public transport promotes those who are physically inactive (an effect of aging), especially those in low-income groups, and can help them to reach recommended levels of daily exercise (Friedman, 2018). Because of older people's likelihood to lack important nutrients, the food available can also impact their well-being. This is influenced by community planning, determining whether food is accessible, healthy and fresh. Research shows links between levels of poverty, pollution and the walkability of an area (Weuve et al., 2004). However, increasing levels of physical activity can also reduce levels of pollution creating healthier environments for older people. In providing spaces that enable older people to walk more, eat healthier and engage in accessible activities, the sedentary living patterns of older adults can be combated and quality of life can be increased (Friedman, 2018). Providing facilities where group exercise can take place can also help encourage social engagement with other older adults as well as across generations.

Example of enabling healthy lifestyles - Steepleton, Tetbury, Gloucestershire

Elements enabling healthy lifestyles:

- + communal swimming pond
- + productive gardens connected to cooking facilities
- + well-connected walkways
- + covered pedestrian connections to access key areas
- + lots of greenery and opportunities for contact with nature
- + well-maintained walkways
- + reduced traffic speeds in certain areas
- + covered parking to allow access
- + separate pedestrian access

Figure 15

How Caring is Commercial Road?

Acts of care:

- + Outdoor market with variety of shopping and dining experiences as well as areas of covered seating (+ positive social interaction & positive diversity)
- + Restricted use of electric scooters (+ accessibility)
- + Well-maintained visually pleasing historic space Victoria Park closely provides green open and flexible space for exercise (+ positive diversity & positive social interaction & health)
- + Some areas with smooth paving in good condition & safe road crossings (+ accessibility & health)
- + Covered entrances to shops & services (+ accessibility)
- + Good amount of seating in some areas (+ accessibility & positive social interaction)

Areas of neglect:

- Underused & poorly maintained buildings (- positive stimulation)
- Poorly maintained & uneven paving & underused spaces (-positive stimulation & accessibility and health)
- Poor street connectivity (-accessibility & health)
- Areas known for crime (- positive social interaction)
- Seating not very comfortable or promoting cross group connections (- positive social interaction and accessibility)
- Prevalence of unhealthy food options (- health)

Acts of care and areas of neglect on Commercial Road

Figure 16

Kauhualuoma and Timonen (2016) highlight commercial centres as significant urban social environments that are used in daily activity. This study will be analysing Portsmouth's main commercial centre, Commercial Road. The methodology used will be visual exploration by looking at maps of the area, using google street view, as well as a visit to Commercial Road. To analyse how caring this area's urban outdoor spaces both the quality and quantity of the acts of care present will be identified. In addition to this the study will look at areas of neglect (which is the opposite of intentionally placing importance on older people and negatively impacts the quality of the acts of care present). Both the severity and quantity of these areas of neglect will be investigated. Each rating is then explored to highlight key experiential aspects of the space. This will create a basis to develop this urban outdoor area into a Caring Commercial Centre.

Positive stimulation 5.5/10

Commercial Road does not have the most pleasant environment to spend time in especially for older adults. Much of the area is poorly maintained with a lot of empty buildings due to store closures. This can make the atmosphere uninviting, decreasing the sense of well-being for the frequent older users.

A strength of this urban space is its variety of amenities in the area, there is a range of shops and services (mainly banking) older users can be seen to frequent. The marketplace is an asset utilised by older adults. It takes place on certain days of the week, which means that the space changes in density of amenities at different times. There could be a broader provision of services that are valuable to an older person's daily life, especially those with accessibility needs. For example, health services are currently a long walk for those who have decreased mobility. Another asset can be seen in Commercial Road's connection to Victoria Park. However the two spaces can feel disconnected because of their different atmospheres and spatial and visual connectivity. Nevertheless, Victoria Park adds diversity by providing access to a natural, historic and more tranquil environment. Although the Charles Dickens memorial on Arundel Street has the potential to promote education and culture, the atmosphere of unsafety, poor lighting and low maintenance has left it under utilised. The resources could better encourage cross generational relationships and provide more targeted facilities for healthier lifestyles. This would increase diversity by providing more variety of engaging and well-being promoting activities. Examples could include beautiful areas of public domain that can be used for exercise, and more green spaces and water features with accessible seating. Close proximity to the motorway and busy roads, makes the area a high pollution zone due to car exhaust fumes but also means that there can be unpleasant sounds from traffic and highly populated areas. The high levels of pollution in this area have a negative impact on

Figure 17

older people who are at high risk of developing disease and can be more sensitive to sensory stimulation. In regards to positive stimulation Commercial Road offers some clear assets to its older users, however they could be developed further. Development is needed to reduce levels of pollution, noise pollution, the limitation of services provided and the maintenance and aesthetics of the area.

An image showing contrast between the older people enjoying the covered and inviting market seating area and the unused and decaying buildings behind them.

Figure 18

An image showing the abandoned and unsafe atmosphere after dark which is likely to be intimidating to older adults.

Positive people to people interaction 5/10

The spine of Commercial Road is substantially populated especially by the market area and the fountain which could potentially provide opportunities for the older user to socialise, make new connections and partake in a sense of community. However, there is a clear sense of segregation among different age groups. In figure you can see that age groups remain separated into students, older people, younger people and middle aged with some. Physically there is a lack of flexibility to facilitate spontaneous social experiences this is due to because of the way the space is arranged - in places there seems to be an oversupply of trees and seating which reduces quality of light as well as the ability to hold marches or open air events like a protest or silent disco. After it gets dark, it is a rare sight to see an older user, as there is an atmosphere of unsafety. This can be seen in figure where it is mainly younger adults and teenagers present. The unsafety of the space is evidenced by the considerable risk of crime within the area. In November 2021 there were 522 crimes reported within the area compared to 296 crimes on Palmerston Road another commercial district in Portsmouth (Police.uk, 2021). As described earlier in this paper, if older users feel unsafe it can inhibit them from fully utilising an urban space. In addition, social experiences and an older person's enjoyment of a space is more likely when the environment offers the opportunity to stop, rest and feel at ease. This is most seen on the main spine where the main pedestrian flow is and the seating has back support and handrails. However a considerable amount of seating is not being fully utilised for comfort reasons and the risk of crime in certain areas as can be seen in figure. Work could be done to reduce risk of crime by adding more lighting and creating more visual and spatial connection to inconspicuous areas. This should be done by planners working with local police and authorities.

Access to urban amenities 4 /10

The connectivity between urban amenities is poor. Even for the healthy younger adults using the area, reaching different built spaces and amenities can be tedious and time consuming. This is then emphasised for older users who have a slower walking gait and are more likely to have accessibility issues. Additionally, a lot of areas are poorly maintained and there is a high prevalence of uneven flooring, resulting in an increased risk of slipping, tripping and injury. From an ergonomic perspective the walking experience is not enjoyable and can be uncomfortable, especially for older people who are more sensitive to the difficulties. When looking at the seating provided on Commercial Road, not all seating is comfortable or suitable for an older user. This can be seen on Arundel street where the seating is made of large rocks and is not ergonomic or not comfortable to sit on. Supportive seating can be seen in some areas such as outside of cafes and closest to bus stops. A positive element can be seen in places that offer covering above storefronts allowing older users to utilise the space in all weather conditions, however there could be more covered seating available. From the station and at the start of Commercial Road by the bus stops there has been intentionality to make smooth and well-maintained crossings. On Arundel Street the Charles Dickens memorial is nicely paved which reduces likelihood for older pedestrians to fall. Moreover, restriction of electric scooters on pavement makes the spine of commercial roads safer and more walkable without fear of fast vehicles creating risk of injury. Overall, there are some attempts to increase accessibility for older people but there is a lack of intentional care for elders.

Figure 19 An image of an older person using a mobility aid on the smoother side of the pavement next to uneven paving.

Figure 20 An image of older people enjoying the sunshine and greenery in Victoria Park, encouraging them to do physical activity such as walking.

Provision of healthy resources 4/10

There is a lack of dedicated space for physical activity for all ages, especially the older user. Currently there is only a gym that is mainly targeted to and utilised by younger users. In terms of green spaces that promote physical activity and mental well-being, Victoria Park is the only space in the area that offers older users a place to get physical exercise especially by providing a pleasant place to walk. However the park could be more accessible by being better connected to the rest of the area. Furthermore, increased rates of air pollution within the area pose a high risk to health outcomes for the older user. Dietary choices can be a powerful vehicle to prevent chronic disease and help manage disease, something that is even more important in the older generation who are known to have a higher risk of nutritional deficiencies. Nevertheless, Commercial Road has an abundance of unhealthy fast-food options. Healthy food options such as fresh and seasonal local vegetables and fresh meat can be gained from the Tesco's in the area and when the market takes place. All in all, there could be greater provision of healthy resources for the older user to utilise - further intentional care for the health of the older user is required.

A Caring Urban Outdoor Space

Suggested change:

- + Pockets of well distributed open air with greenery and facilities for social engagement and health
- + Improved pedestrian routes to cut walking time
- + Covering over entrances of shops extended with seating area
- + Facades restored and renewed to celebrate local culture and history
- + Facades restored and renewed to celebrate local culture and history
- + Health & support services input in accessible area

Figure 21 is a diagram representing changes to Commercial Road that would make it increase the level of care for its older users. From the analysis and the visit to commercial road it is clearly a place that older people frequent even despite the areas of neglect, particularly during daytime. The aim is to show how the area can be transformed into a place that allows older users to take their time, enjoy good company and be healthy. This transformation is represented by showing a particular area of potential. The top part of the diagram is a street view of the connecting walkway from Slindon Street to Arundel Street which is within a crime problem area on Commercial Road and is an example of a place with potential to add diversity, health, access and positive social interaction. There is a clear attempt to celebrate culture and education in the Charles Dickens' Memorial however it is not an inclusive effort because of the dreary atmosphere, lack of support in street furniture and the threat of crime. The street connectivity is also notably poor and makes the area feel enclosed and disconnected from the rest of the area. In order to eliminate the areas of neglect the actions of care within Figure 21 were included to create an atmosphere that can be enjoyed by those who are experiencing the effects of aging. Figure 21 also includes a map of a new street pattern that includes more choice for pedestrian routes that will decrease walking time to amenities. To further density of amenities more pockets of beautiful public zones where outdoor physical activity classes can take place as well as social events like protests and silent discos. Moreover the suggestion to add a hub in the former debenhams building that houses health services and support for older people so that they do not have to travel far from the other amenities of the area.

Figure 21

In summary, it has been made clear that within the discussion of urbanism and aging populations, as urban designers and planners we must be active to enable everyone to age optimally. The Alternative Age-friendly Handbook is made in collaboration by Population Ageing, Urbanisation and Urban Design Research Unit at the University of Manchester, the Age-friendly Manchester Design Group (Manchester City Council), the 'Tiny Experimental University', the RIBA's Research and Innovation Group and the Age UK Research team. The handbook suggests that urban practitioners should be more involved in creating spaces that care for older people (Handler, 2014). The four categories of care for older people in urban spaces are identified in this essay as crucial for older adults to live optimised lives without the barriers presented by younger-centred spaces. These younger-centred spaces do not allow older people to age in place as they want to (Smith, 2009). The key issues found in this paper are that these spaces seem to neglect allowing aging people to take more time and or choose their preference of stimulation. Therefore, there comes a point when they can no longer use these spaces.

During the research for this study there was limited evidence of urban outdoor spaces that are currently successfully targeting the care of older people. This highlights the need for urban planners to resolve this area as the percentage of older people continues to increase alongside the need for more urban spaces. The key barriers to achieving this are funding and planning in order to reshape cities into havens of well-being for those of all (Arup, 2015). This should prompt a shift in priorities for the makers of our cities. In conjunction with this subject a discussion is to be had about the shift in lifestyles of urban liver. The decline in working people available to support those who do not work within urban places will mean a greater need for services and possibly less people to deliver them (Government Office of Science, 2016). This prompts urban designers to resolve the question:

What if urban landscapes looked after older people in a way that enables everyone to maintain independence for as long as possible?

The definition of an older person is continuously evolving as people live longer and stay healthier and dependent for longer. This is an area of research that should continue in momentum so that we can appropriately cater for the needs of those who have entered older age. Throughout this study personal preference and the diversity of people within this age group has become a qualification for the acts of care. This suggests that different urban outdoor spaces will have different priorities and ways of achieving the four acts specific to their location and their users. In the example of diversity, Mount Sterling, Illinois (Kiku Obata & Company, 2011) the designers mention the importance of ongoing discussions with citizens, business owners, makers and the local government in order to identify the most valuable aspects for users. Therefore in order to care for people we also need to listen to what would make them feel cared for. There is a prompt to urban designers to work with healthcare professionals in order for well-being to be at the heart of urban environments as they should no longer be kept separate. There are schemes and initiatives that could be incorporated within architecture and planning such as the NHS' scheme for Personalised Care. Within this area of study it becomes clear that older people should be empowered to be active contributors to and decision makers of urban environments in order to provoke an ideology of respect and social inclusion. Urban planners should think about functional mobility, health and understand ageing as a state of increasing dependency and need.

Poignantly, when investigating the "acts of care" in the case of Commercial road, it makes significant the fact that although a space may have certain elements like ample seating and pedestrian walkways the quality of these spaces is significant as well as the presence of certain assets. When thinking about care it appears to be more than just an obligation but an act of affection towards the older members of society. This project had aimed to produce a caring version of Commercial road however whilst investigating this area of study creating a space that cares for elders becomes much more than ticking boxes on a list. Carroll (2020) writes that the design perspective of ageing has been driven by stereotyping ideology that lacks nuances, and the architectural viewpoint has focused on design as solutions. However there is no straightforward solution. Therefore the diagram presented above begins to suggest how the area can move towards care. Although Commercial Road is considered the heart of Portsmouth in order to fully analyse Portsmouth's public spaces, it could be analysed in comparison to other key urban outdoor spaces within the city. This could offer some other insights as to how this city is doing and create a deeper understanding of how older people within Portsmouth can be cared for.

COVID-19 restrictions emphasised the importance of our outdoor spaces as they can create safe and flexible gathering spaces for people of all ages. These spaces should create valuable and engaging connections: connection between users and parts of the city and into rural spaces. The research suggests that in order for our outdoor environments to care for older people we need to not only provide all the appropriate facilities but also provide them to a standard of quality that empowers everyone as they age. Therefore care becomes the act of lovingly crafting a space to give older people a high quality of life, where well-being is at the forefront. This will then ultimately benefit all city users as we age and share our spaces...

...“improving the quality of outdoor environments eventually benefits all” - Sugiyama and Thomsson (2005)

References

- Age UK. (2013). Challenges of an Ageing Population - Age UK report. <https://www.ageuk.org.uk/latest-press/archive/vision-and-imagination-critical-to-meet-challenges-of-ageing-population/>
- Archdaily. (2022). Songzhuang Micro Community Park / Crossboundaries <https://www.archdaily.com/967372/songzhuang-micro-community-park-crossboundaries>
- Arup. (2015). Shaping Ageing Cities 10 European case studies.
- Ball, M. S., Ball, S. M., & Ball, M. S. (2012). Livable communities for aging populations : Urban design for longevity. John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.
- Cambridge University Press. (2022). Care. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/care>
- Carroll, S. (2020). Co-designing Age-friendly Cities And Communities: Towards an Age-friendly Spatial Practice. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344441930_Co-designing_Age_friendly_Cities_and_Communities_Towards_an_Age-friendly_Spatial_Practice
- CDC. (2018). Well-being concepts. <https://www.cdc.gov/hrqol/wellbeing.htm>
- Collins. (2022). Care. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/care>
- Department of Health. (2001). National Service Framework for Older People. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/198033/National_Service_Framework_for_Older_People.pdf
- Friedman, A. (2018). Designing Sustainable Communities. Bloomsbury Visual Arts. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5040/9781474208444.ch-009>
- Google. (2016). 23 Arundel St. https://www.google.co.uk/maps/@50.7998549,-1.0885967,3a,75y,342.39h,90.1t/data=!3m6!1e1!3m4!1sxQpr-0S_YATSZ4ERVcYdNQ!2e0!7i13312!8i6656?hl=en-GB&authuser=0
- Gehl, J. (2011). Life between buildings: using public space. Island.
- Government Office of Science. (2016). Future of an Ageing Population. (https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/816458/future-of-an-ageing-population.pdf)
- Gov.uk. (2021). Proposed new timetable for State Pension age increases. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/proposed-new-timetable-for-state-pension-age-increases>
- Handler, S. (2014). An Alternative Age-Friendly Handbook. The University of Manchester Library, pp.13-98. <https://www.architecture.com/knowledge-and-resources/resources-landing-page/age-friendly-handbook>
- van Hoof, J., Dikken, J., Buttigieg, S. C., van den Hoven, R. F. M., Kroon, E., & Marston, H. R. (2020). Age-friendly cities in the Netherlands: An explorative study of facilitators and hindrances in the built environment and ageism in design. *Indoor and Built Environment*, 29(3), 417–437. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1420326X19857216>
- Kahana, E., Lovegreen, L., Kahana, B., & Kahana, M. (2003). Person, Environment, and Person-Environment Fit as Influences on Residential Satisfaction of Elders. *Environment and Behavior*, 35(3), 434–453. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916503035003007>
- Kauhalauma, S & Timonen, P (2016) Smooth flows, unhurried stays: everyday organizing in a downtown commercial centre, *Journal of Urban Design*, 21(6), 816-835, DOI: 10.1080/13574809.2016.1234333
- Kernisan, L. (2016). 7 Commonly Neglected Problems to Address for Healthier Aging. <https://betterhealthwhileaging.net/7-commonly-neglected-problems-to-address-healthy-aging>
- Kiku Obata & Company (2011) Mt. Sterling, Illinois, Uptown Long-Range Strategic. Plan https://mtsterlingil.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/Mt_-Sterling-Uptown-LRSP-Final1.pdf
- Lexico. (2021). Care. <https://www.lexico.com/definition/care>
- McKnight, J. (2016). Kiku Obata leads revival of historic district in a rural Illinois town <https://www.dezeen.com/2016/06/14/kiku-obata-company-mount-sterling-illinois-historic-district-regeneration/>
- Nomis. (2022). 2011 Census. https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/sources/census_2011_ksuk
- Office for National Statistics (2018). Living longer: how our population is changing and why it matters <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/ageing/articles/livinglongerhowourpopulationischangingandwhyitmatters/2018-08-13#what-are-the-implications-of-an-ageing-population>
- Phillipson, C. (2011). Developing Age-Friendly Communities: New Approaches to Growing Old in Urban Environments. 279-293 10.1007/978-1-4419-7374-0_18.
- Proctor and Matthews Architects. (2022). Steepleton, Tetbury: Later Living accommodation inspired by historic Cotswolds almshouses. <https://www.proctorandmatthews.com/project/steepleton-tetbury>
- Roser, M. (2017). The Demography of the World Population from 1950 to 2100 . <https://ourworldindata.org/age-structure>
- Smith, A. E., & Smith, A. E. (2009). Ageing in urban neighbourhoods : Place attachment and social exclusion. Policy Press.
- Standard Life. (2021). What is retirement? <https://www.standardlife.co.uk/retirement/guides/what-is-retirement>
- Statista. (2022). Median age of the population of the United Kingdom from 2001 to 2020 <https://www.statista.com/statistics/281288/median-age-of-the-population-of-the-uk/>
- Sugiyama, T., & Thompson, C. W. (2007). Outdoor Environments, Activity and the Well-Being of Older People: Conceptualising Environmental Support. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 39(8), 1943–1960. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a38226>
- World Health Organization (2007). Global Age-Friendly Cities Guide. https://www.who.int/ageing/publications/Global_age_friendly_cities_Guide_English.pdf
- Woolley, H. (2003). Urban open spaces. CRC Press LLC. <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/portsmouth-ebooks/reader.action?docID=178907>
- Weuve, J., Kang, J. H., Manson, J. E., Breteler, M. M. B., Ware, J. H., & Grodstein, F. (2004). Physical activity, including walking, and cognitive function in older women. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 292(12), 1454-1461.

Abstract

In cinema, architectural elements and the spaces they create in a set design have always been used as symbolic context for the narrative of the movie. Architecture has become more and more a protagonist to enhance not only the story of the film but also as a spatial message. Influenced by several indicators such as genre, portrayed socio-economic background, movie set, director, actors, equipment, location and many more, the displayed 'seen' architectural image captures the 'unseen' message of the film.

Previous contemporary South Korean films have been the base for upcoming directors. Old works have given inspiration to the ever worldwide popular Korean films and TV shows that are noticed alongside Western made products. Examples of film that pushed South Korea into the film industry are *Peppermint Candy (1999)*, *Oldboy (2003)* and *Train to Busan (2016)*. The films were not only different in the nationality of the cast, but the unique (and often dark) nature of their narrative and bending of genre. At present, South Korean director Bong Joon-Ho has established himself as one of Korea's well-known idols and is the creator of many contemporary Korean movies including some which have reached Hollywood status. This success has grown within the market and continues to shine as other Korean film and TV shows now thrive on global streaming platforms despite the difference in language.

This study aims to explore the approach of director Bong Joon-Ho from South-Korea in his two most popular movies *Snowpiercer (2013)* and *Parasite (2019)* using two categories of visual indicators: 'Step of the narrative' and 'significant aspects of set design'.

Both films are different but paradigmatic in the presentation of class structure through architecture, through the innovative use and manipulation of visual language and overall set design which will be analysed throughout this study.

TABLE OF IMAGES

8 				
Picture0.jpg	Picture1.png	Picture2.png	Picture3.jpg	Picture4.jpg
13 				
Picture5.png	Picture6.png	Picture7.png	Picture8.png	Picture9.png
15 				
Picture10.png	Picture11.png	Picture12.png	Picture13.png	Picture14.png
18 				
Picture15.png	Picture16.png	Picture17.png	Picture18.png	Picture19.png
19 				
Picture20.png	Picture21.png	Picture22.png	Picture23.png	Picture24.png
20 				
Picture25.jpg	Picture26.png	Picture27.jpg	Picture28.jpg	Picture29.png
21 				
Picture30.jpg	Picture31.jpg	Picture32.jpg	Picture33.jpg	Picture34.jpg
23 				
Picture35.jpg	Picture36.png	Picture37.png		

TABLE OF CONTENTS

4 | INTRODUCTION

5 | LITERATURE REVIEW

7 | METHODOLOGY

7 | STEPS OF NARRATIVE – PARASITE

8 | THE LOOP

9 | MOVEMENT AND DISTURBANCE

9 | BREAKOUT

10 | RESOLVE AND DEVOLVE

11 | STEPS OF NARRATIVE – SNOWPIERCER

11 | THE LOOP

11 | MOVEMENT AND DISTURBANCE

12 | BREAKOUT

12 | RESOLVE AND DEVOLVE

13 | INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY –
PARASITE

14 | LIGHT

15 | EXTERIOR AND INTERIOR

17 | URBAN ARCHITECTURE

18 | DIAGRAMS

19 | INDICATORS OF SET DESIGN TO DEMONSTRATE SOCIAL INEQUALITY –
SNOWPIERCER

19 | LIGHT

21 | EXTERIOR AND INTERIOR

23 | URBAN ARCHITECTURE

24 | DIAGRAMS

25 | CONCLUSION

26 | REFERENCES

“How does architectural space contribute to the representation and oppression of social class in contemporary South-Korean film?”

“A case study comparison between Bong Joon-Ho’s ‘Snowpiercer’ and ‘Parasite’.”

~

My research topic studies social class and inequality represented in film using architecture found in set design and cinematography. This study aims to highlight how both cinema and architecture can be used collectively to visualize and convey narrative successfully. Reviewing literature will consist of material from reports from studios, professionals, critics point of views, not on the quality of the film but moreover the effectiveness of visual/physical in establishing message and progression of the narrative. This review covers the following categories of films: 1) Films directed by Bong Joon-Ho 2) South Korean and American films on social class and 3) Global films portraying social class.

Social class has been used in many films as a basis for narrative. Previous notable movies that do explore inequality include: *‘The Pursuit of Happyness’* (2006) and *‘The Wolf of Wall Street’* (2013). Both are American born ‘Hollywood’ films that present real life narratives of capitalism and economic inequality with the director of ‘The Wolf of Wall Street’, Martin Scorsese being a key influence on our chosen director Bong Joon-Ho, going as far as to quote the elder director when receiving the best director award in 2020. [1]

In East-Asian movies, specifically South Korean films, social class is also narrated and hints at current problems in governments and ever-growing inequality between the rich and poor but in a different cultural setting. Films that show these include: *‘Peppermint Candy’* (1999) and *‘Chilsu and Mansu’* (1988). These South Korean films relate to each other and our current day case study ‘Parasite’ in portraying families that try to escape/climb the socioeconomic ladder and ultimately fight against the government and their developing economy.

Both American and South Korean films have the same theme of social class but have their own respective cultural differences seen in the directing, acting and set design.

Korean Cinema (along with most east Asian productions) is not being distributed widely across the globe, with most theatres showing high end films mostly from Western productions. Scholar Christina Klein refers to Korean cinema and the transnational genres in films of Bong Joon-Ho. Referencing Andrew Higson, and his article published in 1989, with his

reconceptualization of national cinemas. Instead of prioritizing production quality (of the film and representation of national cultures) he pushed the focus on increasing the diversity of consumption. Higson examines the relationship between imported and locally made films and the influencing factors between them and quotes that the South Korean film industry is, after Hollywood, perhaps the most important in the world today. Both industries produce films, however one does have a larger influence on the other. Some Korean film critics have condemned the copying of popular methods and western culture, referring to it as “Copywood”, while characterising its pieces as “Hollywood movies featuring Korean faces and Korean food for the purpose of localization”. Higson states, Bong does not mimic Hollywood; but appropriately reworks genre conventions to explore Korean social and political issues. [1b]

This report is not only a film study but also an architectural review on spatial arrangement and urban planning within the film to visualize the narrative and empower the message of division between rich and poor.

The context that began this study was primarily architectural cinematography. Regarded as a new platform in representation for structures, moving images allowed architects to create a sense of place within a fictional world and become part of a film’s narrative. [2]

Other scholars have written about these case studies and documented their observations in similar reports, however in this essay there is more emphasis on the relationship between the seen physical set design and the unseen political statement intended to cause thought of real-world problems within society. The building of a film has its own intricacies like architecture, where the producers want to transport viewers into the scene to experience the same emotions as the characters. Mark Lamster wrote, “architecture is the most intimate of the arts - we sleep in it, eat in it, work and play in it - there seems to be little audience interest in films about it”. This statement seems to point toward architecture being the medium to shape ideologies into moving images instead of architecture being the main narrative. [2b]

Literature from individuals, reviewers, scholarly material and reporters also highlight the successes, techniques and the deeper message left by the South Korean director.

Both films have gained popularity worldwide and have been successful within the box office. *Snowpiercer* (2013) has earned \$82,195,262 internationally and \$4,563,650 domestically. 6 years later, *Parasite* (2019) earned \$209,650,381 internationally and \$53,369,749 domestically. [3]

Leading up to its remarkable success in the states at the Oscars awards, Bong Joon Ho described and rejected the academy's long historical treatment of films outside its voters familiar understanding. He told Vulture's Alex Jung, "the Oscars are not an international film festival," and added, "They're not very local." This was aimed at the treatment of international films not mainly produced by the U.S, with Bong Joon Ho shining light on the underappreciated East Asian film industry and even Europe. Despite this, *Parasite* (2019) earned four awards and became the first non-English-language movie to win the Academy's top awards. He also encouraged American audiences to "overcome the 1-inch-tall barrier of subtitles." The veteran director's work explores the deep social forces that shape the world, with the movie *Parasite* being no different. This work has found its place in the film industry by being a message to society and using rare methods of genre-bending. This allowed *Parasite* to become a precedent for movies to follow; and be an inspiration for directors around the world regardless of language or culture. [4]

Parasite was inspired by 1960s horror film, *The Housemaid* with Martin Scorsese labelling it a "rich and rewarding" film. Once watched, the thematic parallels are seen between the two. This veteran director is considered the middle ground between Hollywood and South Korean film production using Hollywood as a frame/tool to answer or present real world problems in society. As the film industry is globalized mainly by Hollywood and its major success, Bong keeps the authenticity of the local film industry and neutralizes globalization.

~

The main body of this paper studies 2 categories of indicators:

First category: Steps of the narrative:

1. *Introduction*
2. *The Loop*
3. *Movement and Disturbance*
4. *Breakout*
5. *End (Resolve/Devolve)*

Second category: Indicators of set design to demonstrate social inequality

1. *Light*
2. *Exterior (architecture)/ Interior space*
3. *Urban context*

The study of film can be broken down to the seen image and the unseen message. The seen image is the physical set and the actors that interact and/or are influenced by the spatial design. The unseen message is the reasoning behind the narrative and is influenced by the director and what the overall message is within the screen. There is a fine line between what can be seen and what cannot be seen as there are images that can be missed by the audience on first viewing or those lacking knowledge on screenwriting.

The methodology I adopt in this study is an in-depth analysis of two films by the same Asian director.

Methodology

- 1) Choosing two films that present the message of social class and inequality but with different context.
 - 2) Viewing of both films
 - 3) Timestamping key moments of each film that relate to each category of indicators.
 - 4) A Literature review (that is targeted though film critiques, interviews and awards/prizes won by the director and others) on movie reviews, news articles, film study material, architectural representation on set design. Collating and assessing each piece with each other, backed up with personal audience viewership.
 - 5) Writing results that demonstrate how the physical set and composition of the screen work together to present the social hierarchy/message of the director using techniques from previous/current directors.
- Material from other Films/Novels may be used and referenced when discussing a specific technique in a screenplay.
- (For reference materials from other movies, single scenes may be selected)

~

Steps of the Narrative ~ Parasite

Narrative is how the story is told, rather than what the story is. Todorov's theory of narrative built upon the 3 main acts to a story: beginning, middle and end.

He theorized that at the beginning there is a state of 'equilibrium' where all characters are where they belong, regardless of the equilibrium being seen as happy or not. Moving from the beginning, there must be a 'disruption' to the harmony to cause movement and force the story to progress. This may be caused by the action of characters or natural disasters. Next the

stage of 'recognition' where both the viewers and the characters would realise a prominent problem/change in the equilibrium. After, there is an act of 'repair' where the characters would try to restore the state of equilibrium and upon doing so (or not), they would reach the end and create a new equilibrium.

This theory can be applied to Bong Joon-Ho's feature films, with his interesting choice of endings for both *Parasite* and *Snowpiercer* and many more unique aspects of narrative. [5]

Introduction

In *Parasite* the equilibrium is replicating real world South Korea and mimicking its social injustice in the architecture of its society. The balance is the economic separation between the rich and poor and the decay of economic mobility.

The Loop

We, the viewers are firstly placed in the view of the lower class which are the protagonists of both movies. *Parasite* is set in modern-day South Korea with its culture embused into each scene. The Kim family is first introduced to the audience in their semi basement apartment. As the viewer, we do not have information of how long they have resided there, nor how long the Kims have been at the 'bottom' of the social hierarchy. The other main family the Parks also are in this loop, however, are at the opposite side of the spectrum, living a wealthy and comfortable life. Relating to Todorov's theory of narrative, this is the state of equilibrium.

Their regular lives have been outlined but not put into a scale until a 'disturbance' in the loop.

[00:07:54]

Movement and Disturbance

A noticeable moving point in the narrative is when protagonist Ki-Woo is hired as an English tutor for the wealthier Park family. This disrupts the peace as side character Min is replaced by the poorer Ki-Woo. Min is also placed in a loop within society, effectively being the original 'parasite' trying to rise in society by working for the upper class and the story evolves when Ki-Woo is chosen to replace Min in serving the higher Park family. From there, the Kims slowly start infiltrating the Park family by posing as servants to work for the Park family while still living in poor conditions. As the Kims work for the Parks, they must cope with their slander toward less fortunate people.

This act of 'disruption' continues throughout the film until halfway,

[01:06:41]

a darker truth unfolds. Although the narrative has gradually tipped out of balance, this moment pushes the balance out of control due to the discovery of the 'underground family'. Conflict arises between the lower class Kims and the underground family, however, must hide this conflict from the Park family.

Breakout

There are multiple acts of 'breakout' through the film.

The breakout/rising the hierarchy of the Kim family is present when they traverse vertically through the city to work for the Parks, The Storm that rains down on the city leaving the water to pour down ending at the semi basement apartment of the Kims symbolising they are the bottom of society, where all the dirt and water end up flowing toward.

[01:53:10]

The narrative reaches a climax of conflict where the underground family escape the bunker and attack the Kim and Park family. Todorov's theory of narrative would title this sequence as the repair and although this is far from a cliché happy ending, there is repair in this act as both the 'parasites' have been relieved from tensions between each other and are finally separated from each other.

Resolve and Devolve

The story concludes with all families in a new state of equilibrium and separate from each other. Immediately after the incident, the father of the Kim household Ki-Taek flees down to the original underground basement of the house, the underground family end up dead and the Park family entirely moving out of town. We follow Ki-Woo and his mother mourning the loss of sister/daughter Ki-Jung however Ki-woo, still inflicted with severe brain damage, laughs at her grave. Director Bong Joon-Ho gave this film a very open-ended conclusion as we see in the closing scenes Ki-Woo grow and climb the social ladder to eventually buy the property once owned by the Parks and in doing so, be able to set his father Ki-Taek free. Reviewers theorize that the ending shows economic mobility is impossible within a lifetime for a low-class person, implying that the audience is watching the imagination of Ki-Woo due to brain damage.

Steps of the Narrative ~ Snowpiercer

Introduction

The narrative of Sci-Fi *Snowpiercer* is like *Parasite* in the architecture of society. There are people above/in front, and people below/behind. This can be applied to wealth, health and happiness. The story does not focus on economic wealth, but quality of life regardless of money.

The Loop

In this fictional world, we are given a timeframe in which to set this movie in which is 17 years after the release of a cooling agent 'CW7' upon earth to originally reduce temperatures but instead freezes the planet leaving the entire surviving population on a train that circles its tracks year by year. The narrative's loop is shown in the structure of the train where wellbeing and status rise further toward the front of the train. Each carriage holds the groups of lower, middle and upper class where each works for one another to survive but are treated differently in their quality of life. We follow Curtis as he plots to escape the 'Tail' of the train, move forward and take control of the engine room at the front.

Movement and Disturbance

The obvious turning point of the film comes around the scene where Curtis disrupts the equilibrium and breaks out of the control of the guards.

[00:27:39]

This marks the start of their journey forward toward a better life free from injustice and unfair structure of the train. While moving forward they learn more about the train and each passing carriage, they witness basic phases of humanity that they were stripped of being at the 'tail' of the train. While moving forward they encounter individuals that fight back to preserve the social structure of the train. Curtis and other members from the tail strive to reach the engine room risking their lives to help Curtis reach his goal.

Breakout

Finally, upon reaching the door to the engine room Curtis is left with Minsoo. He then unveils his past to Minsoo and his aspirations to take control of the entire train. With this, Minsoo explains his plans for beyond and the future of humanity saying that there is life outside of the train or outside the loop. Curtis is then invited into the engine room by the train conductor, Wilford. Wilford explains how he knew about this outbreak to Curtis describing Curtis as the perfect leader to take his place. Wilford also explains how this incident restored the impending overpopulation of the train, thus restoring the loop once more. This description of events leads to the narrative of the story reverting to its original state of those who worked up to the front and those content with their position in the train.

While waiting at the door to the engine room, he is caught up by the assassin assigned to hunt the protagonists down. Minsoo is then forced to use collected explosive fuel to destroy the engine room and break out of the entire loop enclosed within the train.

Resolve and Devolve

After the explosion, the viewers are left with Minsoo's daughter Yona and Timmy, a young boy taken to work in the engine. They are the only people that survived the explosion of the train. They leave the trainwreck and peer across the snow-covered earth to eye a polar bear in the distance. This ending scene represents the real breakout of the narrative, where their once linear earth, or the train, has been transformed to the horizontal and level planet.

[01:59:13]

Steps of the Narrative ~ Other Film

The films of Bong Joon-Ho follow the theory of narrative with the end becoming a new beginning but in a blurred and unclear way. His unique style and blurring of these transitions between stages, coupled with his genre bending and diverse cast creates his own narrative formula. 'The Pursuit of Happiness' follows its narrative on a long and downward path, where protagonist Chris Gardener slowly descends through the social ladder as he attempts to land

a job at a company through an unpaid internship program. While doing so he loses money, residency and even his wife. The narrative is then resolved when finally, he gets accepted to work for the company as a broker. The film's narrative is beautifully summarised in the quote, *"maybe happiness is something that we can only pursue and maybe we can never actually have it. No matter what."*

This rejection toward the theory of breakout from the loop/being able to escape socio-economic inequality is a reference to the narrative stage of 'The Loop'. In 'Chilsu and Mansu' (1988) the theme is the impossibility of communication between upper and lower classes. Both main characters Chilsu and Mansu, of lower working class, conduct their disturbance and of the loop with their attempt to communicate to the upper class by standing atop of a billboard, however, are unable to be heard and eventually forced back down, both physically from the rooftop billboard and back into society. The conclusion to the film is abrupt but assumes both characters are thrust back into their category within the Korean community. [6]

Most recently, *Squid game (2021)* is a critique of capitalism and focuses on a narrative of characters that lower themselves into debt and further down the socioeconomic ladder in order to survive and hope to escape their debt. Squid Game addresses this escape through a dystopian tale that is not far from reality and its tension between traumatic experience of work and the impossible escape from wage labour. During the opening episode, our protagonist signs away his organs to pay his loan sharks. This spotlights how South Koreans have high levels of personal debt due to unemployment, easy loans and high interest rates. [7]

~

Indicators of set design to demonstrate social inequality ~ Parasite

[00:13:12]

Light

The first time the sun is seen on film is the ascent of the protagonist up a staircase toward the upper-class family.

The low angle along with glare of the sun above this distinct house sets the tone for the Park family giving indication to who they are and their place in society.

Although the natural sun is present in the opening scene, it is merely part of the background, choked by the underground light that seeps through the only window in the Kim's semi basement apartment replicating a sewer, where light and water flow to and end up, the bottom of the entire street and the bottom of all society.

[00:00:00]

Sunlight is manipulated craftily to depict scenes of joy, distress and calm. Ultimately, it is the filling aspect to each frame determining its mood and directing the viewer to the scene.

The critical tipping point of the film that changes its light-hearted genre arrives at:

[01:06:36]

This act introduces the hidden bunker section of the Park house. As the viewers descend down the narrow suffocating entrance, the once warm light shifts to an ominous olive shade and is no longer the warm light radiated along the surfaces of the Park house's interior.

There are 3 houses, all with their share of light:

- 1) Park house with full light, open plan, wide full height windows
- 2) Kim house, semi basement, with light seeping through ground level down into their house
- 3) The “Bunker”, no natural light, artificial green tint, full basement

[00:43:10]

[01:58:14]

[02:00:32]

These relate to each family and their place in society, with the wealthy having more access to natural and clean light, and those at the bottom being void of the sun forced to use artificial light powered by the family above.

Exterior and Interior space

Cinematography is used in conjunction with the physical landscape constructed by the director to portray narrative and the overall mood of the scene.

The qualities of both interior and exterior spaces construct the area in which characters can move and interact. They are important as it creates atmosphere and enhances the mood at a given point. For example, the introduction of the hidden bunker transforms the genre of the movie from a light-hearted drama into a dark mystery thriller. The descent through the suffocating maze-like hallway increases the tension that was cleared at the ring of the doorbell prior. The sequence of three scenes is coupled with three different coloured backgrounds that appropriately fit the narrative.

Firstly, our main characters are based on ground floor with a warm and dim light contrasted with the heavy cold rain that later becomes a flash flood. Secondly, the ring of the doorbell, in which Chung-Sook opens the door for Moon-gwang leading them both down to the dark concrete basement. Thirdly, the opening of the bunker door and the descent is stained a monotonous artificial green. Elevation is used continuously throughout the film to illustrate on screen the class separation between the families. The reveal of the “Bunker” and the man that lives under, uses descent in the interior design. The long corridors and fast descent make the “Bunker” seem buried under society and literally below the Parks.

[00:46:09]

[01:58:14]

For example, the Kims go up a staircase to their bedrooms
 The Parks go up a staircase to the toilets

Overall shots of the exterior of both family houses capture the narrative, but more importantly the socio-economic difference between the two. We can see this in the first scene of the Park house. The camera places the viewer low and looking upward to the park house behind our protagonist.

[00:56:37]

This low perspective signifies that we are below the park family house with their higher position above the camera, covering natural sunlight and built with minimalistic materials. Contrastingly, the camera is placed also on ground level, but far from the lower-class Kim family apartment. This far shot uses distance to suggest that the Kim family is far from the social status of the audience. These two shots of exteriors are different. One being low but closer, and another being parallel but far from the viewer. This shot manipulation represents all separate classes: 1) Upper class 2) Lower class and 3) Middle class or the viewer.

Colour selection is also used to differentiate class in other films. Jordan Peele's *US* (2019) also bases its narrative off 2 different families. Instead of differences in wealth, the inequality

between quality of life is highlighted. Interiors of both houses have different materials and colours that are enhanced with use of natural light and lack thereof. It is a film that showcases a fictional world of people living on the surface and people living below, both having two dramatically different lifestyles. To conclude, directors design the set to fit narrative and how characters interact with and around the space. Viewers also experience the interior and exterior through the lens of the camera controlled by the director.

Urban Architecture

The urban scale of each location represents each character's placement in the socio-economic hierarchy in the film. The landscape that connects these is important as it shapes the message behind the film. The large-scale structure of Parasite is a vertical pyramid. Although there are only 2 main families that are followed through the film, outside of these is the entire population. This pyramid structure can be applied to real world class structures. Capitalism has led to this divide, as seen in movies about working class families. The pyramid of class presents a small number of successful people at the top, and the working class have many left at the bottom. Specifically in Parasite, the landscape that comes between the upper- and lower-class families resembles an upward slope and not entirely vertical. The Kims neighbourhood street always vertically slopes upward, giving the impression that there's always something above them, while the Parks house has roads that lead upward making their house seem higher vertically and socially. The upper-class family's house was constructed to specifically work with the sun path to make scenes feel like the Park house was at the apex of the neighbourhood. Distance and height separate these two and the injustice is summarised in the flooding scene and events leading toward it.

Parasite: Diagrams

Character Narrative Development

Urban Planning Section

[01:32:36] - Onward

In the scene where the Kims flee to their house in the rain, there is a clear distance, struggle and descent from the Parks to the Kims. Both the rain and social hierarchy descend to the Kims house, while the rain fills up their semi basement home. The structure affects not only the characters, but also the viewers, as we root for the Kims because they are the underdogs. Both families judge each other and only look out for themselves. The audience favours the Parks to climb up from their place in society. There is no way to physically remove the separation between the Kim house and Park house.

A truly vertical hierarchy of class is seen in the film 'Platform' 2019 where each inhabitant is placed on a vertical prison that has a platform of food that descends giving each floor one minute to eat. This eventually leads to the lower floors having no food, thus representing capitalism through architecture.

Indicators of set design to demonstrate social inequality ~ Snowpiercer

Light

In Snowpiercer, Bong Joon-Ho sets this sci-fi story on a train carrying multiple passengers that circle the uninhabitable freezing earth. The set design, visioned by production designer

Ondrej Nekvasil, presents light and colour to represent class inequality. The lower class is placed at the tail of the train, while the upper class is found at the head. The poorest passengers at the TAIL of the train don't receive any light, living in darkness, while moving along the linear path. The opening shots show their living spaces and highlighting the quality of life found at the TAIL of the train. Artificial light buzzes constantly across the dark and dirty carriages.

[00:35:02]

[00:36:00]

These scenes first show the outside world to the characters and audience.

From this point, the journey toward the HEAD shows more and more light and diversity with each carriage, which the TAIL was deprived of. Carriages such as the children's classroom and aquarium seem like normal spaces but are a splendour to our protagonists. The travel forward continues to bring light until [].

[01:24:24]

[01:25:26]

Here the Rave rooms, sauna and drug carts are found. Unlike the gradual increase of light traveling through the train, these species do not have any windows despite their far forward position on the train, like the TAIL, these rooms are devoid of windows and the view of the outside world.

[01:11:30]

Characters Nam-Goog and Yona potentially belong to both sides of the train, however instead of contrasting to either the upper or lower class, their contrast is the outside world. Both characters follow Curtis to derail the train, however instead of trying to oppose the socio-economic hierarchy, they instead plot to escape the train. Nam-Goog tries his best to expose Yona to the earth outside of the carriage walls. Despite being in the learning space of the middle-class children, whilst they are being indoctrinated, Nam-Goog is teaching his child about the real world, breaking the ideology and out of the social class structure.

Colour scheme of both the TAIL section and HEAD section are muted. TAIL is a muddy and dirty green/blue, while HEAD is an off white, impure symbolising a false hope, false life and false redemption of Curtis' revolution and pursuit.

Exterior and Interior space

[00:41:38]

[00:42:25]

Snowpiercer solely uses interior design to highlight the divide between classes. The architectural spaces are Linear in Plan with the narrative set on a train giving one direction for the protagonists. Each carriage moves up in social class.

Colours begin to become more saturated throughout the rising in social rank.

[01:16:16]

Interior space, although squeezed into a carriage, seems enough. This is recognised as compact architecture that homes people and infrastructure.

[01:48:19]

[01:52:42]

The HEAD of the train is considered sacred, with no windows or natural light, the leading lines of the facades and claustrophobic structure, leads in one direction, toward the engine, and further beyond the engine, the train track that loops back on itself.

The middle of the train is the diverse, close but not quite the contemporary capitalist society, with their high-class visuals however is not as educated as the front.

The middle class is the most important and dangerous. Although high in number, they are the ones who are indoctrinated into a system that exploits them, where ideology influences their action. The middle class are manipulated by the HEAD to believe the TAIL is bad and the lowest of the low, pointed out especially by the teacher unto the kids, thus becoming the faceless oppressors. Reflecting the real world, working class to middle class.

[01:07:40]

Urban Architecture

The story follows the narrative of the remaining population living on a train looping eternally. To the characters, the entire train represents the new earth. Side character Timmy quotes, “in the whole wide train”. The designed space reflects upon society and how it is a chain of people ranked above or below one another. Bong Joon-Ho does not refer to any money system nor how the train originally ranked each passenger's wealth which reflects upon the social injustices placed upon people born into less privileged families. This planning of space amplifies the theme of social inequality. This large-scale architecture of the HEAD and TAIL sections is also seen in the script and the content of characters where the higher-class feed ideologies to the lower class to manipulate and try to establish order. The message of main character Curtis’ pursuit to overthrow the train was the plan of both Wilford and Gilliam; and in seeking the rightful for the sufferers of the train, Curtis ultimately pleases the system by bringing down the population and becoming the HEAD himself.

[01:45:48]

Like real world revolutions, this revolution is between the TAIL and HEAD or citizens and the government. Snowpiercer’s ending shows the breaking out of this linear ranking system, where a pursuit of a radical change in the already unfair class structure leads to the end of the train. All passengers have been indoctrinated to believe that the train is the new earth apart from Nam-Goog and his daughter Yona who see outside of the train and its unfair system and seek life in the horizontal earth. This change evolves *Snowpiercer*’ social structure from its 2-dimensional linear path into a 3-dimensional complex urban structure like *Parasite*.

Snowpiercer: Diagrams

Character Narrative Development

Section Circulation

~

Conclusion

Slavoj Zizek: “it’s much easier to imagine the end of all life on earth,
than a much more radical change in capitalism” [8]

In this study, I examined how architectural space could represent the oppression of social class through film. I conducted this study using cinema as it is a popular medium to reach out to a public audience, and with director Bong Joon-Ho’ success in transporting South Korean film across the world, this age-old message of a capitalist society is renewed in a new age filled with much more content. I uncovered the visual representation of these spaces, and their qualities presenting the living conditions and contrast between both higher and lower classes through light, interior/exterior and urban design. In addition, the larger urban scale locates these people distances away from each other. Director Bong portrays the hypothetical movement of the lower class upward or forward and the consequences that lead to disruption in the structure thus corrupting the settled hierarchy eventually leading the structure to crumble or strengthen. Both ‘Steps in narrative’ and ‘Indicators of set design’ visually paint the message of growing inequality and how society can possibly grow apart, creating hatred and divide of space.

The future of both film and architecture have been influenced by the work of Bong Joon-Ho. Predictions include firstly the rise of directors from other cultures and infusing their work with their own ideologies of inequality and secondly, Architecture with its influence on the structure of societies.

Future scholars of this topic should consider urban planning or architecture in placing people relating to their socioeconomic status and find solutions to build a fair society and room for economic mobility. As for Film scholars, further study into propaganda found in film can be exposed, along with more study into architecture within film being a key component in creating narrative.

REFERENCES

- Auerbach, M. P. (2019). Motion picture and television industry. Salem Press Encyclopedia.
- Rotten Tomatoes: Movies | TV Shows | Movie Trailers | Reviews - Rotten Tomatoes.* (n.d.). Www.rottentomatoes.com. Retrieved January 25, 2022, from https://www.rottentomatoes.com/celebrity/bong_oon_ho
- Infographic: The Rise of the South Korean Film Industry.* (n.d.). Statista Infographics. <https://www.statista.com/chart/20781/south-korean-film-industry-rapid-growth/>
- Michelini, M. (2019, March 28). *The Differences Between East And West In Terms Of Culture And Education.* Global from Asia; Global From Asia. <https://www.globalfromasia.com/east-west-differences/>
- Who is Bong Joon-ho? Everything You Need to Know.* (n.d.). Www.thefamouspeople.com. <https://www.thefamouspeople.com/profiles/bong-joon-ho-44962.php>
- Browntable. (2020). Why It Works: Bong Joon-ho's SNOWPIERCER | Analysis [YouTube Video]. In *YouTube*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FYGONRRF9FI>
- [3] *Box Office Showdowns.* (n.d.). Box Office Mojo. Retrieved January 25, 2022, from https://www.boxofficemojo.com/showdown/?ref_=bo_nb_tt_tab
- [2] Tweedie, J. (2021). Cinematography, Architecture, and Design in the Digital Age. *Post45: Peer Reviewed.* <https://post45.org/2021/03/cinematography-architecture-and-design-in-the-digital-age/>
- [1] Bong Joon Ho wins Best Director. (2020). [YouTube Video]. In *YouTube*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ekMI5VHBH4I>
- [4] Giorgis, H. (2020, February 10). "Parasite" Won So Much More Than the Best Picture Oscar. *The Atlantic.* <https://www.theatlantic.com/culture/archive/2020/02/parasite-oscar/606310/>
- Ridgeway-Diaz, J., Truong, T. T., & Gabbard, G. O. (2020). Return of the Repressed: Bong Joon-Ho's Parasite. *Academic Psychiatry.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40596-020-01309-7>
- [1b] Klein, C. (2008). Why American Studies Needs to Think about Korean Cinema, or, Transnational Genres in the Films of Bong Joon-ho. *American Quarterly*, 60(4), 871–898. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40068554>
- [2b] Lamster, M. (Ed.). (2013). *Architecture and film.* Princeton Architectural Press.
- [5] Todorov's Narrative Theory Explained! Media StudiesTheory. (2019). [YouTube Video]. In *YouTube*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f7AfnJd55PI>
- Parasite, Ending Explained - Stairway to Nowhere.* (n.d.). Www.youtube.com. Retrieved November 30, 2021, from <https://youtu.be/ci-gFovSJf0>
- Economic inequality in South Korea.* (2021, September 25). Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Economic_inequality_in_South_Korea
- These 3 Charts Show How Gen Z & Millennials' Media Viewing Is Not The Same.* (n.d.). YPulse. Retrieved January 25, 2022, from <https://www.ypulse.com/article/2020/09/02/these-3-charts-show-how-gen-z-millennials-media-viewing-is-not-the-same>
- [7] Sharzer, G., & Kang, S. (n.d.). "Squid Game" highlights plight of South Korean workers sacrificed for nation's economic gain. *The Conversation.* Retrieved January 25, 2022, from <https://theconversation.com/squid-game-highlights-plight-of-south-korean-workers-sacrificed-for-nations-economic-gain-170441>
- Why are the eyes of the people in the Parasite movie thumbnail blacked out?* (n.d.). Quora. Retrieved January 25, 2022, from <https://www.quora.com/Why-are-the-eyes-of-the-people-in-the-Parasite-movie-thumbnail-blacked-out>
- MonkeyParadise. (2017, October 7). *Capitalism as a Religion: Zizek says "that it's much easier to imagine the end of all life on earth than a much more modest radical change in capitalism."* https://www.reddit.com/r/history/comments/74u2ha/capitalism_as_a_religion_zizek_says_that_its_much/
- Zambelli, A. (2021, November 22). *Film and Architecture [In-Person Film and Architecture].*
Discussing theories and reference films
- Kallitsis, P. (2021, October 14). *Film and Representation [In-Person Film and Representation].*
Methodology and other material suggested

Appendix M: interview with architecture educator transcript

Jennifer Sizer 0:03

Yes, got recording and transcription on the go. Now don't panic too much. If there's anything that you kind of don't want me to include and all that kind of stuff, I can always edit it and edit out and I can leave it from the transcription and that sort of thing. So feel free to speak as freely as you like. This will just be for me and for me to transcribe the transcription thing is kind of going on in the corner.

I always stop that because it kind of distracts me with all the stuff.

Participant 0:35

Yeah, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 0:36

But yeah, so I sent you those dissertations. Did you manage to have a quick look at them?

Participant 0:43

I had a look at 2:00.

Jennifer Sizer 0:44

Yeah, that's good. OK. So what did you think they sort the sort of things that you're familiar with? Which ones did you look at?

Participant 0:53

Yeah. Oh, I can't remember now. I haven't got my my thingy open. So, yeah, I mean, I I was talking to [ANOTHER ARCHITECTURE EDUCATOR] last week.

Jennifer Sizer 0:57

That's all right, I can get them open for you.

Participant 1:03

From from right supports my school of Architecture, Art and Design now, but I'm she's programme lead. I was saying I've been reviewing dissertations and what the Master of Architecture call a written thesis, which is essentially a large dissertation since 2009.

Jennifer Sizer 1:09

Yeah.

Participant 1:22

So I think there's there's common themes throughout all of.

Dissertations that I've I've read over the years, it's quite a long time now, isn't it?

There's particular weaknesses and there's.

And that comes from the way history and theory is taught within schools of architecture traditionally, but also the background of the students as well.

Jennifer Sizer 1:47

Yeah.

Participant 1:48

Many of the students don't necessarily come from humanities backgrounds.

Jennifer Sizer 1:52

Mm hmm.

Participant 1:53

So they're not grounded in the ways of constructing essays the traditional way of constructing essays.

Jennifer Sizer 1:57

Yeah.

Participant 2:01

So there are. Yeah, there are. What, what I read was similar to what I've seen in the past.

Jennifer Sizer 2:11

Fabulous

Participant 2:11

There's a long way to answer your question, but.

Jennifer Sizer 2:14

Yeah, that's a very good way to answer the question because that's given me lots of ideas already. So if we kind of go back then a step because we can have a look at them together, I've got them ready so we can have a look at them together and I'll share them on the screen and stuff. So that's fine. And so in terms of kind of expectations and conventions just for kind of architecture, final pieces so dissertations. So what are your kind of expectations?

Participant 2:21

OK.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 2:40

And conventions that you kind of see, so maybe undergraduates, but postgraduate maybe from your own experience?

Participant 2:44

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 2:46

As well as supervising.

Participant 2:49

OK.

Just in my head, I'm gonna try and work out a way of putting this across which isn't chaotic.

Jennifer Sizer 2:56

No, it's fine.

Participant 3:01

OK, let me let me tell you a bit of an origin story.

Jennifer Sizer 3:05

Yeah.

Participant 3:06

So.

I I I did have three sisters, one of which my late sister, was a bit of a High Flyer. So she turned down Oxford and Cambridge to go to York, but she was a real history buff from really, really early age, and there was quite an age gap between us, so I was always

looking up at what she was doing.
And she was amazing! She set all the highest scores. for writing at secondary school for history, which I came in, beat some of them, which was quite good.

Jennifer Sizer 3:41
Wow.

Participant 3:47
But.

What, that influenced the type of subjects that I took at at a level, so I took economics, politics. History.
And design. So three essay-based exam essay questions with a significant amount of writing in lessons each week for two years,
so I had I had just had the same history teacher as my sister, actually, and she just schooled you in. How do you do this? How do you write an essay that will get you a top mark at at a-level and allow you to progress to university? So I've been immersed in this type of writing for years and years and years and years and years.
So I came into university knowing how to write an essay. I just knew. So all of my marks at undergraduate were 90% + for anything written and considering an architecture course is 50% written, then I was even, if I had a bit of a dodgy moment with my my design, I knew that I'd be pulled up because of the written stuff and that was because. Of.
The structure that we were taught at at a-level which was, you argue, whatever. The question is that you're given an exam or the questions you set yourself for your essay. You answer FOR you answer AGAINST and then you come up with a a summary with your personal view.

Jennifer Sizer 5:22
Uh huh.

Participant 5:22

Obviously, sometimes that's a little bit like you don't do that as you get higher up through the sort of the writing standards, OK.
So I notice on dissertations it doesn't matter which level, you know, undergraduate, postgraduate, PhD, whatever. You can see that students who have done the humanity side. have a tendency to go. I, you know, such and such says this such and such says something different.. But I believe that based on the evidence, there's this, and you can see that and it rolls through. And when I was doing my EdD, that's the sort of like, that's the bit I that's that's how I approach the first couple of years of doing those assessments which is fine so.
Not all students have gone through that. I would now say the **minority** of students, because there's a when I was at school, there wasn't really coursework.
Apart from for design subjects art based subjects, there was a portfolio, but everything was an essay exam, essay essay essay, but none of it was really submitted in advance. So you get some students who are flying absolutely brilliant. So maybe they're, you know, they're your, they your, they're your [REDACTED] grammars, they're your Winchester colleges. They're King King Edward the 6th. You know, they're all those type of Barton Peverell, you know, they come through and they, they do really well, but that I would still say that those dear and the humanities are the essay type subjects are in, in, in the minimum.
So what do you do? You are faced in undergrad at level 4-5 and 6 so first year, second year and 3rd year with some students who cannot write.
And that might be because they just haven't had to write in the past, or because they've got learning needs. I've got significant dyslexia and slight autism and all sorts of stuff. But, you know, it's not really affected my writing, but it does for some people. My wife she's a solicitor. She has significant dyslexia. So I've seen how that sort of...how she moves through essay writing and how uncomfortable it makes her feel.

So what do you do? How do you scaffold that for people that haven't had a sister who was at living breathing genius? Who would go? Oh, well, I think your sentence structure is wrong, and you're talking about past participles. Go away. I just don't want to, like, no it's not important.

What? What do you do?

She was an editor of an academic journal as well, which was just freakishly scary. So. So what? What do you do? Well, you do something that is similar to that. So you go right. OK. Can you? Very simply.

Jennifer Sizer 7:49

Wow.

Participant 7:59

Find somebody that says one thing, find somebody that says a different thing, so you know, not Laurence Llewellyn Bowen on TV. But maybe someone with a bit more granularity of and, and and kudos as a researcher. And then do you think you could write what you think? And at undergraduate level, all the way up to level 6? Probably final year student. That's all right. That's OK.

But then I found that students are still a little bit at sea with that. So what's traditionally happened at [REDACTED]? In my experience, is they go.

We we have said or what's acceptable is, right: find 3 building case studies.

Maybe it's by the same architect.

Compare and contrast.

What are the similarities? What are the differences? So you, see how there's this thing of, you know, what does Bob say? What does Bernadette say? And then what do you say? It's the same thing. So you're pulling out these similarities. So you do compare contrast and then you conclude, compare contrast, conclude. So you could do. I've done it. I've had students who have done it with one architect and they've chosen 3 buildings.

Jennifer Sizer 9:15

Mm hmm mm hmm.

Participant 9:15

I've had students who have chosen a period in history.

And said these three different architects were doing a similar typology. Maybe, let's say, you know Frank Lloyd Wright house, so modernism.

Jennifer Sizer 9:33

Yeah.

Participant 9:34

A École des Beaux-Arts house and a Faye Jane's house that was very white male case study example there and I apologise for that.

But and then you go right, what's in it actually?

So, so again, there's that thing of it's a really simple, really simple scaffolding and that's acceptable. The problem is.

The 5000 words.

For for this.

In in the purest sense of the of of of the definition of a sort of a dissertation, right? It's 5000 words. What do you do? Oh, my word. OK, how do you break that down so that it's in chunks that are manageable based upon that sort of scaffolding technique? And what I've found is you have to sort of guide the students through, and you go right. OK, you've got 5000 words. It's nothing. It's.

Absolutely nothing. Once you take your quotes out of that. If you can guide the students to create a quote bank, OK, you and you may be the.

Weight of quotes within the overall document can be no more than maybe 20% of total text, maybe 25% because you want it to be the students. You don't want it to be the the the quotes. What do you do?

OK, well, think about this as a structure, you say introduction, it's chapter one is about building 1 or architect one. Chapter 2 is about building 2 or architect, architect two. Chapter 3 is about building 3 or architect three. Chapter 5 is conclusion you're looking at 1000 words per per chaptery thing that's manageable.

If you take out quotes, you're really only looking at maybe 800 words per chapter.

And for those students that come from the arts background, where they haven't had to write case studies, I mean they should have done the thing around Mondrian, Expressionism. You know, all that sort of stuff, right? Is that OK? And those with learning needs can't even do that. And over the Christmas period, they're freaking out because.

Jennifer Sizer 11:43

Yeah.

Participant 11:47

You know, traditionally the the dissertations are sort of handed in after Christmas. When I was working in there.

Jennifer Sizer 11:53

Yeah, which is slightly different, yeah.

Participant 11:57

And they've got they've got six month block you know from maybe they'll start working on the a little bit of research over the summer period. They come back to get their dissertation tutor in September and they bang on through on maybe weekly dissertation tutorials until sort of December/January and then they hand in which is which is a bit different. So but it's only it was only 5000 words. So let me just pause a minute. So that's sort of my experiences of undergrad before I go on to the postgrad.

Dissertations.

Additional dissertations in the format of which are changing quite significantly at [REDACTED] 'faculty'. So now it's not just about the written piece, it could be a filmed piece, it could be.

A report. It could be a measured building, survey case study of a historic piece there are so many different things, so I just want to make clear that I'm talking about the sort of the traditional.

Jennifer Sizer 12:52

Yeah.

Participant 12:53

How do you how do you do? How do you do? How do you do? Essays, right.

Let me go on to postgrad.

Yeah, but because of the structure of architectural education, back when I was teaching, which was four years ago, so not not a long time ago, but four years ago.

The Part 1 Royal Institute of British Architects undergraduate degrees three years long, the students go out for a year in practise and they tend to come back within a year or two. The.. we had the majority of students were returning to [REDACTED] after having done three years at undergraduate so.

They do their their first year.

Of masters MArch, Master of Architecture and then in the summer they're asked to consider their two things. The design thesis, you know the the building, the piece de resistance which they come and you know.

Show publicly at the end of the year in a in a in a show which is the sort of culmination of

their two years of of of level 7 studies, and there's what the universe or what the School of Architecture at [REDACTED] calls the written thesis, basically a dissertation.

Jennifer Sizer 14:07

Mm hmm.

Participant 14:11

The full-time students will again have the summer to look at these these two things, the written thesis and the design thesis. They'll get a dissertation sheet or in the the September and then they'll hand in at some point in January, they'll get a semester full on for that. And it's it's a lot more writing time than the undergrad's dissertation. But it's 10,000 words.

Jennifer Sizer 14:30

Yeah, right.

Participant 14:34

So what do you do? It's the same students with the same learning needs.

Very few students have gone through the humanities rigour.

They've passed their undergraduate studies. They've gone into their part one, and they feel that they can successfully write a dissertation.

With a method that they feel comfortable with, even though they left it to the last minute before, they said. [REDACTED], please can you help me? I know it's Christmas Day, but you know, I'm sure you could do this or New Year's Eve, which was always a good one.

Jennifer Sizer 15:04

Oh gosh.

Participant 15:05

Yeah, I've had. I've had Christmas Day. Students do this before, right? So.

You you basically take the same methodology that you've developed with them, but it's longer.

Jennifer Sizer 15:17

Right.

Participant 15:18

So the introduction might stay around about 1000 words, and the conclusion might stay around about 1000 words, but now you're doubling on your chapters and there's more granularity, there's more depth. You might. I mean, you'd you'd encourage the undergraduate students to do this, but you might find that the postgraduate students will go and visit these three buildings in person. So for my dissertation, OK, so when I studied at [REDACTED].

My there was no undergraduate dissertation.

It was called. It was called a history essay.

Jennifer Sizer 15:50

OK.

Mm hmm.

Participant 15:53

It's relatively recent thing to have the.

The dissertation in the undergrad and I'm trying to peel back now. It's probably 2004 it appeared at [REDACTED].

Jennifer Sizer 16:09

Yeah.

Participant 16:10

The the sort of the masters or what was the postgraduate diploma, which is what I did was there was this big, big thing that you did and it was the dissertation. We still only got 6 months to do it. You're still in in the second year of the postgraduate studies.

Jennifer Sizer 16:26

Yeah.

Participant 16:29

So I think.

You know the students feel comfortable with what they've learnt in undergraduate and they apply those rules to to, to postgraduates. So you know the students will go off. Maybe they'll go to. What did I do? So I went to.

I went to, I chose one architect. He was a he was a. He was a monk.

He had designed a load of stuff in Holland, so I went and visited his buildings in in Holland and talked to the monks that lived in his building and did all those things. So, so. And I got a distinction.

So if you're looking at the upper echelons of the marking matrix, you probably want the students to visit measures, speak to, do some deep research. You know that type of stuff.

So and and that seems to work quite successfully. Right So does that work the same for international students as home students? And those with special educational needs?

I would say, depending on the country of origin. But you have the same problems across home and international students. They, they, they suffer the same same problems with writing.

Maybe more? I don't know, maybe more so. Second language, English, maybe a little bit, but we have people coming into the School of architecture that can't write.

Because they've never done it before or they've got significant learning needs, right? So the scaffolding works. However, you get outliers like those students that have done a-levels or GCSE equivalents in Hong Kong or or or or Kenya, or... they're amazing.

You know, or you get the American students here, and they've been beasted in the diploma diploma system, and they're incredible and can stand up and talk about their work because they're they're taught how to do it. It's very formulaic, but they get it. So is there a difference between international and home? A little bit, but not as significant as I thought there would be.

Jennifer Sizer 18:24

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 18:32

OK. Right. Recent change to undergraduate.

There is and you can go back through. I'm just trying to think I've got the book here. No. So there's a couple of people that have read about, written about theory.

And philosophy of architecture. And if you crunch the numbers.

The total number of PhD architecture, PhD students popping out at the end.

Of three years or six years or whatever, it's really low compared to.

Other disciplines massively low. Why is that? Well.

Most architects spend 7 years minimum. I think the average is now 10 or 11 years to qualify as an architect, why would they want to come back and do a PHD, A few do a few do, but that's the that's the reason why architecture PhDs are are are like that right.

So.

Again, up until recently, in Reading was one of the first actually, and so was University of Kent. Research methods started to be taught on architecture programmes.

And I, you know, I mean, I mean but but sort of postgraduate I think Reading have

embedded it at undergraduate now with F [REDACTED], but she's sort of like she's gone now, she's gone to [REDACTED] but so.

You've got academics who are more research than practice?

Starting to teach students about research methods and how you would set out a PhD thesis. In the traditional way that that you are probably incredibly familiar with.

Jennifer Sizer 20:18

Mm hmm.

Participant 20:23

So we had some very, very enthusiastic researcher practitioners who took on the dissertation modules at [REDACTED] dissertation module at [REDACTED] for undergrad and postgrad.

Considering the 5000-word and 10,000-word limits for the undergraduate and the postgraduate they were trying to shoehorn in the chapters, OK, what is your introduction? What is your research methodology for this 5000-word essay? You know what is your analysis of the data? What are your findings? What are your conclusions?

Me screaming internally that how does a poor undergraduate student, who may have issues with learning and writing, deal with this? which is a science. I mean, if it's anything, if your experience is like mine of the EdD, that was a whole six months piece of work that we did. And to learn the difference between all the different very Latin-based terms, that was horrendous. That was just awful.

So if you're an undergrad and you're not just focused on the written part of research methods, then how do you how do you deal with that? So I think they're still doing it. I think they're still teaching it through the research methods. So that's the change.

That's that's been the change from the simple approach that we did have when we didn't really back back back in the day, there weren't many researchers in the School of Architecture at [REDACTED] because we were all about practise. It was all about how does this written work and your research help you to develop as a practising architect?

Jennifer Sizer 22:01

Mm hmm.

Participant 22:09

Or how does it connect to your final design thesis or your final design project? Can you use that semester of research to inform the work that you do and present in public at the grad show at the end of the year? So that was the sort of way that we looked at it, but now it's changed because we do in order to sort of compete against the other disciplines in higher education, we need more doctoral students. We need more academics to be able to bid to get funding in to raise our profile with within the UK and the world.

Does it necessarily fit?

I don't think it does.

It puts the students under a significant amount of pressure and we get to this point where I'm grimacing. I know. I'm grimacing, right?

We get to the point where we have some very enthusiastic staff members who say I'd like you to go out and talk to a participant Paul, please, can you do some interviews? Absolutely. Oh, I know. I know. Loads of people that have experienced Frank Lloyd Wright building. So, I'm going to talk to them about their impressions.

What was your impression of walking through falling water? Wow, that's brilliant. Oh, and by the way, in this six-month period. Oh, and you're doing two other modules which are worth 40 credits.

You'll need to do an ethics review. Is that OK? I've never done an ethics review before. I'm only a year three undergraduate student. Can you can you help me? What happens if I don't get ethics review and the number of students that have come to me even though I haven't

been teaching any more? In December and said my tutor has just said I can't use any of my data until I do like a post-rationalised ethics review because I didn't know I had to do one.

Jennifer Sizer 24:02

Oh gosh.

Participant 24:07

So. That's sort of my experiences of what seemed to work, and there were there was a broad set of of marks from distinction down to fail, but the sort of the scaffolded route. And of course there are going to be that broad set of of marks for the for the more research methods-based dissertations are all written thesis as we call it. But is the quality there? Are they actually getting what they need out of this? Do you need to write about your research methods?

Jennifer Sizer 24:35

Hmm.

Participant 24:42

For a 10,000 word essay, there's a strong argument to say no, but there's a counter argument to say yes, but we need more of these students to go through and become researchers. Maybe they don't all want to become architects.

So yeah, that's the sort of.

That's my experiences of sort of what it was like, what it is like, but also just to add, I I I had a history essay to hand in for my final year, the equivalent to a dissertation when I was architecture undergraduate, I had 10,000 words, maybe even 12,000 words for my postgraduate. My, my second my, my, my.

Jennifer Sizer 25:20

Mm hmm.

Participant 25:24

As postgraduate diploma in architecture, the Part 2 and then I stupidly stayed on for another six months and did a master's thesis.

40,000 words in six months, but again, that was written in a compare contrast conclude that was not..no one had talked to me. I didn't even know there was such a thing as research methods because my tutors, none of whom had PhDs, didn't tell me, but I still got a distinction.

It was called an MArch, but it turned into what we now know as an MArch.

And then of course, I went on and did the senior Fellow, which is crap and.

If advanced, HE ever listen to this? It's crap. So I'm looking into the camera. It's crap.

And then I started doing the the EdD like yourself. First two years absolutely flew because I was able to apply that method. The scaffolding method with Ch [REDACTED], who was the the course lead then, but also my personal tutor throughout the the first two years and.

Jennifer Sizer 26:19

Yeah.

OK. Yeah.

Participant 26:30

My written work became more substantial because I.

Started to understand where I was in the research sort of frame.

And now I've tried to use that knowledge to apply back to, to to the work that students do and find it very difficult.

Talk to an architecture student who really just wants to go on and design and build buildings about epistemologies.

You can't even, a lot of those with with learning needs, can't even say epistemologies. My daughter's just walked into the room. She's got dyslexia, and these words that I was rehearsing after having the [REDACTED] Ch lectures. It's very difficult to speak. It's just they're really difficult. So that's the sort of that that was like 1/2 hour of rambling at you. But that's so that's sort of.

Jennifer Sizer 27:19

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Participant 27:34

So that's my experience of.

Probably 14-15. Sixteen, 16 years of of doing stuff.

Jennifer Sizer 27:44

Yeah.

Participant 27:45

Just to give you a little bit, so I'm I'm an external examiner.

For a Level 3 international architecture programme at the University of of [REDACTED].

Jennifer Sizer 27:59

Mm hmm.

Participant 28:00

The University of [REDACTED] International College it's by [REDACTED].

It's the. It's the equivalent to sort of A-levels, really.

I notice the same issues with writing. They're not embedded with the home cohort at all, they're just coming over doing English. But it's [REDACTED] so it's it's it's it's, you know, it's it's Russell Group standard.

Jennifer Sizer 28:14

Mm hmm.

Participant 28:21

I am an external examiner at an undergraduate part one architecture course at University of [REDACTED].

Which is international and home.

And I see exactly the same struggles.

As I've just described to you.

The person in charge of history and theories, the person in charge of, of dissertations at [REDACTED], is a researcher.

Not a practitioner. And when I say practitioner, I mean the number of buildings he's designed and built are probably in single digits.

So he has tried to crowbar in research methods.

My comment back to the module coordinator and the course leader actually is what are you doing? They're all getting 40s.

Because they don't understand. What is being taught to them, and they're a small cohort as well. So I think there's only like 14 in the year in the final year.

It's really, really spot, right? Add that to the other stuff. So I've run transnational education partnerships in Hong Kong and Singapore.

Final year students. So that's dissertations, obviously, where they have, where the students are basically being taught, University of [REDACTED] modules, but in Hong Kong and in Singapore.

The academics, who are, particularly in Hong Kong, are amazing, but they're practitioners.

They're they're practitioners, but they've come through like five years of architectural

education and, you know, they know how to do dissertations. So they teach their students the way that they were taught, which is the way that I've just described to you.

Jennifer Sizer 30:12

Mm hmm.

Participant 30:13

That I experienced and how we taught. So it's that sort of compare contrast conclude and it was really interesting to see travel 6000 miles around the world you pick up, you pick up a Hong Kong dissertation.

And you go oh, oh, it's exactly the same. So the so the English language actually in Hong Kong, the English language is just outstanding because they do the equivalent to GCSE, they do A-levels.

You know, it was, it was, in a way. You could argue that the dissertations were maybe a little bit stronger than the that the the students that I've seen at [REDACTED]. But there was no research methods because when you're dealing with Hong Kongers, who?

Probably probably Mandarin is is first first language and they have a different they are not taught in the compare contrast conclude they're taught in the oh gosh.

Oh, my brain's gone dead.

Jennifer Sizer 31:16

Confucius type stuff.

Participant 31:16

It's. Confucius. Yeah. So there's no no need to conclude. Why would we conclude it's a it's a spiral of thought.

Jennifer Sizer 31:24

Yeah.

Participant 31:26

Being able to come and say, look right, here's some examples of dissertations. This is how I was taught, not me, but the, you know, the course leaders or the module coordinators in Hong Kong. Do you think you can get to grips with this? They do.

So that's that. There's because my job I've been doing Associate Dean Global for four, nearly four years now, so I've had real experience of going out and reading quite a lot of stuff.

Jennifer Sizer 31:48

Mm hmm yeah.

Participant 31:55

So yeah, and then the other part of my role is education partnerships, which is the local, which is like FE colleges and what I've really noticed is.

The limited amount of purely written work.

So it's either coursework.

Here's a case study. Here's a report. Here's a review.

They're short and sharp and punchy, and there's less examination of knowledge under pressure. There's open book, different thing, but there's no learning the information and then having to write mini two or three thousand word essays in an exam condition. So that is like, completely disappearing, which is quite a good thing. My my daughter's doing. she's very comfortable with that.

But it does have an impact when you've got students who are trying to do bigger things.

Jennifer Sizer 32:50

Knock on effect.

Participant 32:51

Later on, when they're not really being guided about how to do it.

Jennifer Sizer 32:57

So in terms of guiding then, so they're kind of the students don't seem massively prepared and and we've talked previously about this idea of kind of architecture very much being a kind of apprenticeship sort of model to expert and we're talking about average of kind of 10 to 11 years to become an architect. And even then, unless you've got buildings.

Participant 33:12

Yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 33:21

In three digits then you're not an expert anyway. Don't think so. Like that kind of trajectory to expert. It's kind of it takes a takes some really long time.

Participant 33:26

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 33:30

I wonder how much kind of training or experience they get in writing during the course as well, because they do have this dissertation that they're working on. But what happens in like, year one and year two and that kind of thing to support them with that writing, do you think?

Participant 33:38

OK. Yeah, yeah.

OK.

OK. Yeah, right. OK.

And this is really interesting because obviously I've got the external examiner experience now. So I'm not just talking to you about [REDACTED]. I'm talking to you about other other places as well.

So the Royal Institute of British Architects, I suppose the Architecture Registration Board as well.

There's a stipulation for 50% design in architecture programmes.

Jennifer Sizer 34:11

Yeah.

Participant 34:12

So if that's all the designy drawingy stuff building, you know, learning how to how to do. Learning how to architect as I saw written once, which I quite like the verb to architect.

Jennifer Sizer 34:25

Yeah, I like that.

Participant 34:29

What's the other 50% or the other 50% is transmitted knowledge.

And it tends to be in lectures.

Seminars.

Workshops.

So you take that that.

You take that half and you divide it into three.

Because you've got professional practise.

History and theory.

And.

You've got environment and technology.

Now you could argue that thinking about the climate crisis that we're in environment and technology should be 50% of the cost, it's not right.

So if you look at the first, well, if you did, if you in previous years, if you looked at the first year it was.

60 credits design.

20 credits, history and Theory 20 credits, Environment and technology, and 20 credits.

Design and representation. So how do you draw? How do you learn to draw so professional practise doesn't really come in until maybe third year, right?

Jennifer Sizer 35:51

OK.

Participant 35:53

Second year is the same again 60 credits for design and then you used to have an option study which could be a film or it could be a written piece of work because 20 credits

You have History and theory 20 credits.

Yeah, the environment and technology, which is 20 credit.

And the third year was 60 credits design and then it was 20 credit professional practise 20 credit environment and technology and 20 credit dissertation.

Well, history of theories again, but dissertation.

So within within the sort of the the transmitted knowledge I know didactically point at board.

You learn this because this is what you need to know to be an architect.

When they come, when the students come to do their submissions at the end of that 20 credit module, it tends to be in written form.

Jennifer Sizer 36:55

Uh huh.

Participant 36:56

If the history and theory it's probably more recognisable as an essay.

Jennifer Sizer 37:00

Yeah.

Participant 37:01

Choose your period in history. Choose your architect again. Similar to what I was talking to you about for dissertation.

Environment and technology would be probably case study analysis followed by I've applied these calculations to one of my design projects and I found this.

Jennifer Sizer 37:20

Mm hmm.

Participant 37:20

These were the errors. These were the successes, and if I were to do it again, I would probably do this. So it's very chemistry background. You know how you used to set up your experiment, you would go.

Aims, objectives, equipment, blah blah blah blah, right? And then.

So professional practise is normally group work and group group essay or Group Group report and I use the word report.

Jennifer Sizer 37:45

Yeah.

Participant 37:47

Rep and com the representation and communication, the drawing thing in the first year used to be a little mini portfolio of drawings, probably very limited in terms of of writing.

Jennifer Sizer 37:54

Mm hmm mm.

Yeah.

Participant 37:59

So the students do get.

They do get the opportunity to practise these submissions as they go through the different years, are smaller word counts 1000 words or multiple 1000 words? Maybe a 2000 word, maybe a 3000 words, don't scare the students, you know, keep it nice and simple.

Jennifer Sizer 38:13

Mm hmm.

Yeah.

Participant 38:25

It's very difficult to fail those lower-level essays.

Because you don't have...

So yes, staff will be looking at the final assessment artefacts, but they won't necessarily get a chance to have a lot of feedback on drafts.

Jennifer Sizer 38:47

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 38:48

Or they won't hand in drafts They won't have a tutor that works with them in the same way as dissertation.

Jennifer Sizer 38:55

Mm hmm mm.

Participant 38:56

So the way that we used to do this 'cause I used to do the recruitment and outreach for the school at [REDACTED] at the School of Architecture at [REDACTED] The way we did the open day presentations was we'd give the overview of the different years and we'd be talking about we're building. We're building your skills, they will the the assignments you get will be slightly more complicated as you progress. The word count will increase and the subject matter will become more technical until you get your dissertation sheet and you have to work. Write this big 5000 word piece.

You get 6 months to do it? It's like you and you and I like six months of 5000 words. That's amazing. Like a weekend. I mean, that would be fantastic, wouldn't it?

So. So that's the type of that's that's the support that they get, but it's it's it's exactly the same. OK, I'm going to shut up a minute because I'll spin off in something else. Otherwise, does that answer that question that you had? OK. Right. OK.

Jennifer Sizer 39:53

No, no, it's OK. If it finish your thought because you might not come back to it.

Participant 39:59

Why? Why has architecture education? Oh, it's the same in the other things that I'm examining as well. By the way, it's not just [REDACTED] those experiences, right. So why is it like that?

So why does history or English lit or why do they do things slightly differently? Why is architecture education like that? Because.

It comes back to Pupillage and it comes back to learning by doing. It's the experiential learning I'm I'm going to try not to swear during this, but in the old days, in schools of architecture you would do a piece of work. Doesn't matter whether it's written, it doesn't matter whether it's drawn.

And you would go. It'd be really enthusiastic and you'd go in and you'd give it. You'd give it to your tutor and they'd go. This is ****.

Jennifer Sizer 40:41

Mm hmm.

Participant 40:49

Go and do it again.

OK. Can you give me some pointers? Why isn't it very good? No. You need to learn. You need to learn how to make it better.

But can you tell me how to? I can't because I'm an academic and I need to be. I need to be impartial.

OK.

What do I do? You need to learn from precedent.

Precedent, as Barry Russell has written about in a book by Martin Pearce and Maggie Toy that was published in 1994-1995 by Ad Publishing, and it was called educating architects Barry Russell. Throughout the 70s, the 80s.

I think he probably stepped out in that. No, no. And the 90s did this thing called the precedent project.

And you had to learn through the work of others.

You'd be set a project, right? Go and learn about Philip Webb's Red House.

You need to you've got a two-week project you need to go and find out everything you possibly can and then you need to distil it down into two A2 sheets and present what you found and there'll be a written element to that. And there'll also be lots of drawn element.

How do you analyse it and stuff like that? But that Barry Russell approach work, which is which is broadly I think Barry Russell was Princeton as well actually if I'm right. I mean he was, you know, he was proper. He's amazing guy.

That idea of precedent is just there. It's in the DNA of architectural education. How do I learn how to do that? You go and find out through things that have been done before. You, you you very rarely.

Jennifer Sizer 42:35

Mm hmm.

Participant 42:39

You can't. You can't reinvent the wheel with architectural education. You can't because it's been done before, aeons ago or more recently. All right, so when you sat in practise and you're.

Jennifer Sizer 42:45

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 42:50

Building regulations change or planning changes, or a client comes to you and says can you

design a school for me? But I'd like a special educational needs school and you've only ever done primary school or secondary school. You go what do I do? You go out and you go through the journals. You go through the archives. You talk to people that have done SEN schools and you learn and you put it together and you work with the client and the client in, in the academic sense is probably is the tutor. So you go back hundreds of years. You be the pupil and you would have the master. And that's the way it would work.

I need you pupil to go off and do me a timber, a cut timber roof detail. OK. How do I do that? I'm not going to tell you. I'm going to give you some hints, but you need to go and learn, OK. What do I do? Go and measure that cut roof.

Go and measure it and draw it and then bring it back to me. Bring it back. So we're talking like Christopher Wren. So like hundreds of years ago, you know, with this surveying office that the King's surveying office and you'd go. Right. OK. I've done this. Well, that's ****. It doesn't look like that. Go and do it again. And it would be this, like, this beasting, this bleeding. And it still goes on now. And you'd go right, you learn through.

What you see in front of you and you learn through archive and research.

OK. And that and that work, it works, I mean obviously the the approach of of academics has changed.

In a way, right. But that's the way. And that is sort of that's ingrained now. Like I said, that's in the DNA of how you learn as an architecture student. So that's sort of what you find with the dissertations.

I've got I'm of the mind. 'cause I come from the Preston background, which is a student comes to me. He's really struggling. I've given them scaffolding and then they said, but I don't know how to write a dissertation. I go, I will say. Well, here's a dissertation I'll anonymise. Here's a dissertation that failed.

Jennifer Sizer 45:04

Yep.

Participant 45:05

Here's a third, 2:2 2:1 first and.

First plus right? Read these. See what you think. I've got some colleagues who are like. No, no, no, don't share because you're sort of giving the game away.

She's like, no, because they students can probably find the blooming dissertations or ask the guys in previous cohorts or or whatever.

Jennifer Sizer 45:26

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 45:29

So you've got this system that's there that students can.

You can follow Preston's study. It's it's it's fine. It's OK.

And there is there are staff members, there are academics who are dissertation tutors or design tutors who go right. OK, this is this will help you. This will help you. This will help you.

Here you go. Here you go. Here's some feedback. This is where I think you can be. You can improve it and you're along the right lines or you're not along the right lines and keep going.

There are other staff members who sort of say not going to help you at all. It's the beasting, the bleeding, and then you've got others. And these tend to be the practitioners. They spent more time in practise than academia, and they all go.

Jennifer Sizer 46:07

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 46:18

This is how you do it.

This is how you write a brilliant dissertation. This is how you design a brilliant building. I can

think of a number of staff members now. Things have changed a lot, but there's a number of of architects, educators who were like that. No, no, no. You don't draw in that line weight. You draw in this line weight.

Copy me. See, it's the master thing. Copy me and you will excel.

The problem comes when they go into practise and the tutor's no longer there and the wheels fall off because they start designing in the way that they're tutor designed and the practitioner that they're employed by goes. What are you doing? We don't do it like that. We do it like this and they have to relearn. So for me I was taught by a tutor.

Jennifer Sizer 46:53

Yeah.

Participant 47:11

Very strong.

Very successful architect too. Actually. One was a RIBA, a gold medal winner. So you can imagine the ego that was on, you know. And I actually went and worked for his old practise. So it was easy for me to fit into that because I knew the language. I knew everything. But it wasn't until it's partly why I went and set up on my own when I was 30, which is ridiculous. Most architects don't sit up until they're in their 40s, right. I went and set up on my own because I wanted to find out how I designed with. No.

Jennifer Sizer 47:21

Yeah.

Yeah.

Participant 47:44

Stabilisers, with no life jacket.

I need to do it myself and it wasn't really until that point when I was 30 and I sat in my office going Oh my God, how do you design this stuff or how do you write a report? Or how do these things? And I relied on the way I've been taught. I went and looked at precedent. I went and looked at case study. I went and found what an environmental or a sustainability report looked like that needed to be submitted to a City Council or a local authority or something. But that was my.

Jennifer Sizer 48:04

Yeah.

Participant 48:15

That was my reliance.

Jennifer Sizer 48:16

Yeah, that makes sense.

Participant 48:18

Say yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 48:19

And and I wonder with with a lot of that it seems to be this, this constant tension between the kind of well for pracacademics of of want of a better word of this kind of practise and academia because you're kind of preparing the students for being an architect at some point. That that's the kind of ultimate goal. But then as you say, how well are you preparing them and and and where does the dissertation fit into that? Like, is the dissertation really as you kind of said, preparing them to show?

Participant 48:45

None.

Jennifer Sizer 48:49

Like how they can architect or and be an architect? Or is it kind of demonstrating their research knowledge? Like is it the kind of university or the future practise that's kind of manipulating that and influencing that?

Participant 48:59

Yeah.

That's really interesting. So.

So I knew how to research because of my sister and because of my background in doing the humanities subjects at a-level. So I never had a problem with that. I think the thing that's really helpful with this new approach for dissertations or the thesis is you have people saying to you at the university, this is how you undertake research.

Which is great because that's the type of research, although it won't be, you know, libraries for.

Essay subjects or theory.

It'll be well which archive do I look through to find out? You know the best U value for a insulation of a building. The skills are still there. So that's excellent. That's really, really good. I've always thought there's a there's a very small percentage of students that go through the system to study architecture that will come back and teach.

If they do, they'll probably come back as part-time while they run their own practices or or while they are employed in a practice, right so.

Jennifer Sizer 50:07

Yeah.

Participant 50:13

What is the point of the dissertation? The point of a dissertation is.

That the student knows how to write something in professional language.

Report, it's.. a director said to me years and years ago.

Architecture. Even though there's this split down the middle of 50% design and 50% theory, it's probably 10% design actually in practice.

Jennifer Sizer 50:39

OK.

Participant 50:40

The rest of it, 90% is administration.

Business profit and loss planning.

Jennifer Sizer 50:47

Yeah.

Participant 50:49

Good regulations dealing with a client. All of those things. So you could say actually the education system hasn't caught up yet. It's a bit skewed, but it needs the 50% time allocation to help students to learn how to design the 10% later on in in their careers. So it is rip.. and there are some really difficult reports that you need to write.

Even client pitches now, when you go up through the practice sizes. For instance, I'm going to I'm going to pick. Let's go. Let's say you got Google as a client. They're not going to want an A4 Flappy B bid. They're going to want this really amazing thing.

So the dissertation is, and those history essays and the professional practise essays as well

are helping you. How to write that.

And that's what I think it's for. For the small percentage that come back and do a doctorate or a standalone masters like I did.

Or a senior fellow essay, it's it's useful to be taught the proper way, but you talk to a lot of the guys that are on the [REDACTED] course at the moment, doing their fellowships or their senior fellowships, or don't even talk to me about principal fellowships and and they've not gone through the research methods or they've not got a doctorate. They don't know where to start because they go right. I'll go and I'll have a look at precedents or case studies of former senior or accept or or approved, accepted fellow senior fellow and principal for.

Exist or you can't find them or the flipping people within [REDACTED] department go Oh well, we can't share that with you. I'm sorry. And you come back to this whole thing of so you want me to struggle to learn, which is ridiculous.

Jennifer Sizer 52:24

Yeah, yeah, yeah. The hidden.

Yeah.

Yeah.

Participant 52:38

And so again, that's why I think the master's written thesis and the undergraduate dissertation is there is because you're teaching the students to write professionally.

Jennifer Sizer 52:52

Yeah.

Participant 52:53

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 52:54

Should we have a quick look at some of the the ones that we've got? So I don't know which ones you managed to look at.

Participant 53:00

I can't remember now it seems a a while ago. Could I have a comfort break? Is that all right?

Jennifer Sizer 53:03

Yeah. Yeah, of course you can.

Participant 53:07

Alright, let me see if I can.

Do that right, I will see in a minute.

Jennifer Sizer 53:14

Okie dokie.

Participant 53:16

Right.

Jennifer Sizer 53:19

I will do the same.

No, that's perfect timing.

So I don't know if you remember them or not. So we kind of had the caring for older people.

Participant 55:22

OK.

Jennifer Sizer 55:29

Can you see my screen? Yeah.

Participant 55:30

Yeah, I can. Thank you. Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 55:32

Yes, OK. Caring for older people. How are Portsmouth's public space is doing? Which was an interesting one then. There was also this one about arctic architecture.

Participant 55:38

Yeah.

Yeah, could you. So what's really useful for me is sort of like a memory jogger. If you could go to the contents page or the OR the sort of.

Yeah. OK, so this yeah. And and the other one that you went to the the caring.

Jennifer Sizer 55:59

It's one, yeah. Oh, actually 2nd.

Away. And then that one is that's the contents page.

Participant 56:08

Yeah. And then if you go back to the one that you were just on with them, Zaha Hadid looking.

Yeah, that's it again, right. So I would say.

Jennifer Sizer 56:15

Be happy.

Participant 56:18

Those first two I did I glimpsed at all of them. But you know, right. So those first two again, if you look at it in terms of there are five, there are 5 chapters essentially.

And it comes back to that thing that I was talking to you about [yellow 1/3]

Jennifer Sizer 56:32

Yeah.

Participant 56:36

Yeah. Yeah, right. And then you go to the Hadid 1.

Zaha Hadid. And we've got the new one [yellow 2/3]

We've got introduction lit, review method see now....

Jennifer Sizer 56:47

Yeah.

Participant 56:49

So that that's that's fine. So that that sort of that illustrates what I was talking about, which is great and that there are now many, many more.

Academics.

Research academics in architects programmes in the UK and I think.

Jennifer Sizer 57:08

So this [yellow 2/3] is representing for you kind of a new sort of style. Does that make sense or newish sort of style, yeah.

Participant 57:11

You'll.

Yes it does. Yes it does.

How successful it is?

I don't know.

And the reason I say that is 'cause I'm I'm old now, and I've got a long I've got a long thing.

I've got a long. I can look back a long way.

And I'm not sure, if the research methods bit is actually helpful.

Jennifer Sizer 57:50

Yeah, because it's an interesting one because even looking at this, so for me this [yellow 2/3] was one of the ones that was the most kind of what I'm calling in terms of structure, the most generic structure. So having the most recognisable kind of dissertation structure, it was one of those. So it was a good starting point for me to look at because it felt very similar to other dissertations I'd looked at. But even when we're looking at things like.

Participant 58:07

Yeah, yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 58:17

Primary data timeline. So I'm looking at this timeline.

And it's about kind of a timeline of parametricism, if that's how you say that.

Participant 58:27

Yeah, that's right. Yeah, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 58:29

But for me that's not primary data in that respect because they haven't collected it, right? So it's kind of all of a sudden a little bit confusing and then the methodology itself.

Participant 58:36

Yeah.

There's.

Jennifer Sizer 58:43

Doesn't talk about the method.

Participant 58:46

No, no, so, so OK, so this is, this is the thing I think the students will get one hour either every week with their dissertation tutor or one hour every two weeks is something ridiculously small. Right. So if before I I brushed shoulders with the EdD and you said to me what's your method? I would have said well this is the way I did it.

Jennifer Sizer 58:58

Yeah.

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 59:10

I wouldn't say.

Jennifer Sizer 59:11

It's your process.

Participant 59:13

Yeah, I I wouldn't have said, oh, well, actually I've used.

My method is narrative analysis.

As suggested by this particular academic.

Who uses this analytical methodology to I would have just gone? I wanted to. I I wanted to. I wanted to find this out, so I did it this way.

Jennifer Sizer 59:32

Yeah.

Participant 59:39

That's the weakness with using correct terminology in an incorrect manner.

Because this poor student, who was probably really, really engaged.

Might go on to do an M Phil.

Or or or a PhD and think that they have an understanding of what a methodology is. I would say that the lit review is probably the idea of reading lots of things and analysing what you've written, what what you've found is the closest thing to a precedent study.

Jennifer Sizer 1:00:27

Yeah, yeah, it feels similar.

Participant 1:00:29

So there's a bit of comfort there, but what tends to happen is that the students regurgitate everything, don't reference what they've found and don't.

Jennifer Sizer 1:00:31

Yeah.

Participant 1:00:42

Take out the important bits, so it'll just be a dump of information as opposed to. Well, I found this, and actually for my question, this was useful.

Jennifer Sizer 1:00:55

Right.

Participant 1:00:56

The idea of research question is not really is not really unpicked either. My argument is, but my argument I suppose is with a bit of knowledge I think that...., I think the the students would be able to cope with it. It's not that they wouldn't, it's just they don't have the time or capacity to deal with research methods in the traditional sense, along with everything else.

Jennifer Sizer 1:01:27

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 1:01:29

You have fudge all time to write this 5000 words you are dealing with, probably the majority of staff who don't understand what a research method is.

And you don't want to spend as you and I may have found, we may have a shared experience where you have staff members in the doctorate allowing you 9 weeks to write the right questions.

Just don't you just have to do a question and crack on because you've got 12 weeks, 13 weeks.

Jennifer Sizer 1:02:01

Yeah. No, exactly.
Yeah.

Participant 1:02:06

So so I think, yeah, it's, it's, it's, it's interesting to see the staff member that brought this in as a change of process I suppose or change of approach is no longer with us.

Jennifer Sizer 1:02:10

Yeah.
Right. OK.

Participant 1:02:21

He's gone off to a different programme in a different country.

Jennifer Sizer 1:02:24

Mm hmm.

Participant 1:02:25

And he was definitely.
A research practitioner with a doctorate.

Jennifer Sizer 1:02:31

That's interesting.
So with that kind of in mind then, because this student did use a methodology which was an interview, they don't really mention the interview at all until right at the end. And it's funny you should mention the kind of ethics stuff because there's no mention of ethics at all, which is interesting. But if we have a look at this one, this feels a little bit.

Participant 1:02:54

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:02:57

More like the structure you were describing.

Participant 1:03:01

That's right.

Jennifer Sizer 1:03:02

And this for me, feels much more as I was saying with the structure of much more topic based. So these don't have the the recognisable kind of sections.

Participant 1:03:08

That's right.

Jennifer Sizer 1:03:12

And then this one in itself, so it's.
It's a crazy PDF, so I'm so done with the crazy PDFs

Participant 1:03:20

Yeah, yeah, yeah. OK, so.
So one of the components for architectural dissertations and and written theses is that they look beautiful.

Jennifer Sizer 1:03:31

Yes.

Participant 1:03:32

You're you're an architect and you must design everything from a door handle to a building to your dissertation.

Jennifer Sizer 1:03:38

Yeah.

Participant 1:03:41

So that's the I remember doing laying out my artefacts for the first and second year of the EdD in a way that wasn't bog standard and and Charlie said no, it's got to be, you know, 11 point aerial double spaced. So there is that's probably what doesn't look.

Jennifer Sizer 1:03:54

Yeah.

OK.

Participant 1:04:09

As familiar for those outside architectural education.

But yeah, so no, this is this is topic based because it's around Care in the community.

So I would say having had a look at this one.

The student may be trying to be clever.

They might find that.

Their final design project was care in the community.

So you're able then to sit down at the beginning of your final review, your final presentation, and say I've done all this work, but I also wrote my dissertation about this. So unlike Bob, who sat next to me, who wrote about Zaha Hadid and has for the dissertation, and then designed a farm.

Jennifer Sizer 1:05:00

Yeah.

Participant 1:05:07

My work is of a better quality because I've actually spent 12 months looking at this, not six months.

Jennifer Sizer 1:05:09

Right.

OK.

Participant 1:05:13

So there's there's a there's a rationale.

Jennifer Sizer 1:05:15

There's some strategic thinking there. Yeah. Yeah, I get it.

Participant 1:05:19

Oh yeah, and that helps with the external examiners as well. When you come in and and you're right, the student is able to say to the external examiner, well, I did it like this. And they'll say, what was your dissertation about? And you go, oh, well, care in the community.

Jennifer Sizer 1:05:31

Now that's interesting. And it's interesting because you were talking about your own research where you kind of went to see the the monks buildings.

Participant 1:05:40

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:05:41

And the students done something quite similar, so they've obviously gone into these spaces and taken their own photos and that kind of thing. Now for me, that almost felt like almost became like an ethnographic study. But of course, she doesn't really talk about that kind of research method for her. I assume it's just it's still a precedent study, right? It's just kind of.

Participant 1:06:01

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:06:02

But she's going in and taking the photos herself and exploring that.

Participant 1:06:04

Yeah, that's yeah. And and just to hook that back into something that you said earlier. The the way you could get a higher mark was by going and visiting the buildings and using your own photography and that was considered to be primary research investigation.

Jennifer Sizer 1:06:27

Right.

Participant 1:06:29

You measured a building or is your data.

Jennifer Sizer 1:06:32

OK.

Participant 1:06:33

You photograph a building beautifully as your photographs. You've given the effort.

Jennifer Sizer 1:06:35

OK.

Participant 1:06:38

To travel with your brand new wife in the back of the Fiesta all the way to the German border in Holland.

And not book any accommodation.

Yeah.

26 years later, we're still married. I don't know how, but.

But yeah, so this is all about immersing yourself in the subject. Do I need to do an ethics review? No, because it's mine and I don't care.

Jennifer Sizer 1:07:08

Yeah.

Participant 1:07:13

But should you have done one or even if you're analysing buildings, potentially yes, you probably should have done one.

So yeah, I think.

This. Yeah. And this the learned experience of of visiting these buildings.

Of going through the regulations or looking at the government white papers, this student may

go into practice and do care, care homes, respite homes and they'll be able to go into their interview and say because obviously architectural practice is specialised.

Jennifer Sizer 1:07:35

Hmm.
Right.

Participant 1:07:48

Or have specialisms you'll be able to go in and go look what I've done.

Jennifer Sizer 1:07:52

Yeah, that's interesting.

Participant 1:07:53

As opposed to doing a piece on the door handles of Frank Lloyd Wright's buildings, where it's everyone goes, OK, how does that help you? It's interesting. It's interesting, but does it help you?

Jennifer Sizer 1:08:02

Yeah.

And then on a similar note, we've got another student, then my other student I've looked at who definitely couldn't visit the buildings because they're in the Arctic circle.

Participant 1:08:19

Yeah. But but again, you look so if you keep on the on the contents page at moment, right, so.

Jennifer Sizer 1:08:27

Yeah.

Participant 1:08:30

This isn't an adoption of what I would call the new method.

Jennifer Sizer 1:08:35

Yeah.

Participant 1:08:36

Which is actually the traditional method, right?

This is a quasi version of what we just looked at.

Jennifer Sizer 1:08:45

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 1:08:46

Do you have an introduction overview?

You then have the three chapters that say, well, this is the research that I've done under these themes.

Jennifer Sizer 1:08:56

Mm hmm.

Participant 1:08:57

Climate location. Community settlements. Right now we know this. Now I've revealed this to you in practice in action. What does that look like?

Jennifer Sizer 1:09:10

Mm hmm.

Participant 1:09:11

In conclusion, what have we learned?

And hopefully I answer the question that I've set myself in this way.

Jennifer Sizer 1:09:19

Yeah.

Participant 1:09:20

But if you look and This is why it's mental Jen, absolutely mental, look at the amount of pages they're writing for each one.

It's just.

Jennifer Sizer 1:09:34

Yeah.

Participant 1:09:37

Crazy.

Jennifer Sizer 1:09:37

And the pages are half pictures.

Participant 1:09:41

Yeah, exactly. I would probably just.

Back in when I ran practice or when when I work with contractors, in practice they used to say to me we can we the contractors will be able to weigh a tender pack to basically work out first dibs. What the cost would be before going into the data, right?

Jennifer Sizer 1:10:03

Wow.

Participant 1:10:06

Are academics can probably flip very quickly first glance through a dissertation and go.

Oh wow, I think this is probably in the thirds.

Maybe a third two, two. And for me, you look at the number of pages and you look at the the ratio between words to pictures or images and you're thinking wow, is this really granular enough for a top mark where it might be?

My sister's my late sister's father-in-law.

Did a PhD his PhD in economics and it was 25 pages long because it was an equation.

So sometimes genius comes out of a small amount of stuff.

Jennifer Sizer 1:10:52

Yeah, yeah.

Yeah.

Participant 1:10:56

The ... Yeah, this to me is probably a navel gazing piece because they wouldn't have been able to apply.

Jennifer Sizer 1:11:01

OK.

Participant 1:11:07

Everything that they learned to their final thesis because, sorry, the final design project, because the final design project would be an urban setting somewhere in Hampshire or London.

Jennifer Sizer 1:11:17

Right.

Yes, so not quite as helpful.

Yeah.

Participant 1:11:23

But maybe it's something they want to do in the future.

Jennifer Sizer 1:11:26

Maybe.

Participant 1:11:29

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:11:30

So yeah, so in terms of just kind of visually then they're they're quite different in the in the kind of approaches that they've got for it. So obviously this one's got kind of lots of pictures, but this is a portrait layout it's kind of got 2 columns.

Where the other student uses kind of landscape and some and sometimes two columns again.

Participant 1:11:51

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:11:55

Then this student has kind of used again kind of landscape two columns. I've also got some students that sometimes use 3 columns, but yeah, just wondered what you thought.

Participant 1:12:06

That's right.

So this this all comes back to the fact that architecture dissertations are different.

Architecture written theses are different.

And I think there's a 10% design component.

Jennifer Sizer 1:12:23

Oh, interesting.

Participant 1:12:24

Have a look at that have a look at the rubric. If you can get a hold of one, it's something along the lines of and, and they'll sort of blend grammar spelling.

Jennifer Sizer 1:12:27

Yeah.

Right.

Participant 1:12:35

Overall presentation into this, but the architecture tutors

And probably tutors in graphic design and illustration and all those days are probably looking for an element of designish designish, right? So there's this real, we do. We're not like

English lit or we're not like history where we tell you that it must be double-spaced, 11 point arial. Right. OK. So for me I have written in all sorts of formats. I'm not sure if this will come across.

Jennifer Sizer 1:13:04

Yeah, I can kind of see it, but with your blur, it's gonna blur. Yeah, if you take your blur off, it might work. Yeah. Perfect.

Participant 1:13:05

Right. So I wonder if I take let me take.
Right. OK, right. So that is landscape, right?

Jennifer Sizer 1:13:16

Yeah.

Participant 1:13:17

And the former is.

Jennifer Sizer 1:13:20

Yeah. Very similar, yeah.

Participant 1:13:21

That. OK, so my dissertation was was very like that. So that's a piece. This is a piece of work from 19... May 2000 that was submitted, right.
This which was.97 Right was April.

Jennifer Sizer 1:13:39

Yeah. portrait Yeah.

Participant 1:13:42

But like that, Chicago.

Jennifer Sizer 1:13:44

Yeah.

Participant 1:13:47

You know, referencing all right.

Jennifer Sizer 1:13:49

For Chicago and no pictures.

Participant 1:13:51

No pictures, no. This one was the equivalent to my BA3 dissertation.
And it was about an architect who no one knew about, called Albert Fray. OK, there is one tiddly little picture on the front. It's A4 format. Photographs are in the back in illustrations, right. But.

Jennifer Sizer 1:14:11

Right. OK.

Participant 1:14:15

It's blocks of text.

Jennifer Sizer 1:14:17

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 1:14:18

Harvard APA. Referencing because we we switched.
Right then my 40,000 beast, which was the MArch.
Is.
Portrait.
And then if I just flip through, all right?

Jennifer Sizer 1:14:40

OK. Yeah.

Participant 1:14:41

Images down one side text is one column.
There are no, it's no holds barred. You can do what you want.
And the reason why?
It's quite successful for those that consider the graphic design quality of their work.
Is is. It's easy to do because.
They're taught how to use Indesign and illustrator for their other work, whereas a English lit student or a history student wouldn't be they're taught word, and that's that's it, right. So all the students will be typing it for architecture students. Architecture students will teach typing it in Word, but then they'll copy and paste it. And when it comes to organising images indesign is a lot easier to do. So there's a there's there's more knowledge about graphic design there, and they're told well, they can do whatever they want.

Jennifer Sizer 1:15:15

Right.
Yeah, yeah.

Participant 1:15:40

So that's the tradition that goes back like decades and decades and you know.

Jennifer Sizer 1:15:46

And what influences those choices do you think?

Participant 1:15:57

OK, so I've I'm I'm sure people say it's true all the time. I'm writing a book at the moment for our RIBA publishing.
And the method I used for the sort of design quality, the graphic design of that book is myself and my co-author. We went and looked at loads of books.

Jennifer Sizer 1:16:16

Yeah.

Participant 1:16:17

To find out what we liked, and then because we both have skills in Indesign, Adobe Indesign, we are able to mimic the ones we liked on a layout and just copy.
And then you give that to the other graphic designer in the publishing house. This is, that's fine. And that's what I've always done. That's what my co-authors always done. And that's what I think students do. They'll go through the library or they'll read through other dissertations and they'll go Wow. Oh, I really like that.
And that's it. It becomes a bit nuanced where, like here and again, this is Illustrator or Indesign for you. You can shape text as if it's the body.

Jennifer Sizer 1:17:00

Yeah, yeah. I've never seen anything like it. I've got to be honest, especially during a dissertation.

Participant 1:17:03

Yeah. And you go. Yeah. And you say, well, look, everything that I'm writing about is to do with ..Care.

The care of the body care of the mind, and I'm going to represent that by doing this, I would argue it's not done successfully here, however, they've tried.

Jennifer Sizer 1:17:19

Yeah.

But it's bringing that person kind of front and centre. So before you even start writing the dissertation you've got, you've got this. This is like on the first page before we even kind of get into the introduction, these facts and figures are kind of front and centre in a person format. So you're making sure they're thinking about that person.

Participant 1:17:27

But yeah, just.

Yeah.

That's that's. Yeah, it's exactly right. And.

Yeah, I wouldn't be surprised if, you know, they'd even considered shaping the dissertation. The physical dissertation, like a person.

Jennifer Sizer 1:18:00

Interesting.

Participant 1:18:01

But then that had been rejected because how did you bind it?

You know, so, but, but yeah. So I think that's where it comes from. You know, you, you, you. You're even taught.

Jennifer Sizer 1:18:05

True.

Participant 1:18:14

That when you're doing a fee bid, a fee proposal, it should be visually enticing for the client. So it's like.

It's it's, its practice. It's academia, it's, you know.

Jennifer Sizer 1:18:25

So they're kind of seeing other people's dissertation, so they might see something like this and kind of follow a similar, sort of format. Do you think it's just other people's dissertations that they've seen, or is there other texts that they've seen that might help? I remember speaking to Steve Parnell up in Newcastle and asked him if he thought that architectural magazines influenced students. And he basically said students don't read architectural magazines. So no.

Participant 1:18:40

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:18:52

It was interesting.

Participant 1:18:52

OK, so yeah, now since Rosie's husband, isn't it?
Rosie Parnell she's a genius.

Jennifer Sizer 1:18:59

Yeah.

Participant 1:19:03

OK, I have I have a problem with architects educators at the best of times.

So students do read books, journals, literature.

The the better ones will go into a library, or they'll buy books and they'll cherish those books and it will normally be because the books look amazing and they smell amazing and.

Jennifer Sizer 1:19:25

Yeah.

Participant 1:19:33

The paper's tactile and.

However.

What? You'll what? I think students doing now.

Is they look at online content.

Jennifer Sizer 1:19:46

Yeah. OK.

Participant 1:19:47

So the book may be online as a PDF, or they'll go to the architectural practice website, which is normally, you know at the top practices. It's just their websites are incredible. And again, you can take a screenshot. You can bring that image into Indesign, you can trace over it, get rid of the original and then you've got a format.

Jennifer Sizer 1:20:00

Yeah.

Right.

OK.

Participant 1:20:08

And then you just populate it with your own images and and yeah, so I so I think is a panacea of of resource.

Jennifer Sizer 1:20:11

with your own images, right?

Participant 1:20:19

I would say students look at everything. I mean, I've even done so I've I've seen stuff on Netflix where I've screenshot the television.

Brought the image into indesign and traced over it and then used that because sometimes the layout of Netflix is super clean. I mean like you know, and when they're either, whether it's the trailer.

Jennifer Sizer 1:20:38

Right.

Participant 1:20:44

Whether it's the layout of how you navigate around a page on Netflix, all these things. It's all inspiration. It's all source.

Jennifer Sizer 1:20:52

Yeah.

Participant 1:20:53

For for the students. So I think, yeah, I sort of I'll reject Parnell's reaction on this occasion and say they do.

Jennifer Sizer 1:21:03

Yeah, I think I think you're probably right and it is and it, but it's probably broader because I could kind of look at the architecture magazines and I could see that they looked some of them look fairly similar. And I'd in my kind of naive head, I was kind of like obviously they're just copying that. But actually I think you're right that it's kind of much more nuanced and it is lots of different influences and kind of visual things that they've seen and they're kind of combining that.

Together to kind of create their own.

Participant 1:21:31

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:21:32

Ideas and their own way of.

Participant 1:21:33

Yeah, definitely so. So the the difficult thing when you're starting out is.

What are the.. and I know it sounds really stupid, but what are the dimensions of the margins in the gutters on the page?

Is is the text force justified into boxes or is it unjustified?

What is the gap between the bottom of figure 17 and the top of the image now? All of these things are set out on, you know when it looks good, you just know.

Jennifer Sizer 1:22:01

Yeah.

Yeah.

Participant 1:22:08

And.

99% of getting it right in architecture is lining things up. So if you know it works on somebody else's web page.

Jennifer Sizer 1:22:17

Yeah.

Participant 1:22:19

Book, journal, whatever it is they're looking at, you can use that as a tracing and then you can start positioning your own stuff and then you can adapt.

Jennifer Sizer 1:22:29

Yeah.

Participant 1:22:30

But it comes back to precedent. What am I doing? I'm looking because I don't know what I'm doing and no one's really going to help me. And you know, my tutor has already told me that they're not going to tell me. So where do I go? I'll go and find something that I can copy.

Jennifer Sizer 1:22:43

Yeah.

Participant 1:22:44

And then adapt the weak students copy and that's it. The stronger students copy and adapt.

Jennifer Sizer 1:22:48

Yeah. OK, that's interesting.

Participant 1:22:54

But yeah, so I think and I I think, yeah, I think the Barry Russell essay would be a really nice one for you to look at actually the fact he was my tutor years ago but but yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:23:01

Yeah, I'll have a look.

Was that the educating architects one?

Participant 1:23:08

That's right, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:23:09

Yeah, the precedent one because yeah, I think that precedent stuff is it's just part of the pedagogy and it's just kind of embedded in it and it becomes so much part of it. But I think that's probably why I've found architecture quite interesting because that's kind of how linguistics works as well because you don't know how to write until you've looked at that genre and how it was written. So it's that kind of it, it's it's a similar way of thinking about things I think.

Participant 1:23:31

Yeah, it's, it's.

Yeah, it's the analysis of so and master students struggle this when we say go and do some precedent or case study research. If they come back with just a series of photographs, we say OK, so that's the bottom level of understanding. Now trace over it.

Jennifer Sizer 1:23:55

Yeah.

Participant 1:23:56

What's your analysis? What have you found out? What have you learned? How does this help you answer the problems that you have. That's then when precedent study really becomes effective.

Jennifer Sizer 1:24:05

Yeah.

Participant 1:24:06

To solve problems.

As opposed to just looking at it as eye candy, which is easy to do because photographers of architecture are amazing.

Jennifer Sizer 1:24:11

Yes.

Participant 1:24:18

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:24:19

Yeah, no, definitely. And I wonder how much their other pieces of work have influenced things as well, because obviously during those three years you've got that 50% design as you said. So they're using all these kind of models to create like some of the stuff that was in the design element modules I've I've said in my own work that I can't use them because they're not texty enough, because there's just not enough text for me. But it is that kind of portfolio element where they kind of showing their designs and labelling it and that kind of thing. And I wonder if.

Participant 1:24:46

Yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:24:55

Being kind of taught what looks good and how it should appear and that kind of thing throughout. And then they're bringing that into the dissertation because you can understand from my perspective, I could look at 100 dissertations and never see an image. So it's seeing so many images and seeing columns and landscape and all this kind of stuff, it must come from somewhere.

Participant 1:24:59

Yeah.

Oh.

Yeah, yeah.

Yeah, yeah.

Undoubtedly, it's from the knowledge that they've gained probably even before. If they're really good. I mean, I went into architectural practice at 13.

Jennifer Sizer 1:25:20

Yeah.

Participant 1:25:27

So I was I was inculcated at a very early age, so I when I went to university I could do some stuff.

When when you're looking at a-level or btech students or T-level students, they're going to take that knowledge into their undergraduate and by the time they got to their third year.

They're going to really, really know.

And the other thing which is interesting, the reason why I was looking around was just trying to find a book that significantly influenced me when I was at university. Oh, there it is. Yeah, I've got it. But I can't get it out now. Can I get it out? Yeah, I can. Right. So.

Right. Look at that full bleed across.

Jennifer Sizer 1:26:05

Oh wow.

Participant 1:26:09

See if I can find a texty, right? That's. I don't know if you can see that's like 3 words on it. But if you go into the.

Jennifer Sizer 1:26:15

I was going to say if that's your definition of texty 3 words, OK, that one's more texty. Yeah.

Participant 1:26:20

Right, right. But so this is John Pawson's book that's called Minimum. And although he's not an architect, he did do his part one. And I think he dropped out of his Part 2 at the Architectural Association. But yeah, 1996 it's.

a It's a Taschen book. Beautiful, full-bleed images. Text is all at the beginning of the book and.

I sculpted myself as.

AA brutalist or minimalist throughout my studies.

Jennifer Sizer 1:26:54

Right.

Participant 1:26:56

So I put myself into a box and I labelled the box and then everything that I was interested in was brutalism and minimalism.

Architectural practices and I'll use the term loosely literature.

For brutalism, and minimalism was presented in a particular way, so I adopted those ways in the way that I created my own work. Radicalism and minimalism was a bit hard for me.

Jennifer Sizer 1:27:17

Mm hmm. Yeah, interesting.

Yeah.

Participant 1:27:26

So I added colour.

That's the adaption. That's the adaptation of what you've seen of the of the precedent. So yeah, absolutely there are going to be certain things that the students say, Oh my goodness me, I'm in love with this stuff. And then that will, particularly in 3rd year where it all, hopefully it all comes together.

Jennifer Sizer 1:27:40

Yeah.

That's really interesting.

Participant 1:27:47

They've got this, they've got this thread that goes through their work.

And.

It influences everything.

Jennifer Sizer 1:27:58

Yeah. And it's that combination of influences that's really interesting because I had really thought about it that way that yeah, so this guy really is into Zaha Hadid stuff and each of the images are very Zaha Hadid like they feel very like that, you know, even the stuff that isn't her stuff feels like it's kind of, yeah, I don't know, like even the way it's kind of pictured. It almost feels very modern and.

Participant 1:28:12

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:28:23

Things. So yeah, I kind of get that how that would work.

Participant 1:28:25

Absolutely. I mean, you know, if you sit down with that student with a cup of tea or a cup of

coffee or a pint in the pub and you say, what do you want to do after you've finished, they'll probably go. I'd love to work for Zaha Hadid's practice.

Jennifer Sizer 1:28:35

Yeah.

Yeah, yeah, yeah, that's obviously what they're thinking.

Participant 1:28:39

So you're going OK.

So. So you're writing about this 'cause you love it. And and you, my, my advice to students was always.

Write about something you're passionate about.

Jennifer Sizer 1:28:51

Yeah, yeah.

Participant 1:28:53

So you go all right then, and and maybe it can help me in my future career in getting a job.

You know, when I go into, as Patrick Schumacher, isn't it? Is there. He's taken over from

from Zaha Hadid when I'm in that interview in London or wherever it is in Switzerland and I

go look, I even did my dissertation about Zaha Hadid. They're like, Oh my God, you're one of the congregation.

Come and work for us.

Jennifer Sizer 1:29:16

One of the congregation? Come on in.

Participant 1:29:18

Yeah, it is one of those. It is architecture is a bit like that.

Jennifer Sizer 1:29:22

Yeah, that's really interesting. And it's interesting that it's almost kind of you can trace that back so you can trace those potentially some of those influences back.

Yeah, even at this kind of early stage, those kind of influences are kind of there. So we're saying then that we think that this one is kind of in terms of structure is more of a kind of new new for architecture traditional for everybody else. And then this is this is kind of the opposite.

Participant 1:29:35

Yeah, yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:29:52

Kind of more topic-based and more kind of what we would expect to see.

Participant 1:29:55

Yes.

Jennifer Sizer 1:29:59

In terms of kind of chapters and that sort of thing and kind of precedent sort of study with images and that kind of stuff and then this one is a bit maybe a bit of a hybrid between the two maybe.

Participant 1:30:03

Yeah.

Yeah.

But I think it's probably more like the second one, the the yellowy blue one, it's just done in a slightly different way. So they're they're they're unpicking themes.

Jennifer Sizer 1:30:16

OK.

Yeah.

Participant 1:30:24

I don't think it's, not being funny. You know, I don't think I doubt this one got a distinction.

Jennifer Sizer 1:30:32

Can't remember what they got. I can find out then.

Participant 1:30:32

But if we're.

But if the if we're purely looking at contents.

Then I would say it's probably closer to the.

To the care in the community one.

So in my head I'm calculating what I think that dissertation is and I'll see what you say, and then I'll see if I'm right.

Jennifer Sizer 1:30:54

Let me look.

Just trying to find it.

Participant 1:31:10

It's right. No, no, no hassle if you can't. I'm just. I'm interested.

Jennifer Sizer 1:31:14

Don't worry, because I will if I can't find it now, I will. Oh, so the.

Arctic one was.

2:1 overall.

So high pass with some distinction. So distinction include in Part 2 so demonstrate critical and analytical interpretive skills through the use of scholarly sources and or primary research. So kind of a high 60s I think.

The other one.

Participant 1:31:46

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:31:49

So 60s for that one, but a very credible piece of work trying to work out which one that is because I've I've confidentialised everything, so I'm trying to work out based on what they've said.

Participant 1:31:59

Yeah, of course.

Jennifer Sizer 1:32:03

Maybe.

OK, let me try that one.

Ah, and then.

Yeah, the Zaha Hadid 1 is.

2:1 for the first element, 22 for the 2nd element, and two one for the first element, so probably high 50s, low 60s.

Participant 1:32:28

OK, I was gonna say I'd have pitched that about 55.

Jennifer Sizer 1:32:32

Yeah, I think you're probably right. I think it's, it's got, it's got slightly higher, I think overall, but I think you're about right, that's really interesting.

Participant 1:32:33

Without reading it.

Yeah. So.

Yeah.

So.

Yeah.

It comes back for me to that contract is weighing the initial tender package.

So what's your gut? Instinct. And then you go into real granular sort of analysis of what they've written. So yeah, does any of the past hour and 45 help what we've talked about?

Jennifer Sizer 1:33:06

It's amazing. Honestly, this is so helpful. This is kind of confirming what I feel like the the dissertations are telling me which is really helpful.

I'm just trying to see if I can find the other one.

Oh, I think the the first student, the care and the community student that might be this one that got mainly really high, so kind of excellent and stuff overall, so.

Participant 1:33:33

OK.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:33:36

And I think it's parts of this read like a very competent master's level literature review so.

Participant 1:33:41

OK. Well, I think that's possibly because the student gave the effort to go and take photographs of, you know, immerse themselves in the subject.

Jennifer Sizer 1:33:47

Yeah, yeah, yeah.

Participant 1:33:51

But you know, if you could you imagine putting..

Jennifer Sizer 1:33:52

Yeah.

Participant 1:33:57

The two that aren't structured traditionally in front of [REDACTED] Ch, it just.

Jennifer Sizer 1:34:02

Yeah. Oh, gosh. Can you imagine?

Participant 1:34:04

It just go. What is this? I'm sorry. This isn't a....This isn't done in the traditional way.

Jennifer Sizer 1:34:11

Yeah, no, exactly that.

Participant 1:34:12

And that's the problem. It doesn't make it any less valuable.
The student has still learned a lot.

Jennifer Sizer 1:34:22

Yeah.

Participant 1:34:23

But the output is done in a different in a different way.

Jennifer Sizer 1:34:27

Yeah, no exactly that. And it's I think it's just kind of showing me that.

That so for me it's just the range that's available to them because where my research is kind of focusing on choices, so that language isn't about, this is the really tricky thing. Language isn't about rules, it's actually about choices. And it's saying to the students, you have choices available to you. These are the choices that you can't choose from because you can't, for example, make it in the shape of a person because then you can't bind it.

Or whatever. So it's that kind of these are the choices available to you and these are the choices that are used more often. So that kind of idea of like a precedent study. So the kind of idea that the structure goes from a very sort of traditional university dissertation of introduction, method. So they can kind of opt for that or they can go all the way along here, which is a much more topic-based one which is much more kind of case study-based.

Participant 1:35:11

Yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:35:29

And kind of secondary data.

So it's kind of showing them that they have this client that they can go along. There's also another one called like a traditional complex, which is so in some ways kind of what they're doing because because it's a case study, it depends how they approach it. But it's the kind of idea of almost like you're saying about like the experiment type thing. It's almost like having different experiments. So you kind of see them separately, but not many of them do that at undergraduate level. I imagine they might do it at postgrad. So it's kind of seeing that.

Those are the structures I was predicting, but I I haven't really seen any structures that with this topic-based stuff before, particularly undergraduate level like you might see at a doctoral level where the traditional structure isn't named like that. But for I don't know, the first student to like not even have an introduction/conclusion type thing. She just kind of just jumps in with.

Participant 1:36:08

Yeah, yeah.

Yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:36:25

Why? Why do we care that stuff? And it's like, wow?

Participant 1:36:27

Well, yeah, but but but in a way. And this is where I'm trying to think.

Oh, I haven't got it. So you know how a traditional Shakespearean play is set out as epilogue. Ding, Ding, Ding, Ding, Ding. For my undergraduate dissertation. No, my. So my My postgraduate diploma. I didn't use the word introduction. I used the word epilogue, so I changed everything.

Jennifer Sizer 1:36:57

Yeah.

Participant 1:36:58

scene 1 was chapter one was, so I did all those things. Now in a way you could read her question as being a question that opens up an overview of the topic, so.

Jennifer Sizer 1:37:00

Yeah.

Yeah.

Participant 1:37:11

That question is an introduction.

Jennifer Sizer 1:37:13

Yeah.

Participant 1:37:16

And most academics should be able to deal with that.

Jennifer Sizer 1:37:20

It.

Participant 1:37:20

And and and flex and go. Oh no. It is an introduction. So I think students are students are just fantastic. I love it. I think it's. I think it's really, really good.

Jennifer Sizer 1:37:24

Definitely, yeah.

It's it's amazing and it's amazing for me because I think as I say, I spend a lot of time trying to explain to students, it's not about the rules, it's about the choices that you have. And it's just really interesting that architecture students seem to have many more choices than other students where other students are kind of bound by that kind of introduction method. They have to use that particular structure. I'm teaching a dissertation lot at the moment. I've got some food scientists and stuff. And they're like, yeah, we're not allowed to use pronouns. Pronouns are banned.

We're not allowed to use I or we or you or anything. And I'm like, oh, my gosh. Oh, yeah. Right. We'll move on from that. But yeah. So it's that kind of idea that they do have so many choices available to them just in terms of structure. And then that texture is even more interesting then. So if they decide to do portrait or landscape or columns or not, where the pictures live, how the pictures kind of interact with the text, and I think.

Participant 1:38:07

Wow. Wow.

Jennifer Sizer 1:38:25

What you've kind of explained is actually those influences.

On those choices are very nuanced and can come from three years of study, but can also be external to that as well, so it can be kind of they're watching Netflix and really like the look of that or whatever. So one of the one of the dissertations I discounted was because it didn't felt like, I feel like an architecture dissertation. It was one about the film parasite and another film where he was looking at the interiors.

Participant 1:38:41

Yeah, yeah.

Jennifer Sizer 1:38:55

And it almost felt like a film study dissertation. So I ended up discounting it. But it was obviously that.

Very heavily, influenced by film so.

Participant 1:39:01

Yeah.

Yeah. Yeah. Well, you look at dogs for [REDACTED] He's in the School of architecture. He has an architecture PhD, but it was on the.

Zombie and horror sets of films.

Which yeah, which is architectural. So I would argue that, you know, the parasite dissertation student has probably learned quite a lot that they can apply to their design and practice through the work that they've done with, with, with film. So we get, we get.

Jennifer Sizer 1:39:33

OK.

Yeah.

Participant 1:39:38

All sorts, but that's. That's because as a practitioner, you don't know what's going to come through the door next as a client project, you just don't know, so you have to be a bit versatile. But This is why I think at [REDACTED], I had so many concerns that there was only one way to do the dissertation at [REDACTED], and I was like, really in 5000 words.

Jennifer Sizer 1:39:45

Yeah.

Yeah.

Participant 1:40:01

They're all going to fail. Oh, surprise.

So.

But yeah, OK. Oh, I'm glad that was useful.

Jennifer Sizer 1:40:12

Help. I'll stop. I'll stop the recording just in case.

I don't know how to hang on, make it stop.

No, stop recording, OK?

Jennifer Sizer stopped transcription